

RISIS

"Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Deliverable 6.4 (WP6)

Report on technical conditions & harmonisation of datasets

Workpackage leader: **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH**,
with contributions from all WP6 partners (see DoW)

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1 Objectives of WP6 – Task 6

WP6 constitutes the core workpackage of RISIS with respect to pushing forward the structured and systemic opening of RISIS data infrastructures (see Figure 1). **The overall objective is to coordinate and organise the preparation for the opening of 10 data infrastructures.**

Figure 1: WP6 Work program and Tasks

This report shifts emphasis to Task 6 of WP6. It will conclude WP6 with a second report for each dataset containing – based on the initial reports from Task 1 – full documentation on each dataset, taking into account the changes introduced through the collective work, including all updates, new access conditions, harmonization’s, etc. Furthermore, the second reports will in some more detail explain conditions of ‘relevant’ use. The full documentations systematically bring forward information that is necessary for the researcher entering RISIS in a harmonized and clear manner. This is essential since, by July 2016, 9 out of 10 RISIS datasets are open for to be accessed by outside researchers via the RISIS portal. The documentations can be downloaded at the RISIS webpage (<http://risis.eu/publications>) and the RISIS datasets portal for each dataset specific website (<http://datasets.risis.eu>).

2 Outline of the reports

To provide a harmonized reporting of all datasets, a harmonised structure of the report has been developed (see also Deliverable D6.1). The outline for the reports is as follows:

- 1 **Basic characteristics**
 - Name and short description of the infrastructure
 - Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)
 - Legal name of operating organization
 - Database location and type of access (access on site, online, etc.)
- 2 **Information on substantive content of xyz**
 - 2.1 **Definition and description of observations**
 - Units and definition of observations (e.g., records on firms or programmes, etc.)
 - Number of observations (usually the rows in the database on the main unit of observation)
 - 2.2 **Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)**
 - Where are the data retrieved from (e.g., own survey, public information, etc.)
 - How are the data processed in terms of data cleaning (e.g. harmonisation of names, etc.)
 - 2.3 **Information on all variables/indicators**
 - Description of all variables and/or indicators that are given for the main units of observation (e.g. number of publications, number of patents, etc.)
 - 2.4 **Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage**
 - Information on the sectorial classifications used (e.g., economic sectors, technological fields, organizations types, etc.), and listing of all categories for each classification scheme
 - Information on the temporal coverage used (e.g. annual data from 1990-2010, etc.)
 - Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used (e.g. EU-27 member states, regional breakdown using NUTS classification revision 2010, etc.)
 - 2.5 **Quality and accuracy of data**
 - Information on the number of missing values
 - Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system
- 3 **Legal issues encountered and access conditions**
 - Legal issues concerning access of the database
 - Owner of raw data
 - Current practice for opening up of the database to external users
 - Legal necessities for potential opening procedures
- 4 **Technical structure of xyz**
 - 4.1 **Information on the data base system**
 - Current data base system used (e.g. Microsoft Access)
 - Planned future technical changes concerning data base system
 - 4.2 **Technical variable definition**
 - Labeling of all variables
 - Data type of all variables (e.g., float, string, etc.)
 - Current usage and definition of unique identifiers (if applicable)
 - 4.3 **Description of the Entity Relationship Model of xyz (if applicable)**
 - Definition of single tables
 - relation between the tables via unique identifiers.
 - 4.4 **Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)**
 - Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures
- 5 **Further planning of the opening of xyz**
 - Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset
 - Necessary updates and/or technical changes
 - Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset
 - Suggestions on demonstrations to be presented at the annual RISIS week 2015

3 Reports on each dataset

This section provides the reports on each dataset under consideration in alphabetical order:

- CIB
- ETER
- EUPRO
- JOREP
- LeidenRanking
- MORE1
- MORE2
- Nano
- Profile
- SIPER
- VICO

All reports can also be downloaded on the RISIS website under
<http://risis.eu/publications/>

Report on the content and technical structure of the **CIB** Infrastructure

Université Paris-Est Marne-la-Vallée

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Report Del 6.4, Workpackage 6, coordinated by
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of the CIB infrastructure (Task 1 of WP6)

Foreword

This report is dedicated to the CIB (Corporate Invention Board) database that will be opened as part of the RISIS infrastructure. The CIB is an original patent database, which combines financial information extracted from the “ORBIS” financial database (Bureau van Dijk) and patent data extracted from the PATSTAT-IFRIS patent database. As it has been mobilised for setting up the CIB database, the PATSTAT-IFRIS database (not opened as such as part of the RISIS infrastructure) built on the PATSTAT database (from the European Patent Office) is presented in a separated report (Report on PATSTAT-IFRIS patent database) .

The figure below summarises the linkages between databases.

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Report on the content and technical structure of the *Corporate Invention Board (CIB)* infrastructure (Task 1 of WP6)

1 Basic characteristics of CIB

- Name and short description of the infrastructure

The Corporate Invention Board (CIB) database developed by Ifris collect patents applied for from 1986 to 2009 by 2058 large firms with the highest annual R&D investments¹. It contains 16 224 135 applications of patents of invention² (among which 8 218 645 are priority patent applications) and gives information related to applicants and inventors, the patent application filing date, the patent office where the patent was filled, the type of patent, technology field categories, the patent title and abstract, citations to other documents. It also gives the name and country of the large firm to which the applicants of the patent belong to.

- Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The Corporate Invention Board (CIB) database has been developed for complementing the “Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard” produced annually by European Commission’s Institute for Prospective Technological Studies. The industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard³ 2008 analyses the performances of the 2000 industrial companies (1000 based within the European Union, 1000 outside) with the highest annual R&D investments; it covers 80% of world total private R&D. The corresponding CIB database focuses on the outputs of these R&D investments. It provides, through patent statistics, information on technologies and geographical location of the corporate inventive activities. The CIB project has identified the consolidated portfolios⁴ of patents applied for over 20 years (1986-2009) by the large industrial companies from the industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard 2008. The original set of 2000 companies has been enriched with selected Chinese and Indian companies, which results in a total of 2809 corporations. The CIB database

¹ In this document “large firms” will often be used to mean “large firms with the highest annual R&D investments”

² ipr_kind : PI

³ <http://iri.jrc.ec.europa.eu/scoreboard.html>

⁴ According with Orbis consolidation rules - a threshold of 50,01% of final ownership- subsidiaries’ patents have been consolidated within the corporation’s patent portfolio

includes 8.2 million priority patents, which represent 38.4% of the total number of priority patents applied for across the world between 1986 and 2009. This unique database allows analysing the transformation of global patent portfolios of industrial groups in the last decades.

- Legal name of operating organization

UPEM - IFRIS

- Database location and type of access:

MySQL server at Ifris. It is accessible on site at Ifris at Marne-la-Vallée (France).

2 Information on substantive content of *CIB*

2.1 Definition and description of observations

- Units and definition of observations (e.g., records on firms or programmes, etc.)

The CIB database gives information related to priority patent applications of large firms i.e. the very first patent application, anywhere in the world to protect an invention. The priority date is used to determine the novelty of the invention, which implies that it is an important concept in patent procedures. For statistical purposes, the priority date is the closest date to the date of invention.

- Number of observations (usually the rows in the database on the main unit of observation)

From 1986 to 2009, the Corporate Invention Board database includes 8 218 645 priority patent applications (number of `appln_id` in table `firm_tls201_ifris`). It includes 8 109 182 priority patents that directly involved an applicant that belongs to a large firm (also shown in table `firm_tls201_ifris`) and 109 463 additional priority patents included in the Inpadoc family of those 8 097 126 priority patents but for which no applicants are part of a large firm. It also includes 8 005 490 non-priority patents i.e. further extension of the large firms' priority patents.

The CIB database includes 2319 large firms (`guo_id` in Table `orb_guo_cor`). 2058 of them had applied for priority patents between 1986 and 2009 (`guo_id` in Table `orb_guo_cor` and `firm_tls001_rappln_id`).

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

- Where are the data retrieved from (e.g., own survey, public information, etc.)

The firm database

Our first data source is the “Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard” (2008 edition) that lists the 2000 industrial companies (1000 based within the European Union, 1000 outside⁵) with the highest annual R&D investments. This initial set was complemented with 500 Indian and Chinese firms declaring R&D investments between 1999 and 2009 in the Computstat database and with name of the 500 most important firms as assignees of WIPO⁶, EPO and USPTO patents. Then using the Orbis database edited by Bureau van Dijk Electronic Publishing we defined the global ultimate owner (GUO) for each of the firms and identified all subsidiaries in which one of the GUOs had more than 50.01% of shares in 2008. We ended with a list of 2319 GUO and 168 533 different subsidiaries. Using the data cleaning and harmonizing methodology developed by Magerman et al. (2006), we prepared a list of cleaned GUO and subsidiaries names that was further enriched by adding firm acronyms, firm old names and standardized names from the Pastat database. The final list of firm names contained 316 676 different names. The next issue was to define the home country of the firm. Following the practice of the “Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard”, the home country of the firm (GUO and all its subsidiaries) was defined according to the location of the GUO headquarters.

At last a classification of firms according to industrial sectors was added. It uses the ICB (Industry Classification Benchmark) classification already included in the Industrial R&D Investment Scoreboard files developed by Dow Jones and the Financial Times Stock Exchange (FTSE)⁷. It classifies each of the firms into 10 industries, 18 super sectors and 41 industrial sectors.

The patent database

We used the PATSTAT-IFRIS database, built on PATSTAT version October 2011 provided by EPO (see report “PATSTAT-IFRIS database” for detailed description).

- How are the data processed in terms of data cleaning (e.g. harmonisation of organization names, etc.)

⁵ The excel file can be downloaded in:

https://www.dropbox.com/s/bc4crb102m1fpev/2008_top_1000_EU_companies.xls

https://www.dropbox.com/s/f2tfpespqj61v4e/2008_top_1000_non-EUcompanies.xls

⁶ World Intellectual Property Organization, the international organization that deals with all geographical patent extensions.

⁷ Information on the icb can be found in <http://www.icbenchmark.com/>

Matching the firm database with the patent databases

The 316 676 firm names were matched with all the applicants standardized names (doc_std_name) of priority patent applications in the Patstat database. Basically matching the firm database and the patent database was carried out in two ways: matching both name (exact spelling and proxy) and firm country of our firm list with Patstat applicant standard name and applicant country when this latter information was present in the Patstat database and only exact firm spelling of our firm list when the applicant country information missed. Manual checking was carried out to discard false retrieved patent.

Schematic view of the CIB database building

Identification of "natural persons" among applicants

We ended with 9 586 238 distinct applicants (distinct key_applt) and 19 067 701 inventors (distinct key_invt).

Identification of natural persons (opposed to legal persons) among applicants in the CIB database was carried out by matching the name of the applicants (both person_name and doc_std_name) with a list of natural persons.

If the applicant of the CIB belongs to this list, the field “applt_type_person_name” and/or “applt_type_doc_std_name” will be filled with “natural_person” If the applicant doesn’t belong to that list, the fields “applt_type_person_name” and/or “applt_type_doc_std_name” are left empty⁸.

This list where the type of applicant was defined contains the spellings of natural persons from the two fields: person_name and doc_std_name and has been built by combining: i) a list of inventors that also applied for the patent. These natural applicants are easily retrieved within each patent since their person_name and doc_std_name are included both in the applicant field and in the inventor field, ii) a list of applicants that were not inventor but whose name was identified as a possible candidate for natural person (including graphics such as Roger, John ...) and who applied to less than 100 patents (that latter condition reduces dramatically the presence of legal persons), iii) a list for natural name defined in the project “Nano 2009”. It includes names / surnames identified by Magerman, names / surnames automatically identified in the nano database and a list of names identified manually.

3 406 658 applicants (key_applt) are tagged as ‘Natural person’ either in the field “applt_type_person_name” or in the field “applt_type_doc_std_name”.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

- Description of all variables and/or indicators that are given for the main units of observation (e.g. number of publications, number of patents, etc.)

For each firm (aggregation of the guo and its subsidiaries), the database gives:

- Name of the firm using various spellings (guo_name, guo_name_std, guo_name_patstatstd in Table orb_guo_corr),
- Acronym of the firm (guo_acronym in Table orb_guo_corr),
- Database id of the firm (guo_id in Table orb_guo_corr and Table firm_tls0018rappln_id and Table firm_tls0018rappln_id_group),
- IndexScoreBoard of the firm (IndexScoreBoard in Table orb_guo_corr). This is the firm’s id in the Industrial R&D investment Scoreboard,
- Industry Classification of the firm (ICB in Table orb_guo_corr). It give the sector of the firm according to ICB categories (see below),
- Country where the firm’s headquarters is located (guo_ctry in Table orb_guo_corr),

⁸ In that case, we cannot undoubtedly assess the status of the applicant since our list of natural persons is not exhaustive but it is reasonable to expect a high rate of legal persons.

- Country code where the firm's headquarter is located (guo_etrycode in Table orb_guo_corr) following the international two letter country code (ISO alpha-2),
- Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes of the firms (guo_sic_core_code and guo_sic_core in Table orb_guo_corr). It is the business classification codes that the U.S. government assigns to businesses. SIC coding is used primarily to classify a company's main industry and line of business⁹.

The CIB database lists of firm's priority patents and gives information related to these patents according to the information available in Patstat or added classification (inventors address, applicants address, date of applications, type of patent, patent office, title, abstract, patent family, technology field classification). (see Patstat report for detailed information on patent data)

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

The numbers of patents given in tables shown below are calculated considering the number of priority patent applications (appln_id) given in table t1s 201 (unless other specifications) crossed with information from other tables (table orb_guo_corr for firm's sectors and country and table ipc_technology_frac_ifris for patent technology field).

Information on the sectorial classifications used (e.g., economic sectors, technological fields, organizations types, etc.), and listing of all categories for each classification scheme

1) **Sector of firms**

Firms in the CIB database are classified according to industrial sectors using the Industry Classification Benchmark (ICB)¹⁰. It is an industry classification taxonomy launched by Dow Jones and FTSE in 2005 and now owned solely by FTSE International. It is used to segregate markets into sectors within the macroeconomy. The ICB uses a system of 10 industries, partitioned into 19 supersectors, which are further divided into 41 sectors, which then contain 114 subsectors¹¹

The distribution of firms in CIB at the levels of Industry and Sectors of the ICB categories are given below.

Industry	Nber of firms	Nber of first filings
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⁹ http://www.ehow.com/facts_7277558_primary-sic-code_.html#ixzz33qksBG58

¹⁰ Firms are classified just in one sector

¹¹ <http://www.icbenchmark.com/>

Basic Materials	241	992 950
Consumer Goods	330	2 123 837
Consumer Services	81	105 594
Financials	58	19 392
Health Care	354	284 444
Industrials	596	2 172 644
Oil & Gas	52	84 868
Technology	532	2 261 313
Telecommunications	27	124 757
Utilities	48	56 755
Total	2319	8 226 554

Number of priority patents (1986-2009) and number of firms by industries

Sector	Nber of firms	Nber of first filings
Oil & gas producers	34	63 822
Oil equipment, services & distribution	17	21 013
Alternative energy	1	33
Chemicals	162	706 265
Forestry & paper	17	12 321
Industrial metals	44	261 327
Mining	18	13 037
Construction & materials	67	133 850
Aerospace & defence	49	82 109
General industrials	51	288 751
Electrical components & equipment	76	522 980
Electronic equipment	103	846 562
Commercial vehicles & trucks	40	76 069
Industrial machinery	154	188 240
Industrial transportation	15	937
Support services	41	33 146
Automobiles & parts	111	891 510
Beverages	10	9 821
Food producers	70	35 863
Household goods	50	87
Household goods	50	114 891
Leisure goods	31	1 003 468
Personal goods	58	68 197
Health care equipment & services	67	66 933
Pharmaceuticals & Biotechnology	5	411
Biotechnology	122	30 107
Pharmaceuticals	160	186 993
Food & drug retailers	9	4 009
General retailers	23	6 816
Media	22	73 357
Travel & leisure	27	21 412
Fixed line telecommunications	21	106 689
Mobile telecommunications	6	18 068

Electricity	32	31 450
Gas, water & multiutilities	16	25 305
Banks	23	15 728
Nonlife insurance	8	406
Life insurance	2	91
Financial Services	25	3 167
Software & Computer Services	1	10
Computer services	37	281 239
Internet	11	6 031
Software	150	51 986
Computer hardware	61	1 079 886
Electronic office equipment	15	267 106
Semiconductors	129	343 175
Telecommunications equipment	128	231 880

Number of priority patents (1986-2009) and number of firms by subsectors

2) Technology fields of patents

Patents are classified according to technology categories. The categories used in CIB are those build by WIPO (see PATSTAT-IFRIS report for detailed information): 5 domains, 35 fields and 401 subfields.

The distributions of priority patent applications from 1986 to 2005 by domains and fields and subfields are shown below.

Domain_code	Domain_name	Number of priority patent applications
TD01	Electrical engineering	3 886 482
TD02	Instruments	1 776 426
TD03	Chemistry	1 539 908
TD04	Mechanical engineering	2 262 804
TD05	Other fields	486 957

Note: a patent can be affected to several domains

Field_code	Field_name	Number of priority patent applications
TF01	Electrical machinery, apparatus, energy	802 990
TF02	Audio-visual technology	939 461
TF03	Telecommunications	648 241
TF04	Digital communication	334 167
TF05	Basic communication processes	203 618

TF06	Computer technology	986 537
TF07	IT methods for management	107 787
TF08	Semiconductors	755 505
TF09	Optics	848 169
TF10	Measurement	535 894
TF11	Analysis of biological materials	48 570
TF12	Control	269 146
TF13	Medical technology	210 372
TF14	Organic fine chemistry	190 462
TF15	Biotechnology	69 484
TF16	Pharmaceuticals	146 889
TF17	Macromolecular chemistry, polymers	272 165
TF18	Food chemistry	40 158
TF19	Basic materials chemistry	261 976
TF20	Materials, metallurgy	278 481
TF21	Surface technology, coating	284 335
TF22	Micro-structural and nano-technology	11 933
TF23	Chemical engineering	228 246
TF24	Environmental technology	155 609
TF25	Handling	283 912
TF26	Machine tools	259 927
TF27	Engines, pumps, turbines	342 854
TF28	Textile and paper machines	363 841
TF29	Other special machines	284 163
TF30	Thermal processes and apparatus	217 356
TF31	Mechanical elements	306 859
TF32	Transport	485 389
TF33	Furniture, games	140 409
TF34	Other consumer goods	157 230
TF35	Civil engineering	205 918

Note: a patent can be attributed to several fields

sfields	Number of priority patent applications	Number of priority patent applications
T01F01	Lighting	40 734
T01F02	Displaying Advertising	59 548
T01F03	Transmission Systems	10 731
T01F04	Transmission Of Digital Inf	281 875
T01F05	Basic Electronic Circuitry	203 618
T01F06	Mechanic Digital Comput	885 330
T01F07	Data Processing Systems	107 787
T01F08	Semiconductor Devices	755 505
T01F09	Optical Elements Systems	395 060
T01F10	Measuring Length Thickness	64 831
T01F11	Mat Analysis by Chem/Phys Prop	48 570

T01F12	Control Systems in General	61 650
T01F13	Surgery-Diagnosis	110 538
T01F14	Cosmetic Preparations	40 519
T01F15	Compounds Of Unknown Constitution	270
T01F16	Medical Preparations	143 179
T01F17	Polysaccharides	4 168
T01F18	New Plants	6 485
T01F19	Disinfectants	29 675
T01F20	Casting and Powder Metallurgy	55 180
T01F21	Apparatus For Applying Liquids	22 684
T01F22	Micro-Structural Technology	9 169
T01F23	Boiling	255
T01F24	Fire-Fighting	3 445
T01F25	Manipulators	23 889
T01F26	Mechanical Metal-Working	2 745
T01F27	Machines Or Engines for + Displacement	1 185
T01F28	Methofs for Clothes	451
T01F29	Soil Working	7 450
T01F30	Steam generation	7 750
T01F31	Fluid Pressure Actuator	14 861
T01F32	Vehicles	372 661
T01F33	Furniture and Dom Equipt	85 047
T01F34	Tobacco	3 424
T01F35	Permanent ways	2 279
T02F01	Cables with Special Electric Properties	54 827
T02F02	Arrangements For Control	99 934
T02F03	Waveguides	19 299
T02F04	Selective Content Distrib	120
T02F06	Speech Anal. Or Synth.	35 720
T02F09	Photograph Apparatus	111 654
T02F10	Measuring Distances Levels	48 638
T02F12	Regulating Non Electric Variables	32 757
T02F13	Dentistry	4 681
T02F14	Use of Cosmetics	38 409
T02F15	Peptides	17 524
T02F16	Therap Activ Of Chem Comp	82 013
T02F17	Treatment Of Rubbers	1 845
T02F18	Treatment of Dough	2 865
T02F19	Repellants	3 259
T02F20	Inorganic Chem	59 297
T02F21	Liquid Application Processes	36 754
T02F22	Nano-Technology	2 902
T02F23	Separation	5 461
T02F24	Protection against Fire and Chemicals	1 510
T02F25	Packaging Machines	14 626

T02F26	Machine Tools	72 176
T02F27	Piston Machines Or Engines	2 592
T02F28	Repairing Footwear	290
T02F29	Planting	8 499
T02F30	Combustion Apparatus Using Solid Fuel	178
T02F31	Engineering Elts or Units	283 415
T02F32	Railways	16 528
T02F33	Sports and Games	55 541
T02F34	Shirts	917
T02F35	Hydraulic Eng Found Soil-Shifting	4 991
T03F01	Resistors	14 096
T03F02	Info Storage Based Record Carrier	299 320
T03F03	Aerials	34 683
T03F04	Wireless Comm	72 290
T03F06	Static Stores	88 584
T03F09	Photographic Processes	29 775
T03F10	Multivariable Measuring	28 747
T03F12	Regulating Electric Variables	18 435
T03F13	Veterinary	417
T03F14	Organic Chemistry	27 063
T03F15	Apparatus For Enzymology Or Microbiology	9 697
T03F17	Macromol with C-to-C Unsaturated Bonds	78 361
T03F18	Preseving food	3 064
T03F19	Fertilisers	2 836
T03F20	Glasses	24 080
T03F21	Layered Products	93 994
T03F23	Evaporating and extraction and separetion and degaseification	9 492
T03F24	Separating Gases	10 214
T03F25	Labelling Machines	1 953
T03F26	Grinding and Polishing	131 924
T03F27	Machines Or Engines for - Displacement	20 196
T03F28	Production of Brushes	627
T03F29	Harvesting	11 475
T03F30	Combustion Apparatus Using Fluent Fuel	6 088
T03F31	Stroring Distributing Non Solids	9 018
T03F32	Land Vehicles	95 027
T03F34	Corsets	189
T03F35	Other Subjects Building	3 717
T04F01	Magnets	56 955
T04F02	Scanning details of television	7 207
T04F03	Transmission	206 484
T04F09	Apparatus For Processing Exposed Photographic Materials	7 047
T04F10	Measuring Volume Flow	22 675

T04F12	Checking Devices	68 144
T04F13	Blood Vessel Filters	32 762
T04F14	Acyclic or Carbocyclic Comp	77 852
T04F15	Micro-Orga Enzymes Culture Media	39 677
T04F17	Macromol withouth C-to-C Unsaturated Bonds	89 545
T04F18	Dairy Products	2 825
T04F19	Explosives	2 008
T04F20	Refractories	63 969
T04F21	Coating Metallic Material	114 824
T04F23	Separation and Filters	8 863
T04F24	Filtering Gases	941
T04F25	Containers for Storage	66 042
T04F26	Tools Or Benches	33 179
T04F27	Steam Engine Plants	5 155
T04F28	Working Paper	4 227
T04F29	Harvested Produce	5 957
T04F30	Burners	9 232
T04F31	Mechanical Control Systems	5 428
T04F32	Ships	7 886
T04F34	Outerwear	3 457
T04F35	Surfaces for roads and sport grounds	99
T05F01	Capacitors	30 461
T05F02	Details of TV syst	229 134
T05F03	Broadcas Communication	14 323
T05F09	Photomechanics of Surfaces	95 252
T05F10	Weighing	5 408
T05F12	Signalling Systems	34 351
T05F13	Furniture for Patients	5 439
T05F14	Heterocyclic Compounds	62 084
T05F15	Fermentation Or Enzyme-Using Processes	17 629
T05F17	Derivatives Of Natural Macromolecules	380
T05F18	Edible Oils	2 004
T05F19	Organic Dyes	15 231
T05F20	Metallurgy of Iron	50 693
T05F21	Electrolytic Or Electrophoretic Processes	28 204
T05F23	Distillation	13 339
T05F24	Separating by Liquids	78
T05F25	Transport of Storage Devices	49 297
T05F26	Nailing Or Stapling Tools	7 188
T05F27	Cyclic Machines Or Engines	19 830
T05F28	Printing	279 800
T05F29	Horticulture	8 595
T05F30	Grates	181
T05F32	Launching of Vessels	1 265

T05F34	Suspenders	150
T05F35	Bridges	13
T06F01	Electric Switches	51 838
T06F02	Pictorial Communication	119 332
T06F03	Multiplex Communication	52 971
T06F09	Photomecha Prod Of Surfaces	229 862
T06F10	Measuring Vibrations	6 055
T06F12	Traffic Control Systems	45 981
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T06F14	Compounds with Elts Other Than C H Halogen O N S Se or Te	17 920
T06F15	Measur Proc with Enzymes Or Micro-Orga	21 297
T06F17	Inorg Or Non-Macromol Organ Subst	81 205
T06F18	Coffee and Tea	1 807
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T06F21	Crystal Growth	22 523
T06F23	Regeneration of Filters	177
T06F24	Other Separating	853
T06F25	Handling Thin Material	87 809
T06F26	Percussive Tools	1 540
T06F27	Lubricating Of Machines Or Engines	11 179
T06F28	Mechanical Processing Of Skins Hides Or Leather	81
T06F29	Prod of Dairy Products	488
T06F30	Feeding Fuel To Combustion Apparatus	2 837
T06F32	Weapons on Vessels	819
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T07F09	Holography	5 961
T07F10	Optical Measurements	23 449
T07F12	Educational Or Demonstration Appliances	25 281
T07F13	Medical Containers	5 506
T07F14	Sugars Nucleotides	8 489
T07F15	Micro-Organisms-General	8 559
T07F17	Compositions Of Macromol Comp	145 300
T07F18	Chocolate	4 081
T07F19	Paints and inks	69 514
T07F23	Separating Liquids and Solids	119
T07F24	Separating Combination	492
T07F25	Lifting	48 496
T07F26	Multi-Purpose Tools	2 021

T07F27	Cooling Of Machines Or Engines	12 782
T07F28	Threads or Fibers	24 797
T07F29	Husbandry	9 031
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T14F18	Treatment of Alcoholic Beverages	398
T14F19	Working-Up Tar	877
T14F23	Chem and Phys Processes	5 210
T14F24	Absorbing noise from roads	37 127
T14F26	Presses	6 999
T14F28	Sewing	4 982
T14F29	Working Of Foodstuffs	1 114
T14F30	Furnaces ovens	18 127
T14F34	Other Life saving and Amusement	1
T14F35	Building	29 440
T15F01	Static Electricity	2 093
T15F02	Printed Circuits	182 095
T15F10	Geophysics	45 889
T15F18	Vinegar	43
T15F19	Working-Up Of Peat	32
T15F23	Chem Or Phys Lab Apparatus	7 887
T15F24	Gas-Flow Silencers	7 577
T15F26	Presses	7 500
T15F28	Mechanical Or Pressure Cleaning of Textile	23
T15F29	Preparing Grain and Fruit	1 862
T15F30	Heat Exchange	32 060
T15F34	Bookbinding	23 564
T15F35	Locking Safing	11 147
T16F01	Other subjects electricity	1
T16F10	Meteorology	14 702

T16F18	Sugar Juices	50
T16F19	Cracking Hydrocarbon Oils	12 909
T16F23	Crushing and Milling	7 397
T16F24	Furnaces	5 059
T16F28	Marking Inspecting Seaming Or Severing Textile	692
T16F29	Working Cement or Stone	16 671
T16F34	Writing Implements	3 866
T16F35	Openings in Building Ladder	33 197
T17F10	Horology	2 103
T17F18	Sugar	156
T17F19	Wet Production Of Acetylene	7
T17F23	Separation of solid materials	3 809
T17F24	Combustion Products	12 284
T17F28	Pleating Ktiling Or Goffering Textile	68
T17F29	Working of Plastics	129 187
T17F34	Decorative Arts	6 242
T17F35	Earth Or Rock Drilling	1
T18F10	Details Of Instruments	11 572
T18F18	Extraction Of Sugar	51
T18F19	Production Of Gas From Solid C-Material	2 596
T18F23	Centrifuges	15 611
T18F28	Other Treatments	14 525
T18F34	Saddlery and Upholstery	1 258
T19F10	Other subjects nucleonics	3 507
T19F18	Synthesis Of Sugars	31
T19F19	Modifying Combustible Gases Containing CO	1 152
T19F23	Spraying	3 709
T19F28	Dyeing Or Printing Textiles	5 430
T19F29	Manufacturind or Shaping	18 848
T19F34	Trimmings	108
T20F18	Drying Sugar	4
T20F19	Fuels	7 551
T20F23	Generating Mechanical Vibrations	8 024
T20F28	Decorating Textiles	216
T20F29	Processes Of Compounding	73 679
T20F34	Laundering	28 534
T21F18	Working-up of Sugar	39
T21F19	Lubrifiant	14 188
T21F23	Separating Solids and Sorting	18 173
T21F28	Paper Making	23 420
T21F29	Pitching Machines	1
T21F34	Wall Floor Covering	2 937
T22F19	Lubrifiant indexed	9 426
T22F23	Cleaning	722

T22F29	Sugar Production	2
T22F34	Rope non electric cable	2 276
T23F18	Sugar Juices	1
T23F19	Fats	2 376
T23F23	Chemical Processing Of Skins Hides Or Leather	1 086
T23F29	Evaporation Apparatus	5
T23F34	Cooling Or Freezing Apparatus	33 763
T24F18	Sugar	2
T24F19	Fatty Acids	1 031
T24F23	Treating Textile	1 237
T24F29	Cutting of Sugar	42
T24F34	Organs Harmoniums	805
T25F19	Detergent Compositions	27 547
T25F23	Finishing Dressing Tentering Or Stretching Textile	2 026
T25F29	Weapons	1
T25F34	Pianos	672
T26F18	Sugar Synth	253
T26F23	Bleaching	3 411
T26F34	Musical Instruments	569
T27F23	Phase transformation Of Gases	8 524
T27F34	Automatic Musical Instruments	566
T28F23	Drying	12 543
T28F34	Aids For Music	1 632
T29F29	Weapons	6 123
T29F34	Electrophonic Musical Instruments	13 364
T30F29	Ammunitions Blasting	5 982
T30F34	Sound-Producing Devices	16 937
sfields	Number of priority patent applications	count(distinct b.appln_id)
T01F01	Lighting	40 734
T01F02	Displaying Advertising	59 548
T01F03	Transmission Systems	10 731
T01F04	Transmission Of Digital Inf	281 875
T01F05	Basic Electronic Circuitry	203 618
T01F06	Mechanic Digital Comput	885 330
T01F07	Data Processing Systems	107 787
T01F08	Semiconductor Devices	755 505
T01F09	Optical Elements Systems	395 060
T01F10	Measuring Length Thickness	64 831
T01F11	Mat Analysis by Chem/Phys Prop	48 570
T01F12	Control Systems in General	61 650
T01F13	Surgery-Diagnosis	110 538
T01F14	Cosmetic Preparations	40 519

T01F15	Compounds Of Unknown Constitution	270
T01F16	Medical Preparations	143 179
T01F17	Polysaccharides	4 168
T01F18	New Plants	6 485
T01F19	Disinfectants	29 675
T01F20	Casting and Powder Metallurgy	55 180
T01F21	Apparatus For Applying Liquids	22 684
T01F22	Micro-Structural Technology	9 169
T01F23	Boiling	255
T01F24	Fire-Fighting	3 445
T01F25	Manipulators	23 889
T01F26	Mechanical Metal-Working	2 745
T01F27	Machines Or Engines for + Displacement	1 185
T01F28	Methofs for Clothes	451
T01F29	Soil Working	7 450
T01F30	Steam generation	7 750
T01F31	Fluid Pressure Actuator	14 861
T01F32	Vehicles	372 661
T01F33	Furniture and Dom Equipt	85 047
T01F34	Tobacco	3 424
T01F35	Permanent ways	2 279
T02F01	Cables with Special Electric Properties	54 827
T02F02	Arrangements For Control	99 934
T02F03	Waveguides	19 299
T02F04	Selective Content Distrib	120
T02F06	Speech Anal. Or Synth.	35 720
T02F09	Photograph Apparatus	111 654
T02F10	Measuring Distances Levels	48 638
T02F12	Regulating Non Electric Variables	32 757
T02F13	Dentistry	4 681
T02F14	Use of Cosmetics	38 409
T02F15	Peptides	17 524
T02F16	Therap Activ Of Chem Comp	82 013
T02F17	Treatment Of Rubbers	1 845
T02F18	Treatment of Dough	2 865
T02F19	Repellants	3 259
T02F20	Inorganic Chem	59 297
T02F21	Liquid Application Processes	36 754
T02F22	Nano-Technology	2 902
T02F23	Separation	5 461
T02F24	Protection against Fire and Chemicals	1 510
T02F25	Packaging Machines	14 626
T02F26	Machine Tools	72 176
T02F27	Piston Machines Or Engines	2 592

T02F28	Repairing Footwear	290
T02F29	Planting	8 499
T02F30	Combustion Apparatus Using Solid Fuel	178
T02F31	Engineering Elts or Units	283 415
T02F32	Railways	16 528
T02F33	Sports and Games	55 541
T02F34	Shirts	917
T02F35	Hydraulic Eng Found Soil-Shifting	4 991
T03F01	Resistors	14 096
T03F02	Info Storage Based Record Carrier	299 320
T03F03	Aerials	34 683
T03F04	Wireless Comm	72 290
T03F06	Static Stores	88 584
T03F09	Photographic Processes	29 775
T03F10	Multivariable Measuring	28 747
T03F12	Regulating Electric Variables	18 435
T03F13	Veterinary	417
T03F14	Organic Chemistry	27 063
T03F15	Apparatus For Enzymology Or Microbiology	9 697
T03F17	Macromol with C-to-C Unsaturated Bonds	78 361
T03F18	Preseving food	3 064
T03F19	Fertilisers	2 836
T03F20	Glasses	24 080
T03F21	Layered Products	93 994
T03F23	Evaporating and extraction and separetion and degaseification	9 492
T03F24	Separating Gases	10 214
T03F25	Labelling Machines	1 953
T03F26	Grinding and Polishing	131 924
T03F27	Machines Or Engines for - Displacement	20 196
T03F28	Production of Brushes	627
T03F29	Harvesting	11 475
T03F30	Combustion Apparatus Using Fluent Fuel	6 088
T03F31	Stroring Distributing Non Solids	9 018
T03F32	Land Vehicles	95 027
T03F34	Corsets	189
T03F35	Other Subjects Building	3 717
T04F01	Magnets	56 955
T04F02	Scanning details of television	7 207
T04F03	Transmission	206 484
T04F09	Apparatus For Processing Exposed Photographic Materials	7 047
T04F10	Measuring Volume Flow	22 675
T04F12	Checking Devices	68 144

T04F13	Blood Vessel Filters	32 762
T04F14	Acyclic or Carbocyclic Comp	77 852
T04F15	Micro-Orga Enzymes Culture Media	39 677
T04F17	Macromol withouth C-to-C Unsaturated Bonds	89 545
T04F18	Dairy Products	2 825
T04F19	Explosives	2 008
T04F20	Refractories	63 969
T04F21	Coating Metallic Material	114 824
T04F23	Separation and Filters	8 863
T04F24	Filtering Gases	941
T04F25	Containers for Storage	66 042
T04F26	Tools Or Benches	33 179
T04F27	Steam Engine Plants	5 155
T04F28	Working Paper	4 227
T04F29	Harvested Produce	5 957
T04F30	Burners	9 232
T04F31	Mechanical Control Systems	5 428
T04F32	Ships	7 886
T04F34	Outerwear	3 457
T04F35	Surfaces for roads and sport grounds	99
T05F01	Capacitors	30 461
T05F02	Details of TV syst	229 134
T05F03	Broadcas Communication	14 323
T05F09	Photomechanics of Surfaces	95 252
T05F10	Weighing	5 408
T05F12	Signalling Systems	34 351
T05F13	Furniture for Patients	5 439
T05F14	Heterocyclic Compounds	62 084
T05F15	Fermentation Or Enzyme-Using Processes	17 629
T05F17	Derivatives Of Natural Macromolecules	380
T05F18	Edible Oils	2 004
T05F19	Organic Dyes	15 231
T05F20	Metallurgy of Iron	50 693
T05F21	Electrolytic Or Electrophoretic Processes	28 204
T05F23	Distillation	13 339
T05F24	Separating by Liquids	78
T05F25	Transport of Storage Devices	49 297
T05F26	Nailing Or Stapling Tools	7 188
T05F27	Cyclic Machines Or Engines	19 830
T05F28	Printing	279 800
T05F29	Horticulture	8 595
T05F30	Grates	181
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T14F10	Radio Direction-Finding	109 215
T14F18	Treatment of Alcoholic Beverages	398
T14F19	Working-Up Tar	877
T14F23	Chem and Phys Processes	5 210
T14F24	Absorbing noise from roads	37 127
T14F26	Presses	6 999
T14F28	Sewing	4 982
T14F29	Working Of Foodstuffs	1 114
T14F30	Furnaces ovens	18 127
T14F34	Other Life saving and Amusement	1
T14F35	Building	29 440
T15F01	Static Electricity	2 093
T15F02	Printed Circuits	182 095
T15F10	Geophysics	45 889
T15F18	Vinegar	43
T15F19	Working-Up Of Peat	32
T15F23	Chem Or Phys Lab Apparatus	7 887
T15F24	Gas-Flow Silencers	7 577
T15F26	Presses	7 500
T15F28	Mechanical Or Pressure Cleaning of Textile	23
T15F29	Preparing Grain and Fruit	1 862
T15F30	Heat Exchange	32 060

T15F34	Bookbinding	23 564
T15F35	Locking Safing	11 147
T16F01	Other subjects electricity	1
T16F10	Meteorology	14 702
T16F18	Sugar Juices	50
T16F19	Cracking Hydrocarbon Oils	12 909
T16F23	Crushing and Milling	7 397
T16F24	Furnaces	5 059
T16F28	Marking Inspecting Seaming Or Severing Textile	692
T16F29	Working Cement or Stone	16 671
T16F34	Writing Implements	3 866
T16F35	Openings in Building Ladder	33 197
T17F10	Horology	2 103
T17F18	Sugar	156
T17F19	Wet Production Of Acetylene	7
T17F23	Separation of solid materials	3 809
T17F24	Combustion Products	12 284
T17F28	Pleating Kilting Or Goffering Textile	68
T17F29	Working of Plastics	129 187
T17F34	Decorative Arts	6 242
T17F35	Earth Or Rock Drilling	1
T18F10	Details Of Instruments	11 572
T18F18	Extraction Of Sugar	51
T18F19	Production Of Gas From Solid C-Material	2 596
T18F23	Centrifuges	15 611
T18F28	Other Treatments	14 525
T18F34	Saddlery and Upholstery	1 258
T19F10	Other subjects nucleonics	3 507
T19F18	Synthesis Of Sugars	31
T19F19	Modifying Combustible Gases Containing CO	1 152
T19F23	Spraying	3 709
T19F28	Dyeing Or Printing Textiles	5 430
T19F29	Manufacturind or Shaping	18 848
T19F34	Trimmings	108
T20F18	Drying Sugar	4
T20F19	Fuels	7 551
T20F23	Generating Mechanical Vibrations	8 024
T20F28	Decorating Textiles	216
T20F29	Processes Of Compounding	73 679
T20F34	Laundrying	28 534
T21F18	Working-up of Sugar	39
T21F19	Lubrifiant	14 188
T21F23	Separating Solids and Sorting	18 173

T21F28	Paper Making	23 420
T21F29	Pitching Machines	1
T21F34	Wall Floor Covering	2 937
T22F19	Lubrifiant indexed	9 426
T22F23	Cleaning	722
T22F29	Sugar Production	2
T22F34	Rope non electric cable	2 276
T23F18	Sugar Juices	1
T23F19	Fats	2 376
T23F23	Chemical Processing Of Skins Hides Or Leather	1 086
T23F29	Evaporation Apparatus	5
T23F34	Cooling Or Freezing Apparatus	33 763
T24F18	Sugar	2
T24F19	Fatty Acids	1 031
T24F23	Treating Textile	1 237
T24F29	Cutting of Sugar	42
T24F34	Organs Harmoniums	805
T25F19	Detergent Compositions	27 547
T25F23	Finishing Dressing Tentering Or Stretching Textile	2 026
T25F29	Weapons	1
T25F34	Pianos	672
T26F18	Sugar Synth	253
T26F23	Bleaching	3 411
T26F34	Musical Instruments	569
T27F23	Phase transformation Of Gases	8 524
T27F34	Automatic Musical Instruments	566
T28F23	Drying	12 543
T28F34	Aids For Music	1 632
T29F29	Weapons	6 123
T29F34	Electroponic Musical Instruments	13 364
T30F29	Ammunitions Blasting	5 982
T30F34	Sound-Producing Devices	16 937

Note: a patent can be affected to several subfields

- Information on the temporal coverage used (e.g. annual data from 1990-2010, etc.)

The CIB database covers a period of time ranging from 1986 to 2009

The distribution of priority patent applications from 1986 to 2009 by application filling year is shown below.

Application filling_year	Number of priority patent applications
1986	246 570
1987	264 902
1988	263 912
1989	270 380
1990	285 572
1991	294 736
1992	281 169
1993	296 662
1994	282 952
1995	309 709
1996	313 578
1997	335 507
1998	350 054
1999	363 908
2000	383 527
2001	392 436
2002	391 698
2003	401 079
2004	421 582
2005	432 577
2006	421 750
2007	414 839
2008	404 406
2009	285 677
Total	8 109 182

- Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used
The information is detailed in the Patstat report

ISO 3166 a standard developed for the current names of countries, dependencies, and other areas of particular geopolitical interest, on the basis of lists of country names obtained from the United Nations and maintained by the ISO 3166 Maintenance Agency established by the ISO Council, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). The international two letter country code (ISO alpha-2) is used as Harmonized country code.

The distributions of firms and priority patent applications from 1986 to 2009 by firm's country and firm's continent are shown below.

Harmonized country name	Harmonized country code	Number of firms	Number of priority patents
NETHERLANDS ANTILLES	AN	1	6 755

AUSTRIA	AT	25	5 511
AUSTRALIA	AU	9	3 042
BELGIUM	BE	39	14 161
BERMUDA	BM	11	20 383
BRAZIL	BR	9	1 618
BAHAMAS, THE	BS	1	32
CANADA	CA	25	18 916
SWITZERLAND	CH	41	73 733
CHINA	CN	80	60 965
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	2	18
GERMANY	DE	182	397 198
DENMARK	DK	43	15 783
SPAIN	ES	21	2 259
FINLAND	FI	59	34 277
FRANCE	FR	109	152 648
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	260	89 416
GIBRALTAR	GI	3	74
GREECE	GR	6	178
HONG KONG	HK	6	3 970
HUNGARY	HU	2	743
IRELAND	IE	11	2 167
ISRAEL	IL	10	2 714
INDIA	IN	326	7 220
ITALY	IT	51	17 311
JAPAN	JP	245	5 418 369
SOUTH KOREA	KR	18	492 731
CAYMAN ISLANDS	KY	5	6 433
LIECHTENSTEIN	LI	1	2 033
LUXEMBOURG	LU	5	1 119
MALTA	MT	1	31
MALAYSIA	MY	1	0
NETHERLANDS	NL	49	98 262
NORWAY	NO	8	2 895
NEW ZEALAND	NZ	2	598
PANAMA	PA	1	1 090
POLAND	PL	3	204
PORTUGAL	PT	4	3
RUSSIA	RU	3	237
SWEDEN	SE	77	51 140
SINGAPORE	SG	5	999
SLOVENIA	SI	2	30
TURKEY	TR	2	41
TAIWAN	TW	41	75 198
UNITED STATES	US	513	1 053 152
SOUTH AFRICA	ZA	1	329

Patents are counted at the firm level. For patents co-applied by several firms, double counting is applied. A patent shared by firm A and firm B counts as one patent for firm A and one patent for firm B. As a consequence the total is higher than the total number of patents applied for in the CIB database.

Continent	Number of firms	Number of priority patents
Africa	1	329
Asia	734	6 062 207
Europe	1024	995 002
Latin America and the Caribbean	11	2 740
Northern America	538	1 072 068
Oceania	11	3 640
Total	2319	8 135 986

The distribution of priority patent applications from 1986 to 2009 by national or regional patent office is shown below.

Country of the patent office (appln_auth)	Number of priority applications	Country of the patent office (appln_auth)	Number of priority applications	Country of the patent office (appln_auth)	Number of priority applications
JP	5 319 006	LU	683	CR	22
US	1 252 880	TR	589	TH	20
KR	488 898	DO	433	BX	18
DE	383 434	ID	419	TJ	14
EP	130 561	YU	355	GT	13
GB	117 300	HK	340	BA	10
CN	112 929	XH	336	MD	9
FR	102 821	PT	291	EE	7
TW	31 725	MY	268	MW	7
SE	23 992	CS	246	VE	7
IT	15 885	HR	230	MC	6
FI	15 452	EG	220	MT	6
AU	14 204	GR	193	PK	6
IN	11 592	CU	188	NI	5
CH	11 566	RO	183	VN	5
CA	8 515	SU	182	BD	4
NL	8 121	PH	156	SM	4
DK	7 314	MA	128	BH	2
AT	4 184	IS	105	BY	2

IE	4 074	PE	90	KP	2
BR	4 058	CL	77	KZ	2
NO	3 282	SI	72	MK	2
ES	3 278	SK	71	OM	2
CZ	3 112	BG	69	SY	2
IB	2 964	LV	53	TN	2
ZA	2 911	SV	47	AE	1
SG	2 794	AP	45	AM	1
EM	2 222	OA	44	AZ	1
HU	1 928	PA	42	CY	1
BE	1 615	LT	40	IR	1
IL	1 503	DZ	38	JO	1
RU	1 418	EC	38	LB	1
NZ	1 381	UA	31	LK	1
AR	1 028	GC	29	NG	1
MX	1 019	ZW	29	PY	1
PL	974	EA	26	SB	1
DD	970	RS	26		
CO	870	HN	23		
UY	754	ZM	23		

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

- Information on the number of missing values (no ipc, no inventors, no date, no addresses, no countries)

The Patstat database includes artificial priority patents for which no information is available to the exception of the filing patent office and date of filing. When possible, filling of missing information of artificial patents was carried out (retrieved from other patents belonging to the same patent family) in the PATSTAT-IFRIS (see PATSTAT-IFRIS Report for further details). When missing applicants were filled, it allows to also consider artificial patents when matching the patents DB and the firm name list.

In CIB, 11,4% of the patents are artificial patents that were enriched prior to DB matching.

Patent origin	Number of first filing
Non artificial	7 187 452
Artificial	921 730
Total	8 109 182

1) Dates of patent applications

All the patent applications are given an application filling date and an application-filing year.

2) Missing information on patent inventors or patent applicants

As detailed in the PATSTAT-IFRIS section, patent often displays missing information on inventors and/or applicants. Despite several step to recover information from other databases (Regpat and Inpi databases), patents lacking inventor or applicant information are still present in the CIB database.

Different case of missing information exists:

- The database gives no information on any inventor (or applicant) of a patent. In that case, the patent application is present (with its appln_id) in table firm_tls201_appln_ifris but absent of the table invt_addr_ifris that includes only patent with at least a few information on inventors (or table applt_addr_ifris only patent with at least a few information on applicants).
- The number of priority patents (appln_id in firm_tls201_appln_ifris) without any information on inventors is 110 771 (appln_id not in table invt_addr_ifris). The number of priority patents (appln_id in firm_tls201_appln_ifris) without any information on applicants is 11 971 (appln_id not in table applt_addr_ifris)¹². The number of priority patents (appln_id in firm_tls201_appln_ifris) without any information on applicants nor on inventors is 28 (appln_id not in table applt_addr_ifris nor in table invt_addr_ifris). The number of priority patents applied for an entity belonging to a large firm (appln_id in Table firm_tls001_rappln_id) without any information on inventors is 110 739 (appln_id not in table invt_addr_ifris).
- The database gives information on inventor (or applicant) of a patent but this information may be partial (absence of the inventor or applicant name, address, country). In that case, the patent application is present (with its appln_id) in table invt_addr_ifris (or table applt_addr_ifris) but some fields are still empty after the filling steps described in the PATSTAT-IFRIS section.

The tables shown below give the number and share of given or missing information for inventors (or applicants) in the final CIB database (priority patents from 1986 to 2009). The statistics are calculated using data from table invt_addr_ifris for inventors and from table applt_addr_ifris for applicants.

Source	PersonName of inventors	Number	Share (%)
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¹² Patents without any information on applicants are patents belonging to inpadoc families of firm priority patents (see 2.1 of this report for further explanations)

Patstat Raw data	WithoutPersonName	6	0,00
Patstat Raw data	WithPersonName	14 663 514	76,32
ARTIFICIAL	WithoutPersonName	5	0,00
ARTIFICIAL	WithPersonName	2 975 012	15,49
INPI	WithPersonName	163 765	0,85
PROPAG	WithPersonName	1 115 432	5,81
REGPAT	WithPersonName	294 250	1,53
Total		19 211 984	100,00

Table invt_addr_ifris gives information for all inventor names (except 11) of the priority patents. $\frac{3}{4}$ of this information was given in the initial Patstat raw data (76%); 15% by retrieving information in patent families of artificial patents (see Pastat report for details).

The table below describes number and share of present and missing information in fields related to addresses of inventors. It gives statistics on two fields, the address field (complete information on the address) (field adr_final from Table invt_addr_ifris) and the country field (field ctry_final from Table invt_addr_ifris)

Source	Address of inventors	CtryCode	Number	Share (%)
Patstat Raw data	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	2 303 170	11,99
Patstat Raw data	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	7 889	0,04
Patstat Raw data	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	1 916 813	9,98
Patstat Raw data	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	10 435 648	54,32
ARTIF	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	2 106 892	10,97
ARTIF	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	1 826	0,01
ARTIF	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	254 981	1,33
ARTIF	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	611 318	3,18
INPI	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	163 388	0,85
INPI	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	375	0,00
INPI	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	2	0,00
PROPAG	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	1 113 399	5,80
PROPAG	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	2 033	0,01
REGPAT	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	293 202	1,53
REGPAT	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	1 048	0,01
Total			19 211 984	100,00

Source	PersonName of applicants	Number	Share (%)
Patstat Raw data	WithoutPersonName	2	0,00
Patstat Raw data	WithPersonName	7 592 258	78,25
ARTIF	WithoutPersonName	3	0,00

ARTIF	WithPersonName	1 660 617	17,11
INPI	WithPersonName	63 212	0,65
PROPAG	WithPersonName	268 955	2,77
REGPAT	WithPersonName	117 882	1,21
TOTAL		9 702 929	100,00

Table `applt_addr_ifris` gives information for all applicant names (except 5) of the priority patents. Most of this information was given in the initial `Patstat` raw data (78 %) and artificial patents (17%).

The table below describes number and share of present and missing information in fields related to addresses of applicants. It gives statistics on two fields, the address field (complete information on the address) (field `adr_final` from Table `applt_addr_ifris`) and the country field (field `ctry_final` from Table `applt_addr_ifris`).

Source	Address	CtryCode	NbAddressesApplications	Share (%)
Patstat Raw data	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	870 397	8,97
Patstat Raw data	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	1 173	0,01
Patstat Raw data	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	1 184 853	12,21
Patstat Raw data	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	5 535 837	57,05
ARTIF	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	666 940	6,87
ARTIF	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	360	0,00
ARTIF	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	694 294	7,16
ARTIF	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	299 026	3,08
INPI	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	63 208	0,65
INPI	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	2	0,00
INPI	WithoutAddress	WithoutCtryCode	2	0,00
PROPAG	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	268 531	2,77
PROPAG	WithAddress	WithoutCtryCode	424	0,00
REGPAT	WithAddress	WithCtryCode	117 876	1,21
REGPAT	WithoutAddress	WithCtryCode	6	0,00
total			9 702 929	100,00

3) Missing information on patent IPC code

140 203 priority patents (`appln_id` in Table `firm_tls201_appln_ifris` do not have any information on IPC (`appln_id` not in table `firm_appln_ipc techno`). 134 476 of them are priority patents of firms (present in Table `firm_tls001_rappln_id` and not in table `firm_appln_ipc techno`).

- Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

No external current assessment is available but exchanges on methodological strategies for DB building with FhG ISI are regularly programmed.

Various sources of noise have been identified:

- Quality for ORBIS information
- Quality of standardisation for applicants' names
- Patents where information does not allow a unequivocal allocation

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

- Legal issues concerning access of the database

Information can only be opened at aggregated level (i.e. group level). It can not be opened at a non aggregated level (i.e. at subsidiaries level) as it builds directly on ORBIS proprietary data.

- Owner of raw data:
- EPO and UPEM IFRIS for patent information
- Bureau van Dijk, IPTS and IFRIS for corporate data

Current practice for opening up of the database to external users :

The access to the CIB data within the RISIS project requires that the partners previously subscribe to the Patstat database (version Patstat 2011 Autumn or more version). The access is limited to academic exploitation and collaborations. No contractual use of the CIB data is allowed.

- Legal necessities for potential opening procedures: a Patstat subscription from users is required

4 Technical structure of *CIB*

4.1 Information on the data base system

- Current data base system used (e.g. Microsoft Access)

The current data base system is My SQL 5.1.63 with MyISAM as the default storage engine. In term of maintainability and backup, the main advantage of this storage engine is to use three different files for each table of a database:

- the data file has a .MYD (MYData) extension;
- the index file has a .MYI (MYIndex) extension;
- the structure file has a .frm extension.

MySQL is optimized for an intensive usage: a high level of accessibility and efficiency, for a low amount of users

- Planned future technical changes concerning data base system

No changes planned

4.2 Technical variable definition

- Labeling of all variables
- Data type of all variables (e.g., float, string, etc.)
- Current usage and definition of unique identifiers (if applicable)
- Name of the firm using various spellings (Table orb_guo_corr):

guo_name (varchar(255))

guo_name_std (varchar(255))

guo_name_patstatstd (varchar(255))

- Acronym of the firm (Table orb_guo_corr):

guo_acronym(vvarchar(255))

- Database id of the firm (Table orb_guo_corr, Table firm_tls0018rappln_id, Table firm_tls0018rappln_id_group):

guo_id : unique identifier (int(11))

- IndexScoreBoard of the firm (Table orb_guo_corr). This is the firm's id in the Industrial R&D investment Scoreboard:
IndexScoreBoard (double)
- Industry Classification of the firm (Table orb_guo_corr). It give the sector of the firm according to ICB categories (see below):
ICB (int(11))
- Country where the firm's headquarters is located (Table orb_guo_corr):
guo_etry (varchar(50))
- Country code where the firm's headquartes is located (Table orb_guo_corr) following the international two letter country code (ISO alpha-2):
guo_etrycode (varchar(50))

- Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) codes of the firms (Table orb_guo_corr). It is the business classification codes that the U.S. government assigns to businesses. SIC coding is used primarily to classify a company's main industry and line of business¹³:
 guo_sic_core_code (int(11))
 guo_sic_core (varchar(255))

The table below presents the country harmonisation that has been applied.

continent	region	lib_etry_harm	etry_harm	guo_etrycode	NbGUO
Africa	Southern Africa	SOUTH AFRICA	ZA	ZA	1
Asia	Eastern Asia	CHINA	CN	CN	80
Asia	Eastern Asia	HONG KONG	HK	HK	6
Asia	Western Asia	ISRAEL	IL	IL	10
Asia	South-central Asia	INDIA	IN	IN	326
Asia	Eastern Asia	JAPAN	JP	JP	245
Asia	Eastern Asia	SOUTH KOREA	KR	KR	18
Asia	South-eastern Asia	MALAYSIA	MY	MY	1
Asia	South-eastern Asia	SINGAPORE	SG	SG	5
Asia	Western Asia	TURKEY	TR	TR	2
Asia	Eastern Asia	TAIWAN	TW	TW	41
Europe	Western Europe	AUSTRIA	AT	AT	25
Europe	Western Europe	BELGIUM	BE	BE	39
Europe	Western Europe	SWITZERLAND	CH	CH	41
Europe	Eastern Europe	CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	CZ	2
Europe	Western Europe	GERMANY	DE	DE	182
Europe	Northern Europe	DENMARK	DK	DK	43
Europe	Southern Europe	SPAIN	ES	ES	21
Europe	Northern Europe	FINLAND	FI	FI	59
Europe	Western Europe	FRANCE	FR	FR	109
Europe	Northern Europe	UNITED KINGDOM	GB	BM	11
Europe	Northern Europe	UNITED KINGDOM	GB	GB	260
Europe	Northern Europe	UNITED KINGDOM	GB	GI	3
Europe	Northern Europe	UNITED KINGDOM	GB	KY	5
Europe	Southern Europe	GREECE	GR	GR	6
Europe	Eastern Europe	HUNGARY	HU	HU	2
Europe	Northern Europe	IRELAND	IE	IE	11
Europe	Southern Europe	ITALY	IT	IT	51
Europe	Western Europe	LIECHTENSTEIN	LI	LI	1
Europe	Western Europe	LUXEMBOURG	LU	LU	5
Europe	Southern Europe	MALTA	MT	MT	1
Europe	Western Europe	NETHERLANDS	NL	AN	1
Europe	Western Europe	NETHERLANDS	NL	NL	49
Europe	Northern Europe	NORWAY	NO	NO	8
Europe	Eastern Europe	POLAND	PL	PL	3
Europe	Southern Europe	PORTUGAL	PT	PT	4

¹³ http://www.ehow.com/facts_7277558_primary-sic-code_.html#ixzz33qksBG58

Europe	Eastern Europe	RUSSIA	RU	RU	3
Europe	Northern Europe	SWEDEN	SE	SE	77
Europe	Southern Europe	SLOVENIA	SI	SI	2
Latin America and the Caribbean	South America	BRAZIL	BR	BR	9
Latin America and the Caribbean	the Caribbean	BAHAMAS, THE	BS	BS	1
Latin America and the Caribbean	Central America	PANAMA	PA	PA	1
Northern America	Northern America	CANADA	CA	CA	25
Northern America	Northern America	UNITED STATES	US	US	513
Oceania	Australia and New Zealand	AUSTRALIA	AU	AU	9
Oceania	Australia and New Zealand	NEW ZEALAND	NZ	NZ	2

The table below presents the nomenclature of industrial super sectors, sectors and subsectors that has been used for firms.

industry	code ndus	supersector	codeS uper	sector	code Sect	subsector	code Sub
Oil & Gas	1	Oil & Gas	500	Oil & gas producers	530		0
Oil & Gas	0	Oil & Gas	0	Oil equipment, services & distribution	570		0
Oil & Gas	0	Oil & Gas	0	Alternative energy	580		0
Basic Materials	1000	Chemicals	1300	Chemicals	1350		0
Basic Materials	0	Basic Resources	1700	Forestry & paper	1730		0
Basic Materials	0	Basic Resources	0	Industrial metals	1750		0
Basic Materials	0	Basic Resources	0	Mining	1770		0
Industrials	2000	Construction & Materials	2300	Construction & materials	2350		0
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	2700	Aerospace & defence	2710		0
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	General industrials	2720		0
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Electronic & Electrical Equipment	2730	Electrical components & equipment	2733
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Electronic & Electrical Equipment	0	Electronic equipment	2737
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Industrial Engineering	2750	Commercial vehicles & trucks	2753
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Industrial Engineering	0	Industrial machinery	2757
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Industrial transportation	2770		0
Industrials	0	Industrial Goods & Services	0	Support services	2790		0
Consumer	3000	Automobiles &	3300	Automobiles & parts	3350		0

Goods		Parts					
Consumer Goods	0	Automobiles & Parts	0	Beverages	3530		0
Consumer Goods	0	Automobiles & Parts	0	Food producers	3570		0
Consumer Goods	0	Personal & Household Goods	3700	Household goods	3720		0
Consumer Goods	0	Personal & Household Goods	0	Leisure goods	3740		0
Consumer Goods	0	Personal & Household Goods	0	Personal goods	3760		0
Consumer Goods	0	Personal & Household Goods	0	Tobacco	3780		0
Health Care	4000	Health Care	4500	Health care equipment & services	4530		0
Health Care	0	Health Care	0	Pharmaceuticals & Biotechnology	4570	Biotechnology	4573
Health Care	0	Health Care	0	Pharmaceuticals & Biotechnology	0	Pharmaceuticals	4577
Consumer Services	5000	Retail	5300	Food & drug retailers	5330		0
Consumer Services	0	Retail	0	General retailers	5370		0
Consumer Services	0	Media	5500	Media	5550		0
Consumer Services	0	Travel & Leisure	5700	Travel & leisure	5750		0
Telecommunications	6000	Telecommunications	6500	Fixed line telecommunications	6530		0
Telecommunications	0	Telecommunications	0	Mobile telecommunications	6570		0
Utilities	7000	Utilities	7500	Electricity	7530		0
Utilities	0	Utilities	0	Gas, water & multiutilities	7570		0
Financials	8000	Banks	8300	Banks	8350		0
Financials	0	Insurance	8500	Nonlife insurance	8530		0
Financials	0	Insurance	0	Life insurance	8570		0
Financials	0	Real Estate	8600	Real Estate Investment & Services	8630		0
Financials	0	Real Estate	0	Real Estate Investment Trusts	8670		0
Financials	0	Real Estate	0	Real Estate Investment Trusts	8670		0
Financials	0	Financial Services	8700	Financial Services	8770		0
Financials	0	Financial Services	0	Equity Investment Instruments	8980		0
Financials	0	Financial Services	0	Nonequity Investment Instruments	8990		0
Technology	9000	Technology	9500	Software & Computer Services	9530	Computer services	9533
Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Internet	9535
Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Software	9537

Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Computer hardware	9572
Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Electronic office equipment	9574
Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Semiconductors	9576
Technology	0	Technology	0	Software & Computer Services	0	Telecommunications equipment	9578

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of *CIB* (if applicable)

- Definition of single tables

Here are described tables that are specific of the CIB database, i.e. not present in the Patstat Ifris database (those tables being described in the the Patstat Ifris section)

Table orb_guo_corr: this table give information related to the firms. The fields of this table are described in section 2.3

Table firm_tls001_rapln_id: this table links firms (guo_id) with priority patents (apln_id)

- relation between the tables via unique identifiers:
The list of unique identifiers related to patents is shown in the Patstat report. An additional identifier is present in CIB. It identifies the firm (guo_id).
The guo_id is used to relate Table firm_tls001_rapln_id and Table orb_guo_corr.

The database relational model, that connects the CIB and the PATSTAT IFRIS database is shown below. The first block presents the fields specific for the CIB. The second block presents additional fields that have been developed for matching patent data and financial data. Finally, the third diagram connects these 2 blocks with the PATSTAT IFRIS relational model.

CIB

New Layer

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)

- Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures (e.g. web interface for data search. etc.)

5 Further planning of the opening of *CIB*

- Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

We need to carry out a selection of fields and tables to be opened within RISIS

- Necessary updates and/or technical changes

None

- Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset

None

Report on the content and technical structure of the

ETER

Infrastructure

USI: Università della Svizzera italiana

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH**

Report on the content and technical structure of the European Tertiary Education Register ETER-RISIS

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TABLE 1. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Full Name
AQUAMETH	Advanced Quantitative Methods for the Evaluation of the performance of public sector research
DG EAC	Directorate General Education and Culture
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EFTA	European Free Trade Agreement
ERA	European Research Area
ETER	European Tertiary Education Register
EUMIDA	European Microdata Project
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
HC	Head Counts
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMDAS	Integrated Manufacturing Data Administration System
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Educational Degrees
NE	National Experts
NIFU	Nordic Institute for Studies in Innovation, Research and Education
NSA	National Statistical Authority
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
RISIS	Research Infrastructure for the Assessment of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy
UAS	Universities of Applied Sciences
UOE	Unesco OECD Eurostat handbook on educational statistics
USI	Università della Svizzera italiana

1 Basic characteristics

1.1 Overview of the facility

The ETER-EUMIDA facility is a set of databases providing a register of European Higher Education Institutions and containing basic statistical information on them, including descriptors, geographical information, students and graduates, personnel, finances, and research activities. These databases, created by merging data from national statistical authorities, are the only available comprehensive information on European higher education, and thus are of fundamental value for analytical purposes.

The ETER-EUMIDA facility is composed by three components:

- The ETER main database including data on the years 2011, 2012 and 2013 (2014 to be collected). It is available on-line at www.eter-project.com. Data can be downloaded in different formats.
- The EUMIDA database including data on the year 2008. It is available as off-line file (SPSS format).
- A file including additional data for the years 2008, 2011 and 2012, including the numbers of scientific publications, impact, participation to European programs. It is also available off-line as SPSS data file.

The three files share the same identifier system (see below 2.2) and therefore can be easily matched and combined for purposes of analysis.

Coverage is very extensive as both databases include not only doctorate-awarding HEIs, but also second-tier HEIs in binary systems, as well as a large number of specialized schools at the tertiary level. The estimated coverage of tertiary education at the bachelor, master and PhD is around 100%. Coverage currently includes all EU-28 countries, Iceland, Norway, Liechtenstein, Serbia, Switzerland, and FYROM (some countries are missing for some years).

The two datasets are built on the same basic approach, but also display some relevant differences in coverage, data sources, methodology and especially, engineering.

This report presents the characteristics of the ETER dataset and of its infrastructure. We will also highlight differences with EUMIDA, since a major issue for RISIS is to provide joint access to both datasets and present the additional data provided together with ETER and EUMIDA for purposes of scholarly research.

This report refers to the status of ETER in July 2015, after completing the first two waves of data collection have been completed. It draws heavily on the ETER handbook (Lepori, Bonaccorsi, Daraio, et al 2015a), as well as on the accompanying report on data collection (Lepori, Bonaccorsi, Daraio, et al 2015b).

This report reflects the status of the facility at the end of June 2016. It will be subsequently updated as soon as additional releases will be available.

1.2 Context and aims

EUMIDA and ETER have to be seen in the context of the movement towards the provision of micro-data at the level of individual Higher Education Institutions, which started with the PRIME-AQUAMETH project (Bonaccorsi and Daraio 2007). PRIME-AQUAMETH was an experimental project, which proved the feasibility of collecting HEI-level data from different countries and publicly available sources. Further, the project proved that, despite existing comparability problems (Bonaccorsi, Daraio, Lepori and Slipersaeter 2007), these data could be used to provide interesting analytical insights on European higher education (Lepori, Probst and Baschung 2010, Daraio, Bonaccorsi, Geuna, Lepori and et. al. 2011).

Following these results, the European Commission (DG EAC and EUROSTAT) funded in 2010-2011 a large-scale feasibility study for a European Register of Tertiary Education. The EUropean Micro DAta (EUMIDA) project developed a consistent methodology for the delineation of a census of HEIs in Europe and for the data collection from official sources. Further, the project managed to provide the first register of European Higher Education and to collect a large number of data (Lepori and Bonaccorsi 2013, Bonaccorsi 2014).

The European Tertiary Education Register (ETER) was launched in 2013 in order to consolidate and establish the EUMIDA methodology and to prepare for a regular data collection on European Higher Education. It is a service contract from the Directorate General of Education, Audiovisual and Culture (DG-EAC) and realized by a

consortium of four partners (Università della Svizzera italiana, JOANNEUM RESEARCH, NIFU and Università Roma La Sapienza) in cooperation with a number of national experts and national statistical authorities.

ETER builds on the results and experience of the EUMIDA (EUropean MIcroDAta collection) study, and has the following goals:

- To further develop the indicators tested in EUMIDA towards a set of more complete indicators while characterizing HEIs in the ERA by following their main activity dimensions.
- To extend the coverage of the EUMIDA dataset and consolidate the European Higher Education perimeter, i.e. the list of HEIs officially included in the dataset.
- To collect, validate, and publish the data for the defined perimeter for the years 2011 and 2012.
- To document the methodology developed for the project in a methodological handbook, while providing suggestions for the consolidation of the European Tertiary Education Register and for a regular data collection on European HEIs.

As of July 2015, the contract has completed the first two waves of data collection, referring to the year 2011 (respectively the academic year 2011/2012) and 2012 (academic year 2012/2013), finalized the data cleaning, and the dataset was made available on-line.

In July 2015, the European Commission awarded a follow-up contract for two additional years to the same consortium (plus the University of Pisa). The new contract foresees two additional waves of data collection for the year 2013 (to be published in June 2016) and 2014 (to be published in June 2017); some additional variables are foreseen, as well as a stronger focus on policy analysis and dissemination.

1.3 Legal name of the operating organization

The current ETER database is operated by JOANNEUM RESEARCH, Institute of Information and Communication Technology, Graz on behalf of the ETER consortium composed by Università della Svizzera italiana, JOANNEUM RESEARCH, NIFU and Università Roma la Sapienza. While the dataset has been collected through a service contract of the European Commission, and therefore is owned by the EU, the database system itself is proprietary to JOANNEUM RESEARCH.

1.4 Database location and type of access

The ETER database is located at JOANNEUM RESEARCH and is accessible on-line through a web application: www.eter-project.com.

Users can perform searches on the datasets and then download either the whole dataset or parts of it in an Excel format. Additionally, it is possible to download metadata and demographic information on the included HEIs, as well as methodological information on the project (methodological handbook). Public access is available for most of the data. Some data is available for research purposes only. For this data, restricted access under a non-disclosure agreement is possible.

The EUMIDA dataset and the ETER-EUMIDA additional data are available as stand-alone files, which can be provided to interested users under the signature of a non-disclosure agreement. They are available to registered users from the RISIS website.

2 Data content of ETER

2.1 Definition and description of observations

A key task of EUMIDA and ETER was to provide a clear definition of the *observation units* and of the *perimeter* to be considered, i.e. which units should be included in the register and in the data collection.

The unit of observation in ETER are Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). These are defined as entities

- which are recognizable as distinct organizations,
- which are nationally recognized as HEIs, and
- whose major activity is providing education at the tertiary level (ISCED 2011 level 5, 6, 7 and/or 8). R&D activities might be present, but are not a necessary condition for inclusion.

In practice, the definition of HEIs included universities (doctorate-awarding), non-university higher education (like Fachhochschulen) and specialized schools delivering education at the tertiary level. We provide below more detailed information on coverage in respect to the whole of national tertiary education.

The focus on HEIs implies that all data in ETER are aggregated at the level of the whole HEI and no subunit data are provided (even in case of multi-site organizations). The only relevant exceptions are foreign campuses, which follow standard practices in educational statistics and are treated as stand-alone organizations. ETER includes only descriptive information on the existence and localization of other education sites, but no disaggregated data at this level.

The definition of the organization is taken as adopted by national statistical authorities. In most cases, it corresponds to the legal entity, but some departures are possible for associated units and research centres. Different national practices in handling resources, staff, and students, meaning the actual definition may slightly differ by country.

A threshold has been implemented in the perimeter. This implies that institutions must have at least 200 students or 30 employees to be included in the ETER dataset. EUMIDA did not have such a threshold, and all research active HEIs, regardless of size, were included in the EUMIDA perimeter; as a matter of fact, practices in this respect differed between countries, with a few also including very small HEIs, while others were more restrictive.

2.2 Number of units and demography

ETER includes 2675 unique units referring to the year 2011, while EUMIDA includes 2471 units referring to the year 2009. However, the EUMIDA-ETER additional file includes only the 1378 HEIs in the so-called restricted set, for which enough data are available.

ETER introduced stable IDs across time for HEIs, as well as demographic notations to handle processes like births, deaths and mergers. In particular, HEIs common to EUMIDA and ETER carry the same ID and thus can be easily matched: more precisely, 1974 of 2471 HEIs in EUMIDA have been carried over in ETER. Most new cases concern countries not covered by EUMIDA. About 350 HEIs included in EUMIDA have been excluded in ETER because of not reaching the size threshold.

Importantly, no other variable is associated uniquely to IDs, but all HEI characteristics are collected and recorded by individual years, including variables such as HEI name, country, and location.

Technically, *unique records* in the ETER database are characterized by the pair HEI-ID and YEAR. Additionally, consistency across time is maintained as IDs are carried over from year to year when HEIs do not witness demographic changes.

Rules for handling demographic events correspond to the approach of the Business Units Register. For instance, in the case of mergers, the parent organizations ID's are reserved, but become non active, whereas the new organization receives a new ID. A separate record of demographic events is maintained in order to be able to track dependencies (see the ETER handbook for full reference).

The table below provides an overview of demographic events between EUMIDA and ETER. Note that changes in the name of an organization do not necessarily constitute a demographic event and imply a change of ID, which is also the case when an institution changes its legal status.

TABLE 2. OVERVIEW OF DEMOGRAPHIC EVENTS BETWEEN 2009 AND 2011

Event code	Description	N EUMIDA	N ETER	Remarks
0	no demographic event	1974	1974	
1	entry	0	557	Related to the integration of new countries in the dataset
1	entry	0	80	Entries in countries already covered by EUMIDA
2	exit	382	0	Most cases because HEIs are below the size threshold of ETER
3	birth	0	24	
4	death	36	0	
5	merger	32	13	
6	split	1	2	
7	take-over	42	21	
8	spin-out (spin-off)	0	2	Two cases of foreign colleges created by existing HEIs in the perimeter

Source: Lepori et al. (2014b).

2.3 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

As a general rule, ETER data are provided from official sources, like the National Statistical Authorities and/or Research and Higher Education Ministries, meaning data should be considered as officially validated. Primary sources are in most cases administrative data collected at the national level for management and statistical purposes (like the preparation of the EUROSTAT educational statistics).

There are a few exceptions to this rule: in many cases, organizational descriptors and geographical information were provided by the consortium itself based on Internet sources. In a few countries, statistical data were also elaborated by the consortium based on data published online by the NSA. A full documentation of sources is provided in the metadata.

The process was organized in the following main steps.

- a) *Definition of the perimeter.* For the countries participating in EUMIDA, the National Statistical Authorities received a pre-filled sheet including all EUMIDA HEIs in their respective countries and were requested to update the sheet by indicating changes which occurred in the period 2009-2011. A systematic notation of demographic events was provided. The perimeter also included the official name of the HEI (in the national language and English) in 2011 as reference.
- b) *Data collection.* Based on the perimeter, the consortium provided master MS-Excel files for the data collection. These sheets include all variables, as well as remark fields. Moreover, metadata were collected in separate sheets for each individual variable. NSAs are also requested to provide detailed methodological explanations on some variables for which comparability is expected, specifically financial and staff data.
- c) *Checking of the data.* Data sheets received were subject to a set of extensive checks for inconsistencies and problematic values by the consortium (see table 2 below). This was important in order to address issues related to underlying problems in the data, misinterpretation of guidelines, as well as simple mistakes in the handling of the data. A list of checks which have been performed can be found in the ETER handbook.

TABLE 3. DESCRIPTION OF DATA VALIDATION PROCEDURES IN ETER

Type of checks	Description	Procedure
Accuracy checks	Accuracy checks verify that data entered have the right format foreseen by the handbook (for example years as a 4-digit numeric code) and that no logically impossible values are found (foundation year>2011).	Accuracy checks are performed in the data collection sheet and on delivered data. Simple mistakes are corrected directly, whereas unclear cases are reported back to NSAs/NEs for clarification and correction.
Completeness checks	Particular attention in ETER has been devoted to the correct coding of blanks and missing values. As a general rule, ETER does not include any blank cells and the null value ("0") is reserved for the case where it is known that the corresponding value is null. All other cases are coded with special codes like missing ("m"), not applicable ("a"), included in totals ("x") or in another column ("xc") or row ("xr").	Blank cells are highlighted automatically. Clear cases are recoded directly and ambiguous cases (for example between missing and not applicable) are reported back to national experts and NSAs.
Consistency checks	a) These checks control for logical consistency between different variables, for example when the highest degree delivered is at ISCED 7 level, all values for students and graduates at ISCED8 level should be not applicable. Rules in this respect are stipulated in the handbook. b) Further, these checks also control whether the sums of breakdowns by subcategories equals the total and numerical relationships between values (example R&D expenditures lower than total expenditures).	Clear cases are recoded directly and ambiguous cases (for example between missing and not applicable) are reported back to national experts and NSAs. Remaining inconsistencies are flagged.
Deviant cases	Standard ratios are calculated (for example students to graduates) and compared to the national averages. See the handbook for the list of ratios.	Deviant values are identified and checked. In case there are specific reasons, an explanation is added to the metadata for that specific HEI.
Check of missing data	An analysis of missing data is performed (also including issues of breakdowns by subcategories).	When it is expected that data should be available, possibly with some limitations, this is requested to NE/NSAs.
Control of metadata completeness	Metadata are systematically controlled for completeness, taking into account also issues emerging from the checks on the data.	When metadata are missing or incomplete, further information is requested. Quality of metadata is critical for the exploitation of the database.
Expert checks	Expert checks based on knowledge of national systems, as well on information available on the Web and EUMIDA data, are performed in order to ensure that provided data are realistic.	Potentially problematic cases are notified back to national experts and NSAs. When these are related to methodological issues, the corresponding remarks are integrated into the metadata.

2.4 Cleaning of the EUMIDA datasets

The original dataset for the year 2008 produced by the EUMIDA project displayed a number of differences in respect to ETER. The most important ones are:

- The list of variables is partially different, not only concerning their names, but also less variables were included especially for what concerns descriptors and geographical information.
- Some classifications differed, as EUMIDA used the old ISCED-1997 classification, as well as FOE-2007 for the fields of education.
- No systematic coding of missing data was available, they were included as blank cells in the database.
- No flags and less remarks were included in the dataset.

- The documentation of the dataset and metadata is less systematic and less usable, as it was provided in the form of a large word file.

The cleaning of the dataset had the goal of making EUMIDA as similar as possible to ETER in order to allow users to combine in a smooth way the two datasets for the purposes of longitudinal analysis. Following main changes were made:

- Descriptors and geographical information was systematically compared between ETER and EUMIDA and inconsistent cases were cleaned. To the extent of possible, the additional variables introduced in ETER have been integrated in EUMIDA as well (for example postcode and geographical coordinates).
- All EUMIDA variables have been renamed identically to ETER. Variable codes and labels have also been made uniform.
- Blank cells have been coded to ETER standard codes.
- Classifications have been updated. For example ISCED-F-2011 is adopted (the two missing fields not included in FOE-1997 consistently recoded as “xc”).
- Flags and remarks columns have been introduced in order to be able to track any specific issues.
- Accuracy and consistency checks have been run.

The revised EUMIDA file will be available in SPSS format, accompanied by the original metadata file and by a file specifying changes which have been made.

2.5 Information all variables/indicators

Both ETER and EUMIDA include the following groups of variables:

- Institutional descriptors, e.g. the name of the institution and the foundation year.
- Geographical descriptors like the NUTS region, the city of the main seat and its postcode.
- Data on numbers of students and graduates divided by ISCED-2011 level, by gender, fields of education, citizenship and mobility.
- Data on HEI expenditures and revenues.
- Data on the number of staff, divided between academic and non-academic, available both as headcount (HC) and full-time-equivalents (FTE), as well as on the number of professors (HC).
- Data on research activities (PhD students, R&D expenditures).

Differences between EUMIDA and ETER are as follows. ETER includes a few additional variables, especially concerning geographical information and staff. Moreover, in EUMIDA, many variables and breakdowns are only available for the so-called research-active HEIs. These institutions comprise about half of the EUMIDA sample, but most of the students and research activities. Finally, ETER adopts the more recent release of classifications of educational levels (ISCED-2011) and educational fields (ISCED-F).

To the extent of possible, the current version of EUMIDA has been updated and extended to match ETER definitions (see details below). Variables in ETER and EUMIDA also have identical labels in order to make a merge of both datasets easier.

For full reference on the revision and cleaning of the EUMIDA dataset the reader is requested to read the corresponding document.

2.5.1 List of variables

The table below provides a full list of ETER variables, with additional information on their availability in EUMIDA. For complete information and definitions the reader should refer to the ETER handbook. In general, most definitions concerning students, graduates, staff and finances are derived from the UOE data collection handbook (UOE 2006), respectively with the OECD 2002 Frascati manual for R&D expenditures and thus comply with official statistics at EUROSTAT and OECD.

TABLE 4. FULL LIST OF ETER VARIABLES

Dimension	Variables	Differences in EUMIDA
Identifiers	ETER ID Country code National identifier (optional) Institution name (in own language) English institution name (if available) Year	Same variables in EUMIDA.
Basic institutional descriptors	Country Code Legal status Institution category, national definition (in own language) Institution category, national definition (in English, if available) Institution category standardized Foreign campus Foundation year Legal status year Ancestor year University hospital Institutional website	The same variables are also included in EUMIDA.
Geographic information	Region of establishment, NUTS2 code Region of establishment, NUTS3 code Name of the city Postcode Multi-site institution	The same variables are also included in EUMIDA.
Educational activities	Highest degree delivered Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Number of graduates at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Distance education institution	Number of students: only aggregated values for ISCED5-7 are available (no breakdown between levels 5,6 and 7). The 1997 FOE classification is used, hence ISCED-F04 included in ISCEDF03 and ISCED-F06 included in ISCED-F05.
Research activities	Research active institution Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 8, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Number of graduates at ISCED levels 8 (doctorates), by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility R&D expenditure	The 1997 FOE classification is used, hence ISCED-F04 included in ISCEDF03 and ISCED-F06 included in ISCED-F05.
Expenditures	Personnel expenditure Non-personnel expenditure Capital expenditure Accounting of capital expenditure	
Revenues	Core budget Third party funding Private funding Tuition fees	

	Student fees funding	
Staff	Number of academic staff in FTE Number of academic staff in headcounts Number of academic staff, by fields of education gender and citizenship in headcounts Number of administrative staff in FTE Number of administrative staff in headcounts Number of full professors (HC) Inclusion of PhD students Number of total staff in FTE Number of total staff in HC	Staff data only in FTEs. No data by fields and on numbers of professors. No data on gender.
Indicators	Share of women among students ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of women among graduates ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of women among PhD students and graduates (ISCED8). Share of women among academic staff and full professors. Share of foreigners among students ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of foreigners among graduates ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of foreigners among PhD students and graduates (ISCED8). Share of mobile among students ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of mobile among graduates ISCED6 and ISCED7. Share of mobile among PhD students and graduates (ISCED8). Subject concentration of undergraduate students (ISCED5-7). Subject concentration of PhD graduates (ISCED8). Subject concentration of academic staff. PhD intensity Full professors as share of academic staff (headcounts). Academic staff as share of total staff (headcounts). Core budget as a share of total budget. Third-party funds as a share of total budget. Students' revenues as a share of total budget.	Not currently available in EUMIDA
Erasmus mobility data	Number of incoming Erasmus students Number of outgoing Erasmus students	Not currently available in EUMIDA

2.5.2 Additional variables

The additional dataset for ETER-EUMIDA includes variables not covered by the core dataset, but relevant for purposes of analysis of higher education. The current set of variables includes:

- The number of participations of EU Framework Programmes derived from the EUPRO database.
- The number of publications of HEIs derived from the Leiden rankings.
- A correspondence table with the OECD/EUROSTAT functional urban areas, which allows matching ETER with data on regional development (<http://www.oecd.org/regional/redefiningurbananewwaytomeasuremetropolitanareas.htm>).

This set of variables might be expanded in the future. For full reference on the additional dataset the reader should consult the corresponding document with detailed description of variables and sources.

2.6 Temporal, geographical and sectoral coverage

2.6.1 Temporal coverage

EUMIDA-ETER data are in principle collected for every year. EUMIDA provides data for the year 2008, whereas ETER for the year 2011 and 2012 and 2013. Data for the year 2014 will be available in summer 2017, respectively 2017.

Depending on the nature of the data and the practices of data collection, individual data refer to slightly different periods as detailed in Table 5. Departures from these reference periods for individual countries are recorded in the metadata.

TABLE 5. REFERENCE PERIODS

Variable	Reference period/date
Descriptors and geographical information	Last day of calendar year (31 st of December).
Expenditures	Calendar year (1 st January – 31 st of December).
Revenues	Calendar year (1 st January – 31 st of December).
Personnel FTE	Calendar year based on person-years.
Personnel headcount	End of first month of beginning of academic year.
Students	End of first month of beginning of academic year.
Degrees (including PhD degrees)	Academic year or calendar year (to be specified).

2.6.2 Geographical coverage

ETER covers all 28 European Union member states, EEA-EFTA countries (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland), as well as candidate countries (the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and Turkey), for a total of 36 countries.

Data for the following countries are currently missing:

EUMIDA 2008: France, Iceland, Liechtenstein, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Montenegro, Serbia and Turkey.

ETER 2011: Belgium (French part), Romania, Slovenia, Montenegro and Turkey.

ETER 2012: Belgium (French part), Romania, Slovenia, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, Turkey, Iceland and Hungary.

ETER 2012: Belgium (French part), Romania, Slovenia, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, Liechtenstein, Montenegro, Slovakia, Turkey, Iceland and Hungary.

2.6.3 Sectorial coverage

ETER aims to provide a fairly complete coverage of the European Higher Education sector (tertiary education), as defined by graduation of at least the ISCED-2011 level 5 (diploma at the tertiary level). The criterion that tertiary education should be a major activity excludes professional organizations (delivering only some curricula), as well as public research organizations (even if they employ PhD students as researchers).

Almost all ETER organizations belong to the higher education sector. There are a few cases of research organizations included in ETER either because they award a large number of PhD degrees or because they are associated with a university.

In general, the ETER coverage matches fairly well the official list of HEIs considered as part of the higher education system at the national level, with the exclusion of very small HEIs. As previously mentioned, a threshold has been implemented; meaning institutions must have at least 200 students and 30 staff (FTE) to be included in the ETER dataset. Coverage at the bachelor, master and PhD level in ETER should be considered as quite complete. The same applies for research activities in the higher education sector. In respect to all tertiary

education (graduating from ISCED level 5 onwards), ETER covers educational providers delivering short diplomas of less than 3 years only to a limited extent (ISCED level 5), like professional schools in the vocational sector or preparatory classes before university studies. In terms of the number of students, ETER includes 85% of the tertiary education students in the countries that delivered data, respectively 65% in the countries that provided information about the perimeter, i.e. the number of higher education institutions.

2.7 Classifications used in the database

2.7.1 Type of HEI

This variable specifies a European-level standardized classification of Higher Education Institutions. It is relevant in order to provide comparative analysis of higher education systems and analyze subgroups. It is available in ETER only.

The following categories are used:

- UNI (university). These HEIs display a largely academic orientation (without excluding some focus on applied research), they have the right to award doctorate degrees, and can bear the full name of “University” (including variants like technological university, etc.). In general, awarding doctorates should be the main criterion to classify HEIs in this category, even if a few doctoral-awarding HEIs might be included in the two following categories.
- UAS (university of applied sciences). These institutions are officially recognized as a part of higher education, though not as universities (see definition above). Commonly these institutions have a focus on professional education. In most cases they do not have the right to award a doctorate (exceptions are possible). Examples are Fachhochschulen (Austria, Germany), Hogescholen (Netherlands), colleges (Norway), and Polytechnics (Finland). This institutional category applies only to countries that have a binary HE system, where these institutions are given a specific legal status. Examples include Norway, Switzerland and the Netherlands.
- Other. All institutions that do not fit the description of university/university of applied science will be categorized as “other.” This may apply to institutions such as art academies and military schools. Also technological and professional schools in countries without a binary system (like the UK or France) should be classified in this way.

2.7.2 Legal status

Consistent with the UOE manual, a classification of HEIs by legal status is provided both in ETER and EUMIDA.

The distinction between *public* and *private* is made according to whether a public agency or a private entity has the ultimate control over the institution. *Ultimate control* is decided with reference to who has the power to determine the general policies and activities of the institution and to appoint the officers managing the school. Ultimate control will usually also extend to the decision to open or close the institution. As many institutions are under the operational control of a governing body, the constitution of that body will also have a bearing on the classification.

Private institutions are further divided between *government dependent* – which either receives more than 50% of their core funding from government agencies or whose teaching staff is paid by a government agency – and *independent private*.

Thus, this classification includes three categories: public, private, private government-dependent.

2.7.3 Geographical classification

ETER provides extensive geographical information on HEIs. For each HEI, the following geographical data is included:

- Country code.
- NUTS 2 and NUTS 3 code of the main seat (only NUTS included in EUMIDA).
- The name of the city and the postcode of the legal seat (not included in EUMIDA).
- Geographical coordinates (derived from the postcode) are foreseen in one of the next releases (not included in EUMIDA).

Additional information is provided for multi-site institutions, i.e. HEIs having establishments in different cities. This includes additional NUTS codes and descriptive information on the locations.

2.7.4 Levels of education

The International Standard Classification of Educational Degrees (ISCED)¹ provides information on the level of curricula and is therefore used to break down numbers of students and graduates. ETER adopts the more detailed ISCED-2011 classification, which includes separate classifications for bachelor (ISCED6), master (ISCED7) and PhD (ISCED8). The classification scheme used in ETER singles out the so-called long degrees (ISCED7 long), i.e. 4-5 year curricula without an intermediate classification. EUMIDA used a simpler distinction between diploma, bachelor, master and PhD, which can, in principle, be matched to ISCED-2011.

The table below provides detailed information on the classification used in ETER.

TABLE 6. ISCED-2011 CLASSIFICATION

ISCED-2011 level	Definition	Criteria
ISCED 5 short-cycle tertiary education	Programs at ISCED level 5, or short-cycle tertiary education, are often designed to provide participants with professional knowledge, skills and competencies. Typically, they are practically based, occupationally specific and prepare students to enter the labor market. However, these programs may also provide a pathway to other tertiary education programs. Academic tertiary education programs below the level of a Bachelor's program or equivalent are also classified as ISCED level 5.	Duration: 2-3 years Entry requirements: ISCED 3 or 4
ISCED 6 Bachelor's or equivalent levels	Programs at ISCED level 6, bachelor's or equivalent level, are often designed to provide participants with intermediate academic and/or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a first degree or equivalent qualification. Programs at this level are typically theoretically-based but may include practical components and are informed by state of the art research and/or best professional practice. They are traditionally offered by universities and equivalent tertiary educational institutions.	Duration: 2-3 years Entry requirements: ISCED 3 or 4 Usually: first degree at tertiary level
ISCED 7 Master of equivalent level	Programs at ISCED level 7, master's or equivalent level, are often designed to provide participants with advanced academic and/or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a second degree or equivalent qualification. Programs at this level may have a substantial research component but do not yet lead to the award of a doctoral qualification. Typically, programs at this level are theoretically-based but may include practical components and are informed by state of the art research and/or best professional practice. They are traditionally offered by universities and other tertiary educational institutions.	Duration: 2-3 years Entry requirements: ISCED 6 Usually: second degree at tertiary level Direct access to ISCED 8 level
ISCED 7long Master or equivalent level long degrees	Long first degree program at a master's or equivalent level with a cumulative theoretical duration (at the tertiary level) of at least five years (that does not require prior tertiary education). These programs will be singled out in ETER when possible, given their different characteristics and their impact on the number of diplomas.	Duration: at least 5 years Entry requirements: ISCED 3 or ISCED 4 Usually: first degree at tertiary level Direct access to ISCED 8 level
ISCED 8 Doctoral or Equivalent level	Programs at ISCED level 8, or doctoral or equivalent level, are designed primarily to lead to an advanced research qualification. Programs at this ISCED level are devoted to advanced study and original research and are typically offered only by research-oriented tertiary educational institutions such as universities. Doctoral	Duration: at least 3 years Entry requirements: ISCED 7 Research-based

¹ ISCED: <http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Pages/international-standard-classification-of-education.aspx>

	programs exist in both academic and professional fields.	programs (not only courses).
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2.7.5 Fields of education

The Fields of Education and Training classification allows breaking down numbers of students and graduates by field of study. It is envisaged to introduce this classification also for academic staff.

ETER adopts the most recent version of the classification, i.e. the Fields of Education and Training 2013 classification². EUMIDA used the previous Fields of Education classification 1997: the main difference between the two classification schemes is that in ISCED-F 2013 two new fields have been distinguished, namely Business, Administration and Law (included in social sciences in the previous schemes) and ICT (included in natural sciences in FOE-1997).

For students and graduates, the breakdown by field of education is provided separately by level of education.

TABLE 7. FIELDS OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING CLASSIFICATION

Code	Name	Subfields	ISCED 1997 FOE
00	General programs and qualifications	001 Basic programs and qualifications 002 Literacy and numeracy 003 Personal skills	01 Basic programs 08 Literacy and numeracy 09 Personal development
01	Education	011 Education	14 Teacher training and education science
02	Humanities and Arts	021 Arts 022 Humanities 023 Languages	21 Arts 22 Humanities
03	Social sciences	031 Social and behavioral science 032 Journalism and information	31 Social and behavioral science 32 Journalism and information
04	Business and law	041 Business and administration 042 Law	34 Business and administration 38 Law
05	Natural Science, mathematics and statistics	051 Biological and related sciences 052 Environment 053 Physical sciences 054 Mathematics and statistics	42 Life sciences Part of 62 (natural parks and wildlife) 44 Physical sciences 46 Mathematics and statistics
06	Information and communication technologies	061 Information & Communication Technologies	48 Computing
07	Engineering, manufacturing and construction	071 Engineering and engineering trades 072 Manufacturing and processing 073 Architecture and construction	52 Engineering and engineering trades (plus most of 85 environmental protection) 54 Manufacturing and processing 58 Architecture and building
08	Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and veterinary	081 Agriculture 082 Forestry 083 Fisheries 084 Veterinary	62 Agriculture, forestry and fishery (minus natural parks and wildlife) 64 Veterinary
09	Health and welfare	091 Health 092 Welfare	72 Health 76 Social services
10	Services	101 Personal services 102 Safety services 103 Security services 104 Transport services	81 Personal services Part of 85 environmental protection (community sanitation and labor protection and security) 86 Security services

² ISCED-F; <http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Pages/international-standard-classification-of-education.aspx>

			84 Transport services
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2.7.6 Citizenship and mobility

ETER includes classification of students, graduates and staff by:

- Citizenship, distinguishing between nationals and foreigners.
- Mobility (students and graduates only), distinguishing between residents (nationals and foreigners who earned their qualifying education in the country) and mobile students.

Both classifications are compliant with standard EUROSTAT definitions from the UOE manual (UOE 2006).

These breakdowns are provided separately by ISCED level (but not by field of education).

3 Quality and accuracy of data

ETER data have been subject to an extensive data validation and quality control procedure, which has been coordinated by the University of Rome La Sapienza together with the other consortium partners. Since ETER has no control over the primary sources, much of the data quality process is concerned with documenting methodological departures and comparability problems in order to make the users aware of potential problems.

EUMIDA data have been subject to some data quality controls, but in a somewhat less systematic way. Documentation of methodological and comparability issues is provided in an accompanying document, but currently not systematically linked to the data themselves.

3.1 Overall data quality approach

The ETER approach to data quality is based on the combination of two integrated processes:

1. preliminary level quality and validation checks performed within the data collection phase on a country basis in order to allow for an easy return on the respondents and the correction of data before online integration (see also chapter 2), and
2. a final quality and validation phase which has the role of performing more complex controls that can provide hints to use data in the appropriate way and improve the quality of the collection in the second wave. In this phase the quality control is performed on data at both a “global” and “local” level.

Different methods are applied:

- A systematic analysis of *internal data quality*, more specifically referring to four dimensions: format accuracy, completeness, consistency, and timeliness (see the ETER handbook for details).
- Advanced statistical methods for *outlier detection* by estimation of the distribution of observations according to a model distribution (mostly a lognormal distribution) and by identification of extreme values which do not fit into this distribution (see the ETER handbook and Ruocco and Daraio 2013, for full details).
- Checks of external validity through comparisons with other data sources or with information available from the Internet; this was particularly useful in order to explain observed inconsistencies and deviant cases, which were due to specific characteristics of the considered HEI.

3.2 Accuracy and consistency

Accuracy evaluates the compliance of the value to the requested format, as defined in the data chapter of the ETER handbook, respectively in the definitions of each variable. This includes characteristics like being non-negative for all financial values, and student and graduate data being integer variables, among others. This also includes the correct coding of missing and null values.

Consistency verifies possible violations of semantic rules defined over the involved data, and specifically between different variables.

Given the nature of the ETER dataset, there is a high number of mutual dependencies between variables, which can be exploited for purposes of data quality analysis. In broad terms, they can be regrouped in the following categories (see a complete list in the ETER handbook):

- Logical dependencies between categorical variables and values. For example, when the highest degree delivered is ISCED 5, all numbers of students and graduates at levels 6-8 have to be coded as “not applicable.” Similarly, if an HEI is non-research active, R&D expenditure should be “not applicable.” Most of these rules are already stipulated in the definition of these variables.
- Sums of breakdowns of variables equal to the total, for example the sum of male, female, and gender unclassified students should be equal to the total.
- Relationships between valued variables. For example, R&D expenditure should be lower than total expenditures. The ancestor year should precede the foundation year of the actual HEI (which, according to the definition in ETER, should precede or be the same as the legal status year).

These dimensions have been systematically checked during the data collection process. A final check on the complete dataset has been performed before publication.

Overall, the current version of the ETER dataset reaches a very good level of accuracy and consistency. Very few remaining cases are due to national specificities or simply to rounding errors. These have been flagged in the dataset.

3.3 Completeness

Completeness of data strongly varies by variable and by country. Overall, we can summarize the situation as follows:

- Descriptors are generally available for all countries, with the exception of a few cases where information on foundation years was not available.
- Financial data (revenues, expenditures, R&D expenditures) are available for only about one-third of the countries in 2011.
- Staff data are generally available in most countries. The main exceptions are countries which provided for the time being only the descriptors and no statistical information. However, the breakdown of academic staff between national and foreign citizenship is available for a much smaller number of countries.
- Students and graduates data are available for most countries, including breakdowns by gender, nationality, and fields of education. The breakdown by mobile students is less widely available. Since this is a breakdown requested by EUROSTAT, but not yet implemented in all countries, the number of countries providing this breakdown is believed to increase.
- The situation is similar for PhD students. Some major countries, such as Spain and the UK, did not deliver data on PhD-students at all.

The level of completeness varies largely by country. In the analyzed dataset there is a group of countries with a very high level of completeness (over 85%) including CH, CY, DE, DK, IE, IT, LI, LU, MT, NO, SE, a second group with an acceptable level (50%-85%) including AT, BG, CZ, EE, ES, FI, GR, IS, LT, LV, MK, NL, PL, PT, and a third group with minor data availability (below 50%) including BE (for French part only descriptors are available), FR, HR, UK.

3.4 Ratios and outlier identification

A central component of the data quality process in ETER was a careful analysis of ratios between variables. This involved two main types of checks:

- a) whether ratios are in a reasonable range which could be expected from the process considered (for example whether ratio between students and graduates is near the usual length of the curriculum), and
- b) whether ratios for individual HEIs and for whole countries are within a reasonable range in the overall distribution. The latter analysis was performed by comparing the distribution of ratios with hypothetical distributions (notably, lognormal) in order to ascertain whether observations are “unlikely” to be generated from the empirically (robustly) estimated distribution.

This analysis identified a number of deviant cases, which were then checked manually. Most cases could be explained by specificities of the observed HEI and have been documented within the dataset. Other cases revealed mistakes which were corrected in agreement with NSAs.

3.5 Metadata and comparability problems

In order to highlight problems of comparability between ETER figures across countries, specific metadata have been collected together with quantitative variables. Although the degree of completeness of metadata is lower than the average level of the dataset and information is sometimes incomplete, metadata are an essential resource in order to understand problems highlighted by the quality control of the data, as in many cases revealed data problems are already explained by the providing NSA. In this respect, data quality and metadata analysis are complementary.

Some emerging issues revealed by the metadata are the following:

- Total expenditure is not perfectly comparable for countries which do not include capital expenditures or with a definition of capital expenditures different from the others.
- The breakdown of revenues by categories, although not always recalled in metadata, may hide different classification choices which can have a minor impact on the comparability of figures.
- Minor specificities about inclusion and classification of staff across countries and within countries among HEI categories (typically universities vs. colleges) may impact full comparability.
- Staff data are available in some countries only in headcounts, in others in Full-Time-Equivalents (FTE).
- Classifications of students by new ISCED levels of education are not straightforward in every country. Nevertheless the problem was solved for the majority of cases, with a few exceptions where no disaggregation was possible.
- Similar consideration applies for classification by field of education: in several countries the ISCED-97 classification was used.
- A breakdown of students and graduates by mobility status is not fully comparable among countries, since different criteria to identify mobile students are adopted (residence, place of prior education).
- Information on R&D expenditure per HEI is available only in a subset of countries.

Metadata can be accessed directly on the ETER website and are sorted by variable and country. Concerning EUMIDA, metadata have been summarized in a written document that can be downloaded together with the data.

3.6 Flags

In order to alert users concerning data and comparability issues, data flags are introduced directly in the dataset (in separate columns alongside the data columns). The dataset includes also short remarks explaining the flag and referring to metadata for full explanations. For example a flag like “d” (definition differs) might be accompanied by the remark that mobile students are counted based on residence (rather than on place of prior education).

The table below provides a full list of flags for the ETER dataset.

TABLE 8. LIST OF FLAGS

Code	Description	Definition
b	Break in time series	When changes in definitions or data collection procedures imply that the data are not comparable across years. This flag will be relevant in the framework of multi-annual data collection.
d	Definition differs	Differences in definitions adopted for data collection imply that the value of the marked cells differs significantly from those complying with the ETER methodology.
i	See metadata	There are specific conditions which imply that the value of a cell should be interpreted in a different way or not directly compared with others.
ic	Inconsistent	Either when the sum of break down differs from the total or another semantic rule is violated.
rd	Rounding differences	When a sum of data does not fully correspond to the total because of rounding differences.
c	Confidential	When data are available, but restricted to public access (this flag is relevant only for user with unrestricted access).
ms	Missing subcategory	This flag is applied to totals in order to warn users that the total does not include one relevant subcategory (for example total expenditures not including capital expenditures).

3.7 Special codes

Special codes replace blank cells, which are not allowed in the dataset, providing more information on why a numerical value cannot be provided. These special codes largely follow standard conventions by Eurostat.

TABLE 9. SPECIAL CODES

Code	Description	Definition
m	Missing	The data is not available.
a	Not applicable	This variable is not applicable for the specific case. For example, number of PhD students in non-doctorate awarding HEIs is coded in this way.
x	Included in totals	The data are not available, but it is included in the total. This applies for example when data on revenues from student's fees are not available, but nevertheless these amounts are included in the total revenues of the HEI.
xc	Included in another column	The data are not available, but are included in the value for another column. This applies for examples when educational fields cannot be split.
xr	Included in another row	The data are not available but are included in another row. This happens in the rare case that two HEIs are part of a holding and have a common budget.
c	Confidential	When data are available, but restricted to public access, this code is displayed in place of the data.
s	Below threshold	This code is displayed in the public dataset when the count of a cell is so low that data protection issues might arise as individuals can be identified (for example number of students below 3).

4 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

4.1 Owner of the raw data

National Statistical Agencies and/or Ministries of Research and Higher Education are the owners of most of the raw data in ETER, and in particular, almost all statistical data.

The consortium itself has collected descriptors from public sources.

Since ETER is under a service contract of the European Commission, the owner of the dataset is the European Commission.

The situation concerning EUMIDA is similar, as the dataset is legally owned by the European Commission. There is however no systematic documentation of data sources and thus it is impossible to track ownership of the raw data (even if most probably originates from the NSAs).

4.2 Access to the data and conditions of use

In many countries, raw data reported in ETER are publicly available at the national level. The NSAs in these countries have confirmed this to the ETER consortium. For other countries with restricted access, the NSAs have signed an agreement for data disclosure, and delivered this to the ETER consortium. These agreements allow public access for the largest part of the data, while a few data (mostly financial) are under restricted access for research purposes (under the condition of non-disclosure of individual data points).

Access to restricted data is possible under signature of a non-disclosure agreement.

Additional datasets and the EUMIDA dataset (as soon as it is available) will be available through the RISIS projects. To this aim, potential users need to register to the RISIS system, accept the RISIS code of conduct and to sign a non-disclosure agreement (which covers both the ETER confidential data and additional data in RISIS).

5 Technical structure of the ETER database

5.1 Information on the database system

The ETER project provides an infrastructure for data collection, which allows for standardization and systematization of the process. This infrastructure includes:

- Templates for data collection including documentation (e.g. flags and special values as commonly used for EUROSTAT-statistics), which guide national data sources (statistical offices, national authorities, other sources) and country experts addressing and supporting national data sources.
- A master database including an upload interface and documentation of database activities (with time and active person).
- A web application, which allows for individual data exports (downloads of all variables for all countries is also possible, such as downloads of staff data for a specific country).

The specific requirements of the ETER project suggest a centralized web server based collection tool, which will be specified for the needs of the two data collection rounds in ETER. The advantage of such a solution is a closer linkage between data collection, feedback and revision (identification of problems and coordinated support) and finally, integration to a raw data set ready for advanced quality, consistency checks and analysis.

The data management tool has been derived from existing tools (imdas/archivis) engaged by JOANNEUM RESEARCH. The existing model of a data management system and centralized data collection was adapted according to the specific needs of the ETER project. Imdas was programmed in Gupta and C# and accesses a relational database, namely an MS SQL Server database. The database is managed via direct and central access by JOANNEUM RESEARCH, which guarantees data security, consistency and quality.

5.2 Technical variable definition

The following table summarizes the set of variables used in ETER and the format the delivered data should have. As the ETER data collection provides special codes, for example missing data, in reality all data are types of "text." Detailed definitions are provided in the ETER handbook.

TABLE 10: LIST OF VARIABLES IN DATASET

Dimension	Variables	Format
Identifiers	ETER ID	Text
	National identifier (optional)	Text
	Institution name (in own language)	Text
	English institution name (if available)	Text
	Year	Integer
Basic institutional descriptors	Country Code	ISO code
	Legal status	Nominal
	Institution category, national definition (in own language)	Text
	Institution category, national definition (in English, if available)	Text
	Institution category standardized	Nominal
	Foreign campus	Binary
	Foundation year	Integer
	Legal status year	Integer
	Ancestor year	Integer
	University hospital	Nominal
Institutional website	Website	

Geographic information	Region of establishment, NUTS2 code Region of establishment, NUTS3 code Name of the city Postcode Multi-site institution	Text Text Text Text Binary
Educational activities	Highest degree delivered Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Number of graduates at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Distance education institution	Nominal Integer Integer Binary
Research	Research active institution Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 8, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Number of graduates at ISCED levels 8 (doctorates), by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility R&D expenditures	Binary Integer Integer Numeric
Expenditures	Personnel expenditure Non-personnel expenditure Capital expenditure Accounting of capital expenditures	Numeric Numeric Numeric Nominal
Revenues	Core budget Third party funding Private funding Tuition fees Student fees funding	Numeric Numeric Numeric Nominal Numeric
Staff	Number of academic staff in FTEs and headcounts Number of academic staff, by fields of education gender and citizenship in headcounts Number of administrative staff in FTEs and headcounts Number of professors Inclusion of PhD students Number of total staff in FTE and HC	Numeric/Integer Numeric/Integer Numeric/Integer Integer Binary Numeric/Integer
Erasmus students	Number of incoming Erasmus students Number of outgoing Erasmus students	Integer Integer

The ETER IDs in combination with the respective reference year is used as a unique identifier, since each ETER ID can only be found once a year.

Besides data on the institutional level, the database includes metadata information in order to consider institutional and country specific characteristics in the data. Metadata include:

- metadata at the institutional level,
- metadata at the country level.

Country level metadata are structured into metadata for descriptor and quantitative variables, which contain information about:

- the content and deviation from ETER definitions,

- the reference period, and
- data sources.

“In-depth information” contains more detailed additional information about the quantitative variables covered in ETER. Finally, country level data also includes the perimeter descriptions and thus provides information about the higher education landscape in the observed countries.

5.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model

The following figure shows the structure of the database and their first data level, the reference year. After the reference year, data are structured by country. For each country, variables are collected at the institutional level, which also includes a set of institutional metadata in order to provide the possibility of detailed data descriptions for institutions. Additionally, the database provides the opportunity to flag data, e.g. in the case of incomparable data, after quality control, and where flags are available for all quantitative variables. In the case of corresponding sub-categories of variables (e.g. male and female students) the flag marking a statistical footnote will apply for all corresponding sub-categories.

FIGURE 1: STRUCTURE OF THE ETER DATABASE

5.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

Completed and validated data collection sheets are imported into the database *imdas pro*, and all collected data are hosted in a secured server environment by JOANNEUM RESEARCH, which is also responsible for data management (cleaning, preparing for upload, uploading, updating) and backup tasks in the process. The existing model of a data management system and decentralized data collection has been adapted according to the specific needs of the ETER project. This will be done by JOANNEUM RESEARCH coordinated with the core partners.

The database also provides the foundation for ETER web application developed from JOANNEUM RESEARCH. The web application enables the user to retrieve data from the whole ETER data set in order to conduct research on micro data of the European higher education sector. The following figure gives an overview about the process starting from collected data until their exploitation in other facilities.

FIGURE 2: FROM COLLECTED DATA TO STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND VALIDATION

The ETER web application includes a short description of the ETER project and the performing consortium members. Starting from the homepage of the ETER web application, three paths are prepared for the user to define an individual query (depending on the information required):

- path1: the user wants to get an overview of the included higher education institutions.
- path2: the user wants to export demographic information or metadata on the country level, or
- path3: the user wants to export data from the ETER micro data set.

5.4.1 Getting an overview about higher education institutions in ETER

The selection field “Higher Education Institutions” offers the possibility to have a closer look at the included higher education institutions in the ETER project. The data are prepared by year and country, and by using the plus sign, a list of all included HEIs in a specific country’s perimeter will appear. Using the magnifier symbol leads the user to a detailed view of the variable (year, country or institution), which includes “ETER ID”, “English Institution Name”, “Year”, and “Country Code”.

5.4.2 Export country level metadata and information about demographic events

By choosing the selection field “Demographic Events & Metadata”, users can gather information about demographic events or country level metadata. The user is forwarded to a platform where the following information can be downloaded.

- an Excel-file where all demographic events for all countries and all institutions since 2009 were collected,
- one Excel-file for every country, where country level metadata for all variables and perimeter descriptions are collected in four unified sheets, and
- an Excel file with four sheets (descriptors, quantitative metadata, in-depth information, perimeter description), where all corresponding metadata are collected and organized by year, country and variable. Using a filter enables the user to choose the desired metadata by year, country and/or metadata variable.

To simplify the handling of institutional data and metadata, the application enables one to switch back directly from the metadata area to the last search by using “Last Search Result”.

5.4.3 Export data from the ETER database

In order to follow path3 the user needs to access “Download ETER Data”, where two different types of access will be provided:

- An open public access, where small numbers and all data, for which public access was restricted by a national statistical authority, are coded.
- A restricted access, where accredited users receive access to the entire dataset for research purposes under the condition that individual data are not disclosed. To this aim, it is envisaged that ETER makes use of the accreditation system which will be established by the EU-FP7 Infrastructure Initiative on Research Infrastructure for the Assessment of Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (RISIS).

In order to follow path3, the user needs to access “ETER Micro Data”, which leads to a mask where the data can be selected by year and/or country. While choosing a year is mandatory to get a search result, the user will get information for all countries at once if she/he does not select a country.

The user can choose to view:

- the entire data set, or
- data sets for one or several specific countries in one or more years.

After choosing the required information, the ETER web application displays the search result, which can be exported by using the selection field “Export Results / create reports.” The following figure shows the result of a search for the year 2011, which leads to all data in the data set for this year.

The result shows all institutions in the data set, which can now be exported to Excel. The export function enables an export of

- all variables at once, using “Export Full Spreadsheet,”
- a specific group of variables (e.g. staff), or
- a predetermined group or related variables (e.g. all revenues and expenditures).

An export of a specific group includes the basic variables

- “ETER ID”,
- “National Identifier”,
- “Institution Name”,
- “English Institution Name”, and
- “Year” plus all variables assigned to a group.

While the export function “Export Full Spreadsheet” enables the export of all variables included in ETER at once, all data for a specific group of variables (see groups and included variables in chapter **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**) can be exported by selecting their name in the export function. Additionally,

four more export possibilities are provided, which cover related variables and present a useful extension for research purposes. The following table will give an overview of these export possibilities and the included variables.

TABLE 11: ADDITIONAL EXPORT POSSIBILITIES

Export possibility	Variables
Export All Expenditures and Revenues	Personnel expenditure Non-personnel expenditure Capital expenditure Expenditure unclassified Total expenditure Accounting of capital expenditures Core budget Third party funding Private funding Tuition fees Student fees funding Revenue unclassified Total revenues Research active institution R&D Expenditure
Export Student Graduates and Research	Highest degree delivered Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Distance education institution Number of graduates at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Research active institution Number of enrolled students at ISCED level 8 by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility Number of graduates at ISCED level 8 by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility R&D Expenditure
Export All Students	Highest degree delivered Number of enrolled students at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, 8 by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility
Export All Graduates	Highest degree delivered Number of graduates at ISCED levels 5, 6, 7, 8 by fields of education, gender, citizenship and mobility

The user can access directly from the search mask to the country level metadata.

5.4.4 Additional functions

The selection field “Last search result” enables the user to call their last query and presents a quick link to the results if necessary. Subscribed users can change their assigned password by using selection field “Settings” and the function “Change Password.” There are no restrictions for the chosen password.

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Report on the content and technical structure of the **EUPRO** Infrastructure

AIT: Austrian Institute of Technology

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of EUPRO v7.4.11 (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

Name and short description of the infrastructure

EUPRO – Database on European Framework Programmes

The EUPRO database comprises information on R&D projects and all participating organizations funded by the European Framework Programmes (FP).

Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The EUPRO database is a significant asset of the Innovation Systems Department of AIT used for basic oriented research projects and contract research for national and international customers, such as the European Commission. It facilitates the analysis of participation patterns of organisations in different priorities of the FP and the investigation of collaborative network structures, including their evolution over time and the development of the European Research Area (ERA).

Legal name of operating organization

AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Database location and type of access (access on site, online, etc.)

EUPRO is accessible onsite at:

AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
Innovation Systems Department
Donau-City-Str. 1
1220 Vienna, Austria

2 Information on substantive content of *EUPRO*

2.1 Definition and description of observations

Units and definition of observations

EUPRO covers information on:

- projects (such as project objectives and achievements, project costs, total funding, start and end date, contract type, information on the call) and
- participations (name of the participating organization, contact person with contact details, organisation type, and geographical location (NUTS2))

Number of observations

EUPRO v7.4.11 comprises information on **63,860 projects** and **337,108 participations**.
Table 1 disaggregates the units of observation by different FPs.

Table 1: EUPRO database - number of projects and participations

Programme	Period	Projects	Participations
FP1	1984 - 1987	3,283	7,929
FP2	1987 - 1991	3,878	19,068
FP3	1990 - 1994	5,528	31,378
FP4	1994 - 1998	14,562	67,858
FP5	1998 - 2002	16,034	78,728
FP6	2002 - 2006	9,709	72,012
FP7*	2007 - 2013	10,866	60,135
Total		63,860	337,108

*Note: Until July 2012

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

Where the data are retrieved from

The core data source for the construction of the EUPRO database is the CORDIS¹ projects database. It contains detailed information on funded projects and project participants of FPs. For the funded projects the CORDIS database lists information on project objectives and achievements, project costs, project funding, temporal location and contract type. It also provides valuable information on the project participants including the full name and address of the organisation, the participating department (partially) and the contact person.

The data on FP collaborations is publicly available. Raw data of the current version (EUPRO v7.4.11) was downloaded in July 2012. We used a wrapper – a type of web scraping program – to extract and structure the information from the website in an automated way. In order to do this, the wrapper opens each project webpage and parses the HTML content. As each webpage follows the same structure it is easy to guide the wrapper to the relevant information, which is then stored in a relational form.

How the data are processed in terms of data cleaning

The quality of the raw data extracted from the CORDIS projects database is not generally sufficient for policy-relevant analyses. AIT has undertaken substantial efforts to improve quality and the level of standardisation of the data and to retrieve and add missing data.

Data cleaning and standardisation includes three major steps:

- identification of unique organisation name,
- identification of unique organisation type, and
- regionalisation (i.e. assignment of geographical locations to European NUTS regions).

The harmonisation of organisations names and the integration of new CORDIS data is ultimately manual, but supported by applying specific matching algorithms developed by AIT. These algorithms are based on statistical properties such as the frequency of adjacent characters in the organisation names and are used to identify similar organisation names that can be attributed to the same organisation. All algorithmically identified name matches are

¹ CORDIS (Community Research and Development Information Service, <http://cordis.europa.eu/>) is the European Commission's primary public repository and portal to disseminate information on all EU-funded research projects and their results in the broadest sense.

manually checked for accuracy. Regionalisation is based on City-to-Nuts correspondence tables.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Description of all variables and/or indicators that are given for the main units of observation

Table 2: Description of variables providing information about projects

Variable	Description
RecCtrNr	unique identifier (record control number) for each project in the database, identical with unique identifier of all projects in the CORDIS projects database
Project Reference	(not-unique) project index, for internal use in the European Commission (matches with Project Id in CORDA)
PrgrType (code)	code (1-7) for the names of the specific framework programme types FP1 to FP7
PrgrType	contains the corresponding names of the framework programmes (e.g., Seventh Framework Programme)
Subprogramme Area	full name of the subprogramme areas in each of the framework programmes
PrAcr	subprogramme acronym in the framework programmes (e.g., FP7-Health)
Title	Full title of the project
ProjAcr	(non-unique) project acronym or abbreviation of the project title
Subject Index	one or more of 68 standardized keywords; in the first three framework programmes distinct combinations of subject indices were allocated by the European Commission to projects of the same subprogram; after FP4 the allocation of subject indices to specific subprograms is more ambiguous; caution: allocation of subject indices seems sometimes arbitrary – check reliability of contents of this variable before usage
Other Indexes	additional keywords to characterize project contents, freely chosen by the project team
Objective, GenInfo (general information), Achievements	distinction of these fields not clearly defined, in practice any of these fields may contain objectives or an abstract of the project.
Partners/Project	number of participants in each project; additional generated information, calculated with the help of table “participants_FP1-7”
Contract type	different types of contracts which regulate size, financing and funding of the research projects (e.g., STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project)
Start Date, End Date	day, month and year of project start and end
Duration (in months)	duration of the project in months (data provided by cordis)
Project Cost	official project costs
Project Funding	financing contribution of the European Union; since not all projects are financed completely, figures in “Project Funding” are equal to or smaller than figures in “Project Cost”.
Project Status	current status of the project (accepted, completed, execution) given in the CORDIS projects database in July, 2012
Project URL	official website of the project

Table 3: Description of variables providing information about participating organisations

Variable	Description
RecCtrNr	unique identifier (record control number) for each project in the database, identical with unique identifier of all projects in the CORDIS projects database; corresponds with the entries in the field RecCtrNr in the projects table (Table 2)
Cnr	unique identifier (control number) assigned internally by AIT, as project participants are not uniquely indexed in the CORDIS projects database; all project-relevant information is indicated with “1”, prime contractor with “2”, and remaining participants with “3”, “4”, etc.
stOrg	standardised organisation name; the EUPRO database currently covers a period of more than 30 years during which organisations have changed to mergers, acquisitions and divestitures. At the moment organisations are labeled by their most recent valid name.
stsubentity	standardised identifier for organisational subunits; incomplete raw data on the participating subunits for FP1 to FP6; with the introduction of the Participant Identification Code (PIC) in FP7 such raw data is no longer available
stOrgType	standardised organisation type
Contact Person	name of contact person, without name affixes like titles, etc.
Tel	phone number of contact person
Fax	fax number of contact person
URL	official website of the organisation
sAddress_orig	complete address information
sPostcode	extracted postal code
sCity	extracted city
sRegion	extracted European Regions
stCtry	standardised country codes; country abbreviations are given as ISO 3166-1 Alpha-3 country codes ²
NUTS2	region code according to the NUTS -2 classification scheme (revision 2010)
CtryType	type of FP association of the country in terms of eligibility for funding (FP7)

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Information on the sectorial classifications used

Table 4: Organisation type

Category	Description
IND	industry
EDU	universities and other educational institutions
ROR	public and private research organisations
GOV	governmental institutions
CON	consultants
NCL	non-commercial/non-profit organisations
OTH	others—mainly special interest groups, like unions, chambers, inter-trade organisations, etc.
N/A	not available

² <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#search/code/>

On a (no longer available) CORDIS website³ subject indices were assigned to different themes. Table 5 contains the list of 68 subject indices and the themes to which they were attributed.

³ Thematic Navigation by Subject Index, http://cordis.europa.eu/themes/home_en.html#cloud (accessed: 13/08/2010)

Table 5: Subject Indices and Themes

Subject Index	Theme
VETERINARY AND ANIMAL SCIENCES	Agriculture and food supply
AGRICULTURE	Agriculture and food supply
FOOD	Agriculture and food supply
AGRICULTURAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	Agriculture and food supply
RESOURCES OF THE SEA, FISHERIES	Agriculture and food supply
MEDICINE, HEALTH	Biology and medicine
BIOTECHNOLOGY	Biology and medicine
LIFE SCIENCES	Biology and medicine
HEALTHCARE DELIVERY/SERVICES	Biology and medicine
MEDICAL BIOTECHNOLOGY	Biology and medicine
NUCLEAR FISSION	Energy
NUCLEAR FUSION	Energy
FOSSIL FUELS	Energy
RENEWABLE SOURCES OF ENERGY	Energy
ENERGY STORAGE, ENERGY, TRANSPORT	Energy
ENERGY SAVING	Energy
BIOFUELS	Energy
HYDROGEN AND FUEL CELLS	Energy
OTHER ENERGY TOPICS	Energy
CLEAN COAL TECHNOLOGIES	Energy
METEOROLOGY	Environment and climate
ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION	Environment and climate
RADIATION PROTECTION	Environment and climate
WASTE MANAGEMENT	Environment and climate
RADIOACTIVE WASTE	Environment and climate
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT	Environment and climate
EARTH SCIENCES	Environment and climate
CLIMATE CHANGE AND CARBON CYCLE RESEARCH	Environment and climate
WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT	Environment and climate
INDUSTRIAL MANUFACTURE	Industry and industrial technology
MATERIALS TECHNOLOGY	Industry and industrial technology
NANOTECHNOLOGY AND NANOSCIENCES	Industry and industrial technology
INDUSTRIAL BIOTECH	Industry and industrial technology
ELECTRONICS, MICROELECTRONICS	Information and Communication Technology
INFORMATION PROCESSING, INFORMATION SYSTEMS	Information and Communication Technology
TELECOMMUNICATIONS	Information and Communication Technology
AUTOMATION	Information and Communication Technology
ROBOTICS	Information and Communication Technology
ICT APPLICATIONS	Information and Communication Technology
NETWORK TECHNOLOGIES	Information and Communication Technology
MEASUREMENT METHODS	Research in practice
MATHEMATICS; STATISTICS	Research in practice
REFERENCE MATERIALS	Research in practice
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH	Research in practice
PROJECT MANAGEMENT METHODOLOGIES	Research in practice
COORDINATION, COOPERATION	Research in practice
POLICIES	Research in practice

LEGISLATION, REGULATIONS	Research in practice
FORECASTING	Research in practice
RESEARCH ETHICS	Research in practice
EVALUATION	Research outputs
STANDARDS	Research outputs
INNOVATION, TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER	Research outputs
BUSINESS ASPECTS	Research outputs
INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS	Research outputs
SOCIAL ASPECTS	Social and Economic Concerns
EDUCATION, TRAINING	Social and Economic Concerns
INFORMATION, MEDIA	Social and Economic Concerns
ECONOMIC ASPECTS	Social and Economic Concerns
REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT	Social and Economic Concerns
EMPLOYMENT ISSUES	Social and Economic Concerns
SAFETY	Social and Economic Concerns
SECURITY	Social and Economic Concerns
CONSTRUCTION TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction
TRANSPORT	Transport and Construction
AEROSPACE TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction
SPACE AND SATELLITE RESEARCH	Transport and Construction
OTHER TECHNOLOGY	Transport and Construction

Information on the temporal coverage used

EUPRO v7.4.11 covers all EU FP projects and participants starting from 1984, with the latest update in July 2012.

Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used

Since we have information on the geographical location of the project participants in the EUPRO database, we can analyse their geographical distribution across Europe at the country-level as well as on the regional level by assigning organisation to European NUTS regions⁴ using NUTS classification revision 2010⁵.

EUPRO covers participations from the following countries:

- *EU 28 Member States*
- *Associated countries* (with science and technology cooperation agreements that involved contributing to the framework programme budget)⁶:
Switzerland; Israel; Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein; Turkey, Croatia, the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia and Serbia; Albania and Montenegro; Bosnia & Herzegovina; Faroe Islands; Republic of Moldova
- *Third Countries* (countries that are not Member States, nor associated countries)⁷

⁴ including the analogous territorial descriptions for Switzerland and Norway

⁵ History of NUTS, http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/nuts_nomenclature/history_nuts (accessed: 24/04/2014)

⁶ FP7 Third Country Agreements, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/116018/fp7-third-country-agreements_en.pdf (accessed: 24/04/2014)

- *International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC)*⁸: Countries eligible for EU funding from Africa, Asia, Caribbean, Pacific, Eastern Europa and Central Asia (EECA), Latin America, Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC) and Western Balkan Countries (WBC) (for the total list see Annex, Table A 1)
- *High-income countries* (normally not eligible for EU funding): United States of America, Canada, Japan, the Republic of Korea, Singapore, Australia and New Zealand, Taiwan, Hong Kong and Macao, Vatican, San Marino, Monaco and Andorra.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Information on the number of missing values

EUPRO v7.4.11 comprises data on 63,860 projects and 337,108 participations (see Table 1). The following two tables give an overview of the number and ratio of missing values for each variable.

Table 6: Number and ratio of missing values of project data

Variable	Missing values	
	Count	Ratio
RecCtrNr	none	0%
Project Reference	none	0%
PrgrType (code)	none	0%
PrgrType	none	0%
Subprogramme Area	15,296	24%
PrAcr	none	0%
Title	1	0%
ProjAcr	24,271	38%
Subject Index	3	0%
Other Indexes	54,540	85%
Objective	20,592	32%
GenInfo	43,383	68%
Achievements	55,940	88%
Partners/Project	none	0%
Contract type	13,759	22%
Start Date	2,144	3%
End Date	2,955	5%
Duration (in months)	8,863	14%
Project Cost	27,422	43%
Project Funding	22,919	36%
Project Status	none	0%
Project URL	58,497	92%

⁷ Cooperation with Third Country Participants in an EC funded FP7 multi-partner research project, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/90400/guideline-third-country-participants_en.pdf

⁸ List of International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC) - Annex 1 of Work Programme 2013 Cooperation, http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/fp7/206006/wp-2013-annex-1-icpc-list_en.pdf, (accessed: 24/04/2014)

Table 7: Number and ratio of missing values of participant's data

Variable	Missing values	
	Count	Ratio
RecCtrNr	0	0%
Cnr	0	0%
stOrg	3,680	1%
stsubentity	287,245	85%
stOrgType	4,515	1%
Contact Person	68,423	20%
Tel	133,451	40%
Fax	142,477	42%
URL	244,810	73%
sAddress_orig	1,227	0%
sPostcode	129,267	38%
sCity	14,216	4%
sRegion	54,495	16%
	(34,655 in EU 28)	11%
stCtry	1,062	0%
NUTS2	13,679	4%
CtryType	0	0%

Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

In general, the original database CORDIS constitutes a reliable resource on all FP projects and participations. However, in some few cases information is incomplete or inconsistent, as for instance the starting and ending dates of projects, in particular for earlier FPs.

In regard to the data acquisition and retrieving system the data is sound and complete. The retrieving system used was a wrapper – a type of web scraping program.

- *Soundness*: The raw data which is extracted from the CORDIS website is copied one-on-one and simply restructured in a relational form.
- *Completeness*: The wrapper parses the HTML content of all project webpages and is guided to the relevant information. Each webpage follows a given structure. Hence, each piece of information is located in the same place and information won't be missed by the wrapper.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

Legal issues concerning access of the database

A complete opening of the database is not foreseen, not least in order to avoid an uncontrolled proliferation of data sets and thus to ensure quality control. Precise rules for access to EUPRO will be defined as an essential precondition for the opening for EUPRO.

Owner of EUPRO raw data

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

Copyright holder for underlying EU FP raw data: © European Union, 1994-2014

Source: CORDIS, <http://cordis.europa.eu/>

Current practice for opening up of the database to external users

While the database is primarily a major asset of the Innovation Systems Department of AIT, and used for both scientific research projects and contract research for national and international customers, AIT has already provided access to data in selected cases in the past, mainly for scientific purposes (joint projects and publications).

Legal necessities for potential opening procedures

In general, access will be possible for joint projects and scientific publications. In addition, the provision of specific extracts of EUPRO, by way of on-site access at AIT premises, is planned. Due to the size and complexity of EUPRO, a dedicated local training and close collaboration with AIT staff is foreseen, usually requiring local presence for some 2-3 weeks.

4 Technical structure of *EUPRO*

4.1 Information on the data base system

Current data base system used

EUPRO is realized as Microsoft Access 2007 database.

Planned future technical changes concerning data base system

None

4.2 Technical variable definition

Labelling and data type of all variables

Table 8: Data type of variables providing information about projects

Variable	Data type
RecCtrNr	Number
Project Reference	Text
PrgrType (code)	Number
PrgrType	Text
Subprogramme Area	Memo
PrAcr	Text
Title	Text
ProjAcr	Text
Subject Index	Memo
Other Indexes	Memo
Objective	Memo
GenInfo	Memo
Achievements	Memo
Partners/Project	Number
Contract type	Text
Start Date	Date
End Date	Date
Duration (in months)	Number
Project Cost	Number
Project Funding	Number
Project Status	Text
Project URL	Text

Table 9: Data type of variables providing information about participating organisations

Variable	Data type
RecCtrNr	Text
Cnr	Number
stOrg	Text
stsubentity	Text
stOrgType	Text
Contact Person	Text
Tel	Text
Fax	Text
URL	Text
sAddress_orig	Memo
sPostcode	Text
sCity	Text
sRegion	Text
stCtry	Text
NUTS2	Text
CtryType	Text

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of EUPRO

Definition of single tables

EUPRO currently consists of six tables (Figure 1): *projects_FP1-7* and *participants_FP1-7*

Figure 1: EUPRO Entity Relationship Model

Relation between the tables via unique identifiers

projects_FP1-7 and *participants_FP1-7* are linked via RecCtrNr (record control number), which is a unique identifier for each project in the database and identical to the unique identifier for the project in the CORDIS projects database. The four remaining tables explain abbreviations used in the respective variables.

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures (e.g. web interface for data search. etc.)

At the current stage, no interfaces are planned. Potential web interfaces may be discussed and implemented during the course of the project, for instance for the provision of specific extracts of aggregated data (e.g., number of organisations/participations per country).

5 Further planning of the opening of *EUPRO*

Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

By establishing a link to various other data sources (e.g. patent data, publications, structural data on firms, universities and PROs) the scientific potential of EUPRO shall be further enhanced. The opening date within RISIS will take place in accordance with other RISIS facilities. Accreditation and access will be formalised in accordance to Task 4 of RISIS WP6.

- New identifier at organisational level (in accordance with WP8)
- Integration of new variables (e.g. NABS code, etc.)
- Adaption to classification schemes defined in other workpackages (e.g., NUTS, organisation type, etc.)

Necessary updates and/or technical changes

The EUPRO database is regularly updated by AIT, usually every second year.

In view of the growing differentiation of frameworks for R&D collaboration in Europe, not the least due to the reinforcement of multilateral arrangements among Member States, further efforts in terms of data retrieval, standardization and refinement will need to be made in the coming years in order to ensure the comprehensive coverage of EUPRO. We will thus extend the EUPRO data set by integrating additional multilateral funding data such as Joint Programming Initiatives, European Technology Platforms, Art. 185-Initiatives, EUREKA, ERANET and COST.

Potentially, a new database model will be defined in an updated version EUPRO. In this version, it is foreseen to add a new organisational table, listing organisations that are linked to projects. The new database model will be developed in accordance to other WPs, in particular the activities in WP8 on the organizational registry.

Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset

The legal access conditions will basically stay the same. Depending on the accreditation systems developed under Task 4 in WP6, changed access conditions will be defined during the course of the project.

Suggestions for example results to be presented at the RISIS week 2015 on the use of the dataset in order to demonstrate its value added (e.g. in conjunction with another dataset)

It can be suggested to use a joint analysis between AIT and USI, joining data from EUMIDA/ETER with EUPRO to explain university participation in FPs by different exogenous factors. Since it is the first matching of two RISIS facilities directly contributing to address a policy relevant research questions, it may suit well to be presented at the RISIS week 2015.

6 Annex

Table A 1: List of International Cooperation Partner Countries (ICPC) participating in EU FP

Country	Code	Type of Country
ANGOLA	AGO	ICPC - Africa
BENIN	BEN	ICPC - Africa
BOTSWANA	BWA	ICPC - Africa
BURKINA FASO	BFA	ICPC - Africa
BURUNDI	BDI	ICPC - Africa
CAMEROON	CMR	ICPC - Africa
CAPE VERDE	CPV	ICPC - Africa
CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC	CAF	ICPC - Africa
CHAD	TCD	ICPC - Africa
CONGO	COG	ICPC - Africa
CONGO, DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	COD	ICPC - Africa
EQUATORIAL GUINEA	GNQ	ICPC - Africa
ERITREA	ERI	ICPC - Africa
ETHIOPIA	ETH	ICPC - Africa
GABON	GAB	ICPC - Africa
GAMBIA	GMB	ICPC - Africa
GHANA	GHA	ICPC - Africa
GUINEA	GIN	ICPC - Africa
GUINEA-BISSAU	GNB	ICPC - Africa
KENYA	KEN	ICPC - Africa
LESOTHO	LSO	ICPC - Africa
LIBERIA	LBR	ICPC - Africa
MADAGASCAR	MDG	ICPC - Africa
MALAWI	MWI	ICPC - Africa
MALI	MLI	ICPC - Africa
MAURITANIA	MRT	ICPC - Africa
MAURITIUS	MUS	ICPC - Africa
MOZAMBIQUE	MOZ	ICPC - Africa
NAMIBIA	NAM	ICPC - Africa
NIGER	NER	ICPC - Africa
NIGERIA	NGA	ICPC - Africa
RWANDA	RWA	ICPC - Africa
SAO TOME AND PRINCIPE	STP	ICPC - Africa
SENEGAL	SEN	ICPC - Africa
SEYCHELLES	SYC	ICPC - Africa
SIERRA LEONE	SLE	ICPC - Africa
SOMALIA	SOM	ICPC - Africa
SOUTH AFRICA	ZAF	ICPC - Africa
SUDAN	SDN	ICPC - Africa
SWAZILAND	SWZ	ICPC - Africa
TANZANIA	TZA	ICPC - Africa
TOGO	TGO	ICPC - Africa
UGANDA	UGA	ICPC - Africa
ZAMBIA	ZMB	ICPC - Africa
ZIMBABWE	ZWE	ICPC - Africa
AFGHANISTAN	AFG	ICPC - Asia
BANGLADESH	BGD	ICPC - Asia
BHUTAN	BTN	ICPC - Asia
CAMBODIA	KHM	ICPC - Asia

CHINA	CHN	ICPC - Asia
INDIA	IND	ICPC - Asia
INDONESIA	IDN	ICPC - Asia
IRAN	IRN	ICPC - Asia
IRAQ	IRQ	ICPC - Asia
LAO PEOPLE'S DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC	LAO	ICPC - Asia
MALAYSIA	MYS	ICPC - Asia
MALDIVES	MDV	ICPC - Asia
MONGOLIA	MNG	ICPC - Asia
MYANMAR	MMR	ICPC - Asia
NEPAL	NPL	ICPC - Asia
OMAN	OMN	ICPC - Asia
PAKISTAN	PAK	ICPC - Asia
PHILIPPINES	PHL	ICPC - Asia
SRI LANKA	LKA	ICPC - Asia
THAILAND	THA	ICPC - Asia
VIET NAM	VNM	ICPC - Asia
YEMEN	YEM	ICPC - Asia
BARBADOS	BRB	ICPC - Carribean
CUBA	CUB	ICPC - Carribean
DOMINICAN REPUBLIC	DOM	ICPC - Carribean
GUYANA	GUY	ICPC - Carribean
HAITI	HTI	ICPC - Carribean
JAMAICA	JAM	ICPC - Carribean
SAINT LUCIA	LCA	ICPC - Carribean
SURINAME	SUR	ICPC - Carribean
TRINIDAD AND TOBAGO	TTO	ICPC - Carribean
ARMENIA	ARM	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
AZERBAIJAN	AZE	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
BELARUS	BLR	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
GEORGIA	GEO	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
KAZAKHSTAN	KAZ	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
KYRGYZSTAN	KGZ	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
Russian Federation	RUS	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
TAJIKISTAN	TJK	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
TURKMENISTAN	TKM	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
UKRAINE	UKR	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
UZBEKISTAN	UZB	ICPC - Eastern Europe and Central Asia (EECA)
ARGENTINA	ARG	ICPC - Latin America
BOLIVIA, PLURINATIONAL STATE OF	BOL	ICPC - Latin America
BRAZIL	BRA	ICPC - Latin America
CHILE	CHL	ICPC - Latin America
COLOMBIA	COL	ICPC - Latin America
COSTA RICA	CRI	ICPC - Latin America
ECUADOR	ECU	ICPC - Latin America
EL SALVADOR	SLV	ICPC - Latin America
GUATEMALA	GTM	ICPC - Latin America
HONDURAS	HND	ICPC - Latin America
MEXICO	MEX	ICPC - Latin America
NICARAGUA	NIC	ICPC - Latin America
PANAMA	PAN	ICPC - Latin America
PARAGUAY	PRY	ICPC - Latin America
PERU	PER	ICPC - Latin America
URUGUAY	URY	ICPC - Latin America

VENEZUELA, BOLIVARIAN REPUBLIC OF	VEN	ICPC - Latin America
ALGERIA	DZA	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
EGYPT	EGY	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
Jordan	JOR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
LEBANON	LBN	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
Libya	LBY	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
MOROCCO	MAR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
SYRIA	SYR	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
TUNISIA	TUN	ICPC - Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPC)
FIJI	FJI	ICPC - Pacific
PAPUA NEW GUINEA	PNG	ICPC - Pacific
SAMOA	WSM	ICPC - Pacific
SOLOMON ISLANDS	SLB	ICPC - Pacific
TONGA	TON	ICPC - Pacific
VANUATU	VUT	ICPC - Pacific

Report on the content and technical structure of the

JOREP

Infrastructure

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

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1 Basic characteristics

1.1 Name and short description of the infrastructure

Name: JoREP 2.0 - Joint Research Programmes database

JoREP 2.0 is a database on joint R&D programmes, which are (i) European-level publicly funded research initiatives, in principle open to all countries belonging to European Research Area (ERA) either because they are established by the European Union or because they are based on international treaties, and (ii) publicly funded research programmes established by a group of countries through a bilateral/multilateral agreement. It provides a quantitative basis for the monitoring of investments in joint R&D programmes in the countries belonging to the ERA, pointing out the policy rationales behind them and their impact. The main focus is on national funding dedicated to the programmes, according to a clear typology of joint R&D programmes, so that cross-country comparisons would be possible. The set of data aims also at describing when, how and serving what purposes European-level initiatives and bilateral/multilateral joint R&D programmes are combined.

The JoREP 2.0 is a relational database implemented in MS Access, its key characteristics are:

- a standard set of descriptors covering the main alternatives concerning organizational features of joint R&D programmes;
- a group of 152 programmes in the sample; about 65% are European-level initiatives, while the others include bilateral/multilateral programmes;
- several data on the volume of funding channelled through these programmes:
 - European-level research programmes funding for the period 2000-2014;
 - bilateral and multilateral research programmes funding for the period 2000-2009;
 - flows to research performers from both types of programmes for the period 2000-2009.
- a large geographical coverage:
 - for the period 2010-2014, 32 countries covered (EU28 countries plus Israel, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey);
 - for the period 2000-2009, data are available for 11 countries selected in order to describe representative situations in the ERA landscape, which include medium-size countries with a well-developed science basis, large countries, Mediterranean countries and Central and Eastern European Member States (Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, Switzerland and the United Kingdom).
- a reasonably good data coverage, only few descriptors being problematic because of limited availability.

1.2 Aim of the database

JoREP 2.0 allows understanding and interpreting the strategies adopted by the different actors involved in joint R&D programmes in terms of the underlying logics which frame their behaviour and decisions concerning if and how to establish joint R&D programmes, how to manage and implement it, linking the findings with broader conceptions of how European integration in the field of S&T policies should take place. JoREP 2.0 also supports, using network or spatial analyses methods, the analysis of important ERA dynamics and Europeanization processes through the study of the behaviour of main national actors (i.e. funding agencies).

The current JoREP 2.0 database structure has been designed in order to store raw panel data on joint R&D programmes and a basic set of descriptors of agencies participating to the programmes

and to better manage the volume of data to be collected in future updates as well as to adapt to potential end-user demands for temporal analysis.

1.3 Legal name of operating organization

The operating organization is the IRCRES CNR – Research Institute on Sustainable Economic Growth of the National Research Council of Italy (<http://www.ircres.cnr.it>)

1.4 Database location and type of access

The database is located at IRCRES CNR in Rome (Italy). The type of access to JoREP 2.0 is ‘on site’ (the user/researcher comes on site and works on a project using the data).

2 Information on substantive content of *JoREP 2.0*

2.1 Definition and description of observations

The conceptual scheme of JoREP 2.0 considers **joint R&D programmes** as the main unit of analysis, characterized by both internal and contextual features.

Joint R&D programmes are publicly funded research programmes for which at least one of them functions is shared between more than one country (or by regions belonging to more than one country). Observations focus primarily on programme attributes and examine in depth the dynamics of participation and fund allocation, describing the funding models adopted and the flows from funding agencies to performers.

JoREP 2.0 stores data on:

- **99 European-level joint R&D programmes¹**
 - which launched a call for proposal in 2013 or 2014 and in which at least one of the EU28 countries or Israel, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey participates (data on funding are provided for the period 2010-2014);
 - which launched a call for proposal in 2008 and 2009 and at least one of the following countries – the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Switzerland, Spain, and the United Kingdom – participates (data on funding are provided for the period 2000-2009 and following years until the end of the programme; data on flows to performers are provided for the period 2000-2009).
- **53 Bilateral/multilateral joint R&D programmes** which launched a call for proposal in 2008 and 2009 in which at least one of the following countries – the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Switzerland, Spain, and the United Kingdom – participates (data on funding and on flows to performers are provided for the period 2000-2009).

¹ The counting refers to the unique ID codes associated to the programmes. The flexible characteristics of the programmes have imposed the creation of a set of rules in order to manage their demography, as outlined in *par. 4.2.1*. For instance, CIRCLE and CIRCLE 2 have a single ID code in the database, being one the continuation of the other. This applies to 24 programmes in the database, which are not counted twice or more times. Differently, the single actions deriving from disaggregation of large programmes have a proper ID code and are counted separately.

Programmes managed by the European Union (Framework Programmes) or by the EU together with a single member state as well as all programmes supporting research infrastructures and careers are excluded.

Secondary units of analysis in JoREP 2.0 are **funding agencies**, defined as formal organization managing at least one of the programme functions listed below:

- definition of the programme goals and mission;
- preparation and diffusion of the call;
- management of the submission process;
- evaluation and selection process;
- decision on which projects to fund;
- management of contract and payments.

JoREP 2.0 describes a basic set of characteristics of **348 national funding agencies** participating at least at one joint R&D programme included in the sample².

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

The first version of JoREP database (v.1.0) – containing data until 31.12.2009 – was based on a data collection performed within the JOREP EC contract³, and developed by a team composed of national experts that also provided evidences for the data validation at their statistical offices.

In the context of EUFP7 RISIS project⁴ WP22 on ‘Enlargement of Databases dealing with ERA dynamics’, an update of the data until 31.12.2014 – in parallel with an enlargement of the geographical coverage – was developed in order to include the most recent information on European-level joint R&D programmes, creating the current version of JoREP (v.2.0).

2.2.1 Data sources

As displayed in *tab. 1*, **combinations of sources** have been used for the descriptors of the same units of analysis.

Main sources for the data collection have been: ERA-LEARN 2020 (formerly NETWATCH) website; calls for proposal publicly available; joint R&D programme websites; joint R&D programme activity reports and evaluation reports; joint R&D programme leaflets; funding agency websites. Nevertheless, some information has been collected directly from ministries or funding agencies, e.g. through interviews or personnel contact.

Other approved sources have been: national statistical offices and GBAORD. Estimations for not-available data, if applicable, and assessment data have been produced by national experts.

² The counting does not consider special ‘agency ID codes’ used to avoid ‘null’ values in the *FundingAgenciesList* when the information on national funding agency is not available (see *par. 4.3.4*). The list of funding agencies will be harmonised according to the work developed for the register of public sector organizations (EUFP7 RISIS WP8, see *EUFP7 RISIS DOW*).

³ JOREP (Investments in joint and open R&D programmes and analysis of their economic impact) was a service contract commissioned by the European Commission [Contract. No. RTD/DirC/C3/2010/SI2.561034] under the Seventh Framework Programme of the European Union for research, technological development and demonstration activities (2007 to 2013).

⁴ EUFP7 RISIS project (Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies), <http://risis.eu>

UNIT OF ANALYSIS	SOURCES
Joint R&D Programmes	ERA-LEARN 2020 (formerly NETWATCH) website
	Calls for proposal publicly available
	Joint R&D programmes' websites
	Joint R&D activity reports
	Joint R&D evaluation reports
	Funding agencies websites
	GBOARD
	Direct contacts with agency personnel
	Estimations
Funding agencies	Funding agency websites
	Direct contacts with agency personnel

Table 1: sources for descriptors of the units of analysis of JoREP 2.0

2.2.2 Data cleaning

Data cleaning foresaw exploratory controls focused on the detection of *non-sampling errors*, whom correction required the recognition of systematic errors and random errors:

- a harmonization of the codes of the units of analysis has been accomplished;
- consistency checks between different descriptors have been undertaken in order to guarantee the coherency of data;
- errors committed in the transcriptions of data have been corrected through format checks;
- a check of referential integrity has been implemented as ultimate database safety check for inconsistent data and mechanism for the synchronization of the archives.

Treatment of empty fields - where values should occur – has been implemented so that in case of a complete non-availability of data a 'not available' code has been entered.

When there was a non-applicability of the field, a 'not applicable' code has been entered.

The presence of empty fields on 'amount' fields (data-type: numeric) indicates the non-availability or non-applicability of data (as remarked on 'data status' fields).

The presence of empty fields on 'remark' fields indicates the absence of remarks.

2.3 Information on all variables

JoREP 2.0 includes variables dealing with the two main units of analysis that characterize the joint R&D programmes dynamic: **programmes and funding agencies**.

Each joint R&D programme descriptor refers to a specific reference year in the programme life, whereas funding agencies descriptors are not changing.

Some of the descriptors are matched with 'remarks fields' included in the database as separated fields.

2.3.1 Joint R&D programme descriptors

The following list provides the main characteristics of the descriptors of joint R&D programmes at the *programme level*, at the *participation level* and at the *beneficiaries' level*.

Programme level

- **Programme identifier** (*prog_ID*). The code identifying the programme.
- **Programme start year** (*prog_start_year*). The year when the specific programme has been officially created, by signing a specific agreement. This might be earlier than the official launch of the funding scheme, as well as the start of funding to performers.
- **Programme end year** (*prog_end_year*). The year when the specific programme has been officially closed. Note: if the programme has only changed name, reconfirming most part of its features, it is considered still active. The end year refers only to the closing of a programme and its successors.
- **Original programme** (*original_prog*). If the programme has been generated by a merging, by a split or a spin-out, the indication of the original programme from which derives.
- **Successor programme** (*successor_prog*). If the programme has been merged, split or taken over, the indication of the successor programme.
- **Demographic transformation** (*demo_transformation*). Description of relevant demographic processes along the programme life (e.g. change of name, taking-over or spin-out).
- **Establishing authority** (*establishing_authority*) The body – EU, national states, regions, funding agencies – which officially established the programme, either by its own decision or by signing some kind of agreement. This includes political authorities, but also funding agencies when the decision is taken at this level. Example. The D-CH-A Lead agency agreement has been established through a direct agreement between the participating research councils and thus these will be considered as the establishing authorities (rather than the national States involved). A ‘remark’ field is provided for this descriptor.
- **Name of the programme in English** (*name_prog_eng*). If the main programme language is not English, the official translation if it exists. If there is no official name in English, the name in the national language is used.
- **Type of instrument** (*type_instrument*). Indication of the type of instrument used by the programme (e.g. ERA-NET, ERA-NET plus, JPI, etc.)
- **Programme duration** (*prog_duration*). This variable distinguishes between:
 - Programmes *limited* in time and with one or few calls.
 - *Periodic* programmes without a time limitation, but with irregular calls.
 - *Regular* programmes without a time limitation and regular calls (e.g. yearly or each two years).
- **Project duration** (*proj_duration*). This variable identifies the typical duration of projects funded by the programme, by using the following scale: less than 2 years, 2-4 years, more than 4 years. By typical, we mean that most of the projects are in this duration range. This information is derived from programme descriptions and calls. Exceptions and specific cases will be noted in the associated ‘remarks’ field.
- **Research topic** (*research_topic*). For classification of programme topics, the Nomenclature for the Analysis and Comparison of Scientific Programmes and Budgets from the Frascati Manual (2007 version) is adopted (see 2.4.1). This classification refers to the socio-economic objective of the programme, not to the actual research content. Please notice that category 12 is not applicable for programmes, while investigator-driven programmes should be classified under

category 13. More specific indications on subtopics can be inserted in the associated 'remarks' field.

- **Submission procedure** (*submission_procedure*). Following categories are used:
 - *Single entry point* when proposal are submitted to a single agency.
 - *Parallel submission* when proposal have to be submitted at the same time to two or more agencies (as in many bilateral programmes).

By submission is meant delivering the whole proposal for the purposes of evaluation and selection. Sending copies for purposes of information is not considered as parallel submission. A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.

- **Selection criteria**. This descriptor provides synthetic information on the importance of the two following criteria in the selection of projects:
 - Scientific quality (*selcri_scientific*).
 - Relevance to strategic or economic priorities (*selcri_relevance*).

These criteria derives from a national experts assessment based on the information from programme descriptions and calls on the following point scale:

- 4: is the most important criterion for project selection.
- 3: it is an important criterion.
- 2: it is an additional criterion.
- 1: it is not a relevant criterion.

Total number of points for the two criteria has to be 5.

A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.

- **Funding model** (*funding_model*). As joint R&D programmes do not necessarily involve cross border flows of funding and the joint call function can be separated from the funding function, different possible options concerning the management of financial flows in joint R&D programmes exist (ERAC, 2010; ERA LEARN 2020 tool box, 2015). This descriptor specifies how national funding for joint programmes is managed. We distinguish between the following models *Common pot* when all financial resources from participating countries are put in a single pot and used for financing the selected projects, independently of the country where research is performed.
 - *Common pot with return rules*, when some relationships are formally requested between national contributions and funding to national performers. The rule should be stated in some official documents (including statutes, policy briefs, and minutes). This model is applied for example by the European Space Agency.
 - *National pot* (virtual common pot) when financial resources for participating countries are managed separately and devoted to national performers. This model is applied, as an example, by ERA-NET programmes.
 - *Mixed-mode*, where the principle of national return is maintained and most of the resources are managed at national level, but there is a compensation mechanism to fund the best ranked proposals anyway, through top-up funding from national contributions.

The selection of the funding model will be based on the most important model adopted, e.g. if 90% of national funding is used in national pot model this category should be used. A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.

- **EU contribution** (*EU_contribution*). This descriptor identifies whether the programme is co-funded by the European Union (yes/no).

- **Coordinator country** (*coordinator_country*). ISO code of the country coordinating the programme.
- **Partner countries** (*partner_countries*) This field lists the ISO codes of the partner countries of the programme. This is a multivalue field, so that multiple values stored in this field can be treated independently in potential query tables. A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.
- **Observer countries** (*observer_countries*). This field lists the ISO codes of the countries participating to the programme as observers. The field is filled only if applicable.
- **Mode of integration** (*integration_mode*). This descriptor identifies how the common programmes activities are institutionalized. We distinguish between three categories:
 - Creation of a specific agency, where joint activities are managed by a supranational agency with an enduring and long-term status (*agency*).
 - Management of joint activities by the way of no permanent structures as joint committees, whose existence is specifically related to the programme itself (*coordination*).
 - Management of joint activities through the delegation to a national agency in one of the participating countries (*delegation*).
 - Independent evaluation and selection, where the project is approved only if both parties decide independently to finance it (*independent selection*).
 A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.
- **ERA category** (*ERA_category*). This descriptor provides a general categorization of joint programmes in terms of their relationships with the European research area. It is thus inserted in the database after data collection based on other descriptors. Following three categories are distinguished:
 - *European-level initiatives* are those joint programmes that are in principle open to all ERA countries either because they are established by the European Union or based on international treaties.
 - *Bilateral programmes within the ERA* are joint programmes established by a closed group of countries (not necessarily two) and which include only ERA countries.
 - *Bilateral programmes outside the ERA* are joint programmes established by a closed group of countries (not necessarily two) and which include also countries not belonging to the European Research Area.
- **Programme type** (*prog_type*). This categorization has been introduced to distinguish the main organizational settings of joint programmes and is based on a set of other descriptions. Following categories are distinguished
 - *Integrated programmes* are those characterized by the existence of a supranational agency (integration mode: agency); they are further divided into integrated programmes with integration of funding (funding model: common pot) and without integration of funding (funding model: national pot).
 - *Coordinated programmes* are those characterized by lighter coordination modes (integration mode: coordination or delegation) and by single-entry point submission. They are further divided into coordinated programmes with delegation (coordination mode: delegation), coordinated programmes with integration of funding (coordination mode: coordination; funding model: real pot) and coordinated programmes without integration of funding (coordination mode: coordination; funding model: national pot).

- *Collaborative programmes* are those characterized by independent selection (collaborative programmes, independent programmes) or those characterized by coordination and parallel submission (collaborative programmes, parallel programmes).

Participation level

- **Reference Year** (*reference_year*). The calendar year to which the amount refers.
- **Participating country** (*participating_country*) Indication of one country participating to a programme included in the JoREP 2.0 perimeter⁵. It corresponds with the national state (or EU) from where funding originates (in case of regional budgets the relevant country).
- **National role** (*national_role*). This descriptor identifies the situation of national participants in the programme, as well as the availability of funds:
 - *Full participation*, if research groups from the considered country can participate to all programme activities without restrictions; in case of programmes with national pot, this means also that full funding is available (e.g. for research purposes).
 - *Full participation with restricted funding*, if research groups from the considered country can participate to all programme activities without restrictions, but availability of funding is restricted to coordination and networking activities.
 - *Limited participation* if research group from the country can participate with limitations, e.g. as external partners or not taking a coordination role.
 - A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.
- **Funding agency** (*funding_agency_ID*). The funding agency receiving the funding amount specifically for this programme. If for a programme there is more than one agency receiving a share of the budget, the amount for each agency should be entered separately. A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.
- **Agency functions**. For each agency, indication is requested if it manages at least one of following functions:
 - Definition of the programme goals and mission (*agencyfunction_mission*);
 - Preparation and diffusion of the call (*agencyfunction_call*);
 - Management of the submission process (*agencyfunction_submission*);
 - Evaluation and selection process (*agencyfunction_evaluation*);
 - Decision on which projects to fund (*agencyfunction_fundingdecision*);
 - Management of contract and payments (*agencyfunction_payments*).

Three options are provided for each field: 'yes', 'no' and 'participation to collective decision' in case a joint committee of agencies representatives takes decisions.

This list include only the agencies taking the lead for each of these functions; other bodies cooperating in these functions (e.g. providing advice or helping in peer-review processes) will be included in the remark section. In cases where at national or European level different functions are managed by different agencies there will be more than one participating agency per country. If there is a two stages submission procedure, answers refer to the final selection stage and provide information on other stages in the remarks section.
- **Origin of funding** (*origin_of_funding*). The exact origin of the budget, including the European Union budget, the national budgets and regional budgets. This variable provides the specific name of the funding source (e.g. French research ministry).

⁵ 'Perimeter' means the set of programmes that comply with the definition chosen for joint R&D programmes.

- **Budget source category** (*budget_source_category*). The classification of the budget source by distinguishing between national budget and regional budget.
- **Budgeting** (*budgeting*). The type of budgeting conforming to the following categories:
 - *Specific budget line*, when funding to joint programmes is explicitly part of a specific budgetary line which can be identified in GBAORD data. In these cases, the level of funds transferred to the funding agency should be derived directly from GBAORD data and comply with the EUROSTAT pilot data on transnational funded programmes.
 - *Earmarked budget*, when there is no specific budgeting line, but it is specified (for example in political decision or strategic documents) that part of the general transfer to a funding agency should be used for the participation to specific programmes. In these cases, data will have to be estimated from these policy documents (possibly by averaging over different years).
 - *Delegated budget*, when there might be a general political decision to participate, but the decision on the level of funding is completely delegated to the agency. In this case, the volume of funds will have to be derived from data of the funding agency and should match the one in the funding to beneficiaries table.
- **Currency** (*currency*) The currency in which the data are expressed. Standard ISO codes is used.
- **Amount** (*amount*). The funding for the whole year expressed in currency units.
- **Budget data source category** (*data_source_category_participation*). This variable provides a categorization of data sources as follows:
 - GBAORD or other budgetary data.
 - Information from funding agency.
 - Other source (specified in the following variable).
 - National expert estimate (will be clarified under remarks).
- **Budget data source** (*data_source_participation*). The exact source of the budget data provided.
- **Potential beneficiary sectors** (*beneficiary_sector_GOV / beneficiary_sector_HE / beneficiary_sector_PNP / beneficiary_sector_PRIVATE / beneficiary_sector_ABROAD*). This descriptor identifies the performing sectors that are legally entitled to get funding from the programme. We use the sectorial classification of the Frascati Manual (*see 2.4.1*), presented in the form of 5 different fields with binary 'data type'. A 'remarks' field is provided for this descriptor.
- **Beneficiary sector data source** (*beneficiary_sector_data_source*). The exact source of the data provided on beneficiary sectors.

Beneficiaries' level

- **Reference Year** (*reference_year*). The calendar year to which the amount refers.
- **Beneficiary country** (*beneficiary_country*). Country the funding amount refers to.
- **Funding agency** (*funding_agency_ID*). The code of the funding agency the funding originates from. If for a programme there is more than one funding agency, the corresponding amounts is entered separately.
- **Currency** (*currency*). The national currency used. Standard ISO currency codes is used.

- **Amount (Public/Private/Total)** (*amount_public/amount_private/amount_total*). For each year, the volume of funding transferred to public and private beneficiaries and the total. The amount for the whole year is expressed in currency units.
- **Status of data on the beneficiaries** (*data_status_beneficiary*). The field indicates the availability/non-availability of data on the beneficiary.
- **Data source category** (*data_source_category_beneficiary*). This variable provides a categorization of data sources as follows:
 - GBAORD or other budgetary data.
 - Information from funding agency.
 - Other source (specified in the following variable).
 - National expert estimate (clarified under remarks).
- **Data source** (*data_source_beneficiary*). Please indicate the exact source from where data has been retrieved.

2.3.2 Funding agency descriptors

The following list provides the main characteristics of the descriptors of funding agencies.

- **National agency identifier** (*funding_agency_ID*) The code identifying the national agency in the format of XX-NN-Acronym of the agency, where XX is the ISO code for the country and NN is the number of funding agencies for the same country running from 01 as long as necessary.
- **Country** (*agency_country*). For national and regional agencies only, the country where the agency is established.
- **Acronym** (*agency_acronym*). The official acronym of the funding agency, if available.
- **Name of the agency in official language** (*agency_name_nat_lang*). The full name in the language of establishment. For international agencies, the official English name should be used.
- **Name of the agency in English language** (*agency_name_eng_lang*). Full name of the agency in English, e.g. the one adopted in policy documents or on the agency website (if available).
- **Status of the agency** (*agency_status*) We distinguish between following categories.
 - *National agency* established by a single country.
 - *European agency*, established through European law (e.g. European Interest Groups).
 - *Intergovernmental agency* established by an international treaty between national states (possibly including also the European Union). These can be at the international, European or (country) regional level (e.g. Nordic Council).
 - *International non-governmental association* e.g. established through an agreement between national or regional funding agencies.
 - *Regional agencies* established by a regional authority.

We notice that this categorization refers to the authority of establishment and not to the geographical space where these agencies fund research.

- **Agency website** (*agency_website*) The official website of the agency, (if available the link to the English section). This information is inserted to quickly retrieve additional information for the purposes of analysis.

- **Total budget** (*agency_tot_budget_2009*). (note: provisionally provided only for funding agencies stored in JoREP 1.0). The total budget of the agency for research project funding is provided for the year 2009 as a rough measure of the size of the programmes it manages. Data is provided in national currency at current prices. For agencies performing other functions than research funding (e.g. ministries) or funding their own research centres, this value should refer to project funding research only.
- **Geographical level** (*agency_geo_level*). Agencies are distinguished between supranational, national and regional. This distinction refers to the institutional embedding, not to the funding activities; e.g. a regional agency, funded under regional law, might support also research outside the region.
- **Agency classification/agency domain** (*agency_classification/agency_domain*). The classification of funding agencies is two-level, the first one refers to the position with respect to the State, while the second one specifies more precisely the domain of activity. At the first level distinguish between following categories:
 - *Governmental agencies* are agencies that are functionally part of the public administration, meaning for example division of ministries, ministerial committees, etc. Typical examples at the European level are DG research (managing the European FP), at national level research ministries. These are divided between:
 - National research/science ministry
 - National sectorial ministry (e.g. energy)
 - Regional government (undivided in subcategories)
 - *Independent agencies* are agencies that have functionally a large degree of independence from the State in managing their activities and selecting the projects to be funded; in some cases this might be realized by a specific legal status granting autonomy. A key criterion to distinguish the two types of agencies is if the State (e.g. ministry) retains the right to take the final decision on granting money to specific projects. These are divided between:
 - Innovation agency, whose mission and funding are oriented towards innovation and creation of economic value;
 - Research councils, whose funding is mainly oriented towards basic research and which have strong connection to the academic community (for example in the composition of decision-making committee);
 - Sectorial agency – related to specific topic (energy, environment, etc.), e.g. sectorial regulatory agencies or sectorial funding agencies;
 - Intergovernmental agency created by international treaty (ESA);
 - EU-implementation agency based on EU law (e.g. the agency managing AAL);
 - International non-governmental association (European Science Foundation).
 - *Performers* are organizations whose main mission is to perform R&D activities, even if might host some funding agencies activities. These are divided between:
 - Public research organizations (PRO) assuming also a function in funding;
 - Private research organizations

2.3.3 Countries' descriptors

The following list provides the main characteristics of the descriptors of countries.

- **Country name** (*country_name*). The list of world countries.
- **Country ISO code** (*country*). Country codes in ISO 3166-1 alpha 2 (see 2.4.1).

- **EC-ATC classification scheme** (*EC_ATC_classification*) The descriptor distinguishes the inclusion of the country between three categories: EU28 countries, countries associated to EU28 and third countries.
- **JoREP sample country** (*JoREP_country*). The descriptor is binary and points out the inclusion/non-inclusion of the country in the JoREP perimeter.
- **Latitude** (*latitude*) The latitude of the capital city of the country.
- **Longitude** (*longitude*). The longitude of the capital city of the country.
- **GERD (Gross domestic expenditure on R&D) as a percentage of GDP** (*gerdbygdp*) (period 2005-2014, source: EUROSTAT).
- **Graduates on population** (*gradbypop*). The ratio between total number of graduates and total population for each country considered (period 2005-2014, source: EUROSTAT).
- **Researchers on population** (*reserbypop*). The ratio between total number of researchers and total population for each country considered (period 2005-2014, source: EUROSTAT).
- **H-Index** (*h_index*). The h-index is an author-level metric that attempts to measure both the productivity and citation impact of the publications of a scholar. It accounts the number of articles produced in a country (h) that have received at least h citations (period 2010-2014, source SCOPUS).
- **Population** (*population*). The total population of the country in the considered year.

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

2.4.1 Classifications used

JoREP 2.0 adopted the Nomenclature for the Analysis and Comparison of Scientific Programmes and Budgets from the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2002) in order to classify research topics, as showed in tab. 2.

01	Exploration and exploitation of the earth
02	Environment
03	Exploration and exploitation of space
04	Transport, telecommunication and other infrastructures
05	Energy
06	Industrial production and technology
07	Health
08	Agriculture
09	Education
10	Culture, recreation, religion and mass media
11	Political and social systems, structures and processes
12	General advancement of knowledge: R&D financed from General University Funds (GUF)

13	General advancement of knowledge: R&D financed from other sources than GUF
14	Defence

Table 2: classification of research topics used in JoREP 2.0

The performing sectors that are legally entitled to get funding from the programme have been classified using sectorial classification of the Frascati Manual (OECD, 2002), contained in *tab. 3*.

GOV	Government sector: Research institutes/governmental institutions with R&D which are mainly financed and controlled by the government.
HEI	Higher education institutions
PNP	Nonmarket, private non-profit institutions serving households/ the general public.
Private	Business enterprise sector: firms/organisations/institutions whose primary activity is the market production of goods or services, including the private non-profit institutions mainly serving the business enterprise sector.
Abroad	

Table 3: performing sector classification used in JoREP 2.0

Countries are classified according to the International Standard for country codes (ISO 3166-1 alpha 2)⁶. The EC-ATC classification scheme, which distinguishes the inclusion of the country between EU28, countries associated to EU28 and third countries is also included as a country descriptor.

2.4.2 Temporal coverage

Annual data refer to the 2000-2014 period:

- Data on funding and on internal features of European-level joint R&D programmes which launched a call for proposal in 2013 or 2014 and where at least one of the EU28 countries or Israel, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey participates are provided for the period 2010-2014;
- Data on funding and on flows to performers of European-level joint R&D programmes and bilateral/multilateral programmes which launched a call for proposal in 2008 and 2009 and at where least one of the following countries – the Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Switzerland, Spain, and the United Kingdom – participates are provided for the period 2000-2009. Data on internal features refers to the year 2009.

Descriptors refer to the last day of reference year. Financial data refer to the calendar year of each year.

2.4.3 Geographical coverage

The geographical coverage of JoREP 2.0 includes 32 countries (EU28 countries plus Israel, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey) for the period 2010-2014; 11 countries (Czech Republic,

⁶ http://www.iso.org/iso/country_codes.htm

Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, Switzerland and the United Kingdom) are also covered for the period 2000-2009.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

In the current version of the database, descriptors of joint R&D programmes at programme level and descriptors of funding agencies (except for funding agencies total budget), revealed a very good coverage of the basic characteristics of the units of analysis.

Nonetheless, these are the features that characterize the quality of participation and budget data of the two data collections (see 2.2):

- Data on European-level initiatives and bilateral/multilateral programmes for the period 2000-2009 (11 countries covered), despite the completeness of the data is rather good in general, have a few descriptors that revealed problematic in terms of availability during the data collection, such as programme budgets and flows to beneficiaries. The share of non-available data is higher for what concerns programme budgets - 18% of missing data - and funding to beneficiaries - 22% of missing data.
- Data on European-level initiatives for the period 2010-2014 (32 countries covered), at participation level, for beneficiary sectors are provided for the programme in general and not punctually for each country. Funding agencies functions are provisionally not available for art.185/JTI/COST/EUREKA/ESA programmes. Data on origin of funding will be added in the next releases of the database.

In terms of data comparability, in some cases, there might have been slight differences in their application across countries, which do not affect comparability. Some quality issues concern the thematic classification – as it is not always easy to fit the different programmes into the classification categories – and the functions of funding agencies.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

3.1 Legal issues concerning access of the database

IRCRES CNR – Research Institute on Sustainable Economic Growth of the National Research Council of Italy is the owner of the JoREP 2.0 database.

3.2 Owner of raw data

According to the EUFP7 RISIS legal specificities, the databases can be fully exploited under the EUEUFP7 RISIS activities for the aims of the project (opening of the infrastructure to external users for research purposes, integration of the infrastructure with other similar).

3.3 Current practice for opening up of the database to external users

Opening to external uses is based on 'site visits' at IRCRES CNR.

4 Technical structure of JoREP 2.0

4.1 Information on the data base system

Being the structure of joint R&D programmes complex, an appropriate system for data management is required which integrate and allow several level of analysis.

Data are implemented in **MS Access 2013**, considering the potential of the software in handling several sets of information from different archives logically related to each other and in creating custom views of data. Currently, no future technical changes about the database system are planned. Nevertheless, the possibility to export new releases of the database to another software for a better fruition is not excluded.

4.2 Technical variable definition

Table 4 summarizes **data-type** of the sets of variables in JoREP 2.0:

DIMENSION	VARIABLES	LEVEL	DATA TYPE
Joint R&D Programme	<i>prog_ID</i>	Programme-level	Short text (Code)
	<i>prog_start_year</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>prog_end_year</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>original_prog</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>successor_prog</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>demo_transformation</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>establishing_authority</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>reference_year</i>	Programme-level	Numeric/Multivalue
	<i>name_prog_eng</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>type_instrument</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>prog_duration</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>proj_duration</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>research_topic</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>submission_procedure</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>selcri_scientific/selcri_relevance</i>	Programme-level	Scale (Numeric)
	<i>funding_model</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>EU_contribution</i>	Programme-level	Binary
	<i>coordinator_country</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>partner_countries</i>	Programme-level	Short text/Multivalue
	<i>observer_countries</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>integration_mode</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>ERA_category</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>prog_type</i>	Programme-level	Short text
	<i>reference_year</i>	Participation-level	Date
	<i>participating_country</i>	Participation-level	Short text (Code)
	<i>national_role</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>funding_agency_ID</i>	Participation-level	Short text (Code)
	<i>agency_function</i> (disaggregated)	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>origin_of_funding</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>budget_source_category</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>budgeting</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>currency</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>amount</i>	Participation-level	Numeric
	<i>budget_data_status</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>budget_data_source_category</i>	Participation-level	Short text
	<i>budget_data_source</i>	Participation-level	Short text

	<i>beneficiary_sector</i> (disaggregated) <i>beneficiary_sector_data_source</i>	Participation-level Participation-level	Binary Short text
	<i>reference_year</i> <i>beneficiary_country</i> <i>funding_agency_ID</i> <i>currency</i> <i>amount_public/amount_private/amount total</i> <i>data_status_beneficiary</i> <i>data_source_category_beneficiary</i> <i>data_source_beneficiary</i>	Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level Beneficiary-level	Date Short text (Code) Short text Short text Numeric Short text Short text Short text
Funding agency	<i>funding_agency_ID</i> <i>agency_country</i> <i>agency_acronym</i> <i>agency_name_nat_lang</i> <i>agency_name_eng_lang</i> <i>agency_status</i> <i>agency_website</i> <i>agency_tot_budget_2009</i> <i>agency_geo_level</i> <i>agency_classification</i> <i>agency_domain</i>	Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level Agency-level	Code Short text (Code) Short text Short text Short text Short text Short text Numeric Short text Short text Short text
Country	<i>country_name</i> <i>country</i> (ISO code) <i>EC_ATC_classification</i> <i>JoREP_country</i> <i>latitude</i> <i>longitude</i> <i>gerdbygdgdp</i> <i>gradbypop</i> <i>reserbypop</i> <i>h_index</i> <i>population</i>	Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level Country-level	Short text Short text (Code) Short text Binary Numeric Numeric Numeric Numeric Numeric Numeric Numeric

Table 4: data-type of the variables stored in JoREP 2.0

4.2.1 Definition of identifiers and demography rules

A set of specific records – containing some unique pieces of information identified by a code – has been designed for the joint R&D programmes and the funding agencies which represent the units of analysis in JoREP 2.0.

The flexible characteristics of programmes and funding agencies have imposed the creation of a **set of rules** in order to manage their demography, as outlined in the table 5:

Demographic Event		Decision about identifier (ID)
Creation of a new joint R&D programme.	Closure of an existing joint R&D Programme.	New independent identifier code (ID) assigned in the case of entry.
Entry of a new funding agency.	Modification of status of a funding agency	Identifiers of disappearing units are reserved and not reused.

Merger between two joint R&D programmes / funding agencies in a new joint R&D programme/funding agency (with new name).	Split of an existing joint R&D programme / funding agency into two or more independent joint R&D programmes /funding agencies	New independent identifier (ID) assigned analogously to entry. Identifiers of antecedent programmes/agencies are reserved and not reused.
Take-over of one programme by another one (death of the programme which was taken over, the taking over programme continues to exist). The new programme retains the identity of the programme taking over.	Spin-out (Spin-off). Split-off of a part of a programme to become a separate programme. Old programme exists unchanged, new programme has new name	In the case of take-overs, the ID of the dominant programme taking over another will be held. The identity of the programme taken over is reserved and not reused. In the case of spin-outs, the ID of the original programme will continue. Analogously to a birth, a new ID is created for the new spinning out.

Table 5: demographic events and decisions about identifiers.

While the **demography of the funding agencies** will be available according to the work developed in EUFP7 RISIS WP8, information on the **demography of the programmes** is traced through some fields inserted in the *ProgrammeCatalogue* table as shown in table 6:

EVENT	FIELD	INFORMATION CONTENT
Creation	<i>Start year</i>	Year of creation of the programme
Closure	<i>End year</i>	Year of closure of the programme
Merger	<i>Original programme</i>	- Indication of the single programmes merged appears in the <i>Original programme</i> field related to the programme born from the merging;
	<i>Successor programme</i>	- Indication of the programme born from the merging appears in the <i>successor programme</i> fields related with the merged programmes.
Split	<i>Successor programme</i>	- Indication of the new programmes born after the split appears in the <i>successor programme</i> field related to programme subject to split;
	<i>Original programme;</i>	- Indication of the programme subject to split appear in the <i>original programme</i> fields related with the new programmes
Take-over	<i>Successor programme;</i>	- Indication of the programme taking over in the <i>successor programme</i> field of the programme taken-over.
	<i>Demographic transformation</i>	- Indication of the process of take-over (in <i>demographic transformations</i> field) associated to the programme taken-over (in <i>ProgrammeHistory</i> table)
Spin-out	<i>Original programme;</i>	- Indication of the original programme in the original programme field of the spun-out programme.
	<i>Demographic transformation</i>	- Indication of the process of spin-out (in <i>demographic transformations</i> field) associated to the programme subject to the spin-out process (in the <i>ProgrammeHistory</i> table)

Table 6: traceability of the demographic events regarding joint R&D programmes

4.3 Description of the Relational Model of JoREP 2.0

The design of JoREP 2.0 database was created in order to better manage the volume of data to be collected in future updates as well as to adapt to potential end-user demands for temporal analysis. It is based on the nature of the main unit of analysis it concerns: joint R&D programmes. Specifically, two features drove the creation of the model:

- A joint R&D programme is a **multilevel entity**, characterized by several or highly diversified attributes. Programme descriptors refer to three different levels: one is the level of the programme – including e.g. research topics; the other is the level of participation – regarding e.g. financial participation of countries and the third one is the level of beneficiaries – concerning e.g. budget allocated to performers.
- Programmes can **change over time** (see 4.2.1): they can undergo specific transformations, potentially each year. Data reveal variability both *within* and *between* programmes, considering internal changes within the programme along the years or participation and allocation dynamics that might change in the same time.

Thus, due to the **multilevel structure** of the joint R&D programmes and considering the need to handle **panel descriptors**, data have been stored into distinct manageable tables within a **relational structure**:

- Allowing to easily browse specific information referring to all levels;
- Accounting for the storage and visualization of longitudinal data.
- Assuring maximum possibility of querying.

4.3.1 Structure of the database

JoREP 2.0 rests on a solid bridge-structure (*fig.1*) including:

- ✓ **Five entity sets**, autonomous archives designed as **parent tables**, divided in:
 - two tables containing the **units of analysis** including
 - i. basic and stationary data about joint R&D Programmes;
 - ii. minimal descriptors of the funding agencies;
 - three **auxiliary sets** containing
 - iii. a list of countries *source of funding for/beneficiary of* the programmes;
 - iv. a list of reference years, as support for panel data collection;
 - v. an auxiliary list of currencies
- ✓ **Five longitudinal data tables**, designed as **child tables**, configuring as
 - **three junction-archives** among the entity sets, containing in-depth data on the historical transformation of the programmes and focusing on the dynamics of the three levels of the joint R&D programmes:
 - a. the internal characteristics of programmes;
 - b. the National participations in term of role and allocated budget;
 - c. the funding received by the beneficiaries of the programme;
 - an **auxiliary set** of panel countries' descriptors;
 - a **support panel archive** containing exchange rates.
- ✓ A web of **one-to-many relationships (1:M)**, in order to create links between parent and child tables – through unique identifiers – synching up data.

Figure 1: the bridge-structure of JoREP 2.0.

The relational model has been studied both in order to register the **demography** of the programmes and in order to follow the **history** of the programmes by year, pointing out the significant internal changes (at the programme-level) and the peculiar features which distinguish the participation and allocation dynamics (at the participation-level and beneficiaries-level).

As showed above (fig. 1), all the theoretical *many-to-many relationships* which link the main entities involved in the programme life – *joint R&D programmes, funding agencies, countries participating/beneficiating, years*– have been treated by creating **junction tables in one-to-many relationship (1:M) with single entity sets**.

So-built relationships envisage that each record in the parent tables (showed at the top and at the bottom of the figure), is related to one or more records contained in the child tables (at the centre of the figure).

All the 1:M relationships have been implemented in the relational model by inserting common fields marked as **primary keys** on the *1 side* and as **foreign keys**⁷ in the *M side*, as showed in MS Access relationship window (fig.2).

Figure 2: the relational model in the MS Access layout.

⁷ The foreign key is a field whose values match the primary key values in the related table. Foreign key values refers to an existing valid record in the entity set (Alexander, Kusleika, 2013).

Primary keys in the parent tables and foreign keys in the child tables automatically verify against each other. All their links represents the connections establishing data integrity between tables (Alexander, Kusleika, 2013). **Referential integrity** has been enforced in order to allow manageable future updates of the database and to prevent potential errors so that:

- When adding a new record to a child table, if a foreign key value is entered, it must exist in the related primary key field of the parent table;
- When changing a record in a parent table if the primary key is changed, the change must be cascaded to all foreign key valued records in any related child tables. Otherwise, the change to the parent table must be prohibited.
- When deleting a parent table record then related foreign key records in child tables must either be cascade deleted or deleted from child tables first.

4.3.2 The units of analysis tables

The individual joint R&D programmes and the single funding agencies – representing the **units of analysis** in JoREP 2.0 – are handled in two autonomous **parent tables**, as unique and distinct entities (forming single records), depending on primary keys.

- **Programme catalogue**

The table contains a primary key (a code) that uniquely identify each joint R&D programme as a single object. Further, it provides a minimal set of attributes in order to identify the main unit of analysis. The few descriptors focuses on the *basic* and *constant* information concerning the joint R&D programmes, including the start and end years and the establishing authorities. This set of information is considered as stationary (*see tab.7*).

Each record in the *ProgrammeCatalogue* has been linked with functionally dependent rows of longitudinal data tables, named *ProgrammeHistory*, *ParticipationHistory*, *BeneficiariesHistory*.

- **Funding agencies list**

It contains a list of formal organizations that manage functions for joint R&D programmes. Each agency is identifiable by a code contained in the table.

JoREP 2.0 collects a set of descriptors of the agencies as background information for the analysis.

Each record in the *FundingAgenciesList* has been linked with a functionally dependent row of longitudinal data tables, named *ParticipationHistory* and *BeneficiariesHistory*.

4.3.3 Auxiliary entity sets in the relational scheme

Two relevant aspects in the programme life – countries participating/beneficiating and single years in which programme exist – form single records in two main **auxiliary entity sets**, depending on primary keys.

- **Countries**

It contains the complete list of National states (associated to their ISO country code) with the indication of the inclusion/non-inclusion in the JoREP geographical coverage. In case of inclusion, the country is matched with the indication of latitude and longitude of its capital city.

Countries are intended both as **source of funding** and **location of performers**. The former is the case of the 1:M relationship with the longitudinal table about participation, in which the *1 side* will only link JoREP 2.0 countries; the latter is the case of the 1:M relationship with the longitudinal table about beneficiaries. Countries are also the references for the funding agencies contained in JoREP 2.0.

Each record in *Countries* has been linked with a functionally dependent row of the longitudinal table of *Countries Descriptors* and with all the single values contained in the multivalued field named *Partner Countries* in the table *Programme History*.

- **Years**

Years a simple list of the reference years for each programme.

Each year is essential to review the evolution of the programmes under all levels. Each record in *Years* has been linked with a functionally dependent row of all longitudinal data table in the database.

A further auxiliary parent table, named *Currencies*, has been envisaged in order to favour monetary conversions.

- **Currencies**

Currencies entity set has been created in order to contain a list of currencies. Each row is linked with the 'currency' fields of the two longitudinal tables regarding participation and beneficiaries.

4.3.4 Child tables and their relationships

Junction tables, configuring as **child tables**, has the task of linking together two or more entity sets – via foreign key –, permitting to browse, select, join, divide information in the database. These tables collect **longitudinal panel data**, being the constant link with the temporal dimension (the 'years' entity set).

All the other relevant **disaggregation** are integrated in the sets of panel data, giving the possibility to follow the dynamic component of the programme **over all levels**.

Thus, a single record in the longitudinal data tables links together one programme with a single or a multiple disaggregation.

- **Programme history.**

Potentially, a joint R&D programme might vary in some **internal characteristics** along the programme life (including e.g. the name of the programme). The table about programme history hosts potentially variable descriptors of joint R&D programmes in order to keep track of the characteristics of the programmes – situated at the 'programme level' – in their evolution. The interest focuses on the descriptors that identify the organizational features of the programmes, including e.g. the research topics, partner countries and the integration mode (*see tab. 7*).

<i>Descriptor</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>Type</i>	
Programme start year	Programme-level	Stationary	PARENT TABLE
Programme end year	Programme-level	Stationary	
Original programme	Programme-level	Stationary	
Successor programme	Programme-level	Stationary	
Establishing authority	Programme-level	Stationary	
Reference year	-	-	LONGITUDINAL TABLE
Name of the programme	Programme-level	Variable	
Type of instrument	Programme-level	Variable	
Programme duration	Programme-level	Variable	
Project duration	Programme-level	Variable	
Research topic	Programme-level	Variable	
Submission procedure	Programme-level	Variable	
Selection criteria	Programme-level	Variable	
Funding model	Programme-level	Variable	
EU contribution	Programme-level	Variable	
Coordinator country	Programme-level	Variable	
Partner countries	Programme-level	Variable	
Observer countries	Programme-level	Variable	
Mode of integration	Programme-level	Variable	
ERA category	Programme-level	Variable	
Programme type	Programme-level	Variable	

Table 7: the split among stationary and variable descriptors at the programme level.

As displayed in *fig. 3*, 1:M relationships link the longitudinal table with two parent table:

- each programme is linked with *ProgrammeHistory* junction table through the ProgrammeID (primary key)/ProgrammeID (foreign key) relationship;
- temporal dimension is linked with the panel table through Year (primary key)/Reference Year (foreign key).

Note: the field *Reference Year* in *ProgrammeHistory* is treated as multivalued (*fig. 3*), so that multiple values stored in the field can be treated independently in potential query tables.

Figure 3: 1:M relationships regarding ProgrammeHistory.

The 1:M relationship between programmes and partner countries (a descriptor of *ProgrammeHistory*) was treated typing the 'partner countries' field as multivalued (*fig. 4*), so that multiple values stored in the field can be treated independently in potential query tables. The set of the possible values of the field is contained in the *Country* table.

Figure 4: the 1:M relationship between programmes and partner countries.

• **ParticipationHistory**

A key task of JoREP 2.0 is to store complete data on the funding flows related to joint R&D programmes. *ParticipationHistory* collects data on the national participation of JoREP 2.0 countries to the joint R&D programmes from the catalogue for each reference year.

The dynamic of participation points out the funding agency executing at least one of the programme function (if applicable), including also the budget allocated to the programme by the agency or by only the Country (if applicable).

The set of descriptors is displayed in *tab. 8*. The list does not include fields on information about data source and remarks.

Descriptor	Level
Reference year	-
Participating country	Participation-level
National role	Participation-level
Funding agency	Participation-level
Agency functions	Participation-level
Origin of funding	Participation-level
Budget source category	Participation-level
Budgeting	Participation-level
Currency	Participation-level
Amount	Participation-level
Potential beneficiary sectors	Participation-level

Table 8: descriptors of joint R&D programmes at participation level

Panel data are stored – for each year of reference – linking all the programmes to the countries from where participation originates and to funding agencies involved (if applicable).

Because of the presence of a value in the ‘country’ field and in the ‘funding agency’ field, two special cases deserve attention:

- *Case 1*: a country can participate with a supranational agency instead of a national agency. The supranational agency will be inserted in the rows of the participation referred to a country.
- *Case 2*: no funding agency might be involved in the national participation or the name of the funding agency is not available. Special code will be used to indicate the absence of some value in order to avoid ‘null’ value in the *FundingAgenciesList*⁸

⁸ For instance, referring to the row of a country, a special code in the ‘agency’ field indicates that the country does not participate to the programme with a funding agency.

Possible combinations between ‘country’, ‘agency’ and ‘budget’ in the participation table are showed in the *tab. 9*:

TYPE OF PARTICIPATION	FIELD CONTENTS		
	Country	Agency	Budget
A country participates with a National funding agency, financing / not financing the programme	ISO code of the country	National agency ID	Amount funded
A country participates with a supranational funding agency, financing/not financing the programme	ISO code of the country	Supranational agency ID	Amount funded
A country participates without a National funding agency, financing / not financing the programme	ISO code of the country	Indication of no agency (special code will be used)	Amount funded

Table 9: descriptors of joint R&D programmes at participation level

Four tables share common attributes with the junction table, enabling the entity sets to be linked together (as showed in *fig. 5*):

- each programme is linked with the *ParticipationHistory* through the ProgrammID/ProgrammID 1:M relationship;
- temporal dimension is linked with the *ParticipationHistory* through the Year/Reference Year 1:M relationship;
- countries are linked with the *ParticipationHistory* through Country/Country 1:M relationship;
- funding Agencies are linked with the *ParticipationHistory* with Funding Agency ID/Funding Agency ID 1:M relationship.

Figure 5: 1:M relationships regarding ParticipationHistory.

● **BeneficiariesHistory**

Each country can beneficiate of a budget for many programmes, through funding agencies. Further, the budget received by a national agency may change by year.

Thus, beneficiaries' history stores a data collection of the budget transferred from each funding agencies to the performers. Data are collected by year for the countries of the performing organization and disaggregated by funding agency managing resources for the programme.

Descriptor	Level
Reference Year	-
Beneficiary country	Beneficiary-level
Funding agency	Beneficiary-level
Currency	Beneficiary-level
Amount (public/private/total)	Beneficiary-level

Table 10: descriptors of joint R&D programmes at beneficiary level.
The list does not include fields on information about data sources and remarks.

The four tables share common attributes with the junction table enabling the entity sets to be linked together (as showed in fig. 6):

- each programme is linked with the history through Programme ID/Programme ID 1:M relationship;
- each beneficiary country is linked with the *BeneficiariesHistory* table through the Country/Country 1:M relationship;
- temporal dimension is linked with the *BeneficiariesHistory* through the Year/Reference Year 1:M relationship;
- Funding Agencies are linked with the *BeneficiariesHistory* with Funding Agency ID/Funding Agency ID 1:M relationship.

Figure 6: 1:M relationships regarding BeneficiariesHistory

• **Countries' descriptors**

A longitudinal table of countries' descriptors has been introduced (see tab.11) in order to favour the match of data of country participations to joint R&D programmes with internal and variable-by-year features of the 32 countries which represent the geographical coverage of JoREP 2.0. Linkages between countries' descriptors table and 'countries' and 'years' tables are showed in fig. 7.

Descriptor	Level
Reference Year	-
GERD as a percentage of GDP	Country-level
Graduates on population	Country-level
Researcher on population	Country-level
H-Index	Country-level
Population	Country-level

Table 11: descriptors of JoREP countries

Figure 7: 1:M relationships regarding Countries' descriptors

- **Exchange rates**

A longitudinal table of exchange rates has been introduced in order to favour the conversion of monetary value in Euros. The table arose from the link between the 'currencies' table and 'years' entity set (fig.8).

Note: budget data for the period 2010-2014 are all provided in Euros.

Figure 8: 1:M relationships regarding ExchangeRates

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

Currently no interfaces with other infrastructures are foreseen.

5 Opening of the database and further planning

▪ *First opening of the database (December 2015)*

First opening of the database occurred in December 2015 and concerned version 1.0 of JoREP, with baseline 2009. In preparation for the opening, JoREP has been subject to a check of all the available information. First concrete steps towards opening were presented during the 'RISIS WEEK 2015' conference (Rome, January 26-29, 2015).

▪ *Opening of the 2.0 database version (June 2016)*

The following list presents the main actions which were implemented in conclusion of RISIS WP22 updating activities, in preparation for the opening of the 2.0 version of the JoREP database (June 2016):

- Updating of European-level programmes data until 2014, according to the activities to be developed in EUFP7 RISIS WP22. Newest data on large programmes (e.g. EUREKA) were collected following internal disaggregation of the programmes in order to collect more specific information;
- Enlargement of geographical coverage. Due to the activities of WP22, it was foreseen that the coverage of the database would be enlarged in order to expand the geographical coverage from 11 countries to EU28 countries plus 4 associated countries;
- Utility and feasibility checks of the list of variables. Data redundancy was limited to the necessary for the integration of tables within the relational database (e.g. repetition of information in multiple fields was treated clustering information in unique fields).

▪ *Further planning and technical changes*

The design of JoREP database has been planned to maintain the focus on the amount spent for joint R&D programmes and their organizational characteristics, but it was also studied with an outlook to future enlargement processes, according to the analysis of ERA dynamics.

The relational model is ready to be expanded in order to potentially host data on institutional funding and project funding⁹ at country level. The mentioned data can be retrieved from the PREF database¹⁰. Furthermore an integration of data which could be derived from other EUFP7 RISIS infrastructures can be implemented.

Further technical changes could be applied in order to enhance the new structure of the database:

- All the 'source fields' 'remark fields' contained in the tables of the database will be removed and replaced with metadata or flags;
- Funding agencies codes will be re-designed in a new format according to the work developed for the register of public sector organizations (EUFP7 RISIS WP8).

▪ *Changing of legal conditions*

No changing legal conditions for accessing the database or parts of the database are foreseen.

⁹ The distinction between 'institutional funding' (institutional block funding) versus 'project funding' is presented and discussed in OECD (2012).

¹⁰ The aim of the PREF-Public Research Funding study is to collect information on and provide an analysis of national public research funding by theme and by type of allocation.

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Report on the content and technical structure of the **CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016** Infrastructure

Universiteit
Leiden

Leiden University

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

Name and short description of the infrastructure

CWTS Leiden Ranking is a web-service of a university ranking focusing on output and impact of research. The underlying data are collected and processed from the CWTS version of Web of Science (WOS).

Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The CWTS Leiden Ranking aims at providing a platform to contribute to the discussion on university rankings. We created this platform to share the standardized way of measuring research output and impact. The measurement regards the performance of universities in a recent period of time (5 years) and is as such cross sectional. The current CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 data cover the publication years 2010-2015 and citations until 2013.

Legal name of operating organization

Universiteit Leiden – Centrum voor Wetenschaps- en technologie Studies (CWTS)

Database location and type of access (access on site, online, etc.)

CWTS Leiden Ranking is online available at <http://www.leidenranking.com> and onsite at

Leiden University, CWTS

Willem Einthoven building

Wassenaarseweg 62A

2333 AL Leiden

The Netherlands

2 Information on substantive content of *CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016*

2.1 Definition and description of observations

Units and definition of observations

CWTS Leiden Ranking covers information on:

- Universities worldwide

Number of observations

CWTS Leiden Ranking comprises information on **750 universities**. These 750 are the most productive ones in 2010-2014 according to data from WoS.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

Underlying data

CWTS Leiden Ranking is created using bibliographic and citation data from the CWTS version of WoS. The CWTS version is an exact copy of the WoS but with specific enhancements to the data (cleaned addresses and sources, added indicators etc.). The address data (affiliation of authors) of millions of publications is processed and cleaned to identify the most productive universities worldwide.

Data processing and cleaning

The CWTS WoS version enables a continuous processing and cleaning of new publication (hence address) data. The process for cleaning universities names regards an hierarchical approach in which first country names are cleaned, then city names and regions before the cleaning of university names starts. Within each city and region variants are identified and harmonized.

Identification of universities

The criteria that have been adopted to define universities for the Leiden Ranking are not very formal. Typically, a university is characterized by a combination of education and research tasks in conjunction with a doctorate-granting authority. However, these characteristics do not mean that the universities are particularly homogeneous entities that allow for international comparison on every aspect. The focus of the Leiden Ranking on scientific research certifies that the institutions included in the Leiden Ranking have a high degree of research intensity in common. Nevertheless, the ranking scores for each institution should be evaluated in the context of its particular mission and responsibilities. These missions and responsibilities in turn are strongly linked to the national and regional academic systems in which universities operate. Academic systems - and the role of universities therein - differ substantially from one another and are constantly changing. Inevitably, the outcomes of the Leiden Ranking reflect these differences and changes.

The international variety in the organization of academic systems also poses difficulties in terms of identifying the proper unit of analysis. In many countries, there are collegiate universities, university systems, or federal universities. Again, instead of applying formal criteria when possible we followed common practice based on the way these institutions are perceived locally. Consequently, we treated the University of Cambridge and the University of Oxford as entities but in the case of the University of London, we distinguished between the constituent colleges. For the United States, university systems (e.g. University of California) were split up into separate universities. The higher education sector in France, like in many other countries, has gone through many reorganizations in recent years. Many French institutions of higher education have been grouped together in Pôles de Recherche et d'Enseignement Supérieur (PRES), or in consortia. In most cases, the Leiden Ranking still distinguishes between the different constituent institutions but in particular cases of very tight integration, consortia were treated as if they were a single university (e.g. Grenoble INP).

Publications are assigned to universities based on their most recent configuration. Changes in the organizational structures of universities up to 2013 have been taken into account. For example, in the Leiden Ranking 2016, the University of Lisbon which merged with the Technical University of Lisbon in 2013 encompasses all publications assigned to the old University of Lisbon as well as the publications previously assigned to the Technical University of Lisbon.

Affiliated institutions

A key challenge in the compilation of a university ranking is the handling of publications originating from research institutes and hospitals associated with universities. Among academic systems a wide variety exists in the types of relations maintained by universities with these affiliated institutions. Usually, these relationships are shaped by local regulations and practices and affect the comparability of universities on a global scale. As there is no easy solution for this issue, it is important that producers of university rankings employ a transparent methodology in their treatment of affiliated institutions.

CWTS distinguishes three different types of affiliated institutions:

1. component
2. joint research facility or organization
3. associated organization

In the case of components the affiliated institution is actually part of the university or so tightly integrated with it or with one of its faculties that the two can be considered as a single entity. The University Medical Centres in the Netherlands are examples of components. All teaching and research tasks in the field of medicine that were traditionally the responsibility of the universities have been delegated to these separate organizations that combine the medical faculties and the university hospitals.

Joint research facilities or organizations are the same as components except for the fact that they are administered by more than one organization. The Brighton & Sussex Medical School, the joint medical faculty of the University of Brighton and the University of Sussex and, Charité, the medical school for both the Humboldt University and Freie Universität Berlin are both examples of this type of affiliated institution.

The third type of affiliated institution is the associated organization which is more loosely connected to the university. This organization is an autonomous institution that collaborates with one or more universities based on a joint purpose but at the same time has separate missions and tasks. In many countries, hospitals that operate as teaching or university hospitals fall into this category. Massachusetts General Hospital, one of the teaching hospitals of Harvard Medical School, is an example of an associated organization.

The treatment of university hospitals in particular is of substantial consequence as medical research has a strong presence in the Web of Science. The importance of associated organizations is growing as universities present themselves more and more frequently as network organizations. As a result, researchers formally employed by the university but working at associated organizations may not always mention the university in publications. On the other hand, as universities become increasingly aware of the significance of their visibility in research publications, they actively exert pressure on researchers to mention their affiliation with the university in their publications.

In the Leiden Ranking 2016, publications from affiliated institutions of the first two types are considered as output from the university. A different procedure has been followed for publications from associated organizations. A distinction is made between publications from associated organizations that also mention the university and publications from associated organizations that do not contain such a university affiliation. In the latter case, publications are not counted as publications originating from the university. In the event that a publication contains affiliations from a particular university as well as affiliations from its associated organization(s), both type of affiliations are credited to the contribution of that particular university to the publication in the fractional counting method.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

CWTS Leiden Ranking indicators for universities

- P: number of publications of a university
- TCS (total citation score): the total amount of citations received (self-citations excluded)
- MCS (mean citation score). The average number of citations of the publications of a university.
- TNCS (total normalized citation score): Total number of citations received normalized by field and publication year.
- MNCS (mean normalized citation score). The average number of citations of the publications of a university, normalized for field differences and publication year. An MNCS value of two for instance means that the publications of a university have been cited twice above world average.
- PP(top 10%) (proportion of top 10% publications). The proportion of the publications of a university that, compared with other publications in the same field and in the same year, belong to the top 10% most frequently cited
- PP(collab) (proportion of interinstitutional collaborative publications). The proportion of the publications of a university that have been co-authored with one or more other organizations.
- PP(int collab) (proportion of international collaborative publications). The proportion of the publications of a university that have been co-authored by two or more countries.
- PP(UI collab) (proportion of collaborative publications with industry). The proportion of the publications of a university that have been co-authored with one or more industrial partners. For more details, see University-Industry Research Connections 2013.
- PP(<100 km) (proportion of short distance collaborative publications). The proportion of the publications of a university with a geographical collaboration distance of less than 100 km, where the geographical collaboration distance of a publication equals the largest geographical distance between two addresses mentioned in the publication's address list.
- PP(>1000 km) (proportion of long distance collaborative publications). The proportion of the publications of a university with a geographical collaboration distance of more than 1000 km.

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Information on the sectorial classifications used

The publications are distributed over the following main fields:

- All fields
- Cognitive and health sciences
- Earth and environmental sciences

- Life sciences
- Mathematics, computer science, and engineering
- Medical sciences
- Natural sciences
- Social sciences

The above fields have been defined using a unique bottom-up approach. Traditionally, fields are defined as sets of closely related journals. This approach is problematic especially in the case of multidisciplinary journals such as Nature, PLoS ONE, PNAS, and Science, which do not belong to one particular field. The seven broad fields of science listed above have been defined at the level of individual publications rather than at the journal level. Using a computer algorithm, each publication in the Web of Science database has been assigned to one of these seven fields. This has been done based on a large-scale analysis of hundreds of millions of citation relations between publications. More information about the main fields and how they are selected via <http://www.leidenranking.com>.

Information on the temporal coverage used

The CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 data cover the publication years 2010-2014 and citations until 2015.

Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used

The CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 data cover 750 most productive universities worldwide. In the current version they represent all regions Africa, Asia, Europe, North America, South America, and Oceania. Within these regions, the ranking covers 49 countries.

The classification used to normalize indicators and distinct main fields is an inhouse publication classification. More information about this classification and main fields at <http://www.leidenranking.com> or <http://www.cwts.nl>.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

It is important to highlight that the assignment of publications to universities is not free of errors. There are generally two types of errors: 'false positives', which are publications that have been assigned to a university when they do not in fact belong to that university, and 'false negatives', which are publications that have not been assigned to a university when they should in fact have been. Considerably more false negatives than false positives should be expected, especially since the 5% least frequently occurring addresses in the database may not have been manually checked. This can be considered a reasonable upper bound for errors, since the majority of these addresses are probably non-university addresses.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

Legal issues concerning access of the database

The data disclosed in the CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 (as well as previous editions) is publically available at <http://www.leidenranking.com>. The data can be used interactively through a web interface and is also available by XLS download.

For more detailed analysis an onsite visit is needed to access the underlying data of the CWTS Leiden Ranking databases. For this we host a guest account and a Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) needs to be signed.

Owner of CWTS Leiden Ranking raw data

Universiteit Leiden, CWTS is the owner of the CWTS Leiden Ranking data.

Copyright holder for underlying WoS data is Thomson Reuters.

Current practice for opening up of the database to external users

The data of the CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 (and previous editions) is publically available via <http://www.leidenranking.com>. A downloadable XLS version is also available of all data.

Legal necessities for potential opening procedures

Access to the underlying CWTS WoS data is possible onsite at CWTS. For this a guest account and signed NDA will be arranged.

4 Technical structure of *CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016*

4.1 Information on the data base system

Current data base system used

CWTS Leiden Ranking is processed and stored in a Microsoft SQL server dedicated web database.

Planned future technical changes concerning data base system

None

4.2 Technical variable definition

Labelling and data type of all variables

The indicators included are as listed in section 3.2. The indicators with the extension ‘_lb’ and ‘_ub’ regard the lower bound and upper bound values used to define the stability intervals.

The following list describes the labelling of the variables, data type is given in brackets:

- University (char)
- Country (char)
- Field (char)
- Frac_counting (0 or 1)
- P (num)
- TCS (num)
- TNCS (num)
- P_top (num)
- P_collab (num)
- P_int_collab (num)
- P_UI_collab (num)
- P_short_dist_collab (num)
- P_long_dist_collab (num)
- MCS (num)
- MCS_lb (num)
- MCS_ub (num)

- MNCS (num)
- MNCS_lb (num)
- MNCS_ub (num)
- PP_top (perc)
- PP_top_lb (perc)
- PP_top_ub (perc)
- PP_collab (perc)
- PP_collab_lb (perc)
- PP_collab_ub (perc)
- PP_int_collab (perc)
- PP_int_collab_lb (perc)
- PP_int_collab_ub (perc)
- PP_UI_collab (perc)
- PP_UI_collab_lb (perc)
- PP_UI_collab_ub (perc)
- PP_short_dist_collab (perc)
- PP_short_dist_collab_lb (perc)
- PP_short_dist_collab_ub (perc)
- PP_long_dist_collab (perc)
- PP_long_dist_collab_lb (perc)
- PP_long_dist_collab_ub (perc)

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016

Definition of single tables

CWTS Leiden ranking 2016 consists of one table (see previous section). The underlying data consists of three tables:

List of Universities:		Universities_publications		Publication indicators	
ID	num	ID	num	Pub_id	char
Name	char	Pub_id	char	Indicator A	num
				Indicator B	num
				Etc.	num

Relation between the tables via unique identifiers

The table *List of universities* is connected to *universities_publications* via ID. The *Universities_publications* table is connected to the table *Publication indicators* via pub_id.

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

Technical information on interfaces with other infrastructures (e.g. web interface for data search. etc.)

The CWTS Leiden Ranking 2016 and previous editions is available via <http://www.leidenranking.com>.

5 Further planning of the opening of *CWTS Leiden Ranking*

Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

The results of the CWTS Leiden Ranking are already online. Underlying tables are available at CWTS onsite. A guest account at the CWTS and a signed NDA is needed to access these tables.

The underlying address data is being updated continuously. This data is also available at CWTS onsite under the same conditions (guest account and signed NDA).

Necessary updates and/or technical changes

The CWTS Leiden Ranking is updated on a yearly basis. In April an update is launched online (website) containing publications until the year before the preceding and citations until the preceding year.

During the RISIS period, new entries will be included in the CWTS Leiden Ranking. We anticipate to include Public Research Organizations (PROs) in the 2017 edition.

Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset

The legal access conditions are expected to remain the same throughout.

Report on the content and technical structure of the **MORE II** Infrastructure

NIFU

Nordic Institute for Studies in
Innovation, Research and Education

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of the *MORE2* infrastructure (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

Name: Mobility Survey of the Higher Education Sector: Mobility and Career Paths of Researchers in Europe, 2012 (MORE2)

Improving the conditions for researcher mobility is (re)emerging as a central priority of European research and innovation policy. This priority is prominent in the Europe 2020 strategy and in current policy initiatives under the European Research Area. These forward-looking objectives build on an extensive tradition in Europe for the study of researcher mobility patterns, the factors shape them and the effects they have. This tradition traces at least back to the European Human Capital and Mobility program (1992).

The Mobility Survey of the Higher Education Sector (MORE) survey is a key study in this tradition. MORE I (2009) is the first in a family of wide-scale empirical studies that focused on the mobility patterns of European researchers and their career paths. It was followed up in 2012 by the MORE2 study to provide internationally comparable data, indicators and analysis in order to support further evidence-based policy development on the research profession at European and national level. The survey of researchers in higher education in Europe was the first work package of this study, complemented by a (limited) survey of researchers outside Europe, case studies on the working conditions and career paths of early stage researchers and on the remuneration of researchers and the collection of a set of internationally-comparable indicators in existing sources. This Report presents the MORE2 HEI survey in Europe and it builds on a parallel report detailing the MORE1 dataset.

MORE2 targeted researchers working in different fields and career stages at higher education institutes in all EU27 countries and 6 (at the time) Associated and Candidate countries¹. The study provides measures of flows of international, interdisciplinary and intersectoral mobility, of factors that influence mobility and non-mobility (motivations and barriers), and of effects that can be linked to researcher mobility. Also topics such as structural PhD training and virtual mobility are addressed. The survey responses thus provide promising avenues for a range of studies to better understand the career development paths of researchers working in Europe.

Important to mention is that the collected data are accurate at country level (EU27, Candidate and Associated countries) thanks to the specific sampling design and implementation.

This Report provides the background information about the MORE2 to indicate the type of dataset it is, how it will be opened up, and how it might be combined with other data. In general, the infrastructure will be operated by NIFU². Access is foreseen in three forms: On-site access at NIFU, thereafter on-line access, and access during approved RISIS training events.

All accessibility environments will respect privacy/confidentiality issues while attempting to provide maximum analytical possibilities/learning outcomes. The platform will be piloted with MORE I data. In time, this pilot will subsequently be complemented by the

¹ Candidate Countries: Croatia, Turkey, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
Associate Countries: Norway, Switzerland, Iceland

² NIFU's legal name is Nordisk institutt for studier av innovasjon, forskning og utdanning (NIFU). www.nifu.no

micro-data from the MORE2³ survey, carried out by IDEA Consult (Belgium). Details of the MORE1 survey are provided in a preceding report on which underlying document builds.

2 Information on substantive content of MORE2

The MORE2 study was to provide internationally comparable data, indicators and analysis in order to support further evidence-based policy development on the research profession at European and national level. It thereby, like the MORE1 study, produced an accurate register of researcher-populations or of universities across Europe.

MORE2 employed a two stage stratified random sampling strategy. It sampled almost 50,000 researchers in around 2.500 clusters and yielded 10,547 valid responses (response rate of 21.5%) through a multichannel survey, combining both CATI (computer-assisted telephone interviews) and CAWI (computer-assisted web interviews).

The responses combine information about (in **bold** information that is new or more elaborated in MORE2 compared to MORE1):

MORE1	MORE2
1. The researcher (country of birth, citizenship(s), gender, age, children),	1. Socio-demographics
2. Education (degrees, graduation year, country, field of highest degree)	2. Education 3. PhD and doctoral training
3. Current position (university/college, faculty, field, position level, seniority)	4. Current employment and working conditions (including contract, status, satisfaction, inter- and transdisciplinary mobility)
4. Mobility events (up to five mobility events, countr(ies), duration, type)	5. Academic mobility and career paths (including PhD, including past and current mobility, including motivations, barriers and effects of mobility) a. PhD mobility b. Further career mobility c. <3 month mobility d. Non-mobility e. Virtual mobility
5. Assessment of mobility among mobile as distinct from non-mobile researchers: a. Detailed focus on most recent mobility event (motivations, push and pull factors, assessment) b. Plans/aspiration to work in another country: (country, rationale and background for choice of destination)	6. Collaboration / Virtual mobility 7. Intersectoral mobility
	8. Awareness of EU policy 9. Comparison research environments (EU – non-EU; EU countries)

The responses provide a snapshot of mobility patterns and career paths of EU27 researchers (in 2012). The sample is distributed across EU27 countries and 6 (at the time) Associated and Candidate countries⁴. The geographical distributions of the final frame, response and response rate are presented below.

³ <http://www.more-2.eu>

⁴ Candidate Countries: Croatia, Turkey, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
Associate Countries: Norway, Switzerland, Iceland

2.1 Definition and description of observations

It is important to mention here that the MORE I frame was built as a first in its kind, based on desk research and web search techniques. The MORE2 study did not fully repeat this intensive exercise but based its frame on the MORE I frame, merged with the EUMIDA database⁵. The applied definitions and principles in this process are described below.

Researchers

MORE2 employed a two stage stratified random sampling strategy based on the population figures in Eurostat. HEI researchers in EU27+6 were selected based on the FRASCATI manual definition⁶. The definition covers professionals with tertiary (or higher) education and not “technicians and equivalent staff” or “other supporting staff”. The accuracy of the definition was confirmed by a question in the survey:

We specifically target “researchers” within this survey, including people:

- carrying out research OR
- supervising research OR
- improving or developing new products/processes/services OR
- supervising the improvement or development of new products/processes/services.

If you consider yourself to fall into one or more of the above categories, we kindly ask you to complete the questionnaire.

I...

- consider myself a researcher
 do not fall in to one of the above categories

Researchers population

The population of researchers, which determines the frame of the study, was estimated using Eurostat’s headcounts for 2009, supplemented where necessary by estimates (based on earlier years or from other statistics). The total population was estimated to be roughly 1.4 million researchers of this type in the EU27+6 countries (of which 1.2 million in EU27). The ETER effort (and its predecessor, Eumida) have since helped to refine the population, standardize the names and location, and provide a map of the distribution of researchers in Europe. As noted, HEI names in the MORE data will be linked to the ETER designations. These can be used to improve the accuracy of the responses via post-stratification techniques (see also sections 2.4 and 5, below).

Fields of Science

⁵ 4 countries were not present in the MORE I frame or the EUMIDA database: Turkey, Croatia, Macedonia (FYROM) and Iceland. To complete this and other lacking information, an additional updating procedure was organised through web search routines on the most relevant directories of universities and on the official sources, i.e. research ministries.

⁶

<http://www.oecd.org/innovation/inno/frascatimanualproposedstandardpracticeforsurveysonresearchandexperimentaldevelopment6thedition.htm>

The classification of the fields of science (FOS) is the main benchmark for the specialization of HEIs and of researchers and it is therefore also the stratification criterion for the sample within each country. MORE2 follows the same criteria as applied in MORE1 and selects 3 fields of science, fully compatible with official statistics and with the EUMIDA project database. The FOS classification is an aggregation of the six FOS classification proposed by the OECD in 2006 according to the following scheme:

- FOS 1 (Natural sciences) and FOS 2 (Engineering and technology) will fall in NATURAL (Abbreviation in the project)
- FOS 3 (Medical sciences) and FOS 4 (Agricultural sciences) will fall in HEALTH (Abbreviation in the project)
- FOS 5 (Social sciences) and FOS 6 (Humanities) will fall in SOCIAL (Abbreviation in the project)

Higher Education Institute (HEI) and HEI cluster

The clusters consist of the individual departments of EU27+6 HEIs. A university department is defined a part of the HEI (faculty or department) that is specialised into only one FOS, regardless of its formal nature within the structure of the institution and standardised in term of size within each country. The precise definition of a cluster is thus "Department A of University B in Country C and Field of Science D". This definition is equal to the one applied in MORE I, although a check led to merge a number of clusters into one according to the rule of one field of science.

All higher education institutes in the merged EUMIDA/MORE1 database, both of public or private nature, were therefore considered eligible for the sample frame under the condition that they included at least one ISCED 6 student (PhD level) and/or one researcher. The HEI cluster database was subsequently updated to update information on existing HEI clusters, include new clusters or delete those that were no longer active.

It is important to note that a two stage stratified cluster-sampling strategy is distinct from a standard random sample survey. Within the each country and field of science (the strata), the MORE2 sample grouped the population units not on researchers but on departments of HEIs. A primary sampling unit (psu) is thus a faculty of a given university in country x and field of science y (cluster).

Two-stage stratified random sampling

Using these definitions and data, the sampling strategy stratified by country (33) and broad fields of science (3 – Natural Sciences and Technology, Medical Sciences and Agriculture, and Social Science and Humanities). This resulted thus in 99 strata (33*3), to be sampled from the 'clusters' at the level of individual university departments. Almost 2,500 HEIs were sampled across EU27+6 countries.

A list of researchers within each cluster was collected and researchers were further selected into the sampling frame under the assumption of random sampling. University department websites were checked for researchers' email addresses (updates and new addresses compared to MORE1). After cleaning, 49,056 individual researchers were identified as targets.

The online survey was launched by email and telephone in May 2012 and closed at the end of July 2012. After cleaning, 10,547 valid responses were yielded.⁷

2.2 Data acquisition and processing

a. Where are the data retrieved from:

The MORE2 survey was carried out in 2012 under the aegis of the MORE2 project. IDEA Consult organised the multichannel survey combining CATI (computer assisted telephone interview) and CAWI (computer assisted web interview). The project documentation about the project is available online⁸. The process of data collection up to data cleaning and editing is outlined in the figure below.

The data-owner is the European Commission.

⁷ For more information, consult MORE2 HEI report, 2012 on which this presentation is based:

http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/more2/Report%20on%20survey%20of%20researchers%20in%20EU%20HEI.pdf.

⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/more2/Final%20report.pdf

Figure 1: Data collection process

Source: IDEA Consult, MORE2 HEI report (2012)

b. How are the data processed in terms of data cleaning (e.g. harmonisation of organization names, etc.):

The dataset have been cleaned. Weights are included for the population and for the strata. The MORE HEI report (2012) describes the data and characteristics of the respondents. A methodological report with details on the sampling strategy and data was delivered, but is not publicly available. HEI names have been harmonized with ETER as indicated in section 5 of this report and further developed in the Activity Sheet 2.4.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

a. Description of all variables and/or indicators:

The variables of the MORE2 dataset cover the following topics (in **bold** information that is new or more elaborated in MORE2 compared to MORE1):

MORE1	MORE2
6. The researcher (country of birth, citizenship(s), gender, age, children),	1. Socio-demographics
7. Education (degrees, graduation year, country, field of highest degree)	2. Education 3. PhD and doctoral training
8. Current position (university/college, faculty, field, position level, seniority)	4. Current employment and working conditions (including contract, status, satisfaction, inter- and transdisciplinary mobility)
9. Mobility events (up to five mobility events, countr(ies), duration, type)	5. Academic mobility and career paths (including PhD, including past and current mobility, including motivations, barriers and effects of mobility) a. PhD mobility b. Further career mobility c. <3 month mobility d. Non-mobility e. Virtual mobility 6. Collaboration / Virtual mobility 7. Intersectoral mobility
10. Assessment of mobility among mobile as distinct from non-mobile researchers: c. Detailed focus on most recent mobility event (motivations, push and pull factors, assessment) d. Plans/aspiration to work in another country: (country, rationale and background for choice of destination)	
	8. Awareness of EU policy 9. Comparison research environments (EU – non-EU; EU countries)

Next to the raw dataset with variables, one of the MORE2 deliverables is an indicator set, accessible online⁹ and with the following structure:

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Subtheme</i>
HR of researchers	Stock of researchers
	Training phase
Employment situation of researchers	Sector of employment
	Characteristics, position, status, contract
	Work satisfaction
Mobility of researchers - Stock	Geographical mobility - current
	Geographical mobility - long term
	Geographical mobility - short term
	Geographical non-mobility
Mobility of researchers - Motives, Barriers, Effects	Geographical mobility - motives
	Geographical mobility - barriers
	Geographical mobility - effects
Mobility of researchers - Non-geographic mobility	Virtual mobility/Collaboration
	Intersectoral Mobility
	Intersectoral mobility - characteristics, position, status, contract

⁹ http://www.more-2.eu/www/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=118&Itemid=125

- b. Information on the sectorial classifications used (e.g., economic sectors, technological fields, organizations types, etc.), and listing of all categories for each classification scheme:

Next to the key definitions of researchers and fields of science (described under section 2.1 as they define the sampling strategy), other classifications are applied for career stage, type of mobility and reference countries.

Career stages R1 to R4

In order to allow for country comparisons in terms of functions and experience levels, the concept of specific career stages was introduced according to the four career stages outlined and defined in the European Commission's communication "Towards a European Framework for Research Careers"¹⁰. Researchers in the MORE2 surveys were asked to self-select into one of these four stages.

These four career stages are:

- **R1: First Stage Researcher** (up to the point of PhD),
- **R2: Recognized Researcher** (PhD holders or equivalent who are not yet fully independent),
- **R3: Established Researcher** (researchers who have developed a level of independence) and
- **R4: Leading Researcher** (researchers leading their research area or field).

More details are provided in Annex 3.

Mobility

Definitions of researchers' mobility used systematically in the indicator descriptions:

- **International mobility versus intersectoral mobility:**
Moving to another country versus moving to another sector (though both can occur in the same move)
- **PhD mobility versus post-PhD mobility:**
Mobility of researchers enrolled in a PhD programme during their R1 career stage versus mobility in any of the following research career stages and, even though the for simplicity selected terminology suggests otherwise, regardless of whether or not the researcher has obtained a PhD.
- **PhD degree mobility versus >3 month mobility during PhD:**
Mobility with the purpose of obtaining the PhD in another country versus mobility of three months or more during the PhD while still obtaining the PhD in the home country
- **>3 month mobility versus <3 month mobility:**
Mobility with duration of 3 months or more versus mobility with duration of less than 3 months
- **Employer mobility:**
Mobility including a change of employer

¹⁰

http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/Towards_a_European_Framework_for_Research_Careers_final.pdf

- **Virtual mobility:**
The use of web-based or virtual technology to collaborate internationally (cf. Annex 1 section 2)
- **Non-mobility or never-mobile researchers:**
Having never been mobile to another country (not within the last ten years nor before)

Reference countries

In the MORE2 HEI data (2012), different countries of reference are collected:

- Panel country: the country identified as country of current employment during the collection of researcher contact details (before the survey)
- Country of current employment (as identified in the survey)
- Country of PhD: country where the researcher is currently enrolled in a PhD programme or has previously obtained his or her PhD.
- Country of citizenship
- Country of residence
- ...

The panel country is the only one collected in preparation of the survey to be one of the dimensions in the stratified sampling strategy. Therefore, unless otherwise indicated in the description of the indicators, panel country is applied as reference and the indicators referring to panel country are accurate at country level.

Other references are sometimes applied, depending on the specific indicator. It is worth mentioning that the panel country and country of current employment are 98.4% of the cases the same.

- c. Information on the temporal coverage used (e.g. annual data from 1990-2010, etc.):

The survey was carried out in the period May-July 2012. For 'researcher mobility' variables, the reference period was either the whole researcher career or the last three years 2009-2012.

- d. Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used (e.g. EU-27 member states, regional breakdown using NUTS classification revision 2010, etc.):

- 27 EU Member States
- Candidate Countries: Croatia, Turkey, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia
- Associate Countries: Norway, Switzerland, Iceland

2.4 Quality and accuracy of data

In general, the sampling and data collection strategy were designed to generate high-quality and accurate data. The aim was to provide representative data **at country level**, with a maximum error of 5% at a probability of 95%. This objective was reached in most countries.

- a. Information on the number of missing values: details of the survey including the extent of missing values is provided in the project work.

Only complete responses were included in the final dataset. In part thanks to the CATI method, the number of partial responses was relatively low (less than 7.5%). Those partial responses with high degree of completion were edited using donor techniques, which allowed 97 responses to be saved for the final dataset.

The responses per strata are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of responses by strata (country x field of science).

Source: IDEA Consult based on MORE2 HEI data (2012)

- b. Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system:

Bug in <3 month mobility question

The combined CATI and CAWI data collection process lowered the risk of partial responses. However, a bug during the programming of the CATI system created an issue related to the <3 month mobility item that followed a different filtering from the CAWI for a subpopulation of respondents. This issue resulted in the lack of information on 2,787 units, a group too substantial not to have an impact on the analysis of <3 month mobility

indicators. Therefore a supplementary survey was launched during the month of September in order to increase the number of correct questionnaires. The 968 additional filled-in questionnaires were then used, together with the original correctly filled-in questionnaires, to implement donor techniques to 1802 units from a deck of 2720 units. The filtering bug has created an issue that has been partially recovered by the supplementary survey, but results will not be as accurate as when all respondents would have given their own information in the original survey. The editing however does allow preserving the minimum representativity requirements for <3 month mobility.

Response bias or seasonal effects

Whereas the editing for partial responses and on <3 month mobility items was meant to complement the information where missing, the editing for non-responses was meant to decrease a potential bias in the answering patterns by calibrating the given responses of all researchers to a proportion that corrects for this potential bias. For example, if researchers that are willing to participate in a survey entitled 'mobility of researchers' are in turn the most mobile researchers in the population, our estimates of mobility would be higher than for the entire population. By surveying non-respondents and comparing their answering pattern to the original respondents' pattern, it is possible to identify and (to some extent) correct this bias. A similar logic applies in terms of seasonal effects due to timing of the survey just before and over summer, which lowered the response rates and could lead to a potential bias of people responding that were still on job during summer.

A non-response survey through both CATI and CAWI allowed to correct for this kind of bias. The estimates were calibrated based on this additional information.

Coverage

The return rate (including also partial responses) was 23%, the response rate (including only the responses used in the analysis) was 21.5%. Only in a few countries, estimates of missing information in the population or concentration of linguistic issues formed a risk to/lowered the accuracy of the data (Iceland, Latvia and Bulgaria). The maximal sampling errors per country are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Max Sampling errors in HC and FTE by country

country	HC
Austria	4.2
Belgium	4.4
Bulgaria	7.7
Croatia	5.8
Cyprus	6.4
Czech Republic	5.6
Denmark	4.8
Estonia	5.9
Finland	5.5
France	5.1
Germany	4.6
Greece	5.5
Hungary	7.2
Iceland	10.1
Ireland	4.9
Italy	4.4

Latvia	9.6
Lithuania	5.0
Luxembourg	5.4
Macedonia (FYROM)	7.6
Malta	6.1
Netherlands	4.1
Norway	5.5
Poland	5.0
Portugal	5.1
Romania	5.6
Slovakia	6.5
Slovenia	5.5
Spain	4.6
Sweden	5.2
Switzerland	4.5
Turkey	6.4
United Kingdom	4.8

Source: IDEA Consult, MORE2 HEI report (2012)

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

- a. Legal issues concerning access of the database: Access to the micro-data is currently restricted to the MORE2 project group.
- b. Owner of raw data (at the time of contract): European Commission DG Research (Directorate B – European Research Area)
- c. Current practice for opening up of the database to external users: External users are directed to the project team-leader (IDEA Consult) and the Commission Scientific Officer (Peter Whitten)
- d. Legal necessities for potential opening procedures: Permission from the data-owner (EU Commission) has been promised. Reference is made to the European Commission and the MORE2 study and consistency in terms of weighting methodology is guaranteed. Further clearance from the respective part of the Commission may be necessary.

Steps to ensure opening have already been made. We have got a green light from the Commission about the opening of MORE 1 and MORE 2.

4 Technical structure of *MORE2 (HEI)*

4.1 Information on the data base system

The data are stored at IDEA Consult in Excel and Stata (12) format as one integrated table. The weighting, clustering, and stratification of the survey design is described in a separate protocol.

4.2 Technical variable definition

- a. The variables are named according to the numbering of the question. Information about the formatting are found in the Annex (below)
- b. Data type of all variables: The data are saved in the appropriate format (e.g. byte for Likert scale). There are nine different types of information based on the 87

questions of the full survey. These nine types of information correspond to a large extent to the 5 types identified in MORE1 and are linked to the conceptual framework of the MORE2 study in the table below.

- c. Current usage and definition of unique identifiers: The unique identifier currently used is a numeric value (“response”) that has been associated with the response. A time-stamp is not associated. An overview of variables is provided in the Annex.

MORE2 survey structure	Conceptual framework
1. Socio-demographics 2. Education 3. PhD and doctoral training	Human resources of researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ‘Stocks’ of researchers • HRST, Scientists and Engineers, R&D personnel • Researchers in their training phase • Researchers working in the HEI sector in the EU • Researchers who have moved from the EU to non-EU countries
4. Current employment and working conditions (including inter- and transdisciplinary mobility)	Employment situation of researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employment sector • Characteristics of employment contract • Position/status of the researcher • Contractual status • Work satisfaction in terms of different aspects of researchers’ career
	Research environment as an attractiveness factor for researchers
5. Academic mobility and career paths (including PhD, including past and current mobility) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. PhD mobility b. Further career mobility c. <3 month mobility d. Non-mobility e. Virtual mobility 6. Collaboration / Virtual mobility 7. Intersectoral mobility	Mobility of researchers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stocks of mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ International mobility intra-EU ○ International mobility extra-EU ○ Intersectoral mobility ○ Virtual mobility • Flows of mobility <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Quantification of movements • Influencing factors of mobility • Motivations for mobility • Effects of mobility
8. Awareness of EU policy 9. Comparison research environments (EU – non-EU; EU countries)	Research environment as an attractiveness factor for researchers

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of *MORE*

- a. Definition of single tables: The dataset currently consists of 1 single table.

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

As with the MORE I dataset, the MORE2 survey results can be further enriched and complemented by linking them to each other and potentially to other datasets.

5 Further planning of the opening of *MORE*

There are currently two finalized survey in the MORE family. These are provided in the RISIS infrastructure. We emphasize again that MORE2 cannot be compare with MORE1 due to differences in the survey and sample designs. A third round (MORE3) is currently in the field: it is possible that this will be added to the RISIS infrastructure.

a. Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

In order to open the MORE2 dataset for on-site as well as on on-line visits, a number of steps must be made to accommodate visitors at NIFU. The steps are:

- Definition of basic terms and principles
- guidelines and terms of use of the dataset,
- Rules and procedures governing the access-infrastructure, including the definition of access conditions for RISIS researchers
- Preparation of the dataset
- Documentation of the dataset
- Tests and remedial efforts to address potential coverage and non-response bias
- Tests and remedial efforts to address potential design and misspecification effects.
- Integration with relevant activities, including linking information from ETER (see also below)
- The technical implementation for dissemination.

A first step will involve making the MORE2 accessible through NIFU and in-house. The next step is to make it available on-line. In subsequent steps, the infrastructure that will allow combined analysis with the previous MORE I data will be explored. MORE I and MORE2 are standalone datasets: integration of the datasets will be made where consistency of the survey design of the two surveys allows.

b. Necessary updates and/or technical changes

Together with MORE1, the sampling designs of the two studies were compared to assess the best form and modes of access to the datasets. We have consulted with the data-owner during this process. It was made clear that the differences in the two datasets are too large to allow them to be compared. **The data-owner (the EU Commission) and the responsible party for collecting the data (IDEA Consult) therefore strongly advise against comparing MORE2 with MORE1.**

The Commission has given RISIS the right to open the two rounds of MORE. To do so, we have worked with the responsible party for collecting the data in both cases (IDEA Consult).

Annex 1: Labels and values

Information on all variables/indicators

Structure:

MORE2
1. Socio-demographics
2. Education
3. PhD and doctoral training
4. Current employment and working conditions (including contract, status, satisfaction, inter- and transdisciplinary mobility)
5. Academic mobility and career paths (including PhD, including past and current mobility, including motivations, barriers and effects of mobility) <ul style="list-style-type: none">a. PhD mobilityb. Further career mobilityc. <3 month mobilityd. Non-mobilitye. Virtual mobility
6. Collaboration / Virtual mobility
7. Intersectoral mobility
8. Awareness of EU policy
9. Comparison research environments (EU – non-EU; EU countries)

Annex 2: Classification career stages

According to the definitions given in the EC's communication Towards a European Framework for Research Careers"¹¹ the different stages are characterized as follows:

A first stage researcher (R1) will:

- “Carry out research under supervision;
- Have the ambition to develop knowledge of research methodologies and discipline;
- Have demonstrated a good understanding of a field of study;
- Have demonstrated the ability to produce data under supervision;
- Be capable of critical analysis, evaluation and synthesis of new and complex ideas and
- Be able to explain the outcome of research and value thereof to research colleagues.”

Recognized researchers (R2) are PhD holders or researchers with an equivalent level of experience and competence who have not yet established a significant level of independence. In addition to the characteristics assigned to the profile of a first stage researcher a recognized researcher:

- “Has demonstrated a systematic understanding of a field of study and mastery of research associated with that field
- Has demonstrated the ability to conceive, design, implement and adapt a substantial program of research with integrity
- Has made a contribution through original research that extends the frontier of knowledge by developing a substantial body of work, innovation or application. This could merit national or international refereed publication or patent.
- Demonstrates critical analysis, evaluation and synthesis of new and complex ideas.
- Can communicate with his peers - be able to explain the outcome of his research and value thereof to the research community.
- Takes ownership for and manages own career progression, sets realistic and achievable career goals, identifies and develops ways to improve employability.
- Co-authors papers at workshop and conferences.”

An established Researcher (R3) has developed a level of independence and, in addition to the characteristics assigned to the profile of a recognized researcher:

- “Has an established reputation based on research excellence in his field.
- Makes a positive contribution to the development of knowledge, research and development through co-operations and collaborations.
- Identifies research problems and opportunities within his area of expertise
Identifies appropriate research methodologies and approaches.
- Conducts research independently which advances a research agenda.
- Can take the lead in executing collaborative research projects in cooperation with colleagues and project partners.
- Publishes papers as lead author, organizes workshops or conference sessions.”

11

A leading researcher (R4) leads research in his area or field. He or she leads a team or a research group or is head of an industry R&D laboratory. "In particular disciplines as an exception, leading researchers may include individuals who operate as lone researchers." A leading researcher, in addition to the characteristics assigned to the profile of an established researcher:

- "Has an international reputation based on research excellence in their field.
- Demonstrates critical judgment in the identification and execution of research activities.
- Makes a substantial contribution (breakthroughs) to their research field or spanning multiple areas.
- Develops a strategic vision on the future of the research field.
- Recognizes the broader implications and applications of their research.
- Publishes and presents influential papers and books, serves on workshop and conference organizing committees and delivers invited talks"

Annex 3. MORE2 Protocol

The MORE2 project

The MORE2 project was carried out by a consortium led by IDEA Consult (BE) with support from European Commission DG Research. The RISIS project complements the original study to present and open the data as one of set of other ERA datasets. It is presented by NIFU (Norway) with support from IDEA Consult.

Basic characteristics

The Mobility Survey of the Higher Education Sector (MORE) survey is a study of researcher mobility patterns, the factors that shape them and the effects they have. It builds on MORE I (2009) survey, which was the first empirical study to focus on the mobility patterns of European researchers and their career paths. It was followed up in 2012 by the MORE2 study in order to support further evidence-based policy development on the research profession at European and national level. MORE2 targeted researchers working in different fields and career stages at higher education institutions (universities and other higher education institutions) in the EU27 member states, associated countries (Iceland, Norway, Switzerland) and candidate countries (Croatia, Turkey, the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia). In total, 33 countries were included in the MORE2 study.

The group of EU27 member states consists of Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, and United Kingdom.

The data and analysis methodology employed

The population-frame for the MORE2 study was primarily estimated on the basis of Eurostat headcounts of researcher-populations and of universities across Europe. MORE2 employed a two stage stratified random sampling strategy based on the population figures in Eurostat, supplemented by other sources including ETER. HEI researchers in EU27+6 were selected based on the FRASCATI manual definition. MORE2 sampled nearly 50,000 researchers in roughly 2,500 clusters. The clusters consist of the individual departments of EU27+6 HEIs. The online survey was launched by email and telephone in May 2012 and closed at the end of July 2012. After cleaning, 10,547 valid responses were yielded, which constitute the total number of researchers in the sample.

Information on the database system

The MORE2 questionnaire includes 9 types of information. Here is an overview.

1. Socio-demographics
2. Education
3. PhD and doctoral training
4. Current employment and working conditions (including contract, status, satisfaction, inter- and trans-disciplinary mobility)
5. Academic mobility and career paths (including PhD, including past and current mobility, including motivations, barriers and effects of mobility)
a. PhD mobility
b. Further career mobility
c. <3 month mobility
d. Non-mobility
e. Virtual mobility
6. Collaboration / Virtual mobility
7. Intersectoral mobility

8. Awareness of EU policy

9. Comparison research environments (EU – non-EU; EU countries)

Four distinct career stages

In the MORE2 data, the researchers are grouped into four distinct career stages¹². The variable “q13careerstage” gives information about these stages. The four career stages are:

- R1 (first stage researcher: doctoral candidate stage or equivalent, without having undertaken a doctorate),
- R2 (recognized researcher: PhD holder or equivalent who is not yet fully independent; post-doctoral stage),
- R3 (established researcher: researcher who has developed a level of independence; research specialist or manager, senior lecturer, senior scientist), and
- R4 (leading researcher: researcher leading his/her research area or field; professor stage).

The MORE2 questionnaire

The MORE2 questionnaire consists of 97 questions. A large number of questions are related to the researchers' careers, working conditions and mobility of researchers. The questions are grouped into several themes:¹³

- Background (q2 to q7)
- Education and training (q8 to q11)
- Current employment as a researcher, including PhD (q12 to q29)
- About your PhD training and mobility experience (q30 to q46)
- Your geographical mobility experience as a researcher (q47 to q62)
- Non-mobility (q63 to q65)
- About collaboration with other researchers (q66 to q67)
- Involvement with non-university sector (q68 to q81)
- Other topics (q82 to q87)
- Choice of job attributes – early stage researcher (q88 to q91)
- Choice of job attributes – later stage researcher (q92 to q97)

In the MORE2 questionnaire, there are three main questions related to mobility: long-term international mobility experience (q47), short-term international mobility experience (q61), and intersectoral mobility (q68). The three main questions related to mobility are only answered by the R2-R4 groups.

The non-response follow-up survey

Two types of non-response surveys were organized for the MORE2 study:

- During the first CATI interviews, a short telephone survey was conducted in case of an explicit refusal to participate to the MORE2 survey. Each time the CATI team received an explicit refusal, the researchers were asked if they had been long term mobile (q47) and/or intersectoral mobile (q68).
- A short web based survey focusing on CATI non-respondents was implemented after the initial data collection process. Researchers were asked if they had long-term mobile (q47), short-term mobile (q61) and/or intersectoral mobile (q68).

¹² Based on

http://ec.europa.eu/euraxess/pdf/research_policies/Towards_a_European_Framework_for_Research_Careers_final.pdf

¹³ The first question (q1) is used to exclude persons that do not considered themselves as researchers from the MORE2 survey.

The non-response survey had as its goal to come up with coefficients to align the shares of in-sample responses with the ones of the population, taking into account non-response bias. These coefficients have been incorporated in the sample weights and have led to adjusted, non-response bias-robust sampling weights. These are included in the MORE2 data under the main names calwq47, calwq61 and calwq68.

The structure of the MORE2 survey

1. Survey Design: two stage stratified random sampling strategy
 - a. Strata: the sample is stratified by country and by field of science. There are 99 strata (33 countries x 3 broad Fields of Science).
 - i. Country strata 1: 27 + 6 countries
 - ii. FOS strata 2: 3 field of science
 - b. Cluster: "Department A of University B in Field of Science C in Country D".
 - c. PSU: a faculty of a given university in field of science x in country y. The PSU depends on the size of the university/departments.
2. Population and response. Distinguish between the following levels:
 - ⇒ Population (n=1,388,000), n=1,389,407 (Eurostat figure 2009)
 - ⇒ Sample (n=49,056)
 - ⇒ Response rate: 21.5%
 - Valid responses (n=10,547)
 - Unit non-response (n=38,517)
 - Gross sample (valid responses + unit non-response) (n=49,064¹⁴): See the Excel file more2_gross_sample
 - ⇒ Item-response for R2-R4 researchers (q41, q61 & q68) (n=8,357)
 - The R1 researchers (n=2,190) did not receive the questions concerning mobility (q47, q61 & q68).
3. Calculation of survey weight
 - a. Design weights: adjust for probability to be included in the sample (inclusion probability):
 - i. Probability that Department A of University B is selected in the strata
 - ii. Probability that researcher from Department A of University B is selected in the strata
 - b. Response rate per stratum:
 - i. See the Excel file more2_sample_distribution.
4. Accounting for response probability and non-response
 - a. Unit non-response: the probability that questionnaire is not responded to by the sampled researcher appears to be non-random.
 - i. Dimension and distribution of unit non-response:
 - ii. Steps to deal with selective non-response:
 1. Non-Response study
 2. Calibration: The editing for non-responses is meant to decrease a potential bias in the answering patterns by calibrating the given responses of all researchers to a proportion that corrects for this potential bias. In order to account for this potential bias one needs to apply the calibrated weights in the MORE2 data.
 - b. Item non-response (probability that specific question is not answered by sampled researcher).

¹⁴ The gross sample number of 49,064 exceeds the sample number of 49,056 by eight units. This is due to eight units being excluded from the gross sample during additional (telephone) contacts as doubles, but not being registered as such in the system. Therefore we cannot ex post identify those eight units and they are still included in the gross sample.

- i. Selective non-response: subgroups are correlated with target variables (q47, q61 & q68 mobility questions). Three factors (youngest quintile, part-time, junior positions) account for most of the non-response. This is entirely due to routing in the survey, since it was always the intention that certain questions were only asked to a subgroup of researchers.
 - ii. Partial responses: Among the returned questionnaires, 757 were partially filled and they have been initially excluded from the sample.
5. The use of weights: The weight “weihc” is applied to the following questions: q1 to q46, q63 to q67, and q82 to q87. Concerning the calibrating: If one uses q47, then one needs to apply the weight “calwq47hc”. If one uses q61, then one needs to apply the weight “calwq61hc”. If one uses q68, then one needs to apply the weight “calwq68hc”. All questions that follow up on q47 (q48 to q59), q61 (q62) and q68 (q69 to q81) do not need to include a calibration adjustment when the indicators that we are calculating are expressed as shares or percentages. However, when the indicator is an absolute number, it is necessary to apply the calibration adjustment.
6. The svyset command: If one uses the weight “weihc”, the svyset command is: svyset university [pweight=weihc], fpc(FPC) strata(strata) || _n. If one uses the weight “calwq47hc”, the svyset command is: svyset university [pweight=calwq47hc], fpc(FPC) strata(strata) || _n. If one uses the weight “calwq61hc”, the svyset command is: svyset university [pweight=calwq61hc], fpc(FPC) strata(strata) || _n. If one uses the weight “calwq68hc”, the svyset command is: svyset university [pweight=calwq68hc], fpc(FPC) strata(strata) || _n.
7. Singleton: When using the svyset command one may receive the following note: “Missing test statistics because of stratum with single sampling unit”. This concerns subgroups of researchers with only one observation included.

Compatibility with the MORE1 HEI survey

The compatibility of MORE1 and MORE2 HEI surveys is limited due to methodological changes in the definitions of mobility and in the survey strategy. We would therefore not recommend to use the results as ‘time series’ data, but rather as different and separate datasets.

The most important differences are listed in the following table:

	MORE1	MORE2
Definition of mobility	Reference country is country of previous education, where education includes PhD.	Reference country is country of highest educational attainment, excluding PhD. Expanded definition in terms of contract types (e.g. to include doctoral candidates under scholarship or stipends).
Sampling strategy	Aimed at representativity at EU level.	Aimed at representativity at country level.
Questionnaire	Singular questions to provide direct answers to the research questions.	Curriculum-approach where the researcher is asked to provide raw data on each education and career step. The data are consequently edited and

		analyzed by the study to provide answers to the research questions.
Analysis	No information on current research career.	Strongly based on information of current research career.

Report on the content and technical structure of the **Nano S&T Dynamics** Infrastructure

Université Paris-Est Marne-la-Vallée

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and innovation policy studies"

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Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of the Nano S&T dynamics database (Task 6 of WP6)

Foreword

The report presents the database dealing with nano science and technology dynamics (Nano DB) that will be opened as part of the RISIS infrastructure. The Nano DB is an original database combining data on publications and patents.

The data is retrieved from the Web Of Science (scientific publications) and from Patstat (patents) through an original dynamic query developed by IFRIS. It gathers 1 182 344 publications and 735 834 priority patents between 1991 and 2010. Three enrichments have been produced dealing with affiliations (type of organisation and harmonisation of institution's names); geolocalisation of all addresses of authors and inventors; geographical aggregation (clusters).

In order to provide comprehensive information on the content and technical structure of the Nano DB this report follows the common structure adopted for RISIS reports: basic characteristics, information on substantive content, legal issues, technical structure, and further developments preparing the opening of the Nano DB.

A specific appendix presents the methodology developed for the dynamic query.

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Report on the content and technical structure of the *Nano S&T dynamics* dataset (Task 1 of WP6)

1 Basic characteristics

a) Name and short description of the infrastructure

The dataset focuses on nano science and technology, considered by many analysts of science dynamics as the new leading science of the time (Bonaccorsi, 2008). The dataset, developed by IFRIS, gathers scientific publications (1991-2010) and patents filed between 1991 and 2009. This represents 1182344 publications (out of which 979517 articles) and 2682429 patent applications (out of which 735834 priority patent applications, i.e. 5% of total world production over the period).

The dataset is organised around 3 major dimensions:

- Organisational with the affiliations of authors and patent grantees
- Geographical dealing with authors, grantees and inventors based on addresses (countries, cities and clusters)
- Thematic based on the subject categories of the WoS, and on technological specialisations of patents.

b) Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The focus of the dataset is to develop all the approaches, methods and techniques to identify, characterise and analyse the dynamics of emerging and fast growing fields of knowledge. This is applied on nano science and technology as the new “dominant science” (understanding matter and phenomena at the nano scale). It is warranted by numerous authors as part of the ‘converging sciences’ and as the new ‘general purpose technology’ of the time. It is in most countries a strong component of research and innovation policies, from the regional to the international level (in particular at European level).

One key methodological stake is that the perimeter of data collected needs to evolve periodically as the “domain” progressively structures itself. This has driven the producers, after having developed a first ‘static’ query (see Mogoutov and Kahane 2007) to develop a new dynamic query, enabling to capture both the stabilised part of the field and, year after year, to adapt to the evolutions of the scientific and technical vocabulary produced. Its objective is to cover both the central established core and its developments, and the on-going explorations (many of which will be short lived but are essential to understand on-going dynamics).

c) Legal name of operating organization

UPEM - IFRIS

d) Database location and type of access

The Nano database is hosted on a MySQL server at IFRIS and is accessible on site at IFRIS at Marne-la-Vallée (France).

2 Information on substantive content of the *Nano S&T dynamics dataset*

The following section describes the two units of analysis – patents and publications – and explains the selection process through which the dataset is built (i.e. the lexical query developed which is fully presented in appendix 1). It will then enter the three harmonisation processes entered into: geographical, institutional and thematic. These harmonisation processes are critical since they enable to link both units (patents and publications) at the geographical, institutional and thematic level to describe overall dynamics.

2.1 Definition and description of observations

a) Units and definition of observations

Patents

The database gives information related to priority patent applications anywhere in the world to protect an invention. The priority date is used to determine the novelty of the invention (it is an important aspect in patent procedures). For statistical purpose, the priority date is the closest date to the date of invention.

Scientific publications

The database gathers publications that correspond to the domain of nano sciences and technologies in journals that are indexed in the web of science and give access to titles, abstracts and author keywords. Their selection is linked to the query developed see below and annex.

b) Number of observations

The dataset contains 1182344 publications (with 2179065 addresses, i.e. on average 1.85 addresses per publication, the focus being on organisations and places not on individual authors). For patents the dataset includes 2682429 patents (with 8832556 inventors). Our analyses focus on priority patents: 735834 over the period with 1834604 inventor addresses (i.e. 2.5 inventor addresses per priority patent).

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

a) Where are the data retrieved from

Patents

We used the PATSTAT-IFRIS database, built on PATSTAT version October 2009 provided by EPO (see next section for detailed description on data gathered).

Scientific publications

Data is retrieved from the Web of Science ¹ and, within it, the following sources have been interrogated:

- Science Citation Index Expanded™ (SCI™ Expanded): Science Citation Index Expanded is a multidisciplinary index to the journal literature of the sciences. It fully indexes over 6,650 major journals across 150 scientific disciplines and includes all cited references captured from indexed articles.
- Social Sciences Citation Index® (SSCI®): The Social Sciences Citation Index is a multidisciplinary index to the journal literature of the social sciences. It fully indexes over 1,950 journals across 50 social sciences disciplines. It also indexes individually selected, relevant items from over 3,300 of the world's leading scientific and technical journals.
- Arts & Humanities Citation Index® (A&HCI®): Arts & Humanities Citation Index is a multidisciplinary index to the journal literature of the arts and humanities. It fully covers 1,160 of the world's leading arts and humanities journals. It also indexes individually selected, relevant items from over 6,800 major science and social science journals.
- Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Science (CPCI-S) This citation index covers conference literature in all scientific and technical fields.
- Conference Proceedings Citation Index - Social Sciences & Humanities (CPCI-SSH): This citation index covers conference literature in all fields of social sciences, arts, and humanities.
- Index Chemicus® (IC®): Index Chemicus contains the structures and critical supporting data for novel organic compounds reported in leading international journals. Many records show the reaction flow from starting material to final product. Index Chemicus is a vital source of new information on biologically active compounds and natural products.

¹ http://images.webofknowledge.com/WOK46/help/WOK/h_database.html

b) How are the data processed in terms of data cleaning (e.g. harmonisation of organization names, etc.)

The query developed

Scientific publications

Most queries start with a seed made of a few keywords that are core to the domain under study – here it is linked like other queries to the prefix ‘nano’ (with classical exceptions like nanoliter). This seed has generated 517050 publications. Semantic analyses of keywords are made on this seed identifying their internal specificity (on the core dataset) and then checked about their external specificity (on the whole WoS). Articles are then extracted on the basis of the vocabulary selected. This is done on the whole period covered (1991-2010) giving what we call the ‘static’ extension. And this is done year after year giving annual vocabularies to download the ‘dynamic’ part of the dataset. Appendix 1 develops in detail this methodology and the different steps to make it operational and robust. As shown in the table the nanostring represents 44% of the dataset while each extension (static and dynamic) represents 28%. Overtime the share of the nanostring increases from 14% in 1991 to 50% in 2006. Since it has remained between 50 and 55%. Overall the growth rate until 2008 is 14% but goes down below 10% over the last two years.

Layer	Number of publications
Nanostring	517 050
Static	332 739
Dynamic	332 555
Total	1 182 344

Fig & tab 1. Scientific publications: overview

Fig & tab 2. Growth of scientific publications

Patents

The present version of the dataset did not develop a new approach but used the vocabulary defined for publication for both static and dynamic extensions. A recent test was made on one year (2005) comparing this approach with the reproduction of the methodology applied for publications on patents. It highlighted a very different core vocabulary but when we compared the 2 sets of patents selected there was over 85% of overlap. Thus, though this is not optimal, the present approach gives a quite fair account of the dynamics in technology.

Note: We plan in the next version of the dataset (end of 2015) to apply the full methodology also for patents.

The nano patent dataset is made only of priority patents. Three aspects need to be noted:

- There is a long delay between the application and the publication by national patent offices of that application (this is linked to the handling of patents by patent offices ; but there are also in some offices like the US patent office, possibilities for firms to ask for a longer delay for publication). This explains why, even if we cover up to the end of 2009, we have only probably half the patents for 2008 and nearly nothing for 2009.
- A specific dimension of patents lie in the existence of interconnected patents through 'families' built upon the connection made by grantees between the new patent and existing patents (for a more in depth definition see the information presented on Patstat in the other report produced by IFRIS on the dataset on large firms, CIB). Families are important since they represent a significant share of the total patents considered: 49% overall, but this percentage goes down regularly: from 71% in 1991 to 36% in 2006-07.
- The pattern of growth is very different compared to the growth of scientific publications. Overall we have a fast growth from 1991 (around 15000 patents) to 2000 (with just over 60000 patents). Then the annual number has rather decreased than increased moving to around 55000 since 2003.

<i>Layer</i>	<i>Numer of priority applications</i>	<i>Total of applications</i>
Nanostring	44 955	96 025
Static	148 267	467 872
Dynamic	181 635	842 132
<i>Total</i>	374 857	1 406 029
FamInpadoc	360 977	2 682 429

Fig & tab 3. *Patents: overview*

Fig & tab 4. *Growth of patents*

Harmonising and categorising institutions

Here we face an interesting paradox. While the information available has witnessed an explosive growth, we still remain very limited in our ability to follow the involvement of organisations whether public and private. We have shown with the CIB dataset (see its presentation report) how difficult it was to rebuild the large firms from the hundreds of legal names under which they patent, either because writing differs from one patent to another, because firms change names and even more because many of their subsidiaries patent. Similar issues are raised for public institutions often associated with multiple spelling, even after the standardisation efforts made by databases (in particular publications and the differences between legal institutions and their schools, departments, institutes and research groups).

The nano database capitalises years of work on multiple projects. They are grouped under two complementary aspects:

- Automatic treatments: we mobilise recognised algorithms to compare chains of characters and when similarity is considered large enough, to associate them to a unique entity
- Construction of a reference dataset: these automatic treatments have been checked, validated and complemented manually in a number of projects, being progressively integrated in a reference dataset that is enriched project after project.

The way to characterise the institutional dimension differs widely between patents and publications. In publications it is part of the address and builds the first two or three elements of the address (with the lab, the department and/or school, the faculty and the

organisation per se). In patents we have the name of the patent filer as it appears in the patent document and the name as Patstat has standardised it.

We have used a two-step process for cleaning names: first allocation to a type, and then harmonisation of names.

Step one. In order to better understand the roles of the different types of institutions, we have built a categorisation around 5 main types: University, Government organisation, Hospital, Firm and other. Appendix 2 lists the queries developed to allocate addresses to one of these types. One immediate issue is that a given written form may belong to more than one entity. The automatic classification offers as a solution the most frequent one encountered. Manual checking has been used to validate it.

Overall it gives 75% of addresses for universities, 18% for government organisations (mostly but not exclusively public research organisations), 5% to firms, 2% for hospitals and 1% other. There are however two issues pending: one is the split between universities and PRO (especially with joint units, quite common in France but also growing in other countries in Europe), the other is the split between universities and hospitals (when being faced with university hospitals). The pragmatic choice made (until RISIS develops a more robust approach) has been to follow the choice of authors in indicating their primary affiliation.

Step two deals with the harmonisation of names. The 2 million plus addresses for publications gave nearly 100000 different written forms (see table below). We used then two complementary treatments: (a) automatic: we measured the distance between written forms using the Levenshtein distance weighted by a Jaccard distance (see Cohen, Ravikumar & Fienberg 2003 for a comparison between similarity measures). This has enabled to reduce by 27% the number of different forms. (b) We have compared with our reference database complemented by a manual check: the latter has enabled another reduction of 32%, leaving us with some 40000 different 'organisations'.

<i>Nano publications 1991 - 2010</i>		<i>%</i>
2 179 065 addresses		
Number of different writing forms	97 194	
1 - Harmonisation based on similarity measures	26 242	27%
2 - Manual harmonisation of written forms	31 187	32%
Total number of harmonised written forms	39 765	41%

Fig & tab 5. *Harmonisation of the name of institutions*

Data geolocalisation

The geolocalisation of data from publications and patents has been done in 3 steps

- Pre-processing: cleaning (getting rid of commas, hyphens and the like) and harmonizing (using approaches described before).
- Patterns extraction: extraction and harmonization of geographical information (cities, postal codes...).
- Geolocalisation: matching with geo-databases or toponymy recognition.

For the last two steps we have used two methods in sequence. First we have compared the geographical data extracted to those of the database GeoName². For bringing addresses together, we have identified recurrent patterns linked to the ways addresses are written in different nations (e.g. the position of names of cities, the number of characters of postal codes) and their translation in regular formats. We have operated a matching per country using three levels: the postal code, the city and the region. We have obtained geographical coordinates (latitude, longitude) and enriched the toponyms linked to our addresses (in particular states in federal countries). All ambiguous situations have been left aside. Still it has geolocalised 91% of total addresses (in publications and patents).

For the 9% left aside, we have proposed the addresses we had to the geolocalisation webservice based (among other) on the Google engine³. This search engine offers 9 levels of accuracy (see table below): any level from 4 to 9 has been considered enough to geolocalise addresses. This has enabled to complement the coverage to nearly 99% (1.19% addresses not covered).

<i>Accuracy⁴</i>	<i>Description</i>
Value	
0	Unknown accuracy.
1	Country level accuracy.
2	Region (state, province, prefecture, etc.) level accuracy.
3	Sub-region (county, municipality, etc.) level accuracy.
4	Town (city, village) level accuracy.
5	Post code (zip code) level accuracy.
6	Street level accuracy.
7	Intersection level accuracy.
8	Address level accuracy.
9	Premise (building name, property name, shopping center, etc.) level accuracy.

Fig & tab 6. *Geolocalisation accuracy*

The table below gives the percentage of geolocalised addresses for all countries with more than 10000 addresses.

<i>Countries with more than 10 000 author's addresses</i>	<i>Harnonised country</i>	<i>Number of addresses</i>	<i>Addresses geolocalised</i>	<i>%</i>
Total for all the 166 countries		2 176 376	2 153 142	98,93%
UNITED STATES	US	471352	471322	99,99%
CHINA	CN	268630	268488	99,95%

² Geoname, <http://download.geonames.org/export/dump/>, 09/2012

³ Geobatch, www.findlatitudeandlongitude.com/batch-geocode/

⁴ Accuracy codes with the web service GeoBatch
<https://developers.google.com/maps/documentation/javascript/v2/reference?csw=1#GGeoAddressAccuracy>

JAPAN	JP	216934	215834	99,49%
GERMANY	DE	138001	137994	99,99%
FRANCE	FR	109136	109118	99,98%
SOUTH KOREA	KR	101996	85863	84,18%
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83113	83103	99,99%
ITALY	IT	73211	73203	99,99%
INDIA	IN	57754	57700	99,91%
TAIWAN	TW	56723	56723	100%
RUSSIA	RU	49725	49599	99,75%
SPAIN	ES	49060	49054	99,99%
CANADA	CA	43182	43182	100%
BRAZIL	BR	31320	31319	100%
AUSTRALIA	AU	30501	28327	92,87%
NETHERLANDS	NL	26337	26335	99,99%
POLAND	PL	24480	24479	100%
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	23737	99,99%
SINGAPORE	SG	21476	21476	100%
SWEDEN	SE	21365	21364	100%
BELGIUM	BE	17875	17870	99,97%
ISRAEL	IL	15025	15025	100%
IRAN	IR	14992	14992	100%
MEXICO	MX	14038	14038	100%
TURKEY	TR	13801	13801	100%
HONG KONG	HK	13099	13099	100%
AUSTRIA	AT	12360	12358	99,98%
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12026	12024	99,98%
FINLAND	FI	11217	11204	99,88%
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	11190	99,99%
GREECE	GR	10574	10536	99,64%
ROMANIA	RO	10474	10452	99,79%
UKRAINE	UA	10005	10001	99,96%

Fig & tab 7. *Geolocalisation of publications*

A similar level of achievement is observed for patents (see table of countries with more than 1000 addresses for inventors), once account is taken of patents without addresses. The retrieval rate is quite weak (overall 31%) even when integrating the different add-ups produced by other organisations than EPO (in particular Regpat by OECD). The holes are concentrated on 3 Asian countries (China 40%, retrieval rate near to nil), South Korea (16%, retrieval rate 2%), Taiwan (2% retrieval rate 36%) and on Russia (5%, retrieval rate 2%). For these countries, there is little to expect but waiting on new versions of Patstat by EPO (one every 6 months). What has surprised us is the high level of holes (no inventor address) for European countries: 40% of total addresses, representing 10% of world holes. There are two ways to address these problems: one is to go back to national databases and see whether a matching by patent number enables

to fill inventor addresses; the other is, in the case patents are part of a family, to develop an algorithm that enables to tap potential addresses. We are developing both and results should be integrated before opening.

Countries with more than 500 inventor's addresses	Inventor's addresses	Filled addresses	%	Geolocalised addresses	%
Total for the 126 countries	554 855	173 521	31%	172 900	98,63%
CHINA	193074	777	0%	761	97,94%
UNITED STATES	120183	115641	96%	115582	99,95%
SOUTH KOREA	80869	1306	2%	1269	97,17%
GERMANY	40809	4724	12%	4714	99,79%
RUSSIA	24470	515	2%	504	97,86%
FRANCE	21100	20482	97%	20450	99,84%
TAIWAN	18494	6672	36%	6452	96,70%
JAPAN	10426	7484	72%	7320	97,81%
CANADA	5424	2902	54%	2902	100,00%
SPAIN	5068	548	11%	547	99,82%
UKRAINE	4903	52	1%	52	100,00%
UNITED KINGDOM	4104	1288	31%	1284	99,69%
ITALY	2704	1184	44%	1179	99,58%
NETHERLANDS	2585	1635	63%	1633	99,88%
SWITZERLAND	2173	1541	71%	1538	99,81%
BELGIUM	1865	1444	77%	1438	99,58%
INDIA	1268	997	79%	996	99,90%
POLAND	1207	61	5%	61	100,00%
CZECH REPUBLIC	1077	22	2%	22	100,00%
ROMANIA	830	13	2%	13	100,00%
ARGENTINA	827	13	2%	13	100,00%
ISRAEL	818	626	77%	626	100,00%
AUSTRIA	773	218	28%	215	98,62%
PORTUGAL	693	24	3%	24	100,00%
SINGAPORE	686	485	71%	483	99,59%
HONG KONG	630	291	46%	291	100,00%
MOLDOVA	619	1	0%	1	100,00%
SWEDEN	584	442	76%	438	99,10%
BULGARIA	576	1	0%	1	100,00%
FINLAND	523	404	77%	403	99,75%

Fig & tab 8. *Geolocalisation of patents*

Clustering the scientific and technological activities

After the location (identification of toponyms), and geolocalisation (allocation of longitude and latitude coordinates), the phenomena of concentration of activities can be approached through an analysis of geographic clustering. This step aims at analyzing the

distribution of S&T activities and at measuring agglomeration effects by identifying the existing clusters. The ambition is to look at clustering effects as they happen and not by considering administrative borders that widely differ between countries.

The simplest solution is to take agglomerates already constructed for other studies. This is the case in the US of metropolitan areas that are updated by the statistics office periodically. But this does not exist elsewhere. So most studies adopt administrative borders (e.g. NUTS 2 or 3 in Europe which are known not to represent any economic or social reality). This is why when studying phenomena at the world level and wanting to avoid 'political definitions' of space, studies are bound to develop clustering approaches. A simple solution to clustering is to work only on distance starting with supposed geographical central locations (in this case working at the city level). This approach supposes that we define a threshold about what a relevant central city is (in our case in our first attempt it was 1000 publications in 10 years), and defining a radius (60km reduced to 30km in some Asian countries). A measure of overlaps (say 20% of joint publications) between clusters formed this way drives to agglomerating initial clusters. We used this first technique on the prototype database with quite good results: 203 clusters worldwide agglomerating over 75% of publications.

However this methodology has a number of drawbacks: it misses fully distributed clusters; limits are defined artificially; there is no continuity in term of size of clusters while a central result was their very uneven distribution. This drove to tailor a new method that addresses these issues. We project all addresses in the geographic space and build a first partition using a density algorithm, DBScan (Ester, Kriegel & Sander, 1996), which is parametered using a minimal distance between two points (two couples of coordinates) and a minimal value for building a cluster (sum of addresses in a given point). The borders of the convex hulls are built using these points. These envelopes build the smallest geographical divisions (initial clusters).

Using the documents (publications and/or patents) as units of analysis, we apply the CHAMELEON method (Karypis, Han & Kumar, 1999). It enables to identify collaboration regimes between individuals (authors and inventors) located in given geographical spaces. We then compare nearby initial clusters (i.e. that are less than 100 km distance) two by two, using the internal and external collaboration values of the initial clusters. Two measures are calculated: relative inter-connectivity and relative closeness that enable defining thresholds for agglomerating clusters (see box 1 for their calculation).

Box 1 : defining Relative Interconnectivity and Relative Closeness

A cluster is defined by the number of nodes (with different geographical coordinates, T_i), the links between these nodes (E_i) and the value of the links is the number of collaborations between the 2 nodes connected by this link (C_i).

The relations between 2 clusters are defined by the number of links between these two clusters ($E_{(i,j)}$) and the total number of collaborations supported by these links ($C_{(i,j)}$).

Calculating the Relative Interconnectivity

RI is the ratio between the total number of collaborations between the two clusters ($C_{(i,j)}$) and the average number of internal collaborations of the two clusters.

$$RI_{(i,j)} = \frac{C_{(i,j)}}{\frac{C_i + C_j}{2}}$$

Calculating the Relative Closeness

The internal closeness (Cl_i) of a cluster (or intra-closeness) is the ratio between the total number of collaborations within that cluster (C_i) and the number of links observed within that cluster (E_i).

$$Cl_i = \frac{C_i}{E_i}$$

Similarly the absolute closeness between two clusters (or inter-cluster closeness, $Cl_{(i,j)}$) is the ratio between the total collaborations observed between the two clusters ($C_{(i,j)}$) and the number of links between these two clusters ($E_{(i,j)}$).

$$Cl_{(i,j)} = \frac{C_{(i,j)}}{E_{(i,j)}}$$

The relative closeness between 2 clusters ($RC_{(i,j)}$) is the ratio between the absolute closeness of the two clusters and the average internal closeness of the two clusters (based upon the number of nodes of the 2 clusters, $T_i + T_j$).

$$RC_{(i,j)} = \frac{Cl_{(i,j)}}{\frac{T_i}{T_i + T_j} \times Cl_i + \frac{T_j}{T_i + T_j} \times Cl_j}$$

Below is an illustration at European level of the application of this combined approach.

Fig & tab 9. Geographical aggregation of inventor addresses in Europe (patents)

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Publications</i>	<i>Patents</i>
Relative Interconnectivity	1.2	2
Relative Closeness	20	12.50
Minimal weight (addresses)	1 000	1 250
Maximum distance	20 Km	20 Km
Number of addresses analysed	2 160 748	1 523 093
Number of initial clusters (after DBScan)	411	186
Number of final clusters (after Chameleon)	383	155

Fig & tab 10. *Parameters for DBScan and Chameleon*

The tests made show that the method is robust. It addresses the three issues raised by the previous method. We are now in the process of defining a method for labeling them. These developments will be finalised by the end of 2014.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

a) Description of all variables and/or indicators that are given for the main units of observation (e.g. number of publications, number of patents, etc.)

Patents

<i>Main units of observation</i>	<i>Examples of variables</i>
Applicant's name	Number of priority patents for applicants
Inventor's name	Number of priority patents for inventors
Subfield, field and domain based on IPC classes	Number of priority patents per subfields
Filing year	Number of priority patents per year
Titles	Vocabulary and frequency of keywords
Abstract	Vocabulary and keyword frequency
INPADOC Family	Number of priority patents per family inpadoc
Geolocalisation of inventor addresses	Number of priority patents per location, Number of priority patents shared by locations
Geolocalisation of applicant addresses	Number of priority patents per location, Number of priority patents shared by locations
Cluster of inventor addresses	Number of priority patents per cluster, Number of priority patents shared by clusters
Cluster of applicant addresses	Number of priority patents per cluster, Number of priority patents shared by clusters

Fig & tab 11. *Main units of observation for nano patents*

Scientific publications

<i>Main units of observation</i>	<i>Examples of variables</i>
Author Full Name	Number of collaborations
Document Title	Vocabulary and keyword frequency
Author Keywords	Keyword frequency
Keywords Plus®	Keyword frequency
Abstract	Vocabulary and keyword frequency
Cited References	Cited-citing counting
Web of Science Times Cited Count	Sum of Times Cited for a specific entity
Year Published	Number of publications per year
Web of Science Category	Number of publications per scientific Category
Subject Area	Number of publications per scientific Category
Harmonized institution	Number of publications for an institution, Number of collaborations for an institution
Type of institution	Number of publications for a type of institution, Number of publications for a type of institutions per countries
Geolocalisation	Number of publications for a location, Number of collaborations for a location
Cluster	Number of publications for a cluster, Number of collaborations between clusters

Fig & tab 12. *Main units of observation for nano publications*

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

For patents tables are calculated using priority patents in table t1s 201 (unless other specifications) for the three layers: NanoString, Static and Dynamic. All the calculations are made from 1991 to 2009 for the patents, and 1991 to 2010 for the publications.

a) Information on the temporal coverage used

Patents

<i>Filing Year</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>1991</i>	<i>1992</i>	<i>1993</i>	<i>1994</i>	<i>1995</i>	<i>1996</i>	<i>1997</i>	<i>1998</i>	<i>1999</i>
NanoString	44955	279	269	347	386	506	497	554	723	972
Static	148267	3970	4082	4945	4992	5656	5756	6611	8451	9452
Dynamic	181635	16	3939	5087	5039	5973	6145	7926	8875	9780
Total	374857	4265	8290	10379	10417	12135	12398	15091	18049	20204

<i>Year</i>	<i>2000</i>	<i>2001</i>	<i>2002</i>	<i>2003</i>	<i>2004</i>	<i>2005</i>	<i>2006</i>	<i>2007</i>	<i>2008</i>	<i>2009</i>
NanoString	1481	3245	3421	4551	5130	6075	6276	6672	3496	75
Static	9632	10552	10800	11421	10995	11452	12706	12040	4583	171
Dynamic	10468	20985	13372	14445	12223	16654	18204	15957	6369	178
Total	21581	34782	27593	30417	28348	34181	37186	34669	14448	424

Fig & tab 13. *Number of priority patents per year and query*

Scientific publications

<i>Year</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>1991</i>	<i>1992</i>	<i>1993</i>	<i>1994</i>	<i>1995</i>	<i>1996</i>	<i>1997</i>	<i>1998</i>	<i>1999</i>	<i>2000</i>
NanoString	53758	1336	1711	2312	3074	4199	5207	6528	7619	9302	12470
Static	116006	7491	8220	9116	10268	10748	11573	13240	13802	14480	17068
Dynamic	43669	980	1450	2193	3132	3520	4578	5515	6275	7191	8835
Total	213433	9807	11381	13621	16474	18467	21358	25283	27696	30973	38373

<i>Year</i>	<i>2001</i>	<i>2002</i>	<i>2003</i>	<i>2004</i>	<i>2005</i>	<i>2006</i>	<i>2007</i>	<i>2008</i>	<i>2009</i>	<i>2010</i>
NanoString	15981	19945	26213	33168	40356	48091	58513	67134	73466	80425
Static	17542	18145	19105	20395	21054	22803	24630	24804	23939	24316
Dynamic	11285	15936	21325	26433	22012	25630	30323	39771	47847	48324
Total	44808	54026	66643	79996	83422	96524	113466	131709	145252	153065

Fig & tab 14. *Number of scientific publications per year and query*

b) Geographic coverage

Patents

<i>Continent</i>	<i>Number of inventor's addresses</i>
Total of filled addresses	554 855
Africa	142
Asia	307056
Europe	119597
Latin America and the Caribbean	2063
Northern America	125607
Oceania	390

Fig & tab 15. *Number of inventor's addresses per continent*

<i>Region</i>	<i>Number of inventor's addresses</i>
Total of filled addresses	554 855
Australia and New Zealand	384
Central America	425
Eastern Africa	18
Eastern Asia	303498
Eastern Europe	34780
Middle Africa	6
Northern Africa	55
Northern America	125607
Northern Europe	6447
Polynesia	6
South America	1435
South-central Asia	1459
South-eastern Asia	930
Southern Africa	48
Southern Europe	8903
the Caribbean	203
Western Africa	15
Western Asia	1169
Western Europe	69467

Fig & tab 16. *Number of inventor's addresses per sub-continent*

<i>Country with more than 500 inventor's addresses</i>	<i>Country harmonized</i>	<i>Inventor's addresses</i>	<i>With filled addresses</i>	<i>Geolocalized addresses</i>	<i>%</i>
Total for the 126 countries		554 855	173 521	172 900	98,63%
CHINA	CN	193074	777	761	97,94 %
UNITED STATES	US	120183	115641	115582	99,95 %
SOUTH KOREA	KR	80869	1306	1269	97,17 %
GERMANY	DE	40809	4724	4714	99,79 %
RUSSIA	RU	24470	515	504	97,86 %
FRANCE	FR	21100	20482	20450	99,84 %
TAIWAN	TW	18494	6672	6452	96,7 %
JAPAN	JP	10426	7484	7320	97,81 %
CANADA	CA	5424	2902	2902	100 %
SPAIN	ES	5068	548	547	99,82 %
UKRAINE	UA	4903	52	52	100 %
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	4104	1288	1284	99,69 %
ITALY	IT	2704	1184	1179	99,58 %
NETHERLANDS	NL	2585	1635	1633	99,88 %
SWITZERLAND	CH	2173	1541	1538	99,81 %

BELGIUM	BE	1865	1444	1438	99,58 %
INDIA	IN	1268	997	996	99,9 %
POLAND	PL	1207	61	61	100 %
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	1077	22	22	100 %
ROMANIA	RO	830	13	13	100 %
ARGENTINA	AR	827	13	13	100 %
ISRAEL	IL	818	626	626	100 %
AUSTRIA	AT	773	218	215	98,62 %
PORTUGAL	PT	693	24	24	100 %
SINGAPORE	SG	686	485	483	99,59 %
HONG KONG	HK	630	291	291	100 %
MOLDOVA	MD	619	1	1	100 %
SWEDEN	SE	584	442	438	99,1 %
BULGARIA	BG	576	1	1	100 %
FINLAND	FI	523	404	403	99,75 %

Fig & tab 17. *Number of inventor's addresses per country*

ISO 3166⁵ is a standard developed for the current names of countries, dependencies, and other areas of particular geopolitical interest, on the basis of lists of country names obtained from the United Nations and maintained by the ISO 3166 Maintenance Agency established by the ISO Council, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). The international two letter country code (ISO alpha-2) is used as Harmonized country code.

Scientific publications

<i>Continent</i>	<i>Number of addresses</i>
Total	2 176 376
Africa	16836
Asia	801142
Europe	748763
Latin America and the Caribbean	60886
Northern America	514534
Oceania	34215

Fig & tab 18. *Number of author's addresses per continent*

<i>Region</i>	<i>Number of addresses</i>
Total	2 176 376
Australia and New Zealand	34195
Central America	14242

⁵ ISO 3166 alpha 2, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ISO_3166-1_alpha-2

Eastern Africa	620
Eastern Asia	657412
Eastern Europe	126873
Melanesia	19
Micronesia	1
Middle Africa	223
Northern Africa	10745
Northern America	514534
Northern Europe	141267
South America	45698
South-central Asia	76208
South-eastern Asia	33520
Southern Africa	4347
Southern Europe	152825
the Caribbean	946
Western Africa	901
Western Asia	34002
Western Europe	327798

Fig & tab 19. Number of author's addresses per sub-continent

<i>Main countries with more than 10 000 addresses</i>	<i>Country harmonized</i>	<i>Number of addresses</i>	<i>Addresses geolocalized</i>	<i>%</i>
Total for all the 166 countries		2 176 376	2 153 142	97%
AUSTRIA	AT	12360	12358	99,98 %
AUSTRALIA	AU	30501	28327	92,87 %
BELGIUM	BE	17875	17870	99,97 %
BRAZIL	BR	31320	31319	100 %
CANADA	CA	43182	43182	100 %
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	23737	99,99 %
CHINA	CN	268630	268488	99,95 %
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12026	12024	99,98 %
GERMANY	DE	138001	137994	99,99 %
SPAIN	ES	49060	49054	99,99 %
FINLAND	FI	11217	11204	99,88 %
FRANCE	FR	109136	109118	99,98 %
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83113	83103	99,99 %
GREECE	GR	10574	10536	99,64 %
HONG KONG	HK	13099	13099	100 %
ISRAEL	IL	15025	15025	100 %
INDIA	IN	57754	57700	99,91 %
IRAN	IR	14992	14992	100 %
ITALY	IT	73211	73203	99,99 %

JAPAN	JP	216934	215834	99,49 %
SOUTH KOREA	KR	101996	85863	84,18 %
MEXICO	MX	14038	14038	100 %
NETHERLANDS	NL	26337	26335	99,99 %
POLAND	PL	24480	24479	100 %
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	11190	99,99 %
ROMANIA	RO	10474	10452	99,79 %
RUSSIA	RU	49725	49599	99,75 %
SWEDEN	SE	21365	21364	100 %
SINGAPORE	SG	21476	21476	100 %
TURKEY	TR	13801	13801	100 %
TAIWAN	TW	56723	56723	100 %
UKRAINE	UA	10005	10001	99,96 %
UNITED STATES	US	471352	471322	99,99 %

Fig & tab 20. Number of author's addresses per country

c) Technological fields and scientific domains

Patents

Patents are classified according technology categories. The categories used are those build by WIPO (see PATSTAT-IFRIS report for detailed information): 5 domains, 35 fields and 374 subfields.

The distributions of priority patent domains and fields and subfields are shown below (Note: a patent can be affected to several domains, fields and sub-fields)

Domain code	Domain name	Number of priority applications
Total		951 807
TD01	Electrical engineering	193947
TD02	Instruments	221638
TD03	Chemistry	379890
TD04	Mechanical engineering	115026
TD05	Other fields	41306

Fig & tab 21. Number of priority patents per domain

Field code	Field name	Number of priority applications
Total		951 807
TF01	Electrical machinery, apparatus, energy	61499

TF02	Audio-visual technology	54660
TF03	Telecommunications	6365
TF04	Digital communication	1492
TF05	Basic communication processes	5992
TF06	Computer technology	9661
TF07	IT methods for management	635
TF08	Semiconductors	53643
TF09	Optics	160585
TF10	Measurement	31358
TF11	Analysis of biological materials	5076
TF12	Control	4874
TF13	Medical technology	19745
TF14	Organic fine chemistry	40618
TF15	Biotechnology	10858
TF16	Pharmaceuticals	34998
TF17	Macromolecular chemistry, polymers	41455
TF18	Food chemistry	12597
TF19	Basic materials chemistry	55023
TF20	Materials, metallurgy	67019
TF21	Surface technology, coating	48028
TF22	Micro-structural and nano- technology	6503
TF23	Chemical engineering	39840
TF24	Environmental technology	22951
TF25	Handling	13987
TF26	Machine tools	13066
TF27	Engines, pumps, turbines	8932
TF28	Textile and paper machines	19437
TF29	Other special machines	27249
TF30	Thermal processes and apparatus	9338
TF31	Mechanical elements	9735
TF32	Transport	13282
TF33	Furniture, games	13304
TF34	Other consumer goods	14208
TF35	Civil engineering	13794

Fig & tab 22. *Number of priority patents per field*

<i>Main subfields with more than 5 000 patents</i>		<i>Number of priority applications</i>
Total for all the 374 subfields		951 807
T01F01	Lighting	8369
T01F02	Displaying Advertising	11932
T01F05	Basic Electronic Circuitry	5992

T01F06	Computing	8204
T01F08	Semiconductor Devices	53643
T01F09	Optical Elements Systems	140685
T01F11	Material Analysis by Chem Phys Properties	5076
T01F14	Cosmetic Preparations	8710
T01F16	Medical Preparations	23824
T01F20	Casting and Powder Metallurgy	6829
T01F32	Vehicles	8095
T01F33	Furniture and Domestic Equipment	8887
T02F02	Arrangements for Control	20076
T02F16	Therapeutic Activity of Chemical Compounds	11174
T02F20	Inorganic Chemistry	24741
T02F22	Nano-Technology	5484
T02F26	Mechanical Metal-Working	6131
T02F31	Engineering Elts or Units	8494
T03F02	Information Storage Based Record Carrier	11622
T03F17	Macromol with C-To-C Unsaturated Bonds	9840
T03F21	Layered Products	7346
T04F14	Acyclic or Carbocyclic Compounds	16323
T04F17	Macromol Withouth C-To-C Unsaturated Bonds	6573
T04F20	Refractories	14233
T04F21	Coating Metallic Material	14681
T04F25	Containers for Storage of Articles	7335
T05F09	Photomechanics of Surfaces	6810
T05F14	Heterocyclic Compounds	6814
T05F20	Metallurgy of Iron	5183
T06F17	Inorg or Non-Macromolr Organ Subst	11089
T06F20	Metallurgy	11963
T06F21	Crystal Growth	18078
T07F01	Discharge Lamps	15385
T07F17	Compositions of Macromolecular Compounds	13207
T07F19	Paints and Inks	9817
T07F28	Threads or Fibers	5520
T08F09	Devices Using Stimulated Emission	5919
T08F13	Methods for Sterilising	5129
T09F01	Batteries and Related	13922
T10F18	Other Foods	5051
T10F24	Solid Waste and Contaminated Soils	6208
T11F10	Chemical Physical Analyses	15075
T12F01	Boards for the Distribution of Electricity	5031
T12F19	Materials for Miscellaneous Applications	13180
T13F24	Absorbing Noise from Roads	10838
T14F23	Chem or Phys Lab Apparatus	24972

T17F29	Working of Plastics	9500
T20F29	Processes of Compounding	5748

Fig & tab 23. Number of priority patents per sub-field

Scientific publications

In a first stage we use the ISI-WoS subject classifications to characterise domains and subject areas. Note: a publication has several subject categories

<i>Main subject categories with more than 10 000 publications</i>	<i>Number of publications</i>
Total for all the 274 subject categories	4 032 893
Physics	389630
Materials Science	351481
Chemistry	314217
Materials Science, Multidisciplinary	280878
Physics, Applied	226973
Chemistry, Physical	166803
Engineering	154761
Physics, Condensed Matter	148371
Optics	121152
Chemistry, Multidisciplinary	117392
Science & Technology - Other Topics	104777
Polymer Science	104146
Nanoscience & Nanotechnology	93476
Metallurgy & Metallurgical Engineering	92796
Electrochemistry	75890
Engineering, Electrical & Electronic	73766
Biochemistry & Molecular Biology	61399
Instruments & Instrumentation	46420
Physics, Multidisciplinary	45248
Materials Science, Coatings & Films	40574
Pharmacology & Pharmacy	37183
Engineering, Chemical	36916
Crystallography	31944
Chemistry, Analytical	31917
Materials Science, Ceramics	31142
Energy & Fuels	31032
Physics, Atomic, Molecular & Chemical	28175
Biophysics	26128
Biotechnology & Applied Microbiology	24628
Nuclear Science & Technology	21592
Cell Biology	21284
Mechanics	20998

Environmental Sciences & Ecology	20033
Spectroscopy	19010
Chemistry, Applied	17983
Environmental Sciences	17757
Chemistry, Inorganic & Nuclear	17090
Engineering, Mechanical	15890
Microscopy	14946
Geochemistry & Geophysics	14548
Engineering, Biomedical	13470
Microbiology	12594
Mineralogy	11726
Chemistry, Organic	11400
Computer Science	11386
Multidisciplinary Sciences	11301
Radiology, Nuclear Medicine & Medical Imaging	11252
Materials Science, Biomaterials	10860
Water Resources	10858
Biochemical Research Methods	10721
Materials Science, Composites	10719
Engineering, Environmental	10514
Astronomy & Astrophysics	10498

Fig & tab 24. *Number of publications per subject categories*

d) Coverage for institutions

Patents

Work in progress

Scientific publications

Table 25 presents the partition of addresses in a country along the type of institution. Overall University addresses represent 75% of the total, Government labs 18%, firms 5% and hospital and others 2% together. The 5 major institutions per country are listed in table 26 (see appendix 3).

Country name	Country code harmonized	Number of addresses for the countries	firm	gvt	hosp	other	univ
Total of addresses		19 83 667	93 971	3 59 617	37 357	13 312	1 479 390
ARGENTINA	AR	7719	43	2720	152	51	4753
AUSTRALIA	AU	30486	751	3794	980	252	24709
AUSTRIA	AT	12342	701	1107	260	420	9854
BELGIUM	BE	17858	904	451	473	191	15839

BRAZIL	BR	31275	309	2755	445	57	27709
CANADA	CA	43152	2179	4594	1661	281	34436
CHINA	CN	281531	3869	57298	1098	66	219199
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12110	313	5726	192	29	5850
DENMARK	DK	9885	809	264	649	96	8067
FINLAND	FI	11217	515	1329	422	24	8927
FRANCE	FR	109105	5299	32251	3358	675	67522
GERMANY	DE	137885	8571	39202	2441	1035	86636
GREECE	GR	10572	137	3035	302	48	7050
HUNGARY	HU	7941	221	3289	41	11	4379
INDIA	IN	57718	882	18384	390	773	37288
IRAN	IR	14975	193	1741	46	62	12933
IRELAND	IE	6073	173	57	192		5651
ISRAEL	IL	15027	421	2635	587	12	11372
ITALY	IT	73134	2326	18070	2239	366	50133
JAPAN	JP	92928	280	57			92591
MEXICO	MX	14079	84	2638	119	9	11229
NETHERLANDS	NL	26323	2418	2509	3068	135	18193
NORWAY	NO	5106	330	920	473	9	3374
POLAND	PL	24455	136	7649	116	44	16510
PORTUGAL	PT	11185	70	764	91	404	9856
ROMANIA	RO	10465	276	4722	86	21	5360
RUSSIA	RU	49884	1108	32568	48	30	16130
SINGAPORE	SG	21484	576	4420	243	8	16237
SOUTH KOREA	KR	101947	6760	12967	354	192	81674
SPAIN	ES	49027	793	13553	1313	555	32813
SWEDEN	SE	21353	1504	589	412	222	18626
SWITZERLAND	CH	23729	2195	1683	809	323	18719
TAIWAN	TW	56811	1402	6258	1202	29	47920
THAILAND	TH	6127	39	635	28	8	5417
TURKEY	TR	13786	88	369	318	11	13000
UKRAINE	UA	10028	92	6838	3	1	3094
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83045	5375	4398	2704	1122	69446
UNITED STATES	US	471900	41829	57378	10042	5740	356894

Fig & tab 25. Institutional coverage: classification of the institutions

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

a) Information on the number of missing values

Missing data for geographical information

Patents

For patents 273000 inventor addresses do not have any harmonized country. They have thus not been geolocalised at this stage. This represents 33% of total inventor addresses. Furthermore in a number of countries Patstat does not include yet inventor addresses: this is systematic for instance in China the second largest country in patenting for nanotechnology. Overall at this stage, we have a quite weak coverage. Work is being done for improving it before opening.

Note on different cases of missing information:

- The Patstat database gives no information on any inventor (or applicant) of a patent. In that case, the patent application is present (with its appln_id) in table firm_tls201_appln_ifris but absent of the table invt_adr_ifris_epwofr_frac_ctry that includes only patents with at least a few information on inventors (or table applt_adr_ifris_epwofr_frac_ctry which considers patents with at least a few information on applicants).
- The number of priority patents (appln_id in firm_tls201_appln_ifris) without any information on inventors is 273 753.
- The database gives limited information on inventor (or applicant) of a patent but this information may be partial (absence of the inventor or applicant name, address, country). In that case, the patent application is present (with its appln_id) in table invt_addr_ifris (or table applt_addr_ifris) but some fields are still empty after the filling steps described in the PATSTAT-IFRIS section.

The geolocalisation of filled addresses is very high by integrating the information and/or add-ups from REGPAT (OECD)⁶, the analysis of the DB of the French Patent Office (INPI) and from the internal analysis of Inpadoc families.

<i>Country Name</i>	<i>Country Harmonized</i>	<i>Addresses for priority patents</i>	<i>Addresses for non singleton priority patents</i>	<i>Non singleton priority patents with addresses</i>	<i>Geolocalised addresses form non singleton priority patents</i>	<i>Non singleton addresses geolocalised</i>
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⁶ OECD REGPAT, <http://www.oecd.org/science/inno/40794372.pdf>

Total		827 618	239 053	131 533	131 168	45,95 %
Vide	Vide	273 753	45 055	59	0	0 %
CHINA	CN	193074	4087	355	345	8,44 %
UNITED STATES	US	120183	90955	88964	88919	97,76 %
SOUTH KOREA	KR	80869	18540	683	667	3,6 %
GERMANY	DE	40809	27068	3941	3933	14,53 %
RUSSIA	RU	24470	1511	337	328	21,71 %
FRANCE	FR	21100	17492	17129	17104	97,78 %
TAIWAN	TW	18494	6219	2399	2336	37,56 %
JAPAN	JP	10426	6561	5376	5289	80,61 %
CANADA	CA	5424	3474	2258	2258	65 %
SPAIN	ES	5068	2695	415	415	15,4 %
UKRAINE	UA	4903	211	29	29	13,74 %
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	4104	2697	1018	1015	37,63 %
ITALY	IT	2704	1310	914	910	69,47 %
NETHERLANDS	NL	2585	1719	1417	1415	82,32 %
SWITZERLAND	CH	2173	1606	1236	1234	76,84 %
BELGIUM	BE	1865	1589	1292	1287	80,99 %
INDIA	IN	1268	723	633	632	87,41 %
POLAND	PL	1207	102	42	42	41,18 %
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	1077	360	21	21	5,83 %
ROMANIA	RO	830	16	8	8	50 %
ARGENTINA	AR	827	95	7	7	7,37 %
ISRAEL	IL	818	573	483	483	84,29 %
AUSTRIA	AT	773	517	165	162	31,33 %
PORTUGAL	PT	693	266	17	17	6,39 %
SINGAPORE	SG	686	485	389	387	79,79 %
HONG KONG	HK	630	264	176	176	66,67 %
MOLDOVA	MD	619	15	0	0	0 %
SWEDEN	SE	584	443	365	364	82,17 %
BULGARIA	BG	576	248	1	1	0,4 %
FINLAND	FI	523	338	297	297	87,87 %
HUNGARY	HU	421	134	60	60	44,78 %
MEXICO	MX	398	136	91	90	66,18 %
BELARUS	BY	390	39	8	8	20,51 %
DENMARK	DK	381	214	142	138	64,49 %
AUSTRALIA	AU	339	215	200	200	93,02 %
SLOVENIA	SI	334	169	24	18	10,65 %
SLOVAKIA	SK	287	56	10	9	16,07 %
BRAZIL	BR	261	99	62	62	62,63 %
NORWAY	NO	246	192	101	100	52,08 %

LATVIA	LV	218	22	1	1	4,55 %
CUBA	CU	182	68	8	7	10,29 %
IRELAND	IE	160	101	69	68	67,33 %
LITHUANIA	LT	150	9	7	7	77,78 %
MALAYSIA	MY	145	58	50	50	86,21 %
TURKEY	TR	137	40	22	22	55 %
LUXEMBOURG	LU	126	111	108	105	94,59 %
VENEZUELA	VE	95	79	75	73	92,41 %
PERU	PE	84	1	0	0	0 %
SAUDI ARABIA	SA	75	12	8	8	66,67 %
URUGUAY	UY	74	64	61	61	95,31 %
Other 76 countries		0	0	0	0	33,2 %

Fig & tab 26. *Missing geographical data for patents*

Scientific publications

Only 1.19% of addresses have not been geolocalised.

Missing information for institution and technological domains

Patents

Only 0,7% (6 677) priority patents have no technological domain.

Scientific publications

5.69% (124 064) of addresses do not have a harmonised institutional name and 5.75% (125 389) have not been allocated to one of the 5 types.

b) Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

Various sources of noise have been identified:

- Patents: we have used the PATSTAT standardisation name as a source for harmonising institutions.
- Publications and patents: in quite a few cases toponyms are ambiguous (even within a country) and this leads to a failure in geolocalisation.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

a) Legal issues concerning access of the database

The dataset is only accessible for research purposes (no commercial use is authorised). An important dimension of the database is that information at the individual level (one publication and one patent) remains confidential; only aggregated data can be published in public reports and/or academic journals.

b) Legal necessities for potential opening procedures

Users need to belong to an institution that has both a subscription to the Web of Science and to Patstat.

4 Technical structure of the dataset

4.1 Information on the data base system

a) Current data base system used

The current data base system is My SQL 5.1.63 with MyISAM as the default storage engine. In term of maintainability and backup, the main advantage of this storage engine is to use three different files for each table of a database:

- the data file has a .MYD (MYData) extension;
- the index file has a .MYI (MYIndex) extension;
- the structure file has a .frm extension.

MySQL is optimized for an intensive usage: a high level of accessibility and efficiency, for a low amount of users.

b) Planned future technical changes concerning data base system

No changes planned

4.2 Technical variable definition

Labelling of all variables. Data type of all variables (e.g., float, string, etc.). Current use and definition of unique identifiers (if applicable).

a) Variables for patents

<i>tls209_appln_ipc_ifris_epwofr</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
ipc_class_symbol	CHAR(15)
ipc_class_level	CHAR(1)
ipc_version	DATE NULL DEFAULT NULL,
ipc_value	CHAR(1)
ipc_position	CHAR(1)
ipc_gener_auth	CHAR(2)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, ipc_class_symbol, ipc_class_level

<i>tls210_appln_n_cls</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
nat_class_symbol	CHAR(15)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, nat_class_symbol

<i>tls205_tech_rel</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
tech_rel_appln_id	INT(10)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, tech_rel_appln_id

<i>tls202_appln_title</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
appln_title	VARCHAR(3500)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id

<i>tls207_pers_appln</i>	
person_id	INT(10)
appln_id	INT(10)
applt_seq_nr	SMALLINT(4)
invt_seq_nr	SMALLINT(4)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, person_id

<i>tls206_person</i>	
person_id	INT(10)
person_ctype_code	VARCHAR(3)
doc_std_name_id	INT(10)
person_name	VARCHAR(300)
person_address	VARCHAR(500)
PRIMARY KEY	person_id

<i>tls208_doc_std_nms</i>	
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doc_std_name_id	INT(10)
doc_std_name	CHAR(100)
PRIMARY KEY	doc_std_name_id

<i>tls204_appln_prior_ifris</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
prior_appln_id	INT(10)
prior_appln_seq_nr	SMALLINT(4)
appln_priority_year	INT(4)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, prior_appln_id

<i>tls201_appln_ifris</i>	
key_appln	VARCHAR(19)
appln_id	INT(10)
appln_auth	CHAR(2)
appln_nr	CHAR(15)
appln_kind	CHAR(2)
appln_filing_date	DATE NULL DEFAULT NULL,
ipr_type	CHAR(2)
appln_title_lg	CHAR(2)
appln_abstract_lg	CHAR(2)
internat_appln_id	INT(10)
appln_filing_year	INT(4)
appln_first_priority_year	INT(4)
no_appt_invt	INT(1)
no_ipc	INT(1)
artificial	INT(1)
singleton	INT(1)
layer	VARCHAR(4)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id

<i>tls211_pat_publn_ifris</i>	
key_publn	VARCHAR(19)
pat_publn_id	INT(10)
publn_auth	CHAR(2)
publn_nr	CHAR(15)
publn_kind	CHAR(2)
appln_id	INT(10)
publn_date	DATE NULL DEFAULT NULL,
publn_lg	CHAR(2)
publn_first_grant	SMALLINT(2)
publn_year	INT(4)
PRIMARY KEY	pat_publn_id

<i>tls203_appln_abstr</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
appln_abstract	VARCHAR(4000)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id

<i>tls218_docdb_fam</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
docdb_family_id	INT(10)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, docdb_family_id

<i>tls219_inpadoc_fam</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
inpadoc_family_id	INT(10)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id

<i>tls214_npl_publn</i>	
npl_publn_id	INT(10)
npl_biblio	VARCHAR(2100)
PRIMARY KEY	npl_publn_id

<i>tls212_citation</i>	
pat_publn_id	INT(10)
citn_id	SMALLINT(4)
cited_pat_publn_id	INT(10)
npl_publn_id	INT(10)
pat_citn_seq_nr	SMALLINT(4)
npl_citn_seq_nr	SMALLINT(4)
citn_origin	CHAR(5)
PRIMARY KEY	pat_publn_id, citn_id

<i>ipc_technology_frac_ifris</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
ipc_class_symbol	CHAR(15)
ipc_class_level	CHAR(1)
ipc_version	DATE NULL DEFAULT NULL,
ipc_value	CHAR(1)
ipc_position	CHAR(1)
ipc_gener_auth	CHAR(2)
nb_ipc	BIGINT(21)
frac_ipc	DECIMAL(5,4)
domaines	VARCHAR(4)
fields	VARCHAR(4)

sfields	VARCHAR(6)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id, ipc_class_symbol

<i>applt_adr_ifris_epwofr_frac_etry</i>	
key_applt	VARBINARY(26)
appln_id	INT(10)
person_id	INT(10)
doc_std_name_id	INT(10)
person_name	VARCHAR(300)
person_address	VARCHAR(500)
person_etry_code	VARCHAR(3)
SOURCE	VARCHAR(7)
PM_PP_COMP	VARCHAR(1)
QUALIF_COMP	VARCHAR(4)
NAME_COMP	VARCHAR(300)
FIRSTNAME_COMP	VARCHAR(300)
ADR_COMP	VARCHAR(500)
STREET_COMP	VARCHAR(40)
ZIP_CODE_COMP	VARCHAR(5)
CITY_COMP	VARCHAR(50)
CTRY_COMP	VARCHAR(2)
METHODE	VARCHAR(4)
frac_applt	DECIMAL(5,4)
adr_final	VARCHAR(500)
etry_final	VARCHAR(2)
etry_lib_ifris_etry_final	CHAR(2)

<i>etry_lib_ifris</i>	
etry_final	CHAR(2)
lib_etry_harm	VARCHAR(100)
etry_harm	CHAR(2)
nomen_geo_ifris_lib_etry_harm	VARCHAR(100)
PRIMARY KEY	etry_final

<i>nano_corpus</i>	
appln_id	INT(10)
layer	VARCHAR(10)
fields	VARCHAR(5)
PRIMARY KEY	appln_id

<i>inv_etry_ifris_epwofr_frac_etry</i>	
key_inv_etry	VARBINARY(26)
appln_id	INT(10)

person_id	INT(10)
doc_std_name_id	INT(10)
person_name	VARCHAR(300)
person_address	VARCHAR(500)
person_etry_code	VARCHAR(3)
SOURCE	VARCHAR(7)
QUALIF_COMP	VARCHAR(4)
NAME_COMP	VARCHAR(300)
FIRSTNAME_COMP	VARCHAR(300)
ADR_COMP	VARCHAR(500)
STREET_COMP	VARCHAR(40)
ZIP_CODE_COMP	VARCHAR(5)
CITY_COMP	VARCHAR(50)
CTRY_COMP	VARCHAR(2)
METHODE	VARCHAR(4)
frac_invt	DECIMAL(5,4)
adr_final	VARCHAR(500)
ctry_final	VARCHAR(2)
ctry_lib_ifris_ctry_final	CHAR(2)

Fig & tab 27. List of fields, types of variable and primary keys for the Nano Patents

b) Variables for scientific publications

<i>tab_address</i>	
address_id	int(10)
address	varchar(255)
address_org	varchar(127)
address_typorg	smallint(2)
address_ctycod	char(2)
address_city	varchar(40)
address_state	varchar(45)
address_poscod	varchar(11)
address_lat	decimal(10,7)
address_lng	decimal(10,7)
PRIMARY KEY	(address_id)

<i>tab_author</i>	
author_id	int(10)
document_id	int(10)
author_abbr	varchar(63)
author_full	varchar(127)

author_order	smallint(2)
author_type	smallint(2)
author_email	varchar(320)
PRIMARY KEY	(author_id)

<i>tab_author_has_address</i>	
author_id	int(10)
address_id	int(10)
PRIMARY KEY	(author_id,address_id)

<i>tab_author_identifier</i>	
identifier	varchar(255)
author_id	int(10)
identifier_type	smallint(2)
PRIMARY KEY	(identifier)

<i>tab_citation</i>	
citation_id	int(10)
citation	varchar(500)
cited_author	varchar(63)
cited_year	year(4)
cited_pub	varchar(90)
cited_volu	varchar(10)
cited_bpag	varchar(10)
cited_doi	varchar(255)
cited_pat	varchar(90)
cited_document_id	int(10)
cited_publication_id	int(10)
PRIMARY KEY	(citation_id)

<i>tab_citation_info</i>	
citation_info_id	int(10)
document_id	int(10)
citation_info_source	smallint(2)
citation_info_count	smallint(4)
citation_info_cited	smallint(5)
citation_info_date	date
PRIMARY KEY	(citation_info_id),

<i>tab_corpus_info</i>	
corpus_info_id	int(10)

corpus_info_name	varchar(255)
corpus_info_parent_id	int(10)
PRIMARY KEY	(corpus_info_id)

<i>tab_document</i>	
document_id	int(10)
language_id	smallint(3)
document_title	varchar(767)
document_abs	varchar(10000)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id)

<i>tab_document_has_address</i>	
document_id	int(10)
address_id	int(10)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,address_id)

<i>tab_document_has_citation</i>	
document_id	int(10)
citation_id	int(10)
citation_order	smallint(4)
citation_type	smallint(2)
citation_source	smallint(2)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,citation_id,citation_order),

<i>tab_document_has_keyword</i>	
document_id	int(10)
keyword_id	int(10)
keyword_source	smallint(2)
keyword_order	smallint(4)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,keyword_id,keyword_source),

<i>tab_document_has_publication</i>	
document_id	int(10)
publication_id	int(10)
doc_pub_date	varchar(15)
doc_pub_year	year(4)
doc_pub_volu	varchar(10)
doc_pub_issue	varchar(7)
doc_pub_bpag	varchar(10)
doc_pub_epag	varchar(10)
doc_pub_npag	smallint(3)

doc_pub_url	varchar(511)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,publication_id)

<i>tab_document_has_subject</i>	
document_id	int(10)
subject_id	smallint(4)
subject_source	smallint(2)
subject_order	smallint(4)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,subject_id,subject_source)

<i>tab_document_has_type</i>	
document_id	int(10)
type_id	smallint(2)
PRIMARY KEY	(document_id,type_id)

<i>tab_document_identifier</i>	
identifier	varchar(255)
document_id	int(10)
identifier_type	char(3)
PRIMARY KEY	(identifier)

<i>tab_file_info</i>	
file_info_id	int(10)
corpus_info_id	int(10)
file_info_path	varchar(255)
file_info_name	varchar(255)
file_info_type	smallint(2)
file_info_date	timestamp
PRIMARY KEY	(file_info_id)

<i>tab_keyword</i>	
keyword_id	int(10)
keyword	varchar(255)
PRIMARY KEY	(keyword_id)

<i>tab_language</i>	
language_id	smallint(3)
language	varchar(20)
language_iso1	char(2)
PRIMARY KEY	(language_id)

<i>tab_publication</i>	
publication_id	int(10)
publisher_id	int(10)
publication	varchar(255)
publication_subt	varchar(255)
publication_type	char(1)
publication_aiso	varchar(90)
publication_a29	varchar(29)
publication_issn	char(8)
publication_isbn	char(13)
PRIMARY KEY	(publication_id),

<i>tab_publisher</i>	
publisher_id	int(10)
publisher	varchar(127)
publisher_addr	varchar(255)
publisher_city	varchar(40)
publisher_web	varchar(2083)
PRIMARY KEY	(publisher_id)

<i>tab_reference</i>	
reference_id	int(10)
document_id	int(10)
file_info_id	int(10)
reference_proc	tinyint(1)
PRIMARY KEY	(reference_id,file_info_id,document_id)

<i>tab_reference_has_tag</i>	
reference_id	int(10)
tag_id	int(10)
tab_order	smallint(2)
tag_bol	int(10)
tag_eol	int(10)
tag_used	tinyint(1)
PRIMARY KEY	(reference_id,tag_id,tab_order)

<i>tab_subject</i>	
subject_id	smallint(4)
subject	varchar(255)
PRIMARY KEY	(subject_id)

<i>tab_tag</i>	
tag_id	int(10)
tag	varchar(3)
PRIMARY KEY	(tag_id)

<i>tab_type</i>	
type_id	smallint(2)
type	varchar(40)
PRIMARY KEY	(type_id)

Fig & tab 28. List of fields, types of variable and primary keys for the Nano Publications

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of Nano

Below is a description of all tables that are specific to the nano database. This means that tables that are present in the Patstat IFRIS database are described in the Patstat IFRIS appendix of the CIB database.

Whole relational diagram of Nano Patents with PATSTAT IFRIS

Fig & tab 29. Relational diagram of Nano Patents

Scientific publications relational diagram

Fig & tab 30. Relational diagram of Nano Publications

4.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures

The databases are accessible with a local access through the software MySQL Workbench⁷.

⁷ MySQL WorkBench, www.mysql.fr/products/workbench/

5 Further planning of the opening of *Nano*

a) Document concrete steps towards opening of the respective dataset

We have 3 on-going developments dealing with: (a) finalizing institutional harmonization (entering changes in the whole dataset); (b) patents (filling missing inventor addresses); and (c) finalizing clustering (naming and qualifying)

This will be done before March 2015.

b) Necessary updates and/or technical changes

We have two major developments starting (which we hope to integrate before the opening of the dataset): (i) move from the 2011 to 2014 Patstat dataset integrating all developments being made on Patstat-IFRIS; (ii) integrate a semantic thematic clustering based on CORTEXT Manager⁸.

c) Changing legal conditions for accessing the dataset or parts of the dataset

None

d) Suggestions

The geographical and institutional harmonisations are critical for articulating this dataset to others. If this can be done we could

- a) link engagement in nanotechnology of European universities with their characteristics (ETER dataset), their academic standing (Leiden ranking) and their presence at European level (EUPRO)
- b) See how large firm engagement in nanotechnology matches with their degree of internationalisation (CIB)
- c) See whether the hypothesis developed about the targeted role of small firms in nano (mostly “B to R”) translates into their positioning in the world of start-up firms (VICO dataset)

⁸ CorText Manager web app, <http://manager.cortext.net/>

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A dynamic query to delineate emergent science and technology: the case of nano science and technology.

Kahane B, Mogoutov A., Cointet J.P., Villard L., Larédo P.

1- Introduction

Building a larger and relevant database out of an initial seed without relying, because of potential bias, on experts is a common challenge for those who wish to study or track a scientific or technological field. Publications and patents are not the only, but definitely an important component of knowledge generation and dissemination and one of the potential sources for innovation. Scientists communicate their findings through publications. Similarly, patents are legal documents to claim ownership of an invention but they also build a public paper trail of technology advancement. Thus publications and patents are an important, relevant and useful tool to follow and represent results of scientific and technological endeavours (Huang, 2010). Data mining is the extraction of relevant and useful information from large volume of data. Publication and Patent data systematically collected in worldwide databases such as the WoS and Patstat are used to track science and technology dynamic. Data mining faces an important challenge in a context of emergence when new technologies experience explosive growth, evolve rapidly and often cross and subvert existing scientific and technology fields. Emerging science and technology (biotechnology in the 1980s, nanotechnology today, other science and technology fields tomorrow), which often carry strong implications and potentialities for science, business and society, add to the challenge. Their content and dynamic are difficult to track at a time when they are struggling to define who they are, what they include and exclude and how they organize themselves internally.

Such is the case for nanotechnology, where the quest for a relevant reliable and replicable way to extract relevant publications and patents, is an on-going process involving several teams worldwide (Glanzel 2003, Noyons 2003, Mogoutov and Kahane, 2007, Porter et al., 2008, Kostoff 2007, Leydesdorff and Zhou, 2007). Nanotechnology is a rapidly evolving emerging and dynamic field. Analysts argue that it is likely to be a “general purpose technology” (Youtie 2008, Laredo et al. 2010) with a potential impact across an entire range of industries and great implications on human health, the environment, sustainability and national security. The perceived potential value of nanotechnologies has led to the increased will of governments, academic institutions, firms and other societal actors to better understand what is happening in the field, who is active and where. There is thus an important challenge to develop robust methods to track the nanotechnology field while it rapidly develops and evolves. As a matter of fact,

good quality and comprehensive extraction of data is a prerequisite for meaningful understanding and analysis. Huang 2010 as well as L'huillery et al. 2010 have compared the different methodologies developed, and reported on their robustness as well as on the similarities and discrepancies of results obtained. They confirmed the robustness and interest of the evolutionary lexical methodology we have developed (Mogoutov and Kahane, 2007). At that time, three requirements were central to the approach developed. First, it should not depend upon experts. Indeed, the on-going and extensive use of expert-based approaches is costly, time-consuming, and challenging to replicate such that the same outcomes result. This is an important restriction when facing a highly dynamic field where borders are constantly evolving requiring terminology requalification at different times. Second, it should allow updates in order to replicate and compare results while the nanotechnology field (and its lexicon) develop and expand. And third, it should be able to track the relative evolution of subfields inside nanotechnologies: in 2007 we translated this into a third requirement of being “modular”.

While the initial development of our methodology was performed in order to extract data from 1998 to 2006, we later engaged in producing an update that could expand the database backward and forward in order to cover years 1991-2011. In our initial methodology, the selection of relevant terms was performed with knowledge built and keywords selected on one single year (2003). A simple solution was to reproduce the selection of terms for 2011, driving us to two semantic universes of nanotechnology, respectively built in 2003 and 2011. However Bonaccorsi (2010) has demonstrated that in a dynamic field such as nanotechnology, keywords often display short life and experience a type of Darwinian selection process. Using this approach, the characterisation of the evolution of the field over 20 years would have only relied on two years for the identification of relevant keywords. There would thus be a risk that we miss the richness of the exploration that shapes the dynamics of knowledge production. Not considering transient keywords that might have emerged and then disappeared, would be a serious drawback in such a dynamic field. There are multiple reasons for this. Two are of particular importance. One is about the learning that a stream of research, even if it goes on with a life of its own, has been experimented but proved not to be useful for colleagues at the time. The other lies in the fact that streams of research which for a while turn to be a dead end, can nevertheless reappear later and become a key resource as demonstrated in many instances. Such a limitation becomes even more visible when taking the whole period under review for identifying relevant keywords. This drove us to add a fourth requirement for such an approach: What is needed is a methodology, which allows us to incorporate and discard in real time relevant terms as they appear and disappear in the nanotechnology story. We need a methodology that allows us to track keywords as characters appear and disappear along the storyline in a movie.

Thus, using nanotechnology as a showcase, we here report a data search strategy made of three consecutive steps. As in all the data search strategies for nanotechnology, we start with an initial seed built through the nanostring. We then use the same principle that we applied in our previous approach, that is expanding the initial seed through a dual process where additional keywords observed during a given period are sorted according to their internal specificity (e.g. the extent to which they provide value added meaning to a publication) and then tested in the overall database for ‘external specificity’ (e.g. the ratio of articles in the seed vs. articles in the overall database of publications). This selection of keywords is first applied on the whole dataset covering the 20 years, enabling a “static extension”. The third step builds the “dynamic extension” where additional keywords are identified through a yearly analysis of internal specificity within the nanostring, and selected depending upon their ‘external specificity’.

Besides being applied in a specific way for nanotechnology, we claim that such a three steps strategy has universal value to describe the dynamics of emergent and fast evolving fields, transcending pre-existing classifications.

The article is built as follows. First, it provides a literature review of different search strategies, pointing to their limitations and explaining how our choices were made. Second, it looks at specific requirements needed when studying nanotechnology and explains how and why we decided to address them. Third, it provides the rationale and the description for the successive steps of our methodology. Fourth, some lessons derived from the nanotechnology example are derived for other emerging fields.

2- Evolutionary query requirements and methodology

As reported by Huang (2010), four different methodologies are used to search nanotechnology articles in the publication databases. They are lexical query, evolutionary lexical query, citation analysis and harvesting publications in core journals. We review them with our four requirements in mind: easiness (enabling wide access by research teams), portability (enabling reproducing results from one place to another), updating (to accommodate for the need for periodic characterisation of evolutions) and capturing dynamics of search (a critical issue in fluid fields facing wide exploration).

Lexical query

Most works and methodologies dealing with emerging fields rely on slight variations of an initial query, often built on a few terms that help define the field with some exclusion of obvious non-relevant terms. In the case of nanotechnology, it defines a nano-string built with the word “nano” plus a joker (“nano*”). For nanotechnology, such an initial

query was developed by Fraunhofer-ISI in 2002⁹ and is still at the core of most publications analysing the content and evolution of the field, whether in publications or in patents (Glanzer et al., 2003; Noyons et al., 2003; Porter et al., 2008). Two limitations exist with this approach. On the one hand, some words like NaNo2 or nanosecond need to be excluded. On the other, in emerging technologies with fast expansion, authors become increasingly attracted and introduce alternative keywords for labelling the field, which need to be incorporated in the search¹⁰. Indeed, we have shown that the core of related keywords experience an even more rapid growth than the entire database of nanotechnology publications (Mogoutov and Kahane, 2007). In both cases, the more precise the exclusion or the inclusion, the greater will be the need for complementary keywords. One possible solution is the use of experts, but Huang, reviewing the existing approaches, underlines the possible bias associated with their subjectivity (Huang, 2010). Thus, automatic methods are needed while manual exclusion or inclusion have to be kept to the minimum. This applies as well for defining the initial seed: in our initial nanostring seed, only nanoliter, nanosecond and chemical formula of NaNO₂, NaNO₃, NaNO and NaNO₅ are excluded.

Automatic evolutionary extension of keywords

In a similar vein (avoid experts subjectivity and bias), automatic and iterative ways of obtaining search keywords have been developed as an alternative to manual extension (Zucker et al, 2007; Mogoutov and Kahane 2007). Out of a first dataset built through the nanostring, a set of keywords is harvested. Keywords are then ranked by their level of relevance to the field, based upon their frequency of appearance (alone or in combination). A mathematical threshold is built on keywords profile and/or an iterative process is mobilized in order to assess the relevance of keywords. As this relevance is assessed within the initial seed only, we speak of internal relevance and later internal specificity of the keywords. The iterative process looks at publications convergence on a relatively consistent set of keywords that change only slightly between iterations (Zucker et al., 2007; Kostoff et al., 2006) or at data distribution (Mogoutov and Kahane 2007). This selection of keywords is dependent on the initial seed collected. This is the drawback of minimizing expert intervention, and the limitations associated with their subjectivity. Most approaches have witnessed successive improvements of the method they use to measure the internal relevance of keywords. Compared to our previous publication, we propose here a new alternative method, which we claim to be of better quality.

⁹ Note that at that time the bulk of present nano publications and relevant keywords did not exist.

¹⁰ Early bibliometric analysis by, for instance Braun and al 1997 have shown that extraction through the use of the simple term “nano*” suffered from the omission of biotechnology-related publications whose keywords were less likely to contain the prefix “nano”.

Automatic Citation analysis

Zitt and Bassecoulard (2006) demonstrated an alternative hybrid lexical-citation approach to extend publications beyond the nanostring. There the second step is done by identification of a “core” literature cited by the seed literature. To extend the seed, they extract other publications citing this core literature while controlling by use of a parameter that strikes a balance between the specificity and the coverage of the publications in order to get a good “noise to silence” ratio (Huang 2010). As for the previous evolutionary extension method, subjectivity of expert intervention is limited while the way the inclusion/exclusion parameter is defined becomes the key factor. The trade-off is between too much “noise” vs. “silence”. Nevertheless, this approach adds another difficulty since its implementation requires setting up a citation linkage between all the papers in the WoS database. This limits this approach to no more than a dozen institutions worldwide with such capacity to access the full web of science database to use the pre-built citation linkages (Mogoutov and Kahane 2007). Thus, as in our previous publication, we discarded this approach in order to keep the portability and feasibility by other teams that we wished in order to achieve dissemination and comparative analysis.

Publications in the core nanotechnology journals

Leydesdorff and Zhou (2007) use journals as the unit of analysis and extract articles from a set of core journals. Using “betweenness centrality” as an indicator for measuring the interdisciplinarity of scientific journals, they distinguish a set of three core nanotechnology journals and a group of 85 journals related to them from which they identify ten core journals on nanotechnology. One of the drawbacks of this approach is that it only covers a small share of the literature. Thus, as demonstrated by Huang (2010), the total number of publications harvested by this approach is 5 to 10 times smaller to what is obtained through other strategies. Moreover, as the technology is emerging and evolving, the set of journals, which publish nanotechnology related articles, is also changing. The analysis based on a very limited number of the core journals chosen at a certain time would thus impair results.

This last argument points to the specific issue of an emerging field and its evolving nature. This result emphasizes the need and requirement for an approach, which will display a strong capacity to reflect and track the intense dynamic of the field. It is in line with the work of Bonaccorsi on search regimes (Bonaccorsi 2008) and its results about the rapidly evolving nature of emerging fields and about the need for approaches and queries that take into account keywords life. This requirement challenged our previous methodology which was built on a modular basis allowing specific subfield analysis but which did not offer any tool to follow on going evolutions. Studying computer science, Bonaccorsi (2010) points to two central phenomena, which happen in an emergent field with rapid expansion and intense dynamics. Firstly, very few research lines and associated keywords succeed in establishing themselves on a long-term basis. In order to capture these, we developed a first “static” extension that looks at keywords, which

have established a significant presence in the field when the whole period of analysis is considered. Besides these success, Bonaccorsi shows that many other tentative lines of research and their associated keywords struggle but do not succeed in maintaining a presence in the field on a long term basis. Thus, without taking on board these exploratory lines of research we would miss a large share of the dynamics, which characterizes the evolution of nanotechnology. Further, we would not be able to catch researches and keywords at the end of the period studied since there are great chances that their presence is still too limited to overcome the limitation of a few years of presence in the database. Thus, in order to capture these tentative lines of research, we had to develop another kind of extension that we call “dynamic extension”. We now report below the different steps through which the initial nanostring is built and then expanded.

3- Methodology

Our approach is based on a multiple step procedure of query building and tests. The methodology is made of the following steps:

- Extraction of publications through the nano string giving the nanostring database
- Selection and cleaning of “main forms” from the nanostring database, giving the universe of keywords to consider
- Extraction of the main forms selected from the entire period in order to build the “static extension” database
- Extraction of main forms selected year by year in order to build the “dynamic extension database”

Step 1: Retrieval of a core ‘nano’ dataset: Extraction of publications through the nanostring

In line with the previous method, we applied the same formal nominalist simple search with the ‘nano’ substring as used in most other methods. In order to limit and reduce bias to minimal we excluded as before only a few terms containing this string but not related to the nanotechnology field (nanosecond, NaNO₂, NaNO₃, NaNO₄, NaNO₅). It is presented in the box below, which takes into account evolutions of the interface proposed by the WoS at the time of downloading.

Box 1 - The query for the nanostring

Note: the introduction by the WoS interface of a lemmatisation has simplified life for managing ‘main forms’ (see below) but it has limited the use of “*” in the construction of the query for abstracts and keywords (TS) driving to a different query as this for titles (TI).

```
TI=((NANO* OR A*NANO* OR B*NANO* OR C*NANO* OR D*NANO* OR E*NANO* OR F*NANO* OR G*NANO* OR H*NANO* OR I*NANO* OR J*NANO* OR K*NANO* OR L*NANO* OR M*NANO* OR N*NANO* OR O*NANO* OR P*NANO* OR Q*NANO* OR R*NANO* OR S*NANO* OR T*NANO*
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OR U*NANO* OR V*NANO* OR W*NANO* OR X*NANO* OR Y*NANO* OR Z*NANO*) NOT (NANO2 OR NANO3 OR NANO4 OR NANO5 OR NANOSECOND* OR NANOLITER*) OR TS=((NANO*) NOT (NANO2 OR NANO3 OR NANO4 OR NANO5 OR NANOSECOND* OR NANOLITER*))
```

From 1991 to 2010, this extraction gave 517050 articles, with an impressive growth of 20% for 15 years rising to 40000 articles in 2005, and then a doubling in 5 years to 80425 articles. We shall see later that the share of this coreset, the nanostring, will regularly increase in relative importance during the first period from 14% in 1991 to 30% in 1999 and 48% in 2005. Since then it has fluctuated around 50% and been on average for the last five years 51%.

Graph 1: Nano science: an overview

Box 2 – Technical notes on the nanostring

The note addresses two issues: coverage and exclusions.

Coverage: the query has been simplified for technical reasons about downloading from the WoS. After tests we decided not to keep for abstracts the same rule as for titles to insure the full presence of words that do not start with the prefix nano. The tests showed that it would reduce the overall volume by 0,6%. As a consequence we decided that extensions would verify that we had not missed too many articles (where the specific term such as subnano* would be in the abstracts only). This approach that reduced downloading time significantly proved to be relevant: for instance, the ‘raw’ static extension (see below) contains 73 multi-terms including nano that theoretically represent more than the total nanostring. Still we only retrieved 777 potential articles showing that this time optimisation was very efficient.

Exclusions: We decided to concentrate ‘targeted’ exclusions afterwards, that is on the effective dataset built. The argument is dual: technical (one of simplicity and efficiency in downloading)

and substantive (we do not master the multi-terms built around the classical exclusion terms – e.g. subnanosecond - and we do not know their potential articulation to other ‘relevant’ multi-terms of the vocabulary). Another interesting aspect lies in the role that the extensions made provide in term of testing the specificity and relevance of the multi-terms identified in the nanostring: this is very efficient in identifying problematic areas (such as those around the measure of the amount of substance concentration).

This has also enabled to take advantage of the progressive work done in particular by Grieneisen and Zhang (2011) and Arora et al. (2013).

We put here the main exclusions operated from the final dataset:

- The 270 taxonomic organisms and species identified by Grieneisen and Zhang (2011).
- The classical terms around plankton (nano & pico), satellites (nanosatellites) and flagel (e.g. nanoflagellates)
- The classical exclusions around grams and moles (all the variations around nanogram, including nanog, and nanomolar).

The latter represents by far the largest set of articles excluded while all the others have only a marginal effect on the dataset.

Step 2: Data set preparation and lexical expansion and extraction

At this stage, we adopt a lexical extension methodology different from the one used in our previous publication. Step 1 provides us with a core dataset of publications related to nanotechnology that needs to be expanded to better cover relevant publications. Expansion requires first extracting terms pertaining to a given corpus. Similarly to what was done in the previously published methodology, titles from articles are extracted and pre-processed from the dataset obtained on step 1: a complete indexation of words present in these titles is performed as well as a lemmatization in order to reduce the number of words with similar meaning in further analysis. Then methodologies diverge. We have made two central changes compared to our previous approach.

The first one deals with the selection of candidate terms for the selection of articles, and the other deals with the approach to the way of defining sub-datasets for computing. First, in our previous method, “word combinations” in titles and abstracts were classified according to their frequency in order to select candidates for further automatic relevant selection. Now the Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools we apply, allow us to identify not only simple terms (e.g. nanotube) but also multi-terms (e.g. carbon nanotube or tubular carbon nanotube) (also called n-grams). While automatic multi-terms extraction is a classical task in NLP, the existing tools are not always well suited when one wishes to extract only the most salient terms. We thus mobilised methods for measuring their specificity. However specificity computing drives to an exponential growth of computer time and resource as datasets grow larger. We have thus developed an automatic method that helps reducing computing requirements. This lexical extraction strategy is not directly applied to the entire corpus. We first split the corpus into 20 sub-corpus, one per year (each sub-corpus gathers all publications published a given year). Lexical extraction is then applied on each sub-corpus and the 2000 most relevant multi-terms are extracted for each year. Hence we can be confident

that we do not miss important terms that only occur in the early times or which are only important during a limited time period.

The selection of the relevant multi-terms is made in two stages. First classical linguistic processes end up defining sets of candidate noun phrases. Second, the most relevant multi-term stems are selected.

a) Defining candidate noun phrases

- We use a Part-of-Speech Tagging tool to classify each word of the text according to its grammatical type: noun, adjective, verb, adverb, etc. This allows focusing on potentially meaningful terms for analysis (nouns and possibly adjectives), leaving aside less interesting terms (such as verbs or adverbs).

- 'Chunking' associates to each word of the text a tag describing its type. As shown in the example below, a noun phrase is then defined as a pattern of successive nouns and adjectives. This step builds the universe of multi-terms. It helps define and extract the minimal meaningful units on which to build further analysis.

Box 3 - Example of chunking process

Therefore<CC> a<DET> finite-volume<ADJ> discretization<N> of<CC> the<DET> 3d<ADJ> self-consistent<ADJ> model<N> was<V> implemented<V>...

Results: two different noun phrases are obtained

- finite-volume<ADJ> discretization<N>

- 3d<ADJ> self-consistent<ADJ> model<N>

- 'Normalizing' corrects small orthographical differences between multi-terms regarding the presence or absence of hyphens. For example, we consider that the multi-terms "single-strand polymer" and "single strand polymer" belong to the same class.

- 'Stemming' drives to gather multi-terms together into a single class if they share the same stem. For example, singular and plurals are automatically grouped into the same class (e.g. "fullerene" and "fullerenes" are two possible forms of the stem "fullerene").

b) Selection of most relevant multi-terms stems

This first processing based on grammatical constraints provides an exhaustive list of possible multi-terms grouped into stemmed classes. The second stage aims at selecting the *N* most relevant terms.

Following an approach defined by Kageura and Umino (1996), we are looking for groups of relevant terms which convey the most interesting semantic unit (high **unithood**) using as a proxy those multi-terms appearing more frequently and being in the longer

phrases¹¹. Meanwhile, we wish these terms to convey strong meaning (high **termhood**) and thus to discard those which may be very frequent in the corpus but do not help characterizing the content of the text. These are for example terms like “review of literature” or “past articles”. For this purpose, we proceed in four stages:

- ‘Counting’: we count each stem according to corresponding multi-terms found in the whole corpus to obtain their total number of occurrences (frequency). In this step, if two candidate multi-terms are nested, we only increment the frequency of the larger chain. For example if “spherical fullerenes” is found, we only increment the multi-stem “spherical fullerene” but not the smaller stem “fullerene”.¹²
- ‘C-value unithood calculation’: for each multi-term stem, we associate the C-value as proposed by Frantzi & Ananiadou (2000). This provides each stem with a unithood value defined as $u(i) = \log(l_i) f_i$ where l_i is the number of terms involved in the multi-term i and f_i designates its frequency.
- ‘Sorting’: Items are then sorted according to their unithood value (Van Eck et al., 2011) and the list is pruned to 4 times the number of multi-terms looked for (see above) starting from the highest C-value. This step removes less frequent multi-term stems.
- ‘Selecting’: A second-order analysis is performed on the 4N list obtained of the terms with highest unithood value in order to exclude those who do not carry special meaning. We adopt the approach proposed by Van Eck et al. (2011) to identify multi-term stems with low termhood. The rationale that we follow is that irrelevant terms should have an unbiased distribution compared to other terms in the list. These terms may appear in any documents in the corpus whatever the precise thematic they address. We first compute the co-occurrence matrix M between each item in the list. We then define the termhood θ of a multi-stem as the sum of the chi-square values it takes with every other class in the list¹³. We rank the list according to θ and only the N most specific multi-stems are conserved.

Thus, through this yearly double process of identifying sets of candidate noun phrases and then of sorting multi-term stems according to their relevance through their unithood and termhood, the final output of our analysis comes to a list of multi-term stems (from now on we shall speak of multi-terms to qualify them) which display both high unithood value and termhood and which can now be ranked according to what we call their **internal specificity**. The power of NLP and the approach developed entailed one important implication: we can work directly at the level of the whole ‘nanostring’

¹¹ This unithood qualification builds on two pragmatic assumptions classically made in multi-word automatic term recognition tasks: pertinent terms tend to appear more frequently and longer phrases are more likely to be relevant.

¹² Nested terms need to be treated carefully because they may induce false positive - for example when the multi-term “self organizing map” is found in a text, we should not count the multi-term “organizing map”, otherwise we would overestimate its unithood even though it does not convey any unit of meaning.

¹³ The endogenous specificity of term i is $\theta(i) = \sum_{j \neq i} (M_{ij} - M_i M_j)^2 / (M_i M_j)$ where $M(i) = \sum_j M_{ij}$. This measure accommodates both the possible bias of item i toward certain other items and still takes into account terms frequency.

and no longer require decomposing it using pre-existing fields (we had 8 such sub-fields in the 2007 query). This drove us to abandon the ‘modular’ approach designed (in part for pragmatic reasons) in our previous approach. This has one important consequence: before we had to consider specifically all potential ‘long-distance’ interdisciplinary papers (i.e. between the selected fields identified) while they are now de facto taken into consideration.

Box 4- Main results of Step 2 on the nanostring

When performing the identification of multi-terms we arrive only at 2000 different multi-terms in 1997, giving a theoretical total number of 34191 multi-terms over the whole period (1991-2010). Redundancy is very high as the total vocabulary is only 4189 different multi-terms with in total more than 17 million occurrences. This means that on average one article is defined by 33 multi-terms, which builds a very rich characterisation.

Introducing the two step extension

The two next steps aim at identifying within the relevant multi-terms selected in the initial seed, those that can be considered as specific to nanotechnology and which we shall use to retrieve complementary articles to those already included in the nanostring. In our previous query we only had a ‘static’ extension, selecting the most relevant multi-terms over the whole period. It aims at enriching the core knowledge that has demonstrated over the period its ability to aggregate scholars and their publications. We propose in this new query to add a dynamic extension. The purpose of such an extension is not to loose track of the explorations made year after year even if they have not succeeded to become ‘core’. This is also important since otherwise by only having a static extension we would not take into account on-going developments. Doing so requires making choices about the overall size of the dataset and caring about the noise-silence ratio. The literature is not very rich about these issues that most of the times remain unaddressed by developers. Looking at our previous query, which covered 9 years only, the lexical extension multiplied the core by 2.6 times. We found similar multipliers in other queries. We thus considered that keeping in line would be a reasonable solution and that we should aim at a theoretical tripling of the nanostring balanced between the static and dynamic extensions. As extensions drive to select more than once articles (if only between the two extensions), and knowing empirically that overtime papers refer more and more explicitly to nanotechnology (Arora et al. 2013, see also the growing share of the nanostring over time), this should drive to a far lower net increase (de facto 2.28 times with each extension representing 28% of the expanded dataset).

In our previous study, we highlighted a very rapid rate of growth (14% per year between 1998 and 2006). We thus took into account that, even if with size the rate of growth might slightly reduce, it would continue to grow arriving to very large yearly levels (de facto the number of publications in 2010 is equal to the total of the first 9

years of the dataset -1991-1999). This drove us to look carefully at the results of Bonaccorsi (2010) in computer science (even though its rate of growth was slower).

First, many new lines of research constantly emerge with new associated keywords and only a few of these new lines of research and associated keywords establish themselves to become persistent. An extension must thus give credit to research directions that have succeeded in becoming persistent. This was already at the core of our previous approach and we kept it: this builds the “static extension”.

Second, this also means that most new lines of research that emerged had only temporary existence. They translate the fact that many researchers at some point explore a new direction (associated with new keywords), and that the evaluation made by colleagues (here measured through their take-up of keywords) was that it was not relevant at this stage. The previous approach did not consider them at all (which can be acceptable over a short period of time), but for a 20 year coverage associated with a 14% yearly growth rate, it becomes difficult to forget all the explorations made that did not prove fruitful (at least at the time of analysis): this would drastically reduce our understanding of de facto dynamics. It would simply forget, in a fast growing emerging field, all the attempts that are made to progressively structure its dynamics. And if we follow Bonaccorsi that large exploration pattern is characteristics of all ‘new’ fields of science. This is why we have added a “dynamic extension”. We now present the two extensions in turn.

Step 3: Static extension query

Step 3 aims at enlarging the dataset around the central dynamics observed in the corset produced, the nanostring.

- Defining the external specificity of multi-terms

We define external specificity as a ratio representing the occurrence of a given multi-term in the nanostring compared to its occurrence in the whole science. This is done by calculating, multi-term by multi-term and year by year, the number of articles that appear in the whole WoS¹⁴. The external specificity ratio of a multi-term is thus calculated yearly. We use their mean over the 20 years of the database for the static extension. All candidate multi-terms are then ranked by their mean external specificity ratio.

- Selecting relevant multi-terms

Our next challenge is then to decide where to cut on the level of external specificity, thus deciding on a threshold above which multi-terms are considered as relevant and selected for downloading new articles. Looking at the literature does not give any robust indication on how to proceed. We decided on a two-step procedure. First, we considered

¹⁴ For this we use only the main form (that is the most frequent form) that appears in the N candidate multi-term stems. This is all the more feasible that the WoS, through its interface, operates a lemmatisation that de facto enables to retrieve the majority of the other forms identified, keeping the order of terms in multi-terms.

that a persistent term translating a successful aggregation of knowledge has to be central for a minimum number of years. We translated this in one central criterion: it must be within the 250 terms with the highest termhood in the different years of presence. This drove to a first selection of 1105 different terms (from the 3930 overall vocabulary and out of a theoretical possibility of some 23500 multi-terms). The second step was to decide upon a threshold. First tests were made on the Web of Science to have an idea of what different thresholds mean: they showed that a threshold of 20% would in theory bring 1.5 million articles (nanostring included), a threshold of 25%, 990000 articles and a threshold of 30% 745000 articles. This reinforced us in our approach to match in size the theoretical addition to the nanostring. For doing so we used our list of terms ranked by declining levels of specificity and measured what each multi-term could theoretically bring (i.e. the expected increment is the total occurrences in the WoS less those of the nanostring). We stop when the theoretical level matches this of the nanostring (that is 517000 theoretical additions)¹⁵. This drove to an effective external specificity threshold of 26% brought by 114 multi-terms that represent the static extension (see box for the characterisation of the static extension). The effective number of new articles was of course far lower: when taking into account duplicate articles (similar articles attracted by two different multi-terms), it de facto increased the seed by a factor of 1.65, adding 330000 articles to the 517000 articles of the nanostring.

Box 5- Positioning the static extension

A Preliminary note: arriving to the effective static extension

When operating the extension, we decided not to exclude any 'nano' term, and thus not to consider potential exclusions of not-relevant nano terms (such as nanomolar) (Only the 'nano' standing alone was excluded). It gave 210 'raw' multi terms.

The second step is to consider the check that is conducted on all 'nano' terms (see box 2). This concerns 73 multi terms (that theoretically overall bring more than the effective nanostring, 590000 potential articles vs. 517000 effective ones). This brings only, as mentioned in box 2, 777 potential new articles, showing that the choice made for simplifying the nanostring was quite efficient.

The third step done (afterwards to characterise the effective extension) is to check for the excluded vocabulary: we in fact find in the raw static extension 24 terms, 19 being fully specific and 4 (linked to subnano* in abstracts only) adding 2790 potential articles. This also provides a measure of their presence in the nanostring – a theoretical total of 26000 articles out of which 71% are linked to multi-terms associated with nanomolar and 19% to multi-terms associated with nanogram.

The effective extension is then built on 114 multi-terms that could theoretically add some 497000 articles.

B Characterising the effective static extension

¹⁵ The technical choice made for extracting articles was to use the possibilities offered by the WoS for multi term words, that is using NEAR/0 that activates lemmatisation; we also have been careful not to accept transitivity in multi-terms; each multi-term has thus a query that rejects the reversed format, as shown in the following example for chemical deposition and for year 2007: TS=((chemical NEAR/0 deposition) NOT ("deposition chemical")) AND PY=2007

The distribution is very skewed showing that only a few multi-terms bring the core of the theoretical expansion: 6 terms bring 51%, 13 terms 66%, 21 terms 75% and 44 terms 90%. It means at the other extreme that 29 multi-terms together bring less than 1% of the theoretical extension,

The thematic orientation of multi-terms is revealing:

- 30 multi-terms deal with observation, manipulation and control techniques (TEM, AFM, STM, NSOM) and make the majority of the theoretical extension (57%).
- The second group concerns materials: TiO₂, CDS, graphene, (nano)porous AAO, carbon based nanotubes & quantum-based (dots, wire...): it gathers 37 multi-terms and altogether 23% of the theoretical extension.
- The third group is linked with the characteristics/properties and characterisation of materials, molecules or genes at the nanoscale: it gathers 36 multi-terms and 12% of the theoretical extension. Finally, and contrary to the dynamic extension (see below) there are few multi-terms dealing with fabrication / expression techniques (11 multi-terms bringing 8% of the theoretical extension).

A third characteristic is linked with their presence over time. Tables 2 and 3 below show that on average nano-based terms (our 73) have been present for nearly 18 years and non nano-based ones (our 114) for one year more, whatever level of presence. There is a progressive appearance of terms during the first decade (starting at 47% in 1991, standing at 84% in 1995 and being all but one present in 2000. For instance, we already speak of nanofabrication in 1991 and carbon nanotubes appear in 1992, as does graphene (20 years before the Nobel price).

Moving from the theoretical to the effective extension drives to a severe reduction in new articles, due to a high level of articles containing more than one multi-term: the static extension is only made of 332000 different articles and represents 28% of the total dataset, multiplying the core set by only 1.65.

The effect of the static extension varies strongly with time: it increases the nanostring by a factor of 5 at the beginning (1991) and this multiplier strongly decreases over time, being below 1 in 2002, below 50% in 2006 to end at 30% on 2009-2010.

Tables 2 and 3: time composition of the static extension

Years of presence	Total	20	19	18	17	16	15	14	13	12	Average
Nano-based extension	73	31	6	6	11	5	6	3	2	3	17,8
Non nano-based extension	114	67	9	12	8	7	2	2	4	3	18,6
Total	187	98	15	18	19	12	8	5	6	6	18,3

Date of presence of multi terms	Total	1991	1995	2000	1991	1995	2000
Nano-based extension	73	21	58	72	29%	79%	99%
Non nano-based extension	114	67	100	114	59%	88%	100%
Total	187	88	158	186	47%	84%	99%

Step 4: Dynamic query

The characteristics of the static extension show the interest of having a more refined extension looking at explorations made year by year. Though many of the selected terms do not display a significant presence over the whole period (measured both through

presence and internal specificity), they nevertheless have been strong in some specific years. The principle of the dynamic extension is to mobilise them for expanding the corpus only for those years where they have had a strong presence and provided they show also a relevant external specificity.

The starting point of the approach is similar to this adopted for the static extension but based on all terms (less those already selected for the static extension), i.e. 4189 terms minus the 210 terms of the raw static extension. We then calculate their external specificity, but here to avoid too brutal variations we use three-year moving averages. This also gives us year by year their expected theoretical increment to the dataset (the overall number of articles in the WoS minus the articles in the nanostring).

For moving to the next step, we considered another result of Bonaccorsi (2010) on computer science. He shows that over time the exploration does not diminish and that the rate of renewal of keywords does also not diminish overtime; only does the selection by colleagues become harsher, most terms remaining orphan (i.e. with very low uptakes). This means that we should be careful not to reduce the level of exploration over the years. This has driven us to adopt a yearly approach to our principle of a theoretical tripling of the nanostring balanced between the static and the dynamic query. As for the static query we thus look for a theoretical doubling of the nanostring (adding 517000 potential new articles). However, contrary to the static extension, we do not do it over the whole period, but year by year¹⁶.

This drives to calculate the nanostring for each year, defining for each given year the theoretical number of publications that need to be extracted through the dynamic extension. We then go back to the yearly list of multi terms ranked in descending order of external specificity. Adding the potential additions term by term, we define the last term to be included to match the nanostring that year. This enables to identify the external specificity threshold that needs to be applied for the corresponding year. We retain, for this year, only the multi terms above this threshold to download articles.

A key feature of the dynamics is that with time (and with the fast rise of publications), the threshold will increase year after year: it moves from 9% in 1991 to 23% in 2000 and 49% in 2010 (see graph below).

¹⁶ As we stop just below the multi-term that trespasses the annual quantitative threshold, the implication of this repetition over 20 years is that the de facto total is just under 500000 potential new articles, and not near to 517000 articles.

Graph 2: yearly external specificity threshold for the dynamic extension

This process drives to a selection table that crosses multi-terms and years. We arrive to 742 different multi-terms. Box 6 provides a detailed analysis of the composition. We had few multi-terms to exclude that are furthermore only concentrated on the first years of the extension. Like in the static extension, the check done on nano-based terms (171) shows that the simplification adopted in the query for the nanostring is relevant. And we end with 558 different multi-terms appearing on average just over 5 years. In itself this is an interesting validation of Bonaccorsi's hypothesis about wide ranging exploration. A second important finding is that the number of terms appearing in one year increases regularly, representing at the end of the period (2010) 40% of the selected vocabulary: this reinforces the discussion engaged by Arora et al. (2014) about the progressive enrichment of a 'common nano-technology lexicon'. One interesting feature is to consider the typical sequences observed over the 20 years of analysis (table 4). Box 6 also shows interesting differences between on one side the overall vocabulary (gathered in 7 major themes) and the 'core' vocabulary that gathers 90% of the potential extension, and on the other side between the static and the dynamic extension with one clear central difference, the former privileging observation/manipulation techniques and the latter fabrication/production ones.

Table 4: typical patterns of yearly occurrences of multi-terms in the dynamic extension; the 20 most frequent patterns

Hash	NbMainForm	NbConcecutYear	FristYear	LastYear
000000000000000000011	38	2	2009	2010
0000000000000000000111	24	3	2008	2010
00001110000000000000	24	3	1995	1997
00000000000000000001111	23	4	2007	2010
000000000000011111111	22	8	2003	2010
00000111000000000000	21	3	1996	1998
000000000000000000011111	19	5	2006	2010
0000000000000000000111111	19	6	2005	2010
00011100000000000000	17	3	1994	1996
00000000000000000001111111	17	7	2004	2010
00000000000001111111111	16	9	2002	2010
000000000000011100000	15	3	2003	2005
000000000001111111111	15	10	2001	2010
000000000111111111111	11	11	2000	2010
00000011100000000000	11	3	1997	1999
000000000000111000000	10	3	2002	2004
00000000000000000001110	10	3	2007	2009
00000000011100000000	9	3	2000	2002
000000001111111111111	9	12	1999	2010
00000000001110000000	9	3	2001	2003

Box 6 – A detailed analysis of the dynamic extension

The year-by-year selection process of relevant couples (multi term x year) drives to 742 different multi terms selected.

a) Excluded terms only appear at very low levels of specificity thresholds, between 1991 and 1995

There are 8 different terms building 36 couples term-year selected and representing 440 occurrences in the nanostring. Only 12 add 1298 potential new articles (specificity below 1) with only 4 couples linked to “micromolar” bringing 75% of the total.

b) The testing of multi-terms containing ‘nano’ gathers 171 terms representing 1308 couples term-year, an average just under 8 years of appearance.

The test shows once more the relevance of the simplification made for the ‘nanostring’ since these terms appear nearly 164000 times in the nanostring, while they only generate 243 potential new articles (thus linked to terms only present in the abstracts).

Looking more in detail on the dynamics of terms, we see a fast increase from an average of 7 terms only in 1991-92 to 70 in 1995 and a peak of 90 terms annually between 2002 and 2005, before going down to 70 terms on average between 2006 and 2010.

We have organised words by main themes in order to measure their respective importance and follow their dynamics (Table 5). This shows three interesting results.

First in term of composition: materials mobilised come first (31% of presence) with measure (21%) and characterisation dimensions (18%). Both these terms share an important feature: their importance reduces in relative terms between the two decades observed, in favour of terms dealing with application (still limited in importance 9%) and even more vis-à-vis terms dealing with three dominant types (tubes, wires and films, 20% of total presence and nearly 80% in the second decade).

Table 5 - the nano-based vocabulary of the dynamic extension

Themes	Terms	Terms	Presence		Share of 2nd decade
	Nber	%	Nber	%	
Nanomaterials (gold...)	49	29%	406	31%	65%
Nano tubes/wires/films	39	23%	268	20%	79%
Nano applications (fibers, powders...)	20	12%	121	9%	67%
Characterisation	31	18%	239	18%	53%
Measure	32	19%	274	21%	40%
total	171	100%	1308	100%	61%

Box 6 continued

c) The dynamic extension per se is made of 558 multi-terms representing 2856 couples term-year, just over 5 years of presence per term on average.

We witness an interesting evolution over time: the number of multi-terms per year compared to the total population (558) increases at the same time the external specificity threshold does (see graph 3): it starts with 1% of the total vocabulary in 1990-91, is around 20 to 25% between 1996-2000, then moves to an average of 31% between 2001-2005 and to 41% in 2008-2010.

An interesting feature is linked to the life cycle of multi-terms depending upon the fact they emerged and died in the first decade (27%), they emerged after 2000 (52%) or they emerged during the first decade and went on in the second decade (21%). Their respective life cycle was 2.9 years for the first, 3.9 years for the second and 8.4 years for the third.

As for the static query there is a clear concentration effect: the first 100 couples bring 42% of the potential extension, the following 100 13%, the following 300 19%. The last 2000 couples only bring 14% of the total potential extension.

The composition shows interesting features compared to the static extension (table 6)

- Observation/manipulation techniques play an important role (12% of terms, 14% of total presence) as in the static extension but to a lesser degree (26% in the static extension). This is the exact reverse for production/fabrication (16% of terms and of presence in the dynamic extension, vs 8% in the static extension).

- Materials (21%) complemented by nano tubes/wires and films (6%) are less important than in the static extension (32%)

- A clear difference between the static and the dynamic extensions lies in the richness of the measurement and characterisation vocabulary, respectively 33+8% and 32%; while applications only appear in the dynamic query but at a marginal level (4%, and 10% if we include nano tubes, wires and films).

The difference is even wider with the nano-based dynamic extension (see above) that has nearly no term dealing with observation, manipulation and production / fabrication techniques, a very different balance between measures and characterisation, and nearly 50% of terms associated with materials and nanotubes/wires and films.

To better grasp the role of the multi-terms in the dynamic extension, we have selected all the terms that potentially bring more than 500 articles, i.e. 162 terms out of the overall 558. Together they potentially bring 442000 articles, compared to an overall total of 492000 potential articles (90%), once excluded multi-terms have been excluded and once account is taken of the selection process implemented.

This is illustrative of the difference between the overall vocabulary and the core vocabulary that generates significant numbers of new articles (table 7): most terms related to nanotubes (without the term nano) do not generate any significant number of articles (they are all in the nanostring). Observation, manipulation, production and fabrication techniques represent overall 28% of the vocabulary; their role in generating articles is far more important (39% of the key vocabulary and 47% of total articles). On the contrary characteristics and properties represent only half of their share of the vocabulary (17% vs 33%) bringing only 14% of total potential articles.

Finally, the static and the dynamic extensions share in common the importance of observation and manipulation techniques, but levels differ widely: 57% of the total potential static extension against only 19% for the dynamic extension. This is counterbalanced by the contrasted importance given to fabrication techniques (respectively 8% and 28% of the respective potential extensions). Both extensions share a near to similar importance given to materials (respectively 23 and 28%) and to characterisation (respectively 12 and 14%)..

Table 6 - A thematic analysis of the vocabulary of the dynamic extension

Themes	Terms	Terms	Presence		Years
	nber	%	nber	%	pres
Observation/manipulation techniques	69	12%	395	14%	5,11
Production / fabrication processes	88	16%	451	16%	5,13
Materials	116	21%	573	20%	4,94
Nano tubes, wires, films, ribbons	28	5%	176	6%	6,29
Applications	29	5%	119	4%	4,1
Measures	44	8%	337	12%	7,66
Characterisation	184	33%	805	28%	4,38
Total	558	100%	2856	100%	5,11827957

Table 7- Core vocabulary generating 90% of the expected dynamic extension

	Terms	Terms	Articles	Potential	
	nber	%	nanosting	articles	%
Manipulation observation	32	20%	93374	86035	19%
Production fabrication	30	19%	108120	123419	28%
Applications	12	7%	11778	13924	3%
Materials	38	23%	125363	122284	28%
Measures	22	14%	38331	34748	8%
Characteristics/ properties	28	17%	63815	62083	14%
	162	100%	440781	442493	100%

Box 7 gives the main characteristics of the effective extension and its role in the overall dataset. One interesting feature is the opposite relative roles of the static and the dynamic extensions over time in an overall dataset where the nanostring has regularly increased in importance to over half of the total since 2006: while the role of the static extension moves from 75% to 15% in 20 years, the dynamic one starts with 10% to finish with 30%. Graph 3 also shows that since 2002-3 the role of the dynamic extension remains stable while the relative growth of the nanostring is linked with a regular decrease of the static extension, as if the common vocabulary over the period is less and less relevant to define the new dynamics at work.

Box 7 - The effective dynamic extension - Main figures

This dynamic extension has been conceived to double the nanostring as was the static extension. Redundancy in the characterisation of articles is far less than expected, bringing the overall total of new articles included to 332000, nearly the same amount brought by the static extension, representing 28% of the whole dataset.

However this 64% increase is obtained very differently than for the static extension: it plays a minimal role in the overall dataset at the beginning of the period moving from 10% in 1991 to an average of 22% in 1996-2000 and then oscillating around 30% since.

Graph 3- the nano DB: evolution of the role of respective layers 1991-2010

4-Conclusion

The ambition of this article is to propose a new automatic evolutionary lexical query to address emerging fields. This query is made of a core component based upon the central keywords associated with the emerging field (in our example “nano”), and of two extensions that tap on one side the progressive ‘stabilisation’ of the field, and on the other the continuous exploration that characterises ‘new dominant sciences’ to follow Bonaccorsi.

This new approach follows our previous one (Mogoutov and Kahane 2007) taking advantage of three developments in primary datasets (in particular the new lemmatisation capacity offered by the WoS), in new approaches and software to analyse contents and extract relevant multi-terms, and in power computing that enabled to move from tens of thousands to millions of units of analysis. To circumvent limitations in our previous query we had to develop a modular approach to extension, while here we propose one, which does not require any ex-ante content choice.

We have made key choices that require further discussions within the community. We think that extension beyond a core set is critical since in an emerging field, both established categories poorly address the emerging field, and since also the vocabulary being not stabilised there is enormous variation in central keywords used for positioning the emerging field. But other studies have reduced their coverage to the core set alone or limited expert-based extensions. Arora et al. (2014) show that after 20 years of development, the scope and variety of the nano-based vocabulary is such that we might have a good image of the present dynamics only using it. We share their results but not the conclusions: we think that this drives to lose all the explorations made in the way, and thus gives a limited image of the effective ‘search regime’ and we think, always following Bonaccorsi and his conclusions on computer science, that the ‘nano’ vocabulary has all chances to miss most of the on-going exploration at the present and still instable frontier of the field. This is why we consider critical to keep extensions until a field is fully institutionalised. (Remember that following existing categorisations, for instance in comparing public research organisations - cf. science metrix 2013 on European PRO - drives to measure the relative performance of different organisations in a disciplinary framework that ignores all new fast growing fields). However the nature and the level of the extension to be made, remain to be discussed. Here we have proposed to differentiate between two types of extensions: a ‘static’ and a ‘dynamic’ extension. The former takes hold of those aspects that are ‘core’ to the emerging field over the whole period of observation, while the latter reflects the variety and multiplicity of explorations made about the potential content and directions of the new field. We think that the results exposed above clearly demonstrate the utility of this dual approach. What remains important to discuss is the extent of the extension. We have read widely and have found no satisfying answer, and often no discussion at all, about this level. Taking work done by the main teams in nano science and technology, we have arrived at an empirical estimate of tripling the initial seed. And we have proposed two complementary methods that we consider relevant for both the static and the dynamic extensions. There is thus further research to be done to better address this question.

Meanwhile, if our pragmatic solution is considered satisfactory, we offer a fully reproducible method for any new emerging field.

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Appendix 2: Automatic allocation of addresses to given types of actors

We have 5 types: universities, government organisations, hospitals, firms and other. For each we have established automatic allocations that are presented below

University / Abbreviations detection

"*_Coll_*" or "*_Fac_*" or "*_Fak_*" or "*_sch_*" or "*_Hsch_*" or "*_TH_*" or "*_Univ_*" or "*_Grad_*" or "*_Ecole_*" or "*_Scuola_*" or "*_School_*" or "*_Polytech_*" or "*_Polytecn_*"

University / Main institutions detection

"*_Caltech_*" or "*_CUNY_*" or "*_ETH_*" or "*_IIT_*" or "*_MIT_*" or "*_NYU_*" or "*_NTH_*" or "*_SUNY_*" or "*_UNWIST_*" or "*_georgia_tech_*" or "*_ASU_*" or "*_cornel*" or "*_FSU_*" or "*_FAMU_*" or "*_Harvard_*" or "*_ISU_*" or "*_LSU_*" or "*_ETH_*" or "*_Mem_Sloan_Kettering_Canc_Ctr_*" or "*_Manchester_Mat_Sci_Ctr_*" or "*_Leiden_Amsterdam_Ctr_Drug_Res_*" or "*_ITN_*" or "*_IPN_*" or "*_IPCMS_*" or "*_IHP_*" or "*_Forschungszentrum_Karlsruhe_*" or "*_ENSERG_*" or "*_ENSEEG_*" or "*_EMPA_*" or "*_Virginia_Tech_*" or "*_UTBM_*" or "*_USP_*" or "*_UNINOVA_*" or "*_UNICAMP_*" or "*_UNESP_*" or "*_UNAM_*" or "*_UMIST_*" or "*_UFSCar_*" or "*_UFRJ_*" or "*_UFPR_*" or "*_TU_Chemnitz_*" or "*_Supelec_*"

Government institute / Abbreviations detection (first part of the address)

"*_Akad_*" or "*_Acad_*" or "*_Mil_*" or "*_Minist_*" or "*_Def_*" or "*_Estab_*" or "*_Govt_*" or "*_Agcy_*" or "*_Inst_*" or "*_Ist_*" or "*_Lab_*" or "*_natl_lab*" or "*_ntl_lab*" or "*_natl_Inst_*" or "*_ntl_inst_*" or "*_ntl_ctr_*" or "*_ntl_res_*" or "*_natl_ctr_*" or "*_natl_res_*" or "*_Acad_*" or "*_adm_*" or "*_Fed_*" or "*_bur_*" or "*_office_*" or "*_survey_*" or "*_metrop_*" or "*_Fraunhofer_*"

Government institute / Abbreviations detection (second part of the address)

"*_Akad_*" or "*_Acad_*" or "*_Mil_*" or "*_Minist_*" or "*_Def_*" or "*_Estab_*" or "*_Govt_*" or "*_Agcy_*" or "*_natl_lab*" or "*_ntl_lab*" or "*_natl_Inst_*" or "*_ntl_inst_*" or "*_ntl_ctr_*" or "*_ntl_res_*" or "*_natl_ctr_*" or "*_natl_res_*" or "*_Acad_*" or "*_adm_*" or "*_Fed_*" or "*_bur_*" or "*_office_*" or "*_survey_*" or "*_metrop_*" or "*_Fraunhofer_*"

Government institute / Main institutions detection

"*_AFRC_*" or "*_ANL_*" or "*_AERE_*" or "*_BNL_*" or "*_CDC_*" or "*_CDCP_*" or "*_CENS_*" or "*_CEN_*" or "*_CEA_*" or "*_CERN_*" or "*_CAB_*" or "*_CENEN_*" or "*_CNRS_*" or "*_CSIRO_*" or "*_CSIC_*" or "*_CNR_*" or "*_CSIR_*" or "*_DESY_*" or "*_DFVLR_*" or "*_EURATOM_*" or "*_FAA_*" or "*_FCC_*" or "*_FAO_*" or "*_INRA_*" or "*_INSERM_*" or "*_KFA_JULICH_*" or "*_MRC_*" or "*_MAFF_*" or "*_NASA_*" or "*_NCI_*" or "*_NEI_*" or "*_NHLBI_*" or "*_NIAID_*" or "*_NIAMDD_*" or "*_NICHHD_*" or "*_NIDR_*" or "*_NIMH_*" or "*_NIH_*" or "*_NOAA_*" or "*_NERC_*" or "*_ORNL_*" or "*_ORSTOM_*" or "*_SERC_*" or "*_FOM_*" or "*_TNO_*" or "*_UKAEA_*" or "*_USAF_*" or "*_USDA_*" or "*_EPA_*" or "*_FDA_*" or "*_USN_*" or "*_Euratom_Assoc_*" or "*_AFSOR_*" or "*_AIST_*" or "*_Russia_Sci_Ctr_*" or "*_ANDRA_*" or "*_Angstrom_Technol_Partnership_*" or "*_ASCR_*" or "*_Australian_Nucl_Sci_&Technol_Org_*" or "*_BESSY_*" or "*_Bhabha_Atom_Res_Ctr_*" or "*_Bundesanstalt_Mat_Forsch_&Prufung_*" or "*_Bur_Rech_Geol_&Minieres_*" or "*_CAS_*" or "*_CCAST_*" or "*_CCLRC_*" or "*_CEIT_*" or "*_Chem_&Chem_Engn_Res_Ctr_Iran_*" or "*_China_Ctr_Adv_Sci_&Technol_*" or "*_Chinese_Ctr_Adv_Sci_&Technol_*" or "*_CIEMAT_*" or "*_CLRC_*" or "*_CMRDI_*" or "*_CNR_*" or "*_CNRS_*" or "*_CNRSM_*" or "*_Combinatorial_Mat_Explorat_&Technol_*" or "*_Comis_Nacl_Energia_Atom_*" or "*_Commiss_European_Communities_*" or "*_Consejo_Nacl_Invest_Cient_&Tecn_*" or "*_CREST_*" or "*_CSIC_*" or "*_Ctr_Adv_Studies_Sci_&Technol_Microstruct_*" or "*_Ctr_Adv_Technol_*" or "*_Ctr_Atom_Bariloche_*" or "*_Ctr_Brasileiro_Pesquisas_Fis_*" or "*_Ctr_Dis_Control_&Prevent_*" or "*_Ctr_Int_Laser_*" or "*_Ctr_Invest_Quim_Aplicada_*" or "*_Ctr_Mat_Elect_Technol_*" or "*_Ctr_Nacl_Aceleradores_*" or "*_Ctr_Nucl_Sci_*" or "*_darpa*" or "*_DEMOCRITOS_Natl_Simulat_Ctr_*" or "*_Dept_Vet_Affairs_Med_Ctr_*" or "*_DERA_*" or "*_DIPC_*" or "*_DLR_*" or "*_doe_*" or "*_Donostia_Int_Phys_Ctr_*" or "*_ECN_Solar_Energy_*" or "*_Elect_Res_&Serv_Org_*" or "*_Electrochem_Res_Ctr_*" or "*_ENEA_*" or "*_Energy_Res_Ctr_Netherlands_*" or "*_ESRF_*" or "*_ETRI_*" or "*_Synchrotron_*" or "*_Forschungszentrum_*" or "*_Fraunhofer_*" or

"*_Fujitsu_Labs_Ltd_*" or "*_Geoforschungszentrum_Potsdam_*" or "*_Geol_Survey_Norway_*" or
 "*_German_Canc_Res_Ctr_*" or "*_GIST_*" or "*_High_Energy_Accelerator_Res_Org_*" or "*_IFW_*" or
 "*_IFW_Dresden_*" or "*_ILL_*" or "*_IMEC_*" or "*_IMRE_*" or "*_Indira_Gandhi_Ctr_Atom_Res_*" or "*_INFM_*"
 or "*_INRS_Energie_*" or "*_INSTM_*" or "*_Int_Adv_Res_Ctr_Powder_Met_&_New_Mat_*" or "*_Int_Supercond*"
 or "*_Interuniv_Microelect_Ctr_*" or "*_IPICyT_*" or "*_ISTEC_*" or "*_JAERI_*" or "*_Japan_Fine_Ceram_Ctr_*" or
 "*_Japan_Sci_&_Technol_*" or "*_JASRI_*" or "*_Jawaharlal_Nehru_Ctr_Adv_Sci_Res_*" or
 "*_Joint_Res_Ctr_Atom_Technol_*" or "*_JRCAT_*" or "*_JST_*" or "*_K_JIST_*" or "*_Kansai_Adv_Res_Ctr_*" or
 "*_KIST_*" or "*_lawrence_berkeley_*" or "*_LBL_*" or "*_LBNL_*" or "*_livermore_*" or "*_LURE_*" or
 "*_Max_Delbruck_Ctr_Mol_Med_*" or "*_Max_Planck_*" or "*_MPG_*" or "*_NASU_*" or "*_Nat_Hist_Museum_*"
 or "*_NatI_Cardiovasc_Ctr_*" or "*_NatI_Met_&_Mat_Technol_Ctr_*" or "*_NatI_Microelect_Res_Ctr_*" or
 "*_NatI_Nano_Device_Labs_*" or "*_NatI_Sci_Council_*" or "*_NCSR_*" or "*_New_York_State_Dept_Hlth_*" or
 "*_NIMS_*" or "*_NIPER_*" or "*_NIST_*" or "*_NIST_*" or "*_NMRC_*" or "*_NREL_*" or "*_Nucl_Res_Ctr_Negev_*"
 or "*_Nucl_Sci_Ctr_*" or "*_Off_Natl_Etud_&_Rech_Aerosp_*" or "*_Off_Naval_Res_*" or "*_Palo_Alto_Res_Ctr_*" or
 "*_Phys_Tech_Bundesanstalt_*" or "*_PRESTO_*" or "*_RAS_*" or "*_Res_Ctr_Energy_Convers_&_Storage_*" or
 "*_Res_Ctr_Rosendorf_*" or "*_Riken_*" or "*_RIKEN_*" or "*_Russian_Res_Ctr_*" or "*_sandia_*" or "*_SAS_*" or
 "*_Sincrotrone_Trieste_*" or "*_SINOPEC_*" or "*_SINTEF_*" or "*_Stanford_Linear_Accelerator_Ctr_*" or
 "*_TRIUMF_*" or "*_UFRGS_*" or "*_UNESP_*" or "*_UOP_LL_C_*" or "*_US_DOE_*" or "*_US_Geol_Survey_*" or
 "*_USN_*" or "*_Vet_Adm_Med_Ctr_*" or "*_Vet_Affairs_Med_Ctr_*" or "*_VTT_*" or "*_WHO_*" or
 "*_Zentrum_Sonnenenergie_&_Wasserstoff*" or "*_Zentrum_Sonnenergie_&_Wasserstoff_*" or "*_ZSW_*"

Hospital / Abbreviations detection

"*_Hop_*" or "*_Hosp_*" or "*_Osped_*" or "*_Med_cent_*" or "*_CHR_*" or "*_CHU_*" or "*_med_ctr_*" or
 "*_clin_*" or "*_eye_ctr_*" or "*_vet_*" or "*_ctr_med_*" or "*_Canc_Ctr_*" or "*_canc_res_*" or "*_heart_*" or
 "*_john_hopkins_*" or "*_Kaiser_Permanente_*" or "*_eye_*" or "*_blood_*"

Firm / Abbreviations detection

"*_Co_*" or "*_Corp_*" or "*_gesell_*" or "*_inc_*" or "*_gmbh_*" or "*_associate*" or "*_bhd_*" or "*_consult_*"
 or "*_llc_*" or "*_ltd_*" or "*_SA_*" or "*_semicon_*" or "*_venture_*" or "*_ab_*" or "*_Spa_*" or "*_AG_*" or
 "*_PLC_*" or "*_SARL_*" or "*_EURL_*"

Firm / Main institutions detection

"*_AEG_*" or "*_ALCOA_*" or "*_ABC_*" or "*_BASF_*" or "*_CBS_*" or "*_DUPONT_*" or "*_GEC_*" or
 "*_ICI_PL_C_*" or "*_3M_CO_*" or "*_NBC_*" or "*_SKF_*" or "*_SK&F_*"

Other

All other names that don't contain the pattern used for the other classes, and also with : "*_Assoc_*" or "*_Fdn_*"

Appendix 3 - Institutions standardised, the five main institutions per country

<i>Main (top 5) institutions per country</i>	<i>Country code harmonized</i>	<i>Total of publications for the countries</i>	<i>Institutions standardized</i>	<i>Number of addresses per institutions</i>
ARGENTINA	AR	7721	cenea	1329
ARGENTINA	AR	7721	univ buenos aires	1288
ARGENTINA	AR	7721	conicet	1174
ARGENTINA	AR	7721	univ nacl la plata	925
ARGENTINA	AR	7721	univ nacl cordoba	425
AUSTRIA	AT	12357	univ tech vienna	2381
AUSTRIA	AT	12357	univ vienna	1887
AUSTRIA	AT	12357	univ linz	1166
AUSTRIA	AT	12357	univ tech graz	887
AUSTRIA	AT	12357	univ graz	727
AUSTRALIA	AU	30507	univ queensland	2838
AUSTRALIA	AU	30507	univ new s wales	2727
AUSTRALIA	AU	30507	univ sydney	2727
AUSTRALIA	AU	30507	CSIRO	2160
AUSTRALIA	AU	30507	univ melbourne	2122
BELGIUM	BE	17872	kul	3549
BELGIUM	BE	17872	univ cathol louvain	1984
BELGIUM	BE	17872	univ antwerp	1947
BELGIUM	BE	17872	univ ghent	1891
BELGIUM	BE	17872	imec	1595
BRAZIL	BR	31330	univ sao paulo	5346
BRAZIL	BR	31330	univ campinas	2956
BRAZIL	BR	31330	univ estad paulista	1983
BRAZIL	BR	31330	univ fed rio janeiro	1696
BRAZIL	BR	31330	univ fed sao carlos	1654
CANADA	CA	43183	univ toronto	4798
CANADA	CA	43183	univ mcgill	3002
CANADA	CA	43183	nrc	2934
CANADA	CA	43183	univ alberta	2668
CANADA	CA	43183	univ british columbia	2401
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	ethz	7243
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	EPFL	5092
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	univ basel	1890
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	univ geneva	1141
SWITZERLAND	CH	23739	EMPA	1029
CHINA	CN	281585	chinese acad sci	48763

CHINA	CN	281585	univ tsinghua	9797
CHINA	CN	281585	univ nanjing	8967
CHINA	CN	281585	univ zhejiang	8094
CHINA	CN	281585	univ china sci & technol	7799
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12117	czech acad sci	5387
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12117	univ charles	1946
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12117	prague inst chem technol	668
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12117	Univ Masaryk brno	532
CZECH REPUBLIC	CZ	12117	univ tech czech	425
GERMANY	DE	138005	max planck	14927
GERMANY	DE	138005	helmholtz	9302
GERMANY	DE	138005	leibniz	6760
GERMANY	DE	138005	KIT	5285
GERMANY	DE	138005	univ munchen	3660
DENMARK	DK	9892	univ tech denmark	3126
DENMARK	DK	9892	univ aarhus	1879
DENMARK	DK	9892	univ copenhagen	1678
DENMARK	DK	9892	univ so denmark	649
DENMARK	DK	9892	univ aalborg	450
SPAIN	ES	49044	csic	10229
SPAIN	ES	49044	Univ Barcelona	3201
SPAIN	ES	49044	univ aut madrid	2468
SPAIN	ES	49044	univ complutense madrid	2285
SPAIN	ES	49044	univ pais vasco	2157
FINLAND	FI	11217	univ helsinki	1994
FINLAND	FI	11217	univ tech helsinki	1939
FINLAND	FI	11217	univ turku	922
FINLAND	FI	11217	univ abo akad	817
FINLAND	FI	11217	vtt	692
FRANCE	FR	109156	cnrs	17053
FRANCE	FR	109156	cea	6904
FRANCE	FR	109156	upmc	5545
FRANCE	FR	109156	univ paris sud	4838
FRANCE	FR	109156	univ lyon claudes bernard	4194
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83092	univ cambridge	7498
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83092	univ oxford	4700
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83092	imperial college	4139
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83092	ucl	3825
UNITED KINGDOM	GB	83092	univ manchester	3638
GREECE	GR	10575	univ thessaloniki	1806
GREECE	GR	10575	ncsr demokritos	1434
GREECE	GR	10575	univ patras	1411
GREECE	GR	10575	FORTH	1003

GREECE	GR	10575	univ tech athens	797
HUNGARY	HU	7946	hungarian acad sci	2912
HUNGARY	HU	7946	univ szeged	1248
HUNGARY	HU	7946	univ eotvos lorand	969
HUNGARY	HU	7946	univ tech & eco budapest	920
HUNGARY	HU	7946	univ debrecen	417
IRELAND	IE	6078	trinity coll dublin	1760
IRELAND	IE	6078	univ coll cork	1137
IRELAND	IE	6078	univ dublin city	682
IRELAND	IE	6078	univ limerick	659
IRELAND	IE	6078	univ coll dublin	611
ISRAEL	IL	15031	technion	2798
ISRAEL	IL	15031	univ hebrew jerusalem	2735
ISRAEL	IL	15031	univ tel aviv	2134
ISRAEL	IL	15031	weizmann inst sci	2042
ISRAEL	IL	15031	Univ ben gurion negev	1731
INDIA	IN	57760	csir	7567
INDIA	IN	57760	indian inst sci	2933
INDIA	IN	57760	bhabha atom res ctr	2413
INDIA	IN	57760	iit kharagpur	2253
INDIA	IN	57760	indian assoc cultivat sci	1617
IRAN	IR	14998	univ tehran	1355
IRAN	IR	14998	univ tech sharif	1244
IRAN	IR	14998	univ islam azad	1117
IRAN	IR	14998	univ tarbiat modarres	805
IRAN	IR	14998	univ tech teheran amirkabir	689
ITALY	IT	73200	cnr	12358
ITALY	IT	73200	univ padua	2628
ITALY	IT	73200	univ roma la sapienza	2419
ITALY	IT	73200	univ bologna	2399
ITALY	IT	73200	univ milano	2256
JAPAN	JP	92937	univ tohoku	12226
JAPAN	JP	92937	univ osaka	10637
JAPAN	JP	92937	univ kyoto	5915
JAPAN	JP	92937	univ kyushu	5567
JAPAN	JP	92937	univ nagoya	5315
SOUTH KOREA	KR	102001	univ natl seoul	9718
SOUTH KOREA	KR	102001	kaist	5795
SOUTH KOREA	KR	102001	univ hanyang	5025
SOUTH KOREA	KR	102001	univ yonsei	4593
SOUTH KOREA	KR	102001	postech	4166
MEXICO	MX	14086	univ nacl aut mexico	4047
MEXICO	MX	14086	inst politecn Nacl	2498

MEXICO	MX	14086	conacyt	1423
MEXICO	MX	14086	univ aut metropolitan mexico	969
MEXICO	MX	14086	Inst Mexicano Petr	606
NETHERLANDS	NL	26336	univ tech delft	3706
NETHERLANDS	NL	26336	univ twente	2752
NETHERLANDS	NL	26336	univ tech eindhoven	2722
NETHERLANDS	NL	26336	Univ utrecht	2176
NETHERLANDS	NL	26336	univ groningen	1949
NORWAY	NO	5113	ntnu	1244
NORWAY	NO	5113	univ oslo	1185
NORWAY	NO	5113	univ bergen	444
NORWAY	NO	5113	sintef	372
NORWAY	NO	5113	univ tromso	190
POLAND	PL	24479	polish acad sci	5628
POLAND	PL	24479	univ tech warsaw	1508
POLAND	PL	24479	univ warsaw	1310
POLAND	PL	24479	univ tech wroclaw	1241
POLAND	PL	24479	univ jagiellonian	986
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	univ aveiro	2250
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	univ porto	1358
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	univ tech lisbon	1358
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	univ minho	1122
PORTUGAL	PT	11191	univ coimbra	909
ROMANIA	RO	10476	romanian acad sci	1279
ROMANIA	RO	10476	natl Inst mat phys	1003
ROMANIA	RO	10476	univ polytech bucharest	898
ROMANIA	RO	10476	univ babes bolyai	779
ROMANIA	RO	10476	univ bucharest	753
RUSSIA	RU	49926	russian acad sci	27843
RUSSIA	RU	49926	univ state moscow lomonosov	4614
RUSSIA	RU	49926	univ state st petersburg	1255
RUSSIA	RU	49926	kurchatov inst	605
RUSSIA	RU	49926	univ state novosibirsk	543
SWEDEN	SE	21366	univ uppsala	3217
SWEDEN	SE	21366	Univ lund	2940
SWEDEN	SE	21366	KTH	2670
SWEDEN	SE	21366	univ tech chalmers	2620
SWEDEN	SE	21366	univ linkoping	1873
SINGAPORE	SG	21484	univ natl singapore	9530
SINGAPORE	SG	21484	univ tech nanyang	6372
SINGAPORE	SG	21484	a.star	3723
SINGAPORE	SG	21484	a star	600

SINGAPORE	SG	21484	chartered semicond mfg ltd	219
THAILAND	TH	6129	univ chulalongkorn	1624
THAILAND	TH	6129	univ mahidol	756
THAILAND	TH	6129	univ chiang mai	715
THAILAND	TH	6129	natl sci & technol dev agcy	449
THAILAND	TH	6129	king mongkuts inst technol	372
TURKEY	TR	13799	univ tech middle east	988
TURKEY	TR	13799	univ hacettepe	910
TURKEY	TR	13799	univ tech istanbul	839
TURKEY	TR	13799	univ bilkent	717
TURKEY	TR	13799	univ gazi	529
TAIWAN	TW	56816	univ natl taiwan	7057
TAIWAN	TW	56816	univ natl cheng kung	5872
TAIWAN	TW	56816	univ natl tsing hua	4861
TAIWAN	TW	56816	univ natl chiao tung	4749
TAIWAN	TW	56816	acad sinica	2341
UKRAINE	UA	10036	ukrainian acad sci	6464
UKRAINE	UA	10036	univ natl kiev	765
UKRAINE	UA	10036	Univ natl lvov	267
UKRAINE	UA	10036	univ natl tech kiev	244
UKRAINE	UA	10036	univ natl kharkov	228
UNITED STATES	US	472303	MIT	9212
UNITED STATES	US	472303	Univ Illinois Urbana	8377
UNITED STATES	US	472303	univ penn state	7073
UNITED STATES	US	472303	univ michigan	7021
UNITED STATES	US	472303	univ northwestern	6955

Fig & tab 31. *Main (top 5) institutions per country*

Report on the content and technical structure of the **PROFILE** Infrastructure

iFQ: Institute for Research Information and Quality Assurance

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of the *ProFile* infrastructure (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

In general, little is known about doctoral education in Germany. Even the total number of doctoral candidates at German universities can only be estimated, official data does not exist. Therefore, reliable information on the conditions, processes and success of doctoral education is essential. Due to the insufficient data availability, the **Institute for Research Information and Quality Assurance e.V. (iFQ)**¹ has set up *ProFile*: A longitudinal study focussing on the situation of doctoral candidates and their postdoctoral professional careers. Since April 2009, doctoral candidates from different universities and other (funding) institutions are surveyed at regular intervals via means of an online survey (see Figure 1). *ProFile* aims at identifying determinants of postdoctoral career development and at providing information on conditions of doctoral education in a comparative perspective via a monitoring approach. Special attention is paid to the effects of structured doctoral programs (Graduate Schools) which have emerged increasingly during the past years. *ProFile* contains a number of explanatory elements which can be connected to career theories of decision making in order to explain career outcomes.

2 Information on substantive content of *ProFile*

A comprehensive documentation of data collection and contents of the Scientific Use File for on-site use can be found under the following URL:

http://risis.eu/profile_data_documentation/

¹ From January 1st, 2016 on the iFQ continues its work as Department 2 "Research System & Science Dynamics" of the German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, DZHW) under the same address:

Schützenstraße 6a

D-10117 Berlin

Phone: +49 (0)30 / 206 41 77-0

Fax: +49 (0)30 / 206 41 77-99

This report still serves as an introduction into the basic characteristics of the project but it will no longer be updated.

2.1 Definition and description of observations

Target population and unit of analysis

ProFile aims at studying the supervision situation of doctoral candidates and careers of doctorate holders. Thus, doctoral candidates and doctorate holders are the units of analysis. Doctoral degrees are defined as advanced study ISCED-8² equivalent research degrees. The data covers doctoral students from all subjects with the exception of Medicine.³

Since there is no information on the total population of doctoral candidates in Germany ProFile cannot claim statistical representativity for this group, but the sampling approach at least ensures representativity on the level of the partnering organisation. ProFile receives the contact data of all doctoral candidates currently working on a dissertation at selected universities and funding organisations in Germany.⁴ In addition to the contact data (names email) ProFile receives subject, gender and year of birth for every person in order to assess how the sample achieved through the survey matches the total population of doctoral candidates at the respective organisation. In 2013 the partnering organisations were seven German universities alongside three funding organisations.⁵ The Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (German Research Foundation, DFG) left the project in 2012 after having provided contact data on doctoral candidates with membership in a Research Training Group (RTG) or with an affiliation to a Collaborative Research Center (CRC) for the years 2009 and 2010. Each ProFile cooperation partner is expected to deliver every year the contact data on the doctoral candidates who have recently started working on their dissertation or who were not reported in the previous year. In the first year, all doctoral candidates at the respective partnering organisation are reported.

² International Standard Classification of Education 2011 (ISCED), <http://www.uis.unesco.org/Library/Documents/2011-international-standard-classification-education-isced-2012-en.pdf>

³ This is due to the fact that an unknowingly large share of doctoral degrees in Medicine may not be ISCED-8 equivalent degrees and that degrees are partially obtained before referral of the ISCED-7 degree.

⁴ With the exception of Medicine, see Footnote 3.

⁵ Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, University of Kassel, Heidelberg University, Freie Universität Berlin, Friedrich Schiller University Jena, Leibniz Universität Hannover, University of Osnabrück, Otto von Guericke University Magdeburg, the Studienstiftung des deutschen Volkes (German National Academic Foundation), Deutscher Akademischer Austauschdienst (German Academic Exchange Service, DAAD) and the Heinrich Böll Stiftung (Heinrich Böll Foundation)

Figure 1 Design of ProFile Survey

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

The contact data undergo duplicate checks before they are imported into the panel database. The actual micro-data are then collected via a bilingual online survey hosted at DZHW. Survey languages are German and English. Due to the complexity of the data acquisition and specifics of the university system in Germany, it is possible that respondents have already completed their doctoral degree when they are invited to the ProFile survey for the first time. This is assessed within the survey.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Preliminary remark on scales used in the surveys

Many of the questions in the questionnaire are assessed on a five point Likert Scale with an adequate wording. There are few exceptions to this rule. Some questions ask for (non-) applicability via a checkbox and a couple of questions provide the possibility to indicate a so called don't know, or not applicable option in addition to the five point Likert scale. Usually only the first and last choice options of the scales are labelled.

Description of variables/indicators

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, DZHW), Berlin, Germany

Table 1 lists the questionnaire topics. The questionnaire has remained rather unchanged over the years 2009-2012. In 2013 revisions were made and additional blocks were incorporated into the questionnaire. What follows below is a more detailed description of the topics covered in the questionnaire.

Table 1 Questionnaire topics

Assessment of current dissertation status
Interruptions
Educational biography of respondents
Current dissertation attempt
Retrospective information on the doctorate
Information on successful completion of the doctorate
Job search during doctoral candidacy
Structural doctoral program (Graduate School, Research Training Group)
Scientific output
Research stays abroad
Supervision during the doctorate
Courses offered during the doctorate
Financing of the doctorate
Vocational goals and aspirations
Personality
Skills and abilities
Socio-demographics

Assessment of current dissertation status

The initial questionnaire section in every survey is dedicated to the current status of the dissertation endeavour. According to the choice made respondents are categorized into different groups:

- persons currently working on the dissertation (doctoral candidates)
- persons who have handed in their thesis and are waiting for final exam (doctoral candidates)
- persons who have currently interrupted the work on their dissertation (for at least two months, doctoral candidates)
- persons who have stopped working on their dissertation (drop outs)
- persons who graduated successfully (doctorate holders)

From 2013 on, it is also possible to indicate “I never intended to do a doctorate./I have not started to work on my dissertation yet.” These persons are immediately filtered to an exit page in the survey and do not receive any further questions in the questionnaire.

Interruptions

Persons who state to have currently interrupted work on their dissertation do receive detailed questions on reasons for interruption but are treated as doctoral candidates throughout the rest of the questionnaire. All persons (with the exception of dropouts) who do not state at the beginning of the questionnaire to have interrupted works on their dissertation at the moment are asked whether they have interrupted work on their dissertation in the last 12 months/during the course of the dissertation respectively. Reasons and duration are assessed in the same way as for those who have are current interrupters.

Educational biography of respondents

This section of the questionnaire deals with educational degrees which were obtained prior to the current dissertation endeavour. All respondents run through this section once. Emphasis is put on university degrees of which a maximum of two can be named. Information is gathered on grades, subjects, source of financial support during studies, name and location of the universities as well beginning and completion date. In addition, information is gathered on previous dissertations attempts, vocational training degrees and school exam (Abitur, the qualifying degree for university studies). In case of aborted dissertation attempts, the reasons are assessed. Information on degrees is filtered on applicability.

Current dissertation attempt

All doctoral candidates are asked at which university they intend to hand in their dissertation (name of university and country). The subject of the dissertation is captured by an open ends answer. The questionnaire asks for reasons for the beginning of the doctorate and the choice of the university, difficulties which had to be managed before starting the dissertation work, the institutional affiliation of the dissertation topic and the starting date of the works on the dissertation.

Retrospective information on the doctorate

Since doctorate holders do not run through the questionnaire section “current dissertation attempt” they receive targeted questions which they are asked to answer in retrospect. The items and questions are similar to those of the doctoral candidates. Subject of the dissertation, enrolment/registration as a student during the time of writing the dissertation, the institutional affiliation of the doctoral project are assessed. Moreover, reasons why a specific university was chosen are asked alongside the reasons for starting the work on the dissertation and difficulties which had to be managed before dissertation work. The beginning and end dates of the dissertation are assessed, where the completion date equivalent to the date of the final exam (and not the publication date of the doctoral thesis).

For the period of the doctoral degree, the range of courses offered and taken, information on supervision situation as well as the significant support persons are gathered. Retrospective assessments and perceived burdens are assessed, too.

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, DZHW), Berlin, Germany

Information on successful completion of the doctorate

Doctorate holders are asked detailed questions on the name of the university for their final exam, the type of dissertation (cumulative, which means a series of peer-reviewed articles versus a monograph), grade, thesis language and whether the thesis has been published already.

Job Search during doctoral candidacy

Doctorate holders and dropouts receive questions on job-search activities during candidacy. The source of job offers (personal networks vs. systematic search) as well branch of jobs are assessed.

Structured doctoral programme (Graduate School, Research Training Group)

Doctoral candidates are asked detailed questions about membership in doctoral programs. Membership duration as well as information on reasons to join and about the selection procedure is reported. Satisfaction with the organization of the selection procedure are asked if applicable.

Scientific output

Doctorate holders and doctoral candidates are asked about the magnitude and types of scientific output produced during their candidacy. This includes conference visits (with own contribution, poster, no contribution), research project proposals and publications (type and number). Status update surveys assess changes in the past 12 months.

Research stays abroad

Doctorate holders and doctoral candidates are asked whether they stayed abroad or in Germany for the purpose of research. Research stays are assessed repeatedly during candidacy in the status surveys. A more detailed purpose (field work, further education etc.), duration and location for each stay are assessed.

Supervision during the doctorate

Doctoral candidates are asked a variety of questions regarding their supervision. These questions are asked repeatedly throughout candidacy in order to gain detailed understanding of possible changes in the supervision situation throughout the candidacy. If a candidate indicates to have changed his supervisor in a status survey the reasons for the change are asked.

One block is concerned with the number of supervisors. Regarding the main supervisor (the person who supervises the candidate most intensively) a number of detailed questions are asked such as, whether the main supervisor is a professor lecturer, Post-Doc etc., whether the main supervisor is also the reviewer and whether doctoral agreements were made and, if so, of what content and type (written versus oral). Whether agreements hold or are broken is assessed as well. A number of items regarding expectations mentioned by the main supervisor are asked and doctoral candidates are asked to assess their main supervisor based on a number of items. The satisfaction with the supervision through the main supervisor as well as the supervision in general is reported.

Courses offered during the doctorate

Course visits are assessed for doctoral candidates and doctorate holders. Type of course, and required participation is assessed alongside an evaluation of the courses taken for the works

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, DZHW), Berlin, Germany

on the dissertation. Doctoral candidates are asked if they desire different course offers. Another section looks at different types of resources available to the doctoral candidates.

Financing of the doctorate

The section looks at the respondent's sources of financial income. Respondents are asked to list all their sources of income in chronological order. For each income source detailed questions are asked such as the scholarship providing organization in case of a scholarship or details regarding the occupational situation for periods of employment. For employment periods it was also asked whether there was a thematic connection between the job and the dissertation topic. Total household income is assessed in addition to the income generated through the respective income sources.

Vocational goals and aspirations

All respondents are asked about their future career plans. This includes the job aspired as well as an assessment of how well the respondents feel prepared for this job and how they perceive their career perspectives in general. Other questions ask how closely the respondents like to have their future career connected to certain activities such as research, teaching, management.

Personality traits

From 2009 to 2012 the questionnaire contained a series of items assessing domain specific control beliefs. The control beliefs were targeted to the situation of doctoral candidates and assessed how well the respondents believed they are able to influence the course of their doctorate by themselves. In 2013 items to assess the so called Big 5 personality traits were implemented.

Skills and abilities

A number of questions regarding key qualifications as well language skills are asked based on a self-assessment. The skills are assessed in the initial survey and in the survey after referral of the doctorate for those who are observed at least twice. Therefore, it is possible to assess change in skills over the course of the candidacy. Doctorate holders are asked which skills were required for the successful completion of their doctorate.

Socio-demographics

All respondents run through this section and are asked the following:

- gender
- parent's educational background
- marital status
- citizenship and country of birth
- children and number of persons in the household

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Classification of research fields / subject areas

German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, DZHW), Berlin, Germany

ProFile makes use of a range of classification schemes for a number of different topics. First, the classifications of research fields used in ProFile are the classification scheme of the German Statistical Office (DESTATIS Studienbereiche) and the Subject Classification of DFG (DFG Subject Areas). ProFile includes doctoral candidates and doctorate holders from all research fields. Only Medicine is covered to a lesser extent which is due to the specifics of the German doctoral degree in Medicine.

Temporal coverage

Data collection in ProFile started in 2009. The persons surveyed in the first survey have started the work on their dissertation partially way before 2009 but there are a few individuals with a candidacy much longer than that. Starting from the second year of partnership with the university or funding organisation the partner provided only the contact data of the new doctoral candidates for the specific year. ProFile therefore looks every year at the cohort of newly beginning doctoral candidates. All doctoral candidates are invited to the yearly status survey until they indicate that they have obtained their doctoral degree or that they have dropped out from their doctoral candidacy without obtaining the degree (dropping out from doctoral training).

Geographical coverage

Geographical coverage is limited to doctoral candidates with supervisors at German universities regardless of their place of residence.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

Representativity of data with regard to the population of doctoral candidates in Germany

As there is no official data on the number of doctoral candidates in Germany, it can hardly be assessed how accurately the ProFile data represents the general population of doctoral candidates in Germany. ProFile therefore does not claim to be a representative sample of doctoral candidates in Germany. However, due to the large range of partners ProFile does include all types of doctoral candidates in Germany ranging from stipends, scientific employees at universities to so called external doctoral candidates, e. g. those working on their degree in industry. ProFile regularly checks how well the sample generated from the survey represents the total population of doctoral candidates at the partnering organisations in terms of subject area, gender and age, because this information is provided by the partners. What can be found there is that women are slightly overrepresented in the survey data when compared to their share at the respective university/funding organisation. The differences in the share of subject areas in the sample and at the institution (total population) are small. With the exception of Medicine, (see comment under 2.4) all subject areas are represented in ProFile. Therefore, the ProFile data are not biased systematically in terms of gender and subject area from the

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known total population at the partnering organisations. Comparisons with the few existing data (estimates and enrolment data⁶) have revealed good coverage so far.

Another method of ensuring data quality is a sophisticated duplicate check management tool. Since it is theoretically possible (and in fact observed in reality) that one and the same doctoral candidate is reported from two different organisations, e.g. one university and one funding organisation, extensive duplicate checks are applied to the data at import. These duplicate checks make sure that the same person is not invited twice to the ProFile survey.

Not all doctoral candidates are observed repeatedly over the course of their candidacy. If one candidate skipped one status update survey he/she will be invited to the next survey.

Response rates

Response rates differ substantially between the types of organisation providing the data. Stipends from foundations are more likely to participate in the survey than doctoral candidates reported from universities. All persons receive up to three reminders to participate in the survey before the survey is closed.

Documentation of missing values

The number of missing values depends on the type of missing values. Types of missing values include the following types:

- item-non-response due to not answering the question,
- item non response due to filtered (skipped) questions,
- item non-response due to technical error,
- item non response due to earlier drop out of the questionnaire,
- item non response due to “don’t know” answer or
- unit non-response in follow up studies.

⁶ Since enrollment for doctoral candidacy is not mandatory this data is biased in favor of educational migrants for whom enrollment is usually expected as proof by their funding organizations.

Report on the content and technical structure of the **SIPER** Infrastructure

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Report on the content and technical structure of the *SIPER* infrastructure (Task 6 of WP6)

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1 Basic characteristics

- SIPER (the Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository) is a database consisting of two main components:
 - an on-line **repository** of evaluation reports (in pdf format) relating to innovation and science policy instruments; and
 - a structured **searchable database** of information relating to the characterisation of the reports and their related content.
- The aim of the database is twofold: to provide on-line access to a unique collection of policy evaluation reports, located at a single location; and to provide an informed analysis of the database contents in a way that is both searchable for policy makers and other stakeholders and provides the basis for additional academic analysis.
- The holding authority is the University of Manchester (UNIMAN), Manchester Institute of Innovation Research (MIOIR)
- The database is located on University of Manchester servers and will be available on-line only (opening date November 2016) – no on-site access will be provided as this will not be necessary.
- The database interface has three sections:
 - SIPER Admin: a password controlled access site used by core SIPER Team members ('super-users') for the overall administration and management of SIPER. Other members of the SIPER Team and external data coders have limited access to certain functions for the upload of documents and data characterisation (FC) input.
 - SIPER (PM) site: Limited access site (password controlled) for data entry on specific judgemental characterisations (JC) of selected evaluation reports – open to policy makers on an invitation-only basis.
 - SIPER Public site: This site offers access to the repository of evaluation reports and provides a searchable interface based on the database of evaluation characterisations. Any evaluation reports located through the search process are downloadable in pdf format.

2 Information on substantive content of SIPER

2.1 Definition and description of observations

- The principle unit of analysis of SIPER are Evaluation Reports relating to publicly funded Science and Innovation support programmes.
- Each evaluation report is subject to a characterisation process which results in the production of a number variables each with one or more associated values
- Observations relate mainly to English-language evaluations but are also supplemented by those in French, Spanish, Portuguese and German where relevant.
- The number of observations is estimated at 700 (June 2016) but an initial target of 1,000 is envisaged by early 2017.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

- Evaluation reports relating to publicly funded Science and Innovation support schemes have been located mainly from publicly accessible web-sites, generally those relating to ministries, government agencies and agencies, national and supra-national organisations, and leading evaluation practitioners.
- The reports have been located through a range of targeted on-line search procedures, supplemented by previously identified reports available to the project team and from personal contacts.
- The data have been retrieved from publicly available evaluation reports, published since 2000, although earlier 'seminal' evaluations may be included on a selective basis. Since SIPER is a 'live' database, data retrieval is an ongoing process and newly published evaluation reports are being continually added.
- Additional data (evaluation reports) have been provided through negotiated access to:
 - OECD evaluation reports
 - DG RTD and DG REGIO evaluation reports
 - Over 145 Austrian evaluation reports¹
 - A research group led by Prof. Sergio Salles-Filho and Dr. Adriana Bin from UNICAMP (São Paulo, Brazil) have been rolling out their work with the SIPER core team since May 2016².
- No data cleaning of these reports is required (other than the conversion of documents in Word format to pdf).
- Data processing consists of a process of in-house analysis and the characterisation of evaluation report contents.
 - Each evaluation retrieved and stored in the repository is read by a member of the internal SIPER Team.
 - It is then characterised (coded) according to a data entry template (see Annex 1a) housed on the SIPER Admin site.
 - The coding is entered directly via the SIPER Admin site into the SIPER databaseThe overall flowchart for processing an evaluation report through the characterisation procedure is shown in Annex 2.
- All SIPER Team members are experienced evaluators and have familiarity with the range of evaluation concepts and terminology; thus, where external assistance is used for data coding (for example, in the case of non-English language evaluation reports), an extensive training process is employed to ensure consistency and common understanding. Random checks on coded data are also conducted by a member of the SIPER core team.
- Despite the shared experience of the SIPER team, a quality control process was introduced in order to ensure that there was minimal variation in the data characterisation process and to enhance mutual understanding. This involved the parallel coding of a number of evaluation reports by the entire team, comparison of the outputs, follow-up team discussion of any coding discrepancies and agreement on future coding protocols. Three iterations of this process were performed.

¹ See Section 6 Stakeholder relations.

² See Section 6 Stakeholder relations.

- The above process is applied to any coders providing external assistance.
- To assist in the process of coding, a Guidance Manual has been produced (see Annex 3).
- An initial assessment of Judgemental Characteristics is made in-house. Policy makers having a direct connection with the programme that forms the subject of the evaluation report are then invited to provide external validation of the information and to provide additional information on the use and uptake of the report. The data collection template relating to this process is provided in Annex 1b.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

- The data collection template is provided in Annex 1a³. The data observations/characterisations fall into a number of variable types and sub-types, namely:
 - General Report information
 - Respondent information
 - About the policy measure being evaluated: Information on the corresponding policy measure: a novel typology of policy measures has been developed building upon previous typologies which cover innovation-support measures and extending to the area of science programmes. The categorisation is multi-dimensional (i.e. reflects modality, target, policy issue and other pertinent variables) – (See Annex 4)
 - Information on the evaluation
 - Basic characteristics of the evaluation
 - Topics covered: Aspects of the programme covered by the evaluation
 - Evaluation design: design approaches employed for the evaluation
 - Data Collection Methods: Methodologies employed to collect the basic evaluation evidence/information
 - Data Analysis Methods: Methodologies employed to analyse the data collected
 - Dissemination: Judgemental Characterisation information input by SIPER Team and validated by relevant Policy Makers
 - Quality issues: Judgemental Characterisation information input by SIPER Team and validated by relevant Policy Makers
 - Impact of the evaluation: Judgemental Characterisation information provided by relevant Policy Makers
 - Comments
- These are more fully elaborated below to indicate the nature of the variables and indicators.

³ Note that the template in the working version of SIPER exists as a web-based input format only. Those reproduced in Annex 1a and Annex 1b are based on a temporary solution, using the on-line survey software package Qualtrics, for gathering coded data whilst the database and administrative interface were under development.

FC data characterisation

- **Respondent information:** *Full name (free text)*
- **About the policy measure being evaluated:**
 - *Title in English – free text*
 - *Title in native language – free text*
 - *Country policy measure belongs to – drop down selection*
 - *Options for multiple countries – free text*
 - *Options for Supranational Bodies – free text*
 - *Target (beneficiary) of support (10 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Modality (how support is provided) – (7 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Explicit policy objectives (why support is provided) – 15 options; non-exclusive)*
- **Information on the evaluation**
 - *Title in English – free text*
 - *Title in native language – free text*
 - *Country evaluation belongs to – drop down selection*
 - *Options for multiple countries – free text*
 - *Options for Supranational Bodies – free text*
 - *Year of first publication – drop down selection*
 - *Evaluation code – unique identifier allocated by administrator*
- **Basic characteristics of the evaluation**
 - *Who conducted the evaluation? – (4 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Timing of the evaluation (4 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Purpose of evaluation (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Does evaluation refer to programme logic/intervention rationale? (3 options; exclusive)*
- **Topics covered:**
 - *Aspects of the programme examined by the evaluation (19 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Option for Quality of outputs; (binary)*
 - *Option for geographical scope of outcomes/impacts (binary)*
 - *Options for geographical level (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for type of impact/effects (6 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for unintended effects (binary)*
 - *Options for additionality (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for sectoral nature of collaboration (4 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for geographical scope of collaboration (4 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for form of collaboration (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for type of mobility (3 options; non-exclusive)*
- **Evaluation design:**
 - *Type of design approaches employed for the evaluation (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for type of quasi-experimental design (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Did evaluation involve comparison between evaluated measure and similar measures? (binary)*
 - *Did evaluation include benchmarking against outcomes of previous phases/evaluations of the measure? (binary)*
- **Data Collection Methods:**
 - *Which data collection methods were employed? (12 options; binary selection)*
 - *Options for type of existing databases/monitoring data (3 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for types of survey used (7 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Options for type of interviews used (7 options; non-exclusive)*

Ctd.

Ctd. from previous page.

- **Data Analysis Methods:**
 - *Which data analysis methods were used? (9 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Option for use of citation analysis of IP data (binary)*
 - *Option for use of citation analysis of publications data (binary)*
 - *Options for type of altmetrics data used (freetext)*
- **Quality issues:**
 - *Did the report refer to objectives of the measure evaluated?*
 - *Did the report clearly state evaluation objectives?*
 - *Assessment of choice and balance of methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment on the evaluation design and implementation of the chosen methodology (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of information sources used in the report (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of analysis presented in the report (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of appropriate coverage of broader context (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of appropriate application of the chosen qualitative methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of appropriate application of the chosen quantitative methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of conclusions and recommendations (sliding scale, 1-100)*

JC data characterisation

- **Dissemination:**
 - *Publication or release date (earliest) of the evaluation report*
 - *Availability of Evaluation Report (7 options – non-exclusive; free text input available on 2 options)*
 - *Was evaluation conducted as a condition of external/international (co)sponsorship? (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Did the policy measure have a dedicated budget for evaluation? (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *What prompted this evaluation? (7 options; non-exclusive)*
- **Quality issues:**
 - *Role of PM in this programme (4 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Did the report clearly refer to the objectives of the measure/programme evaluated? (binary)*
 - *Did the report clearly state the evaluation objectives? (binary)*
 - *Assessment of choice and balance of methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of treatment of evaluation design and methodology (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of information sources used (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of presented analysis (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of coverage of broader context (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of appropriate application of chosen qualitative methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of appropriate application of chosen quantitative methods (sliding scale, 1-100)*
 - *Assessment of conclusions and recommendations (sliding scale, 1-100)*
- **Use of evaluation:**
 - *Did the evaluation report contain any recommendations? (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Was the evaluation intended to be used to inform decision making on the following aspects?*
 - *Design of programme/measure (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Management and implementation of programme/measure (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Termination of measure/programme (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Extension/continuation of measure/programme (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Merger with other measure/programme (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Design of subsequent measures/programmes (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Other attributes/purposes (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Were any actions taken as a result of the evaluation?*
 - *Design of programme/measure (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Management and implementation of programme/measure (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Termination of measure/programme (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Extension/continuation of measure/programme (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Merger with other measure/programme (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Design of subsequent measures/programmes (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *Other attributes/purposes (5 options; exclusive)*
 - *[Conditional question] What was the reason that the evaluation was not subsequently used for the purpose for which it was initially intended? (4 options; exclusive plus free text)*
 - *Who were the primary intended users of the evaluation? (6 options – max 3 selectable)*
 - *Stages of the evaluation in which the primary intended users were actively engaged (5 options; non-exclusive)*
 - *Did evaluation help deepen understanding and knowledge of programme and its effects?*
 - *Understanding and knowledge of this policy measure*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation findings (sliding scale; useful – not useful)*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation process (sliding scale; useful - not useful)*
 - *Understanding and knowledge of STI policies in general*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation findings (sliding scale; useful – not useful)*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation process (sliding scale; useful - not useful)*

Ctd.

Ctd. from previous page.

- *Did evaluation help other groups of stakeholders deepen understanding and knowledge of programme and its effects?*
 - *Understanding and knowledge of this policy measure*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation findings (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation process (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Understanding and knowledge of STI policies in general*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation findings (3 options; exclusive)*
 - *Usefulness of evaluation process (3 options; exclusive)*
- **Comments:** *(free text)*

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

- Information on the sectorial classifications used:
 - A classification scheme for science and innovation policy measures has been developed (see Annex 4).
 - Minimal sectorial data is collected – please refer to Annex 1 to view broad level classifications applied. [None are based on or utilise standard classification systems such as SIC coding]
- Information on the temporal coverage used: The database covers evaluation reports that have been published from 2000 to the present date.
- Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used: A complete set of World countries is utilised as drop-down options. These cover: EU-member states and non-EU countries. No regional data classification has been utilised.

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

- Information on the number of missing values: At this stage, as the database has not gone live, this estimate is not quantifiable.
 - We anticipate that the FC data will not include any missing values since it is input in-house.
 - Should the Policy Maker pilot prove successful, there is a risk that data may include some missing values. However, this is a remediable situation.
- Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system: This is not a relevant issue with the in-house produced data.
- To date, some 700 evaluation reports have been located and are stored in electronic format (pdf).
- We cannot assess the total population of evaluation reports (a target of 1,000 has been set for early 2017); the aim is to continue the collection and coding of reports on an ongoing basis, subject to the continuation of resources.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

- Legal issues concerning access of the database:
 - Although the data has been accessed from public web-sites, in order to adhere to any confidentiality and copyright restrictions, all data displayed in the public site is accompanied by a disclaimer which allows the owner of any report to withdraw it from the SIPER public site provided valid reasons for doing so are provided.
- Owner of raw data:
 - The evaluation reports (electronic format) remain the property of the original publishers or the authors. However, since all are sourced from public sites, they are in theory in the public domain (see disclaimer note above)
 - MIOIR (University of Manchester) retains the right to the characterised/coded data and information derived from the analysis of the evaluation reports. However, it is fully recognised that this is publicly accessible data.
 - Data collected via the Policy Maker characterisation process is obtained under the condition that it retains its anonymity. We are investigating ways in which this may be opened to public use whilst retaining anonymity.
- Current practice for opening up of the database to external users:
 - None (not operational as yet);
 - Opening of the Public website is planned for November 2016.
- Legal necessities for potential opening procedures:
 - None are foreseen other than the provision of a disclaimer over the use and provenance of evaluation reports (see box).

Disclaimer (Public Website)

All evaluation documents have been retrieved from public domain sources. Any users of the SIPER repository should adhere to the relevant source terms and conditions of use, as stated on the source website and/or within the document itself. Any concerns over the use of these documents should be communicated to: superuser.siper@manchester.ac.uk.

4. Technical summary of SIPER

4.1 Information on the database system

- The application is written with MVC4/.Net 4.5. JavaScript / JQuery are also used.
- The application's databases are hosted on the server QLDef.dbs.ds.man.ac.uk, 6503 (SQL Server 2012).
- There are four web applications for the project, technical details explained below:
 - Part A, SiperPortalBasic:
This is basic data gathering tool, available for a limited number of users restricted to the SIPER project team. It offers the basic data gathering

facilities for user to enter certain project data, full details can be seen in the specification for the tool – “P00418a – SiperPortalBasic”. This application was only used as a temporary tool during phase 1, and was not authenticated. The functionalities are covered in the full version of the admin tool (Part B) – see Annex 5.

- Part B, SiperPortalAdmin:
The full version of the SIPER Portal admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the SIPER project team. It is protected by the University’s Central Authentication Service (CAS). The application offers facilities for researchers to administer project data. Full details are covered in the specification “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.
- Part C, SiperPM:
An authenticated site with restricted access available to the external stakeholders (Policy Makers, or PMs), to enable them to work on authorised parts of the project data. This is protected by the application’s own authentication system. Full details are covered in the specification – “P00418c – SiperPortalPM”.
- Part D, SiperPortalPublic:
A public site with searching functionality, accessible to public users and which allows them to search the project data. Full details are covered in the specification – “P00418d – SiperPortalPublic”.

4.2 Technical variable definition

- Labelling of all variables: finalized
- Data type of all variables: varied, details as follows:
 - Integer: for example, DataStageId and PrecedingDataStageCode
 - Nvarchar: for example, QuestionText and PLTitleFor more details about data types please see Appendix 7 – Data table details – v5.1
- Current usage and definition of unique identifiers: Unique Identifiers are automatically generated through the Admin site as researchers upload evaluations onto the system.

4.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model of SIPER (if applicable)

- There are two main tables: evaluations and policy measures. Evaluations include a number of evaluation characteristics; policy measures include a number of policy measure characteristics. These two tables will be linked in a many-to-many relationship (as there are evaluations covering multiple policy measures and there are policy measures that have been evaluated multiple times).

The overall data schema for SIPER is provided below:

5 Further planning of the opening of SIPER

- Identification and collection of further evaluation reports will be undertaken through Summer 2016 and onwards, in liaison with OECD and EC officials, with French and Austrian colleagues and with colleagues from UNICAMP, University de Campinas, Sao Paulo, Brazil.
- In parallel, internal searching for additional reports will be continued in-house.
- Ongoing coding and characterisation of new reports will also be ongoing. Since the production of evaluation reports is an ongoing process, this will continue through the lifetime of SIPER in order to make it a fully comprehensive and up-to-date resource. It is also likely that additional older reports will also be located, especially as we extend the geographic range of the search process.
- We will undertake a pilot of the Policy Maker Judgemental Characterisation process to test the robustness and associated resource costs of this procedure. This will take place Summer 2016 using selected policy makers.
- A 'soft launch' of public version of the facility is anticipated to take place in the European Evaluation Conference in Vienna in November 2016.
- We anticipate that some preliminary findings will be available for presentation at the RISIS week 2017.

6 Stakeholder relations

- Throughout the development of SIPER, a large degree of interest in its future use and implications has been expressed by a number of external stakeholders who have recognised its high visibility and potential, both as a policy tool and as an academic resource.
- Significant interest has stemmed from the OECD, who together with the World Bank are extremely keen to capitalise on the work done on SIPER and to integrate it, in some form or other, with the OECD's Innovation Policy Platform (IPP - <https://www.innovationpolicyplatform.org/>).
- Extensive discussions around this issue have taken place, via phone and in face to face meetings in Paris and Washington. These are ongoing but it is clear that some sort of inclusion of SIPER within the IPP will take place (either through an embedded link in the IPP to the SIPER website or, if technically feasible, through an interactive link between the two resources).
- Interest has also been shown from staff at the DG RTD Joint Research Centre, IPTS – Innovation Systems Analysis Unit. Discussions here have focused on the potential inclusion/linkage of SIPER (particularly the repository of evaluations) in the Research and Innovation Observatory facility (located at: <https://rio.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en>). Activities so far include the exchange of collected evaluation reports between the SIPER team and JRC/IPTS.
- DG RTD staff engaged with the Policy Support Facility Mutual Learning Exercise (PSF/MLE) have also expressed interest in the future accessibility of SIPER. A brief presentation of SIPER was made at the kick-off meeting of the PSF/MLE on the Evaluation of Direct Measures for the Support of R&D which prompted significant interest from policy makers from Denmark, Spain, Norway, Germany and Sweden.

- The SIPER team has started a co-operation with Klaus Schuch, who is President of the Austrian Evaluation Platform. This platform systematically collects all evaluations in Austria and many international evaluations. It is also a network of practitioners and academics including members outside Austria, with a journal and regular workshops. The platform is organising, for the second time in 3 years, an evaluation conference in Vienna (together with IFRIS, Paris, and MIOIR, Manchester), the second one taking place end of November (<https://conference.zsi.at/index.php/OPENEVAL/OPENEVAL2016>).

The platform has made available to us all evaluations conducted in Austria within our time window. This has provided access to over 145 evaluations from Austria, by far the largest contingent of all countries so far. The platform is very interested to support us beyond the collections of the evaluations. We have thus been in discussions to mobilise additional resources through the platform, and had mobilised a PhD student in Austria to help us code the evaluations. However, the career plan of this person has changed and we are now trying to find additional support for and in Austria.
- The SIPER database will be officially announced and launched in the November conference Open Evaluation, thus targeting academics, valuation practitioners and policy makers in equal measure. In addition, as the conference is organised alongside an early career researcher's conference financed by EU SPRI and co-organised by ZSI (Klaus Schuch), IFRIS and MIOIR, we will also involve the next generation in this.
- The research group from UNICAMP (São Paulo, Brazil) have been developing their work with the SIPER core team since May 2016. The team in Brazil (is composed of 2 senior academics, 2 doctoral student assistants with support from junior assistants. The Brazilian partner aims to cover 6 countries (Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Argentina, Uruguay and Mexico); the potential coverage of Spain and Portugal will depend on resources available. The immediate deliverable from the Brazilian partner is an initial list of Latin American evaluations with reflections on issues emerging. They are also working on getting contact details of policy makers. The team has applied for funding from FAPESP (São Paulo Research Foundation) to enable doctoral assistants to come to Manchester in late 2016 for training and exchange; however our training process has already started, and is not constrained by site visits. We keep quality control as a top priority during this collaboration process. We use a comprehensive package of manuals and protocols to streamline training and coding. We also attempt to ensure that the number of people who actually characterize evaluations is minimal to reduce variation. We use a standard inter-coder reliability testing process which involves the newly recruited coders working on evaluations previously characterized by the SIPER core team. We then seek to align their conceptual understandings with ours through this process. We do not impose any time pressure to achieve large quantities, rather we aim to be systematic, expanding the coverage of SIPER in a solid and steady way. All evaluation reports and, where available, associated documentation (Executive Summaries, Annexes, etc.) are uploaded into the SIPER Portal and stored in pdf format in the on-line repository via the SIPER Admin site.

7 Annexes

7.1 Annex 1a: SIPER Evaluation Report (Policy Measure and Factual Characterisation) template

SIPER PL+FC 20151118.pdf

7.2 Annex 1b: SIPER Evaluation Report (Policy Maker Judgemental Characterisation) template

SIPER JC 20151103 .pdf

7.3 Annex 2: SIPER Data coding procedure flowchart

7.4 Annex 3: SIPER Coder manual

(see following pages)

SIPER Coder Manual

Version 1.0

1 Purpose of this Manual

This Manual is intended to provide guidance and assistance to persons involved in carrying out coding tasks associated with the SIPER database (Project Associates, PAs). These coding tasks relate to the characterisation of reports that present the results of evaluations of publicly funded policy measures, instruments and programmes intended to support research, technological development and innovation (RDTI) activities targeted either at the public or private sectors.

It begins with a short description of the SIPER project. This is followed by a more detailed explanation of the processes used to collect relevant evaluation reports and to extract the relevant data from these reports. It then presents a detailed explanation and definition of the core concepts and terminology employed in the data characterisation template. Finally, a glossary of key words and terms is provided.

2 SIPER: brief explanation

The SIPER database has four types of data:

1. Policy measure characterisation (PL): a basic three layer classification of the related policy- measures (according to the typology above). This will be filled in by project associates (PAs).
2. Basic information: evaluation title, author, language, country, related files etc.
3. Factual Characterisation (FC): characteristics that can be inferred from evaluation reports themselves (methods, timing, topics, etc.). This will be filled in by PAs. These characteristics will be fully open to the public (i.e. files will be searchable against most of them and they will be displayed on the web, possible linked to IPP).
4. Judgemental Characterisation (JC): subjective issues such as quality, use, consequences, dissemination, etc. This will be filled in by policy-makers (PM) who were responsible for the measure evaluated. For data integrity reasons, PAs will separately input data for quality and at a later stage we will compare them with PMs' judgements. We will not make JC data publicly available for various reasons, but we will use it for academic research.

This data structure is reflected in our database as follows:

- Part A, SiperPortalBasic – This is the tool for inputting "basic information" on evaluations and storing related files. This is operational at the moment.
- Part B, SiperPortalAdmin – The full version of the SIPERPortal admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the SIPERproject team. This tool will enable us to input policy measure characterisations and factual characterisations (see above). There will also be a workflow management system (assigning tasks to different users, contacting policy-makers and inviting them to fill in the JC).
- The SiperPortalPublic: (This will be implemented in early 2016, specs are in development)
- Part C: A public site with searching facilities, for public users to search the project data.

- Part D: An authenticated sub-site –SiperPortalPM, with the access restricted to the external stakeholders (PMs). This is the interface to which PMs input judgemental characterisation.

3 Evaluation Collection Process

The project aims (in the long term) to include all evaluations of science and innovation policy programmes conducted after 2000 from around the world. The medium term objective is to reach a target figure of around two thousand documents. These will include evaluations in major languages.

To achieve this, we use a three step search strategy to identify those evaluations to be included in SIPER.

Figure 1: A three-step approach to searching evaluations for SIPER

Figure 2 on the next page displays in more detail the third step of this search process.

Step 3 searching evaluations for SIPER through individual country agencies

4 Data Collection Process

Once an evaluation report has been collected, the next step is to ‘characterise’ the factual information it contains (i.e. relating to timing of the evaluation, topics covered, methods used, recommendations reported, etc.). Information is also captured regarding the related policy measure to which the evaluation refers (target group, modality, objectives, country, etc.). Both types of information are obtained through completion of an on-line characterisation template. The aim is to construct a database of these variables that will be searchable by external users. This factual information is augmented by a further ‘judgemental’ characterisation. This is elicited from policy makers (programme managers, etc.) who are connected to or familiar with the evaluation and/or the relevant policy/programme. Again, an on-line characterisation template is used to collect this data which concerns aspects of the evaluation quality, use and dissemination, etc. This latter judgemental information is collected on a confidential basis and is used solely for the purposes of academic research.

The next section is organised along the lines of the characterisation templates and provides detailed explanations of the core concepts and terminology used along with guidelines for the completion of the characterisation templates.

5 Definition of core concepts: Guidance on completing the template

This section is organised along the lines of the data characterisation template and follows the structure of the online input process.

It aims to provide a comprehensive, yet brief, set of definitions and explanations, accompanied by examples as required.

Part 1: About the Policy Measure being evaluated

This section seeks information on some basic characteristics of the measure or programme that is being evaluated in the report under consideration. Please note that all information entered on the template must be derived from the evaluation report itself – please do not make assumptions about any aspects of the programme that are not directly reported by the report authors, even if you are aware such additional information. With the possible exception of the first question (the name of the policy measure/programme in English) we are interested solely in the content of the evaluation report itself.

In the following list of questions, a preceding “*” indicates that the questions is conditional, i.e. it will only appear in the on-line template if a certain answer has been given in a preceding question.

PL0.1 What is the title in English of the policy measure being evaluated?

For those evaluation reports that use languages other than English, please give the name of the policy measure/programme that is being evaluated in English. Note that this question refers to the name of the programme or measure being evaluated, NOT the title of the Evaluation Report itself.

PL0.2 What is the title in the Native Language of the policy measure being evaluated? If the native language is English, please put in the English title again.

For those evaluation reports that use languages other than English, please give the name of the policy measure/programme that is being evaluated in its original language. As above, please note that this question refers to the name of the programme or measure being evaluated, NOT the title of the Evaluation Report itself.

[PL0.3 Please select which country the policy measure belongs to \(if it belongs to more than one country, please select 'Multiple Countries' at the bottom of the list; if it belongs to a supranational body such as the European Commission, please select 'Supranational Bodies' at the bottom of the list\).](#)

This question refers to the country in which the policy measure or programme is managed and administrated – i.e. the country in which the ‘owner(s)’ of the measure is/are located. For example, a cross-border programme may be operated by a single agency located in one country or by several agencies in coordination.

[*PL0.3.1 Your answer to question PL0.3 is 'Multiple Countries'. Which countries does this policy measure belong to? Please specify below, using a semicolon to separate different countries. For example, if the policy measure belongs to Finland and Sweden, please input 'Finland; Sweden'.](#)

Please refer to the instructions for Question PL0.3 above. Do not enter the countries in which the measure/programme is implemented unless these correspond to the location of the managing agencies.

[*PL0.3.2 Your answer to question PL0.3 is 'Supranational Bodies'. Which supranational body/bodies does this policy measure belong to? Please specify below, using a semicolon to separate different supranational bodies. For example, if the policy measure belongs to OECD and EU, please input 'OECD; EU'.](#)

Please refer to the instructions for Question PL0.3 above. It is unlikely that a policy measure/programme will belong to more than one supra-national body although this may be the case for some programmes such those operated jointly by the World Bank and UN agencies, for example.

PL1 Targets (Beneficiary of the support) (Please tick all options that apply)

Here we refer to the primary beneficiary of the monetary or non-monetary supports, rather than broader beneficiaries who benefit indirectly from the measure. The ‘target’ also reflects the goal of the policy – for example, mobility programmes will target individuals although the funding (or other support) will probably be allocated to and administered by a university department. As another example, a research grant or a scholarship can be applied for by an individual researcher but the money is administered (received and accounted for) by their host institution. In addition, such an award is intended to benefit the individual as a component of the wider institution – in these cases both ‘individual’ and ‘Universities’ can be ticked. Similarly, whilst individual managers may apply for grants, tax relief, etc., this action is generally on behalf of the firm they work for rather than for themselves as individuals.

The available options are (multiple answers are allowed):

- 1.1 Individuals (researcher, student, manager, entrepreneur, investor, etc.):** these are the targets of the policy support
- 1.2 Universities (including sub-departments and component institutions):**
- 1.3 Research Organisations (including the full spectrum from public (Public Research Organisations) to private (Research and Technological Organisations)):**
- 1.4 Public organisations (governmental or quasigovernmental agencies, policy making organisations – not directly involved in R&D):** These could include bodies whose activities include the allocation of funding for RTDI activities but which do not perform such activities themselves.
- 1.5 Intermediaries (such as science parks, business incubators, technology parks, knowledge brokers, TTOs, etc.):**
- 1.6 Firms (SMEs focused):** This includes measures that specifically, but not necessarily exclusively, target SMEs
- 1.7 Firms (no size-specific focus):** This includes measures that do not make any distinction between the size of firms that they are intended to support.

- 1.8 **Other funding organisations (NGOs, NPIs, Not-for-Profit, Charities.):**
- 1.9 **Specific industrial sector targeted:** Some measures/programmes often restrict their target to a single or small group of related sectors. Examples might include measures focusing on biotechnology, IT, energy or nanotechnology applications.
- 1.10 **Specific S&T field targeted:** Examples here would reflect either areas of academic or translational research and technology fields with multiple industrial applications, and could include social science research, or areas such as photonics.

PL2 Modalities (How support is provided) (Please tick all options that apply)

There are a number ways that measures and programmes may be delivered. Here we ask to select from a number of options (multiple options may be ticked):

- 2.1 **Direct financial support: grants, loans, guarantees, contracts, etc.:**
- 2.2 **Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.:** Although fellowships are generally provided in the form of a grant, we make a distinction since fellowships often comprise a broader package of support.
- 2.3 **Direct financial support: (non-project specific) institutional block grants including large centres:** These are institutionally-targeted grant support intended to stimulate or maintain specific types of RTDI activities. Generally, the recipient institution has some degree of autonomy over how the support is utilised.
- 2.4 **Indirect financial support: (tax & fiscal incentives (e.g. R&D credits):** support is not given for specific projects, but for a certain type of activity, mostly research and development. The support is not given as a grant or loan, but as a reduction of the tax burden of a company.
- 2.5 **Infrastructure support (e.g. provision of access to and construction/upgrading of research infrastructure):** This can include large-scale infrastructure construction or provision, capital support or equipment grants.
- 2.6 **Non-financial support (e.g. training, coordination and advisory/information support/provision):** This includes any type of support that does not rely on the direct provision of finance (or on financial off-setting). This option refers to the main form of support, it should not be ticked if such support is provided as a minor or subsidiary element of a larger programme of support).
- 2.7 **Prizes and awards (ex ante inducement, ex post performance recognition, etc.):** These include recognition and financial rewards intended to stimulate research and innovation on certain topics (with specified targets) or recognition and financial rewards intended to confer acknowledgment of past achievements.

PL3 Explicit policy objectives (Why the support is provided) (Please tick all options that apply)

The third dimension of our policy typology is defined by the primary policy goals that are intended to be met by the measure/programme. While measures and programmes, particularly those in support of innovation, may have a number of indirect outcomes and impact a number of policy objectives, we are interested only in the main explicit objectives addressed by the measure. Again, multiple options may be selected.

- 3.1 **Enhancement of education and initial/further training:** This includes measures that aim to improve the level and capacity of all forms of education and training, both in the public sector and in the private sector.
- 3.2 **Facilitating personnel mobility:** This can include both inter-sectoral mobility and international mobility, including short term (travel grants) or long term (fellowships, etc.).
- 3.3 **Internationalisation of research, technological development and innovation (RTDI) activities:** Examples could include international collaboration programmes, personnel mobility schemes (see above also), large-scale facility sharing, multi-national research programmes, etc.)

- 3.4 Awareness raising and promotion of public acceptance:** Measures intended to promote public understanding of S&T and also to stimulate public acceptance and demand for new technologies, etc.
- 3.5 Strengthening/improving research management practices:** Measures intended to develop and improve management capacities, either through managerial skills training or similar approaches.
- 3.6 Improving capabilities and capacity (including absorptive capacity):** This includes measures intended to strengthen the RDTI capabilities and capacities of the recipient entities, through developing skill-sets, developing RDTI experience, accessing additional staff and/or equipment, etc.
- 3.7 Supporting collaborative interactions for the production of new knowledge and/or innovation (including project focused approaches, some types of innovation vouchers, etc.):** These include measures that explicitly focus on the objective of developing collaborative RDTI activities with a significant element of joint knowledge production and/or exchange. Thus, the provision of services alone would not be relevant.
- 3.8 Supporting broader (multiple) interactions (e.g. through clusters or networks):** Measures intended to develop collaboration and knowledge exchange on a wider (geographical or virtual) extent than those included in 3.7., including multiple parties.
- 3.9 Supporting the protection of IP:** Any measures aimed at protecting IP, increasing awareness about the protection of IP and improving confidence in the production and use of IP.
- 3.10 Mobilising additional (non-public) financing for innovation (e.g. support of business angels, VCTs, equity schemes, etc.):** Schemes or measures intended to improve access to finance for the support of RTDI-related activities and purposes. Such finance can be provided from private (corporate or individual investment sources) but should involve some form of public support either in the form of administration and awareness raising or through the provision of incentives to investors (matched funding, tax breaks, etc.).
- 3.11 Stimulation of additional RTDI activity (e.g. increasing R&D expenditures):** This includes measures intended to stimulate input additionality on the part of the recipients, rather than simply 'buying' research and innovation activities, although it can arise through the recruitment of additional staff or the purchase of new infrastructure.
- 3.12 Strengthening the quality of RTDI activities (promotion of excellence):** These include programmes and measures intended to improve the quality of research and innovation, for instance based on criteria of excellence.
- 3.13 Creating new RTDI capacity (e.g. new organisations, start-ups, technology-based companies, etc.):** This concerns the creation of new entities rather than the expansion of existing facilities, staff, etc.
- 3.14 Generation or diffusion of innovation targeting the demand for innovation or the interaction between demand and supply (e.g. programmes to support public procurement of innovation, demand subsidies for innovation and awareness raising measures):**
- 3.15 To support priority setting (e.g. foresight exercises):** This can include any measures intended to assist in the identification of RDTI priority areas/topics, such as horizon scanning, which typically, but not exclusively, involve the input of stakeholders.

Section 0: Information of the Evaluation

0.1 What is the title in English of the evaluation?

Many of the evaluation reports that will be included in SIPER are published in their national language and are often unavailable in English. However, here we would like an English translation of the title of the Evaluation report.

0.2 What is the title in the Native Language of the evaluation? If the native language is English, please put in the English title again.

If the evaluation report is not published in English, please give the title of the evaluation report in its original native language.

[0.3 Please select which country the evaluation belongs to](#) (if it belongs to more than one country, please select 'Multiple Countries' at the bottom of the list; if it belongs to a supranational body such as the European Commission, please select 'Supranational Bodies' at the bottom of the list).

This question refers to the country in which the evaluation report was commissioned. Note that this may differ from the country in which the measure or programme is managed and administrated. For example, a cross-border programme may be evaluated by an agency in one of the countries in which it is implemented: an example is the impact evaluations of the EU Framework Programmes which are often commissioned by a single national government.

[*0.3.1 Your answer to question PL0.3 is 'Multiple Countries'. Which countries does this evaluation belong to?](#) Please specify below, using a semicolon to separate different countries. For example, if the evaluation belongs to Finland and Sweden, please input 'Finland; Sweden'. Please refer to the instructions for Question 0.3 above. Do not enter the countries in which the measure/programme is implemented unless these correspond to the location of the country commissioning the evaluation.

[*0.3.2 Your answer to question PL0.3 is 'Supranational Bodies'. Which supranational body/bodies does this evaluation belong to?](#) Please specify below, using a semicolon to separate different supranational bodies. For example, if the evaluation belongs to OECD and EU, please input 'OECD; EU'. Please refer to the instructions for Question 0.3 above. This answer corresponds to the body/bodies responsible for commissioning the evaluation.

0.4 Year of first publication:

Please give the year in which the evaluation report was first published.

0.5 Please put down the code of the evaluation if known.

For example, the evaluation titled as 'Evaluation of the Austrian Industrial Research Promotion Fund (FFF) and the Austrian Science Fund (FWF)' has been automatically coded by SiperPortalBasic as E_AT_0003, then you should put down 'E_AT_0003' below. If you don't know the evaluation code, please ignore this question (it will be allocated a code at a later date).

Section 1: Basic Characteristics

This section refers to some basic information about the evaluation.

1.1 Who conducted the evaluation? (Please tick all options that apply)

Note that several of these options may apply to a single evaluation, although such instances are uncommon.

a. Internal to programme: The evaluation was conducted by the agency responsible for the management/and or administration of the programme or measure.

b. External to programme (within government, including court of auditors): The evaluation was conducted by a body or unit not connected with the management or administration of the programme or measure. For example, some government departments have internal audit or evaluation units which undertake evaluations of programme run by their parent ministry.

c. External to programme and government ('independent'): Typically, this would include evaluations conducted by external consultancies or specialised evaluation bodies in the private or academic sectors.

d. Not specified in the report: The report does not state by whom the evaluation was conducted.

1.2 What was the timing of the evaluation? (Please tick only one option)

a. Ex ante (before the implementation of the measure/programme): The evaluation (sometimes referred to as 'ex ante assessment') was conducted at some point prior to the implementation of the programme or measure, typically during the design or planning phase.

b. Accompanying (on a permanent or repetitive basis during the implementation of the measure/programme): Accompanying evaluations tend to be performed on a frequent or even continuous basis to provide more or less constant support throughout the programme lifetime. They often focus on specific aspects of the measure's performance (for example, management, uptake, etc.).

c. Interim (periodic "ex post", after a specified phase during the implementation of the measure/programme): Interim evaluations tend to be held at specific points in the lifetime of the programme or measure. Many programmes that do not have fixed lifetimes are subject to interim evaluations, typically every few years.

d. Ex post final (after the lifetime of the measure): These may be conducted immediately or after some time following the end of a measure/programme that has a fixed lifetime.

1.3 What was the purpose of the evaluation? (Please tick all options that apply)

a. Summative (descriptive, judgemental): Summative evaluations (also known as impact evaluations) are judgemental and establish the effects of programmes, the difference made on the target group or beyond.

b. Formative (developmental, supporting): Formative evaluations ask how, why, and under what conditions does a policy instrument work, or fail to work? They typically seek information on the contextual factors, management practices, mechanisms and processes underlying success or failure, and their main purpose is to support learning during the programme.

c. Other (please specify):

1.4 Does the evaluation refer to the programme logic or its intervention rationale? (Please tick only one option)

All measures and programmes should be informed and guided by an underlying reasoning for their introduction, which is often based on an identified "failure" or gap in the system. Sometimes, the design of a programme or measure is informed by the creation of a logic chart which sets out to unpack the theoretical or logical sequence by which a policy intervention is expected to bring about its desired effects. Some evaluations may re-visit the original design process of the programme/measure and reproduce or re-construct the logic chart which sets out the objectives, aims, activities, results, outputs, impacts and effects anticipated from the measure. Other evaluations may re-state the original objectives of the measure and describe precisely how the measure was designed and implemented in order to deliver these. Please note: your answer should be based on what is explicitly reported in the evaluation report itself – not on what you may know about the programme or measure being evaluated.

a. Yes, fully – it clearly refers to the rationale for its development and identifies the way in which the intervention achieves the stated objectives (e.g. by using a logic chart model): Here, the evaluation report will clearly explain the underlying rationale for the establishment of the programme or measure – why it was set up, what issues it set out to address together with its stated expected objectives and effects, and it will make explicit the way in which the effects will be achieved.

b. Yes, partially – it refers in a broad sense to the original rationale for establishing the programme/measure: Here, the evaluation report will refer to the underlying rationale of the programme or measure in a less detailed manner, for example "to address a shortfall in the provision of seed funding to SMEs" or "to stimulate collaboration between the university and private sectors" but with no explanation of how the measure/programme was intended to address these problems. It will also not be very explicit in explaining the steps with which the intervention will achieve its aims.

c. No: There is no reference in the evaluation report to the underlying rationale of the measure.

Section 2: Topics Covered

2.1 Which aspect of the programme did the evaluation examine? Please select 'yes' only when the aspect is explicitly evident in the actual report. For each row please make one choice.

On which aspects of the programme did the evaluation provide evidence? In this case, the word 'examine' means not just providing numbers or giving a brief statement or mention of the topic – the topic should be discussed within the text, and should involve an element of in-depth analysis.

2.1.1: Appropriateness of the underlying programme rationale of the measure (does the evaluation examine if the programme is appropriate for the failure or need it addresses?): Further to Q1.4 above, does the evaluation examine and present evidence regarding the appropriateness of a failure or need that the programme or measure being evaluated addresses – i.e. does it test the programme with regard to its underlying rationale and its specific context?

2.1.2 Appropriateness of goals (does the evaluation examine if the measure's goals were appropriate and consistent with the external challenges the measure was meant to address?): Developing on the above issue, the goals of the measure or programme being evaluated should align with the external challenges that it was intended to address: does the evaluation provide any evidence on this consistency?

2.1.3 Appropriateness of design/modality of the measure (does the evaluation examine whether the design/modality of the measure was appropriate to achieve the stated goals?): Again following the above logic, the design/modality of a measure/programme should be appropriate to achieve its stated goals: does the evaluation provide any evidence of how the programme or measure's design was consistent with its intended goals? In order to answer "yes", the design of the measures should be examined against the achieved stated goals; it is not enough just to name them or compare them together.

2.1.4 Coherence/complementarity (does the evaluation examine whether the measure was coherent with, and complementary to, other programmes and policy initiatives?): Measures and programmes frequently exist in a broader suite of similar or complementary policy instruments which may address the same or partially overlapping goals/objectives and/or target groups. Does the evaluation report present any evidence on whether the measure was coherent with, and complementary to, any other co-existing programmes and policy initiatives?

2.1.5 Goal attainment/effectiveness (does the evaluation examine whether the goals of the measure were achieved?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the achievement of the intended goals of the programme or measure being evaluated?

2.1.6 Outputs (does the evaluation examine the direct, immediate results of the measure?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the outputs and results of the measure or programme being evaluated?

***2.1.6.1 Quality of outputs: In Question 2.1.6, you have indicated that this evaluation provides evidence on outputs. Does the evaluation examine whether the outputs of projects were of a high quality?:** The report should explicitly examine the issue of quality of outputs using some criteria or metrics for any justification – qualitative assessments made by interviewees or survey respondents would satisfy this requirement whereas an unsupported statement that the outputs were of high quality would not.

2.1.7 Outcomes and impacts (does the evaluation examine the effects and consequences of the policy measure? Impacts imply a longer term and broader form of effect): Further along the timeline of a measure/programme, this question seeks to assess whether the evaluation report examines (and presents

evidence on) its effects and consequences. In this context, impacts imply a longer term and broader form of effect.

***2.1.7.1 In Question 2.1.7, you have indicated that this evaluation provides evidence on outcomes and impacts. Does the evaluation examine the geographical scope of outcomes and impacts?:** Does the evaluation report present evidence on and make comparisons about the geographical scope of any of its outcomes and impacts?

***2.1.7.2 In Question 2.1.7.1, you have indicated that this evaluation examines the geographical scope of outcomes and impacts. At what geographical level(s)?:** Please indicate the appropriate geographic level to which the evidence on outcomes and impacts relates to. Regional refers to the sub-national level and supra-national refers to outcomes and impacts across several countries. For example, an evaluation of an EU-supported measure might be expected to have impacts across the entire EU.

***2.1.7.3 In Question 2.1.7, you have indicated that this evaluation provides evidence on outcomes and impacts. Does the evaluation examine the following impacts/effects? (Please tick all options that apply):** Impacts and effects may take several forms; they may be restricted to scientific and technological effects or may have wider impacts. The scope of these impacts will be dependent on the nature of the measure/programme itself. In addition, these impacts may be felt at several levels from the individual, at the organisational level or across an entire scientific area or technological sector. Please remember we are seeking to find out if the evaluation report presented evidence of the impacts and effects of the measure/programme on these various areas.

***2.1.7.4 In Question 2.1.7, you have indicated that this evaluation provides evidence on outcomes and impacts. Does the evaluation examine unintended impacts/effects?:** In addition to the expected or desired impacts and effects, programmes and measures may have unintended impacts and effects (regardless if they were in line with the policy goals, i.e. desirable, or not. Did the evaluation present evidence and discuss any of these? A brief mention of any potential outcomes and impacts would not count as evidence.

2.1.8 Value for money/return on investment/cost-benefit efficiency (does the evaluation examine if there were adequate returns on investment?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) whether there were adequate returns on investment, for example in terms of representing value for money, return on investment (ROI) or cost-benefit efficiencies?

2.1.9 Programme implementation efficiency (does the evaluation examine if the measure was well managed and administered?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) whether the measure was well and cost-effectively managed and administered?

2.1.10 Additionality (does the evaluation examine the issue of input, output or behavioural additionality?) (Note: the evaluation may use alternative terms for additionality such as 'incrementality', 'added-value', 'return on investment', 'persistent behavioural change', etc.): Additionality is the change that can be attributed to the existence of the measure or programme, i.e. what the additional effect of the programme is, as compared to what would have happened in its absence. Three forms of additionality are generally examined: input, output or behavioural additionality. See below for a description of each of these terms.

***2.1.10.1 In question 2.1.10, you have indicated that the evaluation examines issues of additionality. Which type(s) of additionality does the evaluation examine? (Please tick all options that apply):**

a. Input additionality (e.g. does the evaluation report examine if the measure stimulated more investment in RTDI than would have occurred in the absence of the measure?)

b. Output additionality (e.g. does the evaluation report examine if the measure stimulated more RTDI outputs than would have occurred in the absence of the measure?)

c. Behaviourial additionality (e.g. does the evaluation report examine if the measure stimulated persistent changes in the behaviours of the participants that would have not occurred in the absence of the measure?)

2.1.11 Policy/strategy development (does the evaluation examine any implications for future strategy development and policy formulation?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present any evidence for) implications for future strategy development and policy formulation? This may be reflected in the evaluation's recommendations (if present) but we are trying to assess if any evidence on which such recommendation can be based is presented in the report.

2.1.12 Gender issues (does the evaluation examine gender issues?): Does the evaluation report present and discuss any evidence that is of relevance to gender issues?

2.1.13 Minority/inclusivity issues (does the evaluation examine minority/inclusivity issues?): Does the evaluation report present and discuss any evidence that is of relevance to minority or inclusivity issues?

2.1.14 Uptake of programme (does the evaluation examine the extent to which the programme attracted applicants? For example, the success rate of applications, the response rate from applicants, etc.): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the extent to which the programme attracted applicants?

2.1.15 Degree of satisfaction of stakeholders (does the evaluation examine the extent to which the policy satisfied stakeholders' needs/expectations?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the extent to which the policy measure/programme satisfied or met the needs and or expectations of stakeholders?

2.1.16 Collaboration/partnership (does the evaluation examine the issue of collaboration and/or partnerships? e.g. the performance of joint research projects.): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the issue of collaboration and/or partnerships? This may not be a relevant issue for all programmes and measures, however.

***2.1.16.1 In question 2.1.16, you have indicated that the evaluation examines the issues of collaboration/partnership. What was the sectoral nature of collaboration/partnership examined (the following options include both individual level and organisational level collaboration/partnership)? Please tick all options that apply:** Note that we regard collaboration as an inter-organisational phenomenon in this question, although the collaboration may take place between individuals located in those organisations. Options are (and multiple options may apply):

a. Firm-Firm: i.e. between private sector entities alone

b. Non-Firm (universities, research organisations and third sector organisations etc.) –Firm: i.e. between a firm and, generally speaking, a public sector, or not-for-profit entity or entities.

c. NonFirm–NonFirm (universities, research organisations and third sector organisations etc.): i.e. between public sector or not-for-profit sector organisations alone.

d. Not specified in the report: No mention is made in the report of the types of entities involved.

***2.1.16.2 In question 2.1.16, you have indicated that the evaluation examines the issues of collaboration/partnership. What geographical level of the collaboration/partnership does the evaluation examine? Please tick all options that apply:** At what level does the collaboration examined in the report take place – between actors within a region, between actors at the national level or between actors in different countries (international)?

***2.1.16.3 In question 2.1.16, you have indicated that the evaluation examines the issues of collaboration/partnership. What forms of collaboration/partnership does the evaluation examine? (Please tick all options that apply):** Does the evidence on collaboration that is presented in the report relate only to interactions between two parties (i.e. bilateral relationships) or between more than two parties (multi-lateral relationships)? For example, a ‘twinning’ programme linking pairs of firms would examine bilateral relationships, while a networking programme would involve multilateral relationships.

2.1.17 Mobility (does the evaluation examine the issue of mobility of personnel?): Does the evaluation report examine (and present evidence on) the issue of mobility of personnel? In this context, mobility may apply to international movement, inter-sectoral movement (e.g. public sector to private sector, or vice versa) or movement between institutions, for example.

***2.1.17.1 In question 2.1.17, you have indicated that the evaluation examines the issues of mobility. What scope of mobility does the evaluation examine? (Please tick all options that apply):** We wish to know at what level does the mobility examined occur, i.e. at the national level only (movement within a single country) or at the international level (movement across national borders)?

2.1.18 Career (does the evaluation report examine the issue of career development/progression?): Are the effects of the programme or measure on the (research) careers of the participants examined and discussed in the report?

2.1.19 Networking (does the evaluation examine the issue of networking? e.g. the creation of virtual communities, e-platforms, workshops, information dissemination channels.): Networking may form a specific objective of the programme or measure being evaluated, although it may often arise as an unintended consequence. Is any evidence of this presented and analysed/discussed in the report?

Section 3: Evaluation Design

3.1 Which type(s) of design approach did the evaluation employ? (Please tick all options that apply):

a. Experimental: Experimental research methods provide evidence about the relative effectiveness of a policy intervention compared with other policy interventions, or doing nothing at all (e.g. the counterfactual). They may utilise two samples (an experimental group and a non-experimental (i.e. control) group) to attempt to isolate the effects of participation in the policy or programme under investigation.

b. Quasi-experimental: Quasi-experimental methods include research designs that compare the outcomes of experimental and control groups by methods other than randomisation. These include: controlled before and after designs (pre-test and post-test comparisons) using either a single group of samples or two or more groups of samples; interrupted time series studies (based on repeated observations over time of valid and reliable standardised measures of outcome); various types of matching designs using matched comparisons of individuals or units before and after an intervention; regression discontinuity designs.

c. Nonexperimental: Non-experimental methods can include in-depth interviews, observational methods, participant observation and ethnography.

***3.1.1 In question 3.1, you have indicated that a quasi-experimental design approach has been employed. Please specify which of the following approaches were used. (Please tick all options that apply):**

a. Before/after comparison: Before/after comparisons involve the comparison of data from the same sample at two separate periods in time.

b. Comparison/control groups: Comparison or control group methods involve comparisons of data from a sample of supported actors/organisations and a sample of actors/organisations that are as similar to the supported group as possible, but have not been supported.

c. Beneficiary self-reporting on the counter-factual (what would have happened in the absence of the programme, etc.):

Beneficiary self-reporting is a more subjective approach which involves asking the recipient/target of the measure what would have happened in the absence of the programme – e.g. if funding had not been received.

3.2 Did the evaluation include comparison between the evaluated measure and similar measures?:

Some evaluations may compare or benchmark the performance of the measure, or aspects of its performance, against similar or comparable measures in operation in the same country or in other countries. Here we mean some form of analytical comparison or in-depth examination between the specific elements and characteristics of the programme/measure and similar measures, rather than a trivial reference to other programmes or measures.

3.3 Did the evaluation include benchmarking against the outcomes of previous phases/evaluations of the measure/programme?:

If previous evaluations of the measure or programme have been conducted or if monitoring data exists, the evaluation may benchmark its results against these to provide some sort of comparison over time. This is often the case for interim evaluations of programmes/measures with long lifetimes. Again, we refer here to thorough discussions/examinations of the comparison data/information rather than simplistic descriptions.

Section 4: Data Collection Methods

4.1 According to the report, which data collection methods and data sources were employed in the evaluation?:

Evaluations may employ several methodologies and approaches to collect data and related information on the programme or measure. We have identified the main approaches and sources below, but other approaches may also be used and we have provided space for these to be added in free text format. Note that this series of questions does not concern the quality of the methods employed, we will investigate this aspect in Section 6, here we are interested only in whether these approaches are reported in the evaluation report.

4.1.1: Existing databases and monitoring data (and Q4.1.1.1): This may include monitoring data collected internally through the implementation period of the programme/measure and/or existing external databases (e.g. the Science Citation Index).

***4.1.1.1 In question 4.1.1, you have indicated that existing databases and monitoring data have been employed. What types of existing databases and monitoring data were employed? (Please tick all options that apply):**

a. Existing internal databases and monitoring data: These would include data collected and maintained by the programme management, often for administrative purposes but beyond simple details such as participant names and contact details.

b. Existing external databases and monitoring data: These would include databases such as those covering publications, e.g. PubMed, Science Citation Index and Patent Office data files.

c. Not specified in the report:

4.1.2 Surveys (and Q4.1.2.1): These include all forms of survey, e.g. on-line, emailed, postal or face-to-face questionnaires. The latter typically employ largely closed (yes/no, multiple choice, etc.) questions, whereas interview pro-formas typically use a high proportion of open questions.

***4.1.2.1 In question 4.1.2, you have indicated that surveys have been employed. What types of surveys were employed? (Please tick all options that apply):**

a. Participants (e.g. programme beneficiaries, those in receipt of support):

b. Non-participants: Those that did not participate (regardless if they applied or not).

c. Unsuccessful Applicants: Those who applied for support but were unsuccessful. This is a subgroup of b).

d. Non-applicants (i.e. members of target group that did not apply): In some cases the report may identify non participants that have not applied. This would be a subgroup of b0 above..

e. Stakeholders directly linked with the programme (e.g. representatives from organizations funding, owning, and managing the policy measures):

f. Other parties/stakeholders (e.g. associations, representatives of comparative programmes, initiatives, context experts and politicians) Please specify: Typically these will not be directly linked to the programme or measure.

g. Not specified in the report:

4.1.3 Interviews (and Q4.1.3.1): These may be conducted via a range of media, e.g. face to face, telephone, Skype, etc.

***4.1.3.1 In question 4.1.3, you have indicated that interviews have been employed. Who were the interviewees? (Please tick all options that apply):**

a. Participants (e.g. programme beneficiaries, those in receipt of support):

b. Non-participants: Those that did not participate and did not apply for support. In some cases it may not be known whether non-participants were also unsuccessful applicants.

c. Unsuccessful Applicants: Those who applied for support but were unsuccessful for a range of reasons.

d. Non-applicants (i.e. members of target group that did not apply): Although these may be the same as group b. Non-applicants, it may be possible in some cases to distinguish those from the target group that actively chose not to apply for support/participate.

e. Stakeholders directly linked with the programme (e.g. representatives from organizations funding, owning, and managing the policy measures):

f. Other parties/stakeholders (e.g. associations, representatives of comparative programmes, initiatives, context experts and politicians) Please specify: Typically these will not be directly linked to the programme or measure.

g. Not specified in the report:

4.1.4 Focus groups/workshops/meetings: These can be used to collect a broad range of qualitative information and also to stimulate discussion and debate to investigate a range of issues and perspectives concerning the programme/measure. They generally involve groups of participants or stakeholders in a moderated discussion.

4.1.5 Peer reviews (including stakeholder reviews): The use of peer opinion is a frequently employed evaluation process, although it is predominantly used in ex ante assessment. Similarly, stakeholders may also be approached for their opinions on the performance and other aspects of a programme or measure. Peer reviews may be conducted using interviews or surveys of individual peer reviewers, or collectively with a peer review panel.

4.1.6 Formalised data on intellectual property (patents, including other related sources such as copyrights, trademarks, utility models, etc.): This type of data collection refers to the capture of codified information on manifestations of intellectual property arising from the programme or measure.

4.1.7 Publications data: This typically, covers scientific and academic publications, but may also include grey literature, reports and other outputs. In this instance, we distinguish it from patent data, which is covered under Q4.1.6 above.

4.1.8 Altmetrics data (twitter, download statistics, etc.): A more novel approach to utilising bibliometric data and information on social interactions, altmetrics looks at a range of data sources derived from on-line social media.

4.1.9 Curriculum Vitae (CV) data: Important data may be derived from the CVs of programme participants, for example, in tracking career development profiles.

4.1.10 Longitudinal/tracking data collection methods/sources: These approaches involve collecting information either from monitoring data or through ex post surveys and interviews to determine the effects of the programme or measure on career progression or on long-term company performances, for example.

4.1.11 Site visits: These are generally employed in the evaluation of institutions or scientific facilities. They involve an intensive analysis by a team of knowledgeable peers and/or stakeholders often carried out over a period of several days, during which staff and management will be interviewed individually or collectively.

4.1.12 Other data collection methods/sources (please specify): We may have omitted other types of data collection approaches, in which case please provide an example as a free text entry.

Section 5: Data Analysis Methods

5.1: Which data analysis methods/approaches were used in the evaluation?

Here we are only interested in approaches that were employed in the evaluation and which are explicitly described in the evaluation report. References to approaches and methods used in preceding or similar evaluations should not be included.

5.1.1 Case study analysis: Case studies are typically undertaken to provide in-depth analysis of processes and outcomes. They are used to provide detailed examinations of a particular instance of the phenomenon under investigation. They may focus on a particular aspect of the programme or measure, such as a specific project, or on a specific firm or institution impacted by the programme or measure. Generally they focus on a restricted number of participants or beneficiaries. They typically involve a number of data collection methods, but tend to focus on qualitative methods such as document analysis and interviews.

5.1.2 Network analysis: This is an approach that aims to map the social interaction between the subjects of an evaluation including the beneficiaries – e.g. those receiving a grant.

5.1.3 Econometric analysis: This involves the use of techniques drawing on advanced statistical methods such as regression analysis, instrumental variables and Heckman style selection models, or advanced economic modelling approaches in order to ascertain the influence of programme variables (as independent variable, such as a grant or a provision of advice) on a dependent variable (such as change increase of sales with novel products).

5.1.4 Descriptive statistics: These are approaches that use basic descriptive statistics, quantitatively describing and analysing the main features of a collection of information related to the programme to analyse the data (such as uptake analysis, i.e. the extent to which target beneficiaries have taken up the support provided by a programme or support measure). In contrast to inferential statistics, descriptive statistics do not analyse how one variable (e.g. number of firms participating) influence another one (overall economic benefit).

5.1.5 Input/output, cost/benefit, return on investment analysis: These are methods used to characterise economic activity triggered or enhanced by the intervention in a given time period, and to predict the reaction of a programme beneficiary (typically a firm) to stimulation. Basically they compare the input to the participant or the cost to the policy provider (i.e. the grant award, for example) to the economic outcomes arising from participation. Terms such as ‘leveraging’ and ‘gearing’ may be used.

5.1.6 Intellectual property (IP) data analysis: These are techniques which use IP data, such as patent statistics, as the unit of analysis in a range of statistical analyses and models, including technometric approaches. Citation analysis may also be applied to patent data.

***5.1.6.1 In question 5.1.6, you have indicated that IP data analysis has been employed. Did the IP analysis include an analysis of citations?** Citations of patent data may be used as a proxy indicator of the quality or extent of impact of the patent information.

5.1.7 Publications data analysis: These techniques utilise data on published outcomes (generally arising from the participants in a programme or measure). Typically such data includes scientific or academic journal articles although other forms of published outputs may be used. Such approaches include bibliometric techniques such as publication counting and citation analysis.

***5.1.7.1 In question 5.1.7, you have indicated that publications data analysis has been employed. Did the publications data analysis include an analysis of citations?** Citation analysis is a frequently employed technique used to provide an indication of the quality or impact of publications.

5.1.8 Altmetrics data analysis: As noted above, this is a more novel approach to using bibliometric data and information on social interactions and examines a range of data sources derived from on-line social media.

***5.1.8.1 In question 5.1.8, you have indicated that Altmetrics data analysis (twitter, downloads statistics, etc.) has been employed. Please specify:** As this is a relatively new form of data analysis, we are interested in the specific type of altmetrics approach employed.

5.1.9 Qualitative or quantitative analysis of texts: Again a new form of analysis, this approach uses automated text searching algorithms to identify interesting textual content and text associations. It is often referred to as ‘text-mining’.

Section 6: Quality Issues

In this section we are interested in your more subjective view of various aspects of the evaluation report and the approaches used. Please note that, as in the preceding sections, we are only interested in aspects and characteristics of the evaluation that have been explicitly mentioned in the report itself.

6.1 Did the report clearly refer to the objectives of the measure/programme evaluated?

In framing an evaluation and the issues it is intended to address, it is often useful to explicitly refer to the objectives that the measure or programme was expected to achieve as these provide a point of reference for the subsequent data collection and analysis process.

6.2 Did the report clearly state the evaluation objectives?

Similarly, the objectives of the evaluation may not entirely match all of the aspects of the programme or measure being evaluated. It may only address a sub-set of programme activities or issues, a restricted set of programme participants or a specific time frame of the programme lifecycle. We are only interested in those objectives that are explicitly mentioned in the evaluation report.

6.3 To what extent do you agree/disagree with the following statements?

Here we are asking for your subjective judgement of a series of questions concerning aspects of the evaluation as reported in the evaluation report. The on-line version employs a series of sliders and values along the scale correspond to the extent to which you agree/disagree with the specific question. As a rule of thumb, the scale can be divided into 20 point intervals, where:

- 0 = completely disagree
- 20 = disagree
- 40 = tend to disagree more than agree
- 60 = tend to agree more than disagree
- 80 = agree to a large extent
- 100 =: completely agree.

Note that it is also to answer “not applicable”, should this issue not be relevant to the evaluation.

Also, please note that your judgement should be made in the context of the stated and explicit objectives of the report and the nature and context of the policy measure, including any resource constraints that the evaluation may have encountered. Does the report (or rather, the information it presents) meet the objectives of the evaluation? Overall, we are looking at the quality of the evaluation, given its particular context and not against an ideal benchmark that could have been achieved given infinite time and personnel resources.

6.3.1 The choice and balance of methods is appropriate given the stated objectives of the evaluation and the nature of the policy measure: According to the information presented in the evaluation report, was the selection of methods in the evaluation made in such a way that it was able to address the objectives and the nature of the policy measure or programme in an appropriate, comprehensive and satisfactory way?

6.3.2 The report reflects critically on the evaluation design and implementation of the chosen methodology, including consideration of its limitations: According to the information presented in the evaluation report, did the report provide a sound rationale for the design of the evaluation and the use of the methods employed. Did the report discuss or highlight any constraints or limitations that could have resulted (e.g. any inability to gain access to high-quality data)?

6.3.3 The information sources used in the report are well documented and referenced: Any information sources should be well referenced and details should be provided of their sources.

6.3.4 The analysis presented in the report was clearly based on the data obtained by the evaluation: There should be a clear and logical link between the quality and type of data obtained and the analytical approaches used and results obtained. The analyses described in the evaluation report should be clearly based on the data obtained by the evaluation collection methodologies.

6.3.5 Given the objectives of the evaluation, the analysis documented in the report covers the broader context (e.g. societal, institutional, policy and economic contexts) appropriately: Did the evaluation examine the broader societal, institutional, policy and economic contexts, etc. in an appropriate manner? Note that the specific objectives of the evaluation (if stated in the evaluation report) may have not necessitated or may have even excluded such a broader-based analysis, thus in which cases such an analysis would not be expected.

6.3.6 The application of the chosen qualitative methods is appropriate and satisfactory, given the purpose/objectives of the evaluation: Where qualitative methodologies were employed for data collection and data analysis, was their use appropriate to the types of information available and the specified objectives of the evaluation?

6.3.7 The application of the quantitative methods is appropriate and satisfactory, given the purpose/objectives of the evaluation: Where quantitative methodologies were employed for data collection and data analysis, was their use appropriate to the types of information available and the specified objectives of the evaluation?

6.3.8 The conclusions and recommendations are clearly based on the results of the evaluation analysis: The conclusions and recommendations of the evaluation (if provided) should be consistent with the results of the evaluation analyses. That is, the recommendations should be clearly drawn from and based on the outcomes of the data analysis.

Section 7: Comments

7.1 If you have any further comments, please write them in the box below. Thanks.

Please use this space to add any comments or questions you have regarding any of the above questions and issues address. This can include explanations of why you have selected a specific response, or anything that is unclear and requires further explanation from the SIPER team.

7.4 Annex 4: SIPER Policy Measure Typology

Science and Innovation Policy Measure Categorisation

1. Modalities (How support is provided)
1. Direct financial support: grants, loans, guarantees, contracts, etc.
2. Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.
3. Direct financial support: (non-project specific) institutional block grants
4. Indirect financial support: tax & fiscal incentives (e.g. R&D credits)
5. (Indirect financial support – norms, standards, regulations) NOT USED
6. Infrastructure support (e.g. provision of access to and construction/upgrading of research infrastructure)
7. Non-financial support (e.g. training ,coordination and advisory/information support/provision)
8. Prizes and awards (ex-ante inducement, ex-post performance recognition, etc.)
2. Targets (Recipient of the support)
1. Individuals (researcher, student, manager, entrepreneur, investor, etc.)
2. Universities (including sub-departments and institutions)
3. Research Organisations (including the spectrum from public (PROs) to private (RTOs))
4. Public organisations (governmental or quasi-governmental agencies, policy making organisations – not directly involved in R&D)
5. Intermediaries (such as science parks, business incubators, technology parks, knowledge brokers, TTOs, etc.)
6. Firms (SMEs focused)
7. Firms (no size-specific focus)
8. Other funding organisations (NGOs, NPIs, Not-for-Profit, Charities...)
9. Specific industrial sector targeted
10. Specific S&T field targeted
3. Policy objectives (Why the support is provided)
1. Enhancement of education and initial/further training
2. Facilitating personnel mobility (including career enhancement)
3. Internationalisation of RDTI activities
4. Awareness raising and promotion of public acceptance
5. Strengthening/improving research excellence, relevance and management practices
6. Improving absorptive capabilities and capacity
7. Supporting collaborative interactions for the production of new knowledge (including project focused approaches, innovation vouchers, etc.)
8. Supporting broader (multiple) interactions (e.g. through clusters or networks)
9. Supporting the protection of IP
10. Mobilising additional (non-public) financing for innovation (e.g. support of business angels, VCTs, equity schemes, etc.)
11. Stimulation of additional RDTI activity (e.g. increasing R&D expenditures)
12. Strengthening the quality of RDTI activities (promotion of excellence)
13. Creating new RDTI capacity (e.g. new organisations, start-ups, technology-based companies, etc.)
14. Diffusion of innovation (including creation or exploitation of new markets, public procurement of innovation)

7.5 Annex 5: SIPER Portal Basic Technical Specifications

(see next page)

HDT2014004a

SiperPortal (Basic)

Version 2.2

Revision History

Version	Date	Author(s) Reviewer Authoriser	Change description
1.0	06/11/2014	Theresa Teng	Initial version.
1.1	10/11/2014	Theresa Teng	Added in: Storage arrangement for uploaded documents: Put publishable and non-publishable ones in different folders in order to enable the University's GSA doing the text search only in publishable ones.
2.0	14/11/2014	Theresa Teng	Added in: Naming convention for uploaded documents: Language code will be used too. Clarifications on a few points.
2.1	18/11/2014	Theresa Teng	Modified: Evaluation details view, Upload document tab: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change the saving rule so user only needs to click one button to save the changes made to all documents. • Use icons for viewing and deleting action for individual document.
2.2	18/11/2014	Theresa Teng	Formatting/spelling changes only.

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1. Overview

SIPER stands for Science and Innovation Policy Evaluations Repository, which is a part of a larger scale multi-partner effort titled The Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS) project. SIPER’s objective is “to identify, collect, characterise evaluation reports and present them to wider stakeholders, and to conduct academic research by analysing these evaluations.”

The SIPER Portal project is required by the MBS’s SIPER team. The project’s requirements for producing web applications and databases for the project are covered in the specification for the SIPER Portal (HDT2014004 – SiperPortal).

There will be three web applications for the project:

- Part A, SiperPortal (Basic) – The basic data gathering tool, for small number of internal users in the Siper project team. It will offer the basic data gathering facilities for user to enter certain project data, full details can be seen in the specification for the tool – “HDT2014004a – SiperPortal (Basic)” (this document). This application will only be used as a temporary tool during phase 1, and will not be authenticated. The functionalities will be integrated into the full version of the admin tool (Part B) at later stage.
- Part B, SiperPortal (Admin) – The full version of the Siper admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the Siper project team. It will be protected by the University’s CAS. The application offers facilities for researcher to administrate project data. Full details will be covered in the specification – “HDT2014004 – SiperPortal”.
- The SiperPortal (Public), which has two main parts:
 - Part C – A public site in the project’s own domain(s), with searching facilities, for public user to search the project data.
 - Part D – An authenticated sub-site – SiperPortal (PM) – in the same public domain(s), with the access restricted to the external stakeholders (Policy Makers, or PMs), for them to work on certain authorized part of the project data. This will be protected by the application’s own authentication system.

Full details will also be covered in the specification – “HDT2014004 – SiperPortal”.

The development work will be carried out in phases (subject to review):

Phase	Description
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database for SiperPortal (Basic) • SiperPortal (Basic)
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Databases for SiperPortal (Admin) and SiperPortal (Public) • Key functionalities of SiperPortal (Admin) for evaluation data • SiperPortal (Public) site styles (static) • Authentication related functionalities of SiperPortal (PM)
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities of SiperPortal (PM) • Integration between SiperPortal (Admin) and SiperPortal (PM)
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities of SiperPortal (Public) • The rest of the functionalities for all applications

2. Assumptions for SiperPortal (Basic)

2.1. Data included in the basic tool's database ([HumSiperBasic]):

[HumSiperBasic] only contains a small subset of the full database, including the following tables. For more details of the database see the Technical Overview section (section 4).

- Pre-defined data that should be set up directly into the database in the required structure:
 - Country
 - DocCategory
 - DocLanguage
 - Status
 - Researcher
- Data to be entered by user in the application:
 - Document
 - Evaluation

The above tables are selected because these are needed to meet the minimum data gathering requirement, and to minimise the possible integration issues in the future.

2.2. Assumptions

The following assumptions are used in this application, and will be used in the later integration process:

- The application will only be used by very small number of users, and with no authentication.
- Evaluation's data in the scope:

The following data will be included for an evaluation in the application:

 - Title: Entered by user.
 - Publication year: Selected by user.
Note: This is a new requirement and will be added in the main database as well.
 - Country: Selected by user using the pre-defined data in [Country] table.
 - Code: Generated by the application with the same format as to be used in the full version of the admin tool. Full details in the relevant section below.
 - Status: This will be set to "New" and won't be changed, but the [Status] table will be used.
 - Documents uploaded: The pre-defined document category and language data (in [DocCategory] and [DocLanguage]) will be used, and more than 1 document can be uploaded.
 - Creator: In order to avoid future integration problem the real researcher data will be used for creator. However the researcher data must be entered into database directly.
- Data not included:
 - PL data, i.e. the questionnaire and usage in the evaluations.
 - FC/JC data, i.e. the questionnaire and characterisations.
 - PM data, i.e. the PM account and assignment.
 - Other supporting data, such as progress note (a manually maintained communication record between SU/PA/PM by the evaluation owner).

3. Functional overview

3.1. Evaluation list

Evaluation list is the starting point for evaluation functionalities.

a) Data on the page:

The evaluations will be displayed in a list with searching / sorting / paging facilities. Details included are

- Code
- Title
- Country
- Publication year
- Number of documents uploaded
- Creator name
- Creation date

The evaluation data is from the [Evaluation] table and other few tables in the database, including [Country], [Document] and [Researcher].

b) Actions available:

- Create new evaluation:
The [Create evaluation] button is available on evaluation list page, pointing to the creating evaluation page (section 3.2).
- Go to evaluation details page:
The evaluation code in the list will be a clickable link, pointing to the evaluation detail page (section 3.3).
- Searching / sorting / paging facilities:
The text entered in the search box will be used to filter the content in the list.
Click the head of a column will get the list sorted by that column.
Number of evaluations per page can be selected from a dropdown list.
Note: The mock page doesn't show the full details of these but they are available.
- Export the list **C**:
The [Export evaluation list] button is available for user to export the list into an Excel file.

Mock page:

The screenshot shows the SIPER Admin Tool interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with 'Evaluation' highlighted. Below the menu is a table titled 'Evaluation list' with the following data:

#	Code	Title	Country	Year	Doc.^v	Creator	Created on
1	E_GB_0001	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	United Kingdom	2011	3	Albus Dumbledore	10/10/2014
2	E_US_0005	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	USA	2010	1	Snape Severus	05/05/2014
3	E_BE_0025	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	Belgium	2013	1	Ron Weasley	25/11/2014

A yellow callout box with an arrow points to the table, containing the text: "Data table with searching/paging/sorting facilities".

3.2. Create new evaluation

This page will be displayed when [Create Evaluation] button on evaluation list page is clicked. It has the following functions:

- a) Get data for creating new evaluation. Minimum data requirement:
 - Evaluation title: Text, length range 1 to 255 characters.
 - Publication year: Selected from a year list.
 - Country: Selected from the [Country] list (220 countries in total, stored in the [Country] table in the database).
 - Document: One initial document must be uploaded. The publishable flag will be defaulted to false, the document category and language will be selected by user from the pre-defined [DocCategory] and [DocLanguage] tables in the database. See more details in 3.3.2 – Uploading document tab.
- b) Generate the rest of the data for the new evaluation:
 - Evaluation Id: For system use only.
 - Evaluation code:

This is unique which will be used as the identifier for evaluations. It's generated with a given format:
E_[2-letter country code]_[4-digit number]

The 2-letter country code is selected from the pre-defined country list; The 4-digit number will be incremented by 1 from the number in the code of the last evaluation from the same country.
Sample: E_GB_0001, E_GB_0056, E_BE_0005, E_CN_0040
 - Status: "New".
 - Researcher's Id who created the evaluation, and the creation date. Researcher's data (manually entered into database directly) is from [Researcher] table in the database.

Evaluation data will be saved into [Evaluation] table in the database, the related document data is saved in the [Document] table.

Note on uniqueness:

The system won't check whether a new evaluation is unique or not. SU will check it manually. However the existing evaluation list with some basic data will be displayed on the page, offering a chance for researcher to do some manual checking.

Mock page:

The screenshot displays the 'SIPER Admin Tool for Researchers' interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with options: Home, Evaluation (selected), Policy measure, Support data, Researcher acct, Policy maker acct, and Report. Below the menu, the 'Create new evaluation' form is visible, featuring input fields for Title, Country, and Publication year, a 'Doc to upload' section with a 'Browse' button, and dropdown menus for Category and Language. A 'Publishable' checkbox is also present. Below the form is a 'Create' button. The 'Existing evaluation list' table is shown below, with the following data:

#	Code	Title	Country	Year	Doc.^v	Creator	Created on
1	E_GB_0001	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	United Kingdom	2011	3	Albus Dumbledore	10/10/2014
2	E_US_0005	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	USA	2010	1	Snape Severus	05/05/2014
3	E_BE_0025	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	Belgium	2013	1	Ron Weasley	25/11/2014

A yellow callout box points to the table with the text: 'Data table with searching/paging/sorting facilities'. The page also includes a '(Standard footer here)' placeholder.

3.3. Evaluation details

Evaluation detail page acts as a dash board for functionalities related to a selected evaluation. A tab structure will be used in order to accommodate the multiple functionalities.

The following tabs will be available in SiperPortal (Admin), which group the functionalities for a selected evaluation:

- Basic data and action
- Upload document
- Policy measure
- Factual/judgemental characterisation

- Progress note

In SiperPortal (Basic), only the first two tabs will be enabled.

3.3.1. Basic data and action tab

This is the first tab to be displayed when the page is launched.

a) Data in the view:

- Data for information only:
 - Code
 - Publication year
 - Country
 - Creator and creation date
 - Last updater and updating date
- Data editable:
 - Title
 - Publication year
 - Remarks

b) Actions available:

- Change title
- Change publication year
- Add remarks

Mock page:

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'A Web Page' with the URL 'http://'. The page content is for the 'SIPER Admin Tool for Researchers'. At the top left is a 'University Logo' and at the top right is a user profile '(Researcher name) Logout'. A navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Evaluation' (highlighted), 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The main content area is titled '(Evaluation title for E_GB_0001)' with a 'Status: New' indicator. Below the title are five tabs: 'Basic data & action' (selected), 'Upload document', 'PL data', 'FC/JC data', and 'Progress note'. The 'Basic data' section contains the following fields:

- Evaluation code:** E_GB_0001
- Created by:** (Creator name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)
- Updated by:** (Updater name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)
- Country:** United Kingdom
- Title:** Title for E_GB_001
- Publication year:** Year list (dropdown menu)
- Remarks:** (Some remarks on the evaluation)

 An 'Update' button is located at the bottom of the form. A '(Standard footer here)' is visible at the bottom right of the page.

3.3.2. Upload document tab

a) Rules for uploading documents:

- PDF is the only acceptable format for documents to be uploaded.

- Document category and language must be selected when uploading. See below for more details.
- Publishable flag must be decided when uploading, indicating if the document can be made available on public site when the evaluation is published. The default value is false.
- A standard format will be used to name the uploaded documents:
[Evaluation code]_[Document category code]_[Document language code]_[2-digit number]
The number will be incremented by 1 from the last document's name for same evaluation and in same document category and language.
Sample names: E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01, E_CN_0025_AP_ZH_02.
- Uploaded documents will be stored in two designated areas on the site:
 - “_Docs_Publishable”, for publishable documents. Documents will be put into sub-folders named by the evaluation code. The folder and its sub-folders will be open to the University's GSA (Google Search Appliance) for text search.
 - “_Docs_NonPublishable”, for non-publishable documents. They will be organised by evaluation code as well. The folder won't be searchable for the University's GSA.
 - A few sample document names:
~_Docs_Publishable\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01.PDF
~_Docs_NonPublishable\E_GB_0005\E_GB_0005_AP_ZH_02.PDF

b) Document category and language:

The document category and language are stored in tables [DocCategory] and [DocLanguage] in the database.

The document category details are stored in table [DocCategory], as displayed below. The code will be used in the standard name for uploaded documents:

Category code	Category name
AP	Appendices
ES	Executive summary
MR	Main report
OT	Other
TR	Terms of reference

Language details are stored in table [DocLanguage], the code will also be used in the standard name for uploaded documents.

c) Actions available:

- Upload new documents:
 - Click [Browse] button to select a document to be uploaded from the local drive. Only PDF format is acceptable;
 - Select category, language, set publishable flag, and click [Upload] button to start uploading
 - A folder will be created (if not already existed) for the evaluation, named after the evaluation code;
 - The chosen file's name will be changed based on the naming convention, and saved in the relevant folder;
 - A record will also be saved in [Document] table in the database, together with uploader id and uploaded date.
- Change category, language and publishable flag for existing documents:

- In the existing document list, make changes for documents, and click [Save] button to save all the changes into [Document] table in the database.

- When a document's category and/or language are changed, the document name must be updated too to reflect the change, so is the path for the document. However the name change will only affect the document itself, not the other documents, i.e., the number part in the document names won't be changed. See the example below in "Remove document".

Example:

Old category:

Main report (code=MR), in English (code=EN)

Old path:

~\UploadedDocuments\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01.PDF

New category:

Executive summary (code=ES), in Chinese (code=ZH)

New path:

~\UploadedDocuments\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_ES_ZH_**.PDF

where ** will be the last E_GB_0001_ES_ZH-document's number plus 1.

- Other relevant details will also be saved, including uploader id and uploaded date.

- View document details:

- Click the [View] icon (an eye), the selected PDF document will be opened in a new tab.

- Note: This can be used for downloading single document.

- Remove document:

- When the [Delete] icon (a bin) is clicked the confirmation window will appear for user to confirm the action.

- If confirmed, the record in [Document] table will be deleted, and the document in the evaluation's document folder will be deleted too. However the name of other existing documents will remain unchanged.

Example:

Evaluation "E_GB_0001" has two documents uploaded, named

"E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01" and "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_02". If

"E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01" is deleted, "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_02" will still keep its name as "02", and not changed to "01".

- Note: This icon will be disabled if it's for the last document.

Mock page:

http://

SIPER Admin Tool for Researchers

[\(Researcher name\)](#) [Logout](#)

[Home](#) [Evaluation](#) [Policy measure](#) [Support data](#) [Researcher acct](#) [Policy maker acct](#) [Report](#)

(Evaluation title for E_GB_0001)

Status: New

[Basic data&action](#) [Upload document](#) [PL data](#) [FC/JC data](#) [Progress note](#)

Upload new document

Document (Selected document name)

Category

Language

Publishable

Associated documents

#	Document name	Category	Language	Publishable	Action
1	Doc 1 name aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa	Main report	English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2	Doc 2 name	Executive S.	English	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Doc 3 name	Appendices	Chinese	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
.....					

(Standard footer here)

4. Technical overview

4.1. General information

- The application will be written with MVC4 / .Net 4.5, data will be stored in SQL database.
- The application's database – HumSiperBasicDev – will be hosted on Irwell, which is a SQL Server (2005) outside of the University's firewall.
- The web applications will be hosted on [\\hum-dev.humanities.manchester.ac.uk](http://hum-dev.humanities.manchester.ac.uk).

4.2. Data schema

The data in the application's database must be integrated into the database for the full version of the admin tool, therefore the schema can't be changed freely.

4.3. Table details

TBA

5. Glossary

Note: This application shares the same glossary in the full version of the admin tool. Not all the terms listed below are applicable in this application.

5.1. User related

Term	Meaning
SU	Super user, the project team leader
PA	Project associate, with a University account
PM	Policy maker, external, no University account
Researcher	SU, PA
Evaluation owner	Researcher who has been assigned to the Evaluation

5.2. Evaluation related

Term	Meaning
En	Evaluation without an owner
Ea	Evaluation with an assigned owner
PL	Policy measure for evaluations
FC	Factual characterisation for evaluations
JC	Judgemental characterisation for evaluations

6. Contacts

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7.6 Annex 6: SIPER Portal Admin Technical Specifications

(see next page)

P00418-b

SiperPortalAdmin

Version 4.4

Revision History

Version	Date	Change description
1.0	27/01/2015	Initial version.
2.0	09/03/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Copyright requirement related changes. • New evaluation workflow related changes. • Assigning/re-assigning/releasing owner and/or PM related changes. • FC/JC working process related changes. • Server related changes.
2.1	20/04/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data schema changed to add new title fields for Evaluation and Policy measure to take information native languages. • Data schema changed to increase the lengths of certain string-typed fields. • New information on databases.
3.0	03/06/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separated SPPublic and SPPM. • Added a new PubType, and some more details in various sections. • Made a few corrections in various sections.
3.1 / 3.11	18/06/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated details related to PubType / ownership change based on the new clarification. • Added the URLs in for internally hosted SP sites. • Updated maximum allowed document size.
3.2	29/06/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduced new DataStages to separate two “SU to consider” cases. • Updated details for post-JC related actions in order to rectify conflict requirements.
3.3	22/07/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated details further for post-JC related actions in order to rectify conflict requirements and cover missing information. • Updated details for owner and PM related data/actions in order to rectify conflict requirements.
3.4	27/10/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added details on document related parts – Publishable documents will be stored in an area outside of the current application, to make them accessible to PM and public sites. • Updated details in various sections: Publishing evaluation part; Approving JC part; PM email related part.
4.0	08/01/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated details on hosting arrangement. • Updated details related to the core data schema change.
4.1	22/01/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated details related to PM re-assigning / releasing.
4.2	04/02/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added details related to abandoning/reviving evaluations.
4.3	18/03/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amended detail related the SU’s general email.
4.4	17/05/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amended details to make specifications of the 3 SiperPortal applications consistent (e.g., number of years used in the year list). • Updated details related to the scale items. • Added in details for maintaining support data.

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7. Overview

SIPER stands for Science and Innovation Policy Evaluations Repository, which is a part of a larger scale multi-partner effort titled The Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS) project. SIPER’s objective is “to identify, collect, characterise evaluation reports and present them to wider stakeholders, and to conduct academic research by analysing these evaluations.”

The SIPER Portal project is required by the MBS’s SIPER team. There will be four web applications for the project:

- Part A, SiperPortalBasic – The basic data gathering tool, for very few users in the Siper project team. It will offer the basic data gathering facilities for user to enter certain project data, full details can be seen in the specification for the tool – “P00418a – SiperPortalBasic”. This application will only be used as a temporary tool during phase 1, and will not be authenticated. The functionalities will be covered in the full version of the admin tool (Part B) at later stage.
- Part B, SiperPortalAdmin – The full version of the Siper Portal admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the Siper project team. It will be protected by the University’s CAS. The application offers facilities for researcher to administrate project data. Full details will be covered in the specification “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin” (this document).
- Part C, SiperPM – An authenticated site with the access restricted to the external stakeholders (Policy Makers, or PMs), for them to work on authorized part of the project data. This will be protected by the application’s own authentication system.

Full details will be covered in the specification – “P00418c – SiperPortalPM”.

- Part D, SiperPortalPublic – A public site with searching facilities, for public user to search the project data. Full details will be covered in the specification – “P00418d – SiperPortalPublic”.

The development work will be carried out in phases (subject to review):

Phase	Description
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database for SiperPortalBasic • SiperPortal Basic
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Databases for SiperPortalAdmin and SiperPortalPublic • Key functionalities of SiperPortalAdmin for evaluation data • SiperPortalPublic site styles (static) • Authentication related functionalities of SiperPortalPM
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities of SiperPortalPM • Integration between SiperPortalAdmin and SiperPortalPM
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities of SiperPortalPublic • The rest of the functionalities for all applications

The relationship of the four applications is illustrated in Appendix 14. (TBA)

8. Authentication and authorisation

8.1. Authentication

The project consists of three parts, each designed for a particular type of user, with different access control and functionalities (Please refer to the Glossary section for terms used):

	SiperPortalAdmin	SiperPortalPM	SiperPortalPublic
User role	Researchers, i.e. SU / PA	External user, i.e. PM	General public
Access control	The University's CAS	The application's own authentication system	None
Main functionalities	Administrative project data	Edit JC	View / search published evaluations

For researchers (internal users), the standard University's account will be used to login. No account details will be stored in the application's database.

For PMs, the account will be created by the internal users, and will be stored in the application's database. More details in relevant parts of this document.

8.2. Authorisation for researcher

Role information of the researchers will be stored in table [Role] in the database.

Details of authorisation rules for different authenticated users can be found in "Appendix 1 – Authorised activities for roles".

8.3. Authorisation for PM

Details of authorisation rules for PM can also be found in "Appendix 1 – Authorised activities for roles".

Authorised actions for PM include the following:

- Change own password.
- Provide comment to FC for assigned evaluations.
- Provide JC for assigned evaluations.

PM can delegate the assignment to someone else. The delegation process is briefly covered in the PM section (3.6), full detail can be found in the specification for SiperPortalPM ("P00418c – SiperPortalPM").

More details in relevant parts of this document.

9. Functional overview

9.1. Outline

The purpose of the SiperPortalAdmin is to provide various facilities for researchers to administrate the Siper project data.

a) Status of evaluations:

Two types of status will be used:

- Data stage:

A unique indicator for an evaluation's data entering status, showing which stage an evaluation is currently in in terms of setting up evaluation data during the whole working process. Certain actions can be taken for evaluations in certain stages.

- Publishing type

A unique indicator for an evaluation's publishing status. The default status is "Data not ready" which can be changed to "Data ready" by both SU and PA's (and PM's) actions, but only SU can decide to publish or store an evaluation.

Data stage details are stored in table [DataStage], and can be summarised as below:

Code	Name	Preceding DataStage	Succeeding DataStage	Change triggered by	Possible matching PubType code
1	New	None	2	SU/PA	NO
2	FC in progress	1	3	SU/PA	NO
3	FC complete	2	4	SU/PA	Any except NO /AB
4	JC in progress	3	5, 6	PM	Any except NO /AB
5	JC complete	4, 6, 7	3, 8	PM	Any except NO /AB
6	SU consider FC	4	5	PM	Any except AB
7	SU consider JC	4	3, 5	PA	Any except NO /AB
8	JC approved	5	-	SU/PA	Any except NO /AB
9	Abandoned	1 ~ 8	1 ~ 8	SU	NO

Publishing type details are stored in table [PubType], and can be summarised as below (Note "Partially published" type is suspended):

Code	Name	Preceding Code	Succeeding Code	Possible matching DataStage
NO	Data not ready	None	RD	1, 2, 6
RD	Data ready	NO	FP, PP, ST	3 ~ 8
FP	Published	RD, PP, ST	PP, ST	3 ~ 8
PP	Partially published	RD, FP, ST	FP, ST	3 ~ 8
ST	Stored	RD, FP, PP	FP, PP	3 ~ 8
AB	Abandoned	Any	Any	9

3 Evaluation data:

An evaluation's data has following major parts:

- Basic data – Title, code, author, country, published year, policy measure (PL)
- Document(s) – An evaluation must have at least 1 document uploaded for it
- FC data – A set of answer to FC questionnaire
- JC data – A set of answer to JC questionnaire

There are other parts of the supporting data:

- PL data – Sets of answer to PL questionnaire

- Pre-defined look-up item lists (e.g. country list, language list, supranational body list)
- Progress note

4 Working process for evaluations:

Once an evaluation is created it will go through various stages. Detailed description about the whole process is in “Appendix 2 – Workflow for evaluations”, a flowchart is in “Appendix 3 – Flowchart for working on an evaluation”.

5 Menu items

The top level menu items include the following

- Home
- Evaluation – e.g., List, details, create new, assign owner/PM, and many other actions.
- Policy measure – e.g., List, details, create new, merge
- Support data – Pre-defined look-up item lists, such as country, supranational body, language, etc.
- Researcher account – Maintain internal user details
- Policy maker account – Maintain PM account
- Report – Generate reports

9.2. Evaluation related pages

Important properties of an evaluation:

- An evaluation must have the following element: Code (generated, unique), title (in English), country, published year, and at least one document. There are other optional elements, full details are in Evaluation Detail page (3.2.3).
- An evaluation is always in unique DataStage and PubType at a time, the DataStage will be changed by various actions taken by researchers or PMs, and the PubType will be changed by SU. Full details about evaluation's DataStage and PubType are summarised in the Outline section (3.1).
- An evaluation will be assigned to an owner (researcher), and later on to a PM as well. An evaluation without owner (En) can only be in the DataStage of "New" if it's created by SU. All the other evaluations should be Ea – i.e., with an assigned owner.
- One evaluation can only have one owner at a time, or have no owner. But a researcher can be owner of many evaluations at same time.
- One evaluation can only be assigned to one PM at a time, and one PM can only be assigned to one evaluation at a time.
- Actions available to an evaluation depend on its DataStage and/or PubType, and its owner's role, although some of the actions can be available to all roles and for all status.

9.2.1. Evaluation list page

Evaluation list is the starting point for evaluation functionalities.

c) Data on the page:

The evaluations will be displayed in a list with searching / sorting / paging facilities. Details included are code, title (in English), country, published year, Data stage (DataStage), publishing type (PubType), number of documents uploaded, owner name, updater name & last updated date.

The default sorting order for the list is by creation date. Other options including evaluation title and code, defined in the application's configuration file (web.config) and can be changed.

The title in native language will not be displayed in the evaluation list.

The evaluation data is from the [Evaluation] table and other few tables in the database, including [DataStage], [Country] and [Researcher].

All the researchers – SU/PA – can view the list of all existing evaluations except the abandoned ones, regardless of the evaluations' ownership.

d) Actions available for different roles:

Action	SU	PA
Create new evaluation	√	√
Go to evaluation detail page	√	√
Generate evaluation report	√	√
Include abandoned evaluations in the list	√	

e) Action details:

- Create new evaluation:

The [Create evaluation] button is available on evaluation list page to both roles, pointing to the creating new evaluation page (3.2.2).

- Go to evaluation details page:

The evaluation code in the list will be a clickable link, pointing to the evaluation detail page (3.2.3).

- Searching / sorting / paging facilities:
 - The text entered in the search box will be used to filter the content in the list.
 - Click the head of a column will get the list sorted by that column.
 - Number of evaluations per page can be selected from a dropdown list.

Note: The mock page doesn't show the full details of these but they are available.

- Export the list:

The [Export evaluation list] button is available for user to export the full evaluation list into an Excel file.

- Include abandoned evaluation in the list – SU only:

Information on whether abandoned evaluations are included in the list will be displayed, and a relevant button is available for SU to choose to include / exclude the abandoned evaluations in the list. The default is to exclude abandoned ones.

Mock page – Evaluation list:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. There is a navigation menu with items: Home, Evaluation (selected), Policy measure, Support data, Researcher acct, Policy maker acct, Report. Below the menu, there are two buttons: 'Create evaluation' and 'Export evaluation list'. The main content area is titled 'Evaluation list'. It contains two options for handling 'Abandoned evaluations excluded': 'Include abandoned evaluations' and 'Exclude abandoned evaluations'. A yellow callout bubble points to the 'Include abandoned evaluations' button with the text 'Only visible to SU'. Below this is a table with the following data:

#	Code	Title	Country	Year	Doc	DataStage	PubType	Owner	Updater
1	E_GB_0001	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	United Kingdom	2011	1	New	Data not complete		
2	E_US_0005	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secret	USA	2010	3	FC complete	Published	Potter H	Potter H
3	E_BE_0025	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaba	Belgium	2013	1	JC in progress	P.Part.Published	Weasley R	

A yellow callout bubble points to the table with the text 'Data table with searching/paging/sorting facilities'. At the bottom right of the page, there is a footer: '(Standard footer here)'.

9.2.2. Create new evaluation page

This page will be displayed when [Create evaluation] button on evaluation list page is clicked. It has the following functions:

c) Get data for creating new evaluation.

Minimum data requirement:

- Evaluation title: Text, length range 2 to 500 characters, in English, will be searchable in SPPublic site.
- **Year published:** Selected from a year list. **A dropdown list of years is used for user to enter data. The list contains 25 years, starting from the current year.**
- Country: Selected from the [Country] list (stored in the [Country] table in the database, sorted by frequency + name, i.e., 10 most frequently used countries will appear on top of the list). It includes 2 special ones: Multiple countries and supranational body, but no details will be entered here.
- Document: One initial document must be uploaded when creating a new evaluation. The document must be in PDF format, and size is within the limit which is set in the application's configuration file (web.config) and can be changed, the default limit is 50MB.

Required details for document:

- The publishable flag, default value will be false.
- The document category will be selected from the pre-defined [DocCategory] table in the database as displayed below. The category code will be used in the standard name for uploaded documents.

Category code	Category name
AP	Appendices
ES	Executive summary
MR	Main report
MP	Multipurpose
OT	Other
TR	Terms of reference

- The document language will be selected from the pre-defined [DocLanguage] table in the database. 10 most frequently used languages will be listed on the top. The language code will also be used in the standard name for uploaded documents.
- The copyright related information, which contains a group of radio buttons to take information on availability type, and a textbox to take further information as free text. Three categories will be used:
 - If the document is publically available online, the [AvailabilityType] in [Document] table will be set to "Online", and URL should be provided and stored in [AvailabilityDetail] in the same table.
 - If the document is publically available offline, the [AvailabilityType] will be set to "Offline", further details stored in [AvailabilityDetail] will be ISBN (or similar).
 - If the document isn't publically available, the [AvailabilityType] will be set to "Non-public", further details in [AvailabilityDetail] will hold information such as from whom it's obtained and when, provided by user.

Optional data:

- Title in native language: Free text, length range 2 to 500 characters.
- Author information: Free text, length range 2 to 1000 characters.

Note:

- The [AvailabilityDetail] will be entered as free text, length range 2 to 1000 characters. There will be no validation.
- The data in pre-defined [DocCategory] and [DocLanguage] tables can be maintained in Supporting data section. See more details there (3.7).

d) Generate the rest of the data for new evaluation:

- Evaluation Id: System generated and for system use only.

- Evaluation code:

This is unique which will be used as the identifier for evaluations. It's generated with a given format:

E_[2-letter country code]_[4-digit number]

The 2-letter country code is selected from the pre-defined country list; The 4-digit number will be incremented by 1 from the number in the code of the last evaluation from the same country.

Sample: E_GB_0001, E_GB_0056, E_BE_0005, E_CN_0040

- DataStage, will be set to 1 (New).
- PubType, will be set to "NO" (Data not complete).
- Researcher's Id who created the evaluation, as the creator, and the creation date. Researcher's data is from [Researcher] table in the database.
- Ownership:

For PA, the newly created evaluation must be assigned to him/herself. For SU this is optional.

Evaluation data will be saved into [Evaluation] table in the database, the related document data is saved in the [Document] table.

Note on uniqueness:

The system won't check whether a new evaluation is unique or not. SU will check it manually.

However the existing evaluation list with some basic data will be displayed on the page, offering a chance for researcher to do some manual checking.

Mock page – Create new evaluation:

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Create new evaluation

Basic evaluation data

Title (English) (Title in English for new evaluation)

Title (Native) (Title in native language for new evaluation)

Author (Author information)

Country Single country Multiple countries Supranational body
Country list

Published year Year list

Assign it to self Optional to SU, but compulsory to PA

Initial document

Doc to upload Browse (Selected document's name)

Category Category list

Language Language list

Publishable

Copyright Publically available online - The URL must be provided.
 Publically available offline - Further details (e.g. ISBN) must be provided.
 Not publically available - Please state from what source you received this document and when.
(Further details on copyright issue)

Create

Existing evaluation list

#	Code	Title	Country	Year	Doc	DataStage	PubType	Owner	Updater
1	E_GB_0001	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	United Kingdom	2011	1	New	Data not complete		
2	E_US_0005	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secret	USA	2010	3	FC complete	Published	Potter H	Potter H
3	E_BE_0025	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaba	Belgium	2013	1	JC in progress	P.Part.Published	Weasley R	

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

9.2.3. Evaluation detail page

Evaluation detail page acts as a dash board for functionalities related to a selected evaluation. A tab structure will be used in order to accommodate the multiple functionalities.

The following tabs are available which group the functionalities for a selected evaluation:

- Edit basic data
- Work with document
- Select policy measure
- Edit factual/judgemental characterisation
- Edit progress note

Different roles have different accessibilities for actions in those tabs. SU has full access to all evaluations regardless of their ownership, but PA only has full access to own evaluations, and read-only right to other ones.

The evaluation's code, title (in English) and DataStage will always be displayed on top. The PubType will be displayed too if it's not "NO". A link pointing to the evaluation list will be available at the bottom of the page.

9.2.3.1. Edit basic data tab – PA

It is the first tab to be displayed when the evaluation detail page is launched. This section covers the PA's version for the tab.

c) Data in the view:

Data	E.type	PA status	E.DataStage	Description
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code Country Creator and creation date Last updater and updating date Current owner and previous owner (if exists) 	Ea, En	Owner and non-owner	Any	Read-only
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Title (in English) Title (in native language) Author Year published 	Ea	Owner	New FC in progress	Editable
			FC complete and beyond	Read-only
Remarks	Ea	Owner	Any except the two below	Editable
	En	Non-owner	JC approved Abandoned	Read-only

A note will be displayed to remind PA that title, author and published year are only editable before FC is completed.

d) Actions available to PA for own Ea:

Action	E.type	PA	DataStage	Description
Change title, author, published year	Ea	Owner	New FC in progress	Relevant field in [Evaluation] get updated when the [Save] button is clicked.
Add/edit remarks	Ea	Owner	Any	Remarks gets updated in [Evaluation] when the [Save] button is clicked.
Claim ownership	En	Non-owner	New	[OwnerId] in [Evaluation] table gets updated when the [Own it] button is clicked

Note:

An evaluation can only have one current owner.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, basic data tab, for PA:

A Web Page
http://
Q

SiperPortalAdmin

[\(PA name\)](#) [Logout](#)

Home
Evaluation
Policy measure
Support data
Researcher acct
Policy maker acct
Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)

Data stage (Current DataStage)

Edit basic data
Work with documents
Select policy measure
Edit FC/JC data
Edit progress note

Basic data

Evaluation code E_GB_0001
 Created by (Creator name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)
 Updated by (Updater name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)

Country United Kingdom

Title (English)

Title (Native)

Author

Published year

Note: Title, Author and Published year can only be updated before FC is completed.

Remarks

Ownership

Owner (Own name, since the PA is the owner of current Ea)

Previous owner (Previous owner name if applicable)

Basic data

Evaluation code E_GB_0001
 Created by (Creator name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)
 Updated by (Updater name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)

Country United Kingdom

Title (English) (Title in English for E_GB_0010)

Title (Native) (Title in native language for E_GB_0010)

Author (Author information)

Published year (Year)

Remarks

Ownership

Owner (Own name, since the PA is the owner of current Ea)

Previous owner (Previous owner name if applicable)

Basic data

Evaluation code E_GB_0001
 Created by (Creator name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)
 Updated by (Updater name) On (dd/mm/yyyy)

Country United Kingdom

Title (English) (Title in English for E_GB_0010)

Title (Native) (Title in native language for E_GB_0010)

Author (Author information)

Published year (Year)

Remarks (Some remarks on the evaluation)

Ownership

Owner (Current owner name or No owner if it's an En)

Previous owner (Previous owner name if applicable)

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

For own Ea and DataStage is "New" or "FC in progress"

For own Ea and DataStage is "FC complete" or beyond

For other's Ea, or for En

Only visible for En

9.2.3.2. Edit basic data tab – SU

It is the first tab to be displayed when the evaluation detail page is launched. This section covers the SU’s version for the tab. SU has full access right to all evaluations, regardless of the evaluation’s ownership.

The data / actions will be grouped in four boxes, as described below:

a) Data / actions in [Basic data] box:

Data	E.type	E.DataStage	Description
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code Country Creator and creation date Last updater and updating date 	Any	Any	Read-only
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Title (in English) Title (in native language) Author Year published 	Any Ea	New FC in progress	Editable – [Save] button
		FC complete and beyond	Read-only
Remarks	Any	Any except Abandoned	Editable – [Save] button
		Abandoned	Read-only

b) Data / actions in [Ownership] box:

The current owner and previous one (if exist) will be displayed. Both researchers’ Ids are in table [Evaluation] (as OwnerId and PreOwnerId).

Other data and actions described below are only available to SU and for DataStages excluding “JC approved” and “Abandoned”. For an evaluation that has already reached “JC Approved” DataStage, owner should have been dropped and become previous owner, and no ownership change should be applied. For an abandoned evaluation the only available action is reviving. SU can change ownership for all the rest of the DataStages.

A dropdown list will show all the available researchers, data is from [Researcher] table. A researcher’s availability is reflected by [RAvailable] in the table, and set in “Researcher account” section (3.5).

Actions:

- Assign the initial owner to an En (i.e. no owner, no geographic scope data, no FC data):

Select a researcher from the dropdown list, click [Assign owner] button. The following will happen:

- The selected researcher will be saved as current owner in table [Evaluation].
- The assignment count in [Researcher] table for the owner will be increased by 1.
- The owner should get a notifying email about the assignment. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignOwner, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

- Release an owner from an Ea:

This button is only enabled for Ea, and before a PM is assigned.

Click [Release owner] button, the following will happen:

- The current owner will be saved as previous one in table [Evaluation], and there will be no owner for the evaluation.
- The assignment count in [Researcher] table for the researcher will be decreased by 1.

- The researcher should get a notifying email about the ownership change. **Auto-email ID = EvReleaseOwner, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
- Dealing with geographic scope data when release owner:

Although geographic scope data is in FC part, it should really be considered as part of the country data for an evaluation, hence is treated differently from the FC questionnaire data. When Geographic scope data is entered the DataStage is still “New”. This data – in [FJSummary] and [FJAdditionalcountry] – shouldn’t be deleted when release owner.

- Dealing with FC data when release owner:

If FC data already exists, i.e., the Ea’s DataStage is “FC in progress” or “FC complete”, information will be displayed to remind SU that the existing FC data from the released owner will be deleted (FC data entered by the released owner can be identified in [FJSummary]). Relevant data in table [FJDetail] will be deleted.

- Change ownership from one to another for an Ea:

This button is only enabled for Ea, and before a PM is assigned.

Select a researcher from the dropdown list, click [Re-assign owner] button. The following will happen:

- The current owner will be saved as previous one; and the new one as the current one in table [Evaluation].
- The assignment count in [Researcher] table for both researchers will be updated.
- Dealing with geographic scope data when re-assign owner:

Geographic scope data should be considered as part of the country data for an evaluation, not as part of the FC data. When Geographic scope data is entered the DataStage is still “New”. This data – in [FJSummary] and [FJAdditionalcountry] – shouldn’t be deleted when re-assign owner, only to change [OwnerId] in [FJSummary].

- Dealing with FC data when release owner:

If the Ea’s DataStage is “FC in progress”, or “FC complete” but no PM is assigned yet, a check box is available for SU to choose to duplicate the existing FC data. The default value is true.

Information will be displayed to remind SU that the existing FC data from the previous owner will be cleared if no duplication is required.

- If no duplication is required: FC data in the questionnaires (i.e. in table [FJDetail]) will be deleted.
- No further action is needed if duplication is required, the owner will be changed in table [FJSummary].

More details on FC data can be seen in FC/JC part (3.4).

- Both researchers should get a notifying email about the ownership change. **Auto-email ID = EvReassignOwner1 and EvReassignOwner2, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

c) Data / actions in [Publishing] box:

Evaluations can only be considered for publishing when its FC data is completed; therefore this box is only available for evaluation when its DataStage is “FC complete” or beyond (but not abandoned). Once FC is completed the PubType value will be turned from “Data not ready” to “Data ready”.

Functions related to evaluation publishing are only available to SU, because only SU can decide whether an evaluation can be published or not.

An evaluation’s publishing type (PubType) will be displayed as a read-only information, with three action buttons: Publish, Partially publish and Store. The three PubTypes – “Published”, “Partially published”, “Stored” – are interchangeable, e.g., a published evaluation can be changed to partially published, or a stored one can be published. Refer to [3.1 Outline] for relations between different PubTypes.

- [Publish] button:

Publish an evaluation means to change its PubType from “Data ready” or “Partially published” or “Stored” to “Published” (PubTypeCode = FP), hence make it visible on the SiperPortalPublic site. More details are in the specification for SiperPortalPublic, here is a brief description on key features of a published evaluation on public site:

- The basic data is available in the evaluation list, including titles, geographical scope related information (country, multiple countries, and supranational body), author, published year.
- Selected PL(s).
- Names of all the uploaded documents are visible, including both publishable and non-publishable ones.
- Full contents of the publishable documents are available for viewing.
- The answers to the publishable questions in FC data (pre-defined and stored in table [FJQuestion]) are visible.

- [Partially publish] button:

This function is suspended.

An evaluation is also possible to be partially published, the PubType will be turned from “Data ready” or “Published” or “Stored” to “Partially published” (PubTypeCode = PP). More details are in the specification for SiperPortalPublic, here is a brief description on key features of a partially published evaluation on public site:

- The basic data is available in the evaluation list, including titles, geographical scope related information (country, multiple countries, and supranational body), author, published year.
- Selected PL(s).
- Uploaded documents are not visible.
- The answers to the publishable questions in FC data are not visible.

- [Store] button:

If an evaluation is considered as not publishable, SU can decide to store it by changing its PubType from “Data ready” or “Published” or “Partially published” to “Stored” (PubTypeCode = ST), hence it won’t appear on the public site.

For an already published evaluation, storing it means to remove it from the public site. A reminding message will be provided.

Note:

- Editing FC data after evaluation is published (or partially published / stored):

After being completed, FC data will only be editable again to SU for DataStage “SU consider FC”. When DataStage is changed to “SU consider FC” in SiperPortalPM site by PM’s submission the evaluation’s PubType will be changed back to “Data not ready”, so to make sure that it won’t appear on SiperPortalPublic site.

- The evaluation’s ownership:

Published evaluation may still need an owner, because JC data may not be completed yet. An evaluation’s ownership will be dropped when its DataStage is changed to “JC approved”, by SU or owner PA in FC/JC tab, by clicking the [Approve JC] button.

d) Actions in [Additional actions] box:

- [Abandon] button:

Availability:

- This action isn't available to evaluations in two DataStages with PM: "FC complete" with PM assigned, and "JC in progress", in order to avoid any possible confusion to PM.
- For evaluations in other DataStages the action is available. A text will be displayed to remind user the result of the action. For an already published evaluation there will be an extra line of text to remind user that the evaluation will be removed from the public site.

Description of the abandoning action:

- No evaluation data will be deleted, only to be marked as in "Abandoned" DataStage / PubType in the [Evaluation] table.
- The current DataStage / PubType will be remembered as previous DataStage / PubType for the evaluation (in [Evaluation] table), and can be used when reviving the evaluation.
- Ownership change:
 - For a "New" evaluation, i.e., an evaluation before it's assigned an owner (En), no need to do anything.
 - For a "JC approved" one where the owner has been dropped but remembered as previous owner, keep the previous owner's information, but no need to email anyone for the change.
 - For an evaluation in all the other DataStages, i.e. an owner still exists, the ownership will be dropped, the owner will be remembered for the evaluation as previous owner in [Evaluation] table, and will get a notifying email. **Auto-email ID = EvAbandon, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

Effect on other tabs / pages / sites:

- A reminding message will be displayed in various boxes / tabs in this page for abandoned evaluation. Relevant data won't be available in those places.
- Checking will be carried out for FC/JC pages and reminding message displayed.
- Once an already published evaluation is abandoned it will disappear from the public site.

- [Revive] button:

Availability:

This action is only available to abandoned evaluations, and is the only available action to this type of evaluation.

Description of the reviving action:

- The DataStage / PubType will be reset to the previous one (in the [Evaluation] table).
- Ownership change:
 - If an evaluation's previous DataStage is "New", no need to do anything.
 - If an evaluation's previous DataStage is "JC approved", no need to reset the owner since there should be no owner for "JC approved" evaluation, but the previous owner should be restored. No need to send any message to the previous owner about the action.
 - For an evaluation in all the other DataStages, there must be an owner once it's revived. The owner should be set to the previous owner saved for the evaluation, and the person should get an alert email about this. **Auto-email ID = EvAbandon, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

Mock page – Evaluation detail, basic data tab, for SU:

The screenshot shows the 'Evaluation details - E_GB_0001' page in the SiperPortalAdmin system. The page is divided into several sections:

- Basic data:** Contains fields for 'Evaluation code' (E_GB_0001), 'Country' (United Kingdom), 'Title (English)', 'Title (Native)', 'Author', and 'Published year'. A 'Save' button is at the bottom. A callout box indicates that the title, author, and published year fields are 'Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"'. Another callout box states that these fields are 'Only editable when DataStage is "New" or "FC in progress"'. A note below the fields says: 'Note: Title, Author and Published year can only be updated before FC is completed.'
- Ownership:** Includes 'Current owner', 'Previous owner', and a 'Researcher list' dropdown. Below the dropdown is an instruction: '(Instruction to remind SU that existing FC data from previous owner will be cleared if no duplication is required when re-assigning a new owner, or if he/she is released)'. A checkbox 'Duplicate FC data when re-assign a new owner:' is checked. 'Assign owner' and 'Release owner' buttons are present. A callout box indicates that the 'Assign owner' button is 'Disabled for En' and that the instruction is 'Only enabled for "FC in progress" or beyond'.
- Publishing:** Shows 'Publishing type' and 'Publishing action' buttons for 'Publish' and 'Store'. A callout box notes: 'The box only visible for "FC complete" and beyond'.
- Additional actions:** Features an 'Abandon?' section with 'Abandon' and 'Revive' buttons. A callout box states: 'Only enabled for "Abandoned"'. A 'Link back to evaluation list' is at the bottom left, with a callout box indicating it is 'Only enabled for evaluation without PM'.

9.2.3.3. Upload document tab – SU/PA

d) Rules for uploading documents:

- PDF is the only acceptable format for documents to be uploaded.
- Document category and language must be selected when uploading. See Creating new evaluation for more details (3.2.2).
- Publishable flag must be decided when uploading, indicating if the document can be made available on public site when the evaluation is published. The default value is false.

- The copyright related information must be provided, detail is the same as in Creating new evaluation, i.e., it includes a group of radio buttons to take information on availability type, and a textbox to take further information as free text. See Creating new evaluation for more details (3.2.2).
- A standard format will be used to name the uploaded documents:

[Evaluation code]_[Document category code]_[Document language code]_[2-digit number]

The number will be incremented by 1 from the last document's name for same evaluation and in same document category and language.

Sample names: E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01, E_CN_0025_AP_ZH_02.

e) Document storage on server:

Uploaded documents will be stored in two areas:

- Publishable documents
 - These documents must be accessible from the public site, hence will be stored outside the application's webroot (i.e. outside the authenticated area). A designated area is created for this purpose; the directory detail will be kept in the application's configuration file (web.config). The file URL will be stored in the [Document] table as physical paths.
 - Documents will be put into sub-folders named by the evaluation code.
 - The directory and its sub-folders can be set to be open to the University's GSA (Google Search Appliance) should text search in PDF is needed in the future.
- Non-publishable documents
 - These documents are not publically accessible and will be stored within the application's webroot (in "App_Data" folder). The directory detail will also be kept in the application's configuration file. The file URL will be stored in the [Document] table as virtual paths.
 - Documents will also be grouped in sub-folders named by the evaluation code.
- A few sample document names:
 - N:\Hum\SiperPortalUploads\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01.PDF
 - ~_Docs_NonPublishable\E_GB_0005\E_GB_0005_AP_ZH_02.PDF

f) Action availability:

Action	Role	E.DataStage	Own Ea	En	Other Ea
Upload documents	SU	Any except Abandoned	√	√	√
	PA	JC approved, Abandoned			
		Any except the two above	√		
Change category, language, publishable flag, and availability detail	SU	Any except Abandoned	√	√	√
	PA	New, FC in progress	√		
View document details	SU	Any except Abandoned	√	√	√
	PA	Any except Abandoned	√	√	√
Remove document	SU	Any except Abandoned	√	√	√
	PA	New, FC in progress	√		

g) Action description:

- Upload new documents:
 - Click [Browse] button to select a document to be uploaded from the local drive. Only PDF format is acceptable;

- A size limit could be set for uploaded documents, in the application's configuration file (web.config). The default value is 50MB.
- Select category, language, set publishable flag, input copyright related details, and click [Upload] button to start uploading
 - A folder will be created (if not already existed) for the evaluation, named after the evaluation code;
 - The chosen file's name will be changed based on the naming convention, and saved in the relevant folder;
 - A record will also be saved in [Document] table in the database, together with the uploader detail and date.

More details are in Create new evaluation section (3.2.2).

- Update details for existing documents:
 - Select an existing document from the document name list and click [select] button, the details will be displayed below.
 - Make changes on relevant parts and click [Update] button to save all the changes into [Document] table in the database.
 - When a document's category and/or language are changed, the document name must be updated too to reflect the change, so is the path for the document.

Example:

Old category:

Main report (code=MR), in English (code=EN)

Old path:

~\App_Data\Docs_NonPublishable\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01.PDF

New category:

Executive summary (code=ES), in Chinese (code=ZH)

New path:

~\App_Data\Docs_NonPublishable\E_GB_0001\E_GB_0001_ES_ZH_**.PDF

where ** will be the last E_GB_0001_ES_ZH-document's number plus 1.

- Note the name change will only affect the document itself, not the other documents, i.e., the number part in the names of other documents won't be changed. See the example below in "Remove document".
- Other relevant details will also be saved, including uploader details and date.

- Other actions for existing documents:

Existing documents will be displayed in a list with most details. User can click the icons to view document details or remove documents.

- View document details:

Click the eye icon for a document, the selected PDF document will be opened in a new tab.

Note: This can be used for downloading single document.

- Remove document:

Click the bin icon for a document, the confirmation window will pop up for user to confirm the action.

If confirmed, the record in [Document] table will be deleted, and the document in the evaluation's document folder will be deleted too. However the name of other existing documents will remain unchanged.

Example:

Evaluation "E_GB_0001" has two documents uploaded, named "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01" and "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_02". If "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01" is deleted, "E_GB_0001_MR_EN_02" will still keep its name as "02", and not changed to "01".

Note: The icon will be hidden if it's for the last document.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, document tab, for SU:

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001)

(Current PubType)

Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

Data stage (Current DataStage)

- Edit basic data
- Work with documents
- Select policy measure
- Edit FC/JC data
- Edit progress note

Upload new document

Document (Selected document name)

Category

Language

Publishable

Copyright

- Publicly available online - The URL must be provided.
- Publicly available offline - Further details (e.g. ISBN) must be provided.
- Not publicly available - Please state from what source you received this document and when.

Update existing documents

Document

Category

Language

Publishable

Copyright

- Publicly available online - The URL must be provided.
- Publicly available offline - Further details (e.g. ISBN) must be provided.
- Not publicly available - Please state from what source you received this document and when.

Existing document list

#	Document name	Category	Language	Publishable	Availability	Action
1	E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01	Main report	English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Online	
2	E_GB_0001_ES_EN_01	Excutive summary	English	<input type="checkbox"/>	Offline	
3	E_GB_0001_MP_ZH_01	Multipurpose	Chinese	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Non-public	
.....						

Delete icon won't be visible for last document

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, document tab, for PA as the owner:

A Web Page
http://

SiperPortalAdmin
(PA name) [Logout](#)

Home
Evaluation
Policy measure
Support data
Researcher acct
Policy maker acct
Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001) Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

(Current PubType)

Data stage
(Current DataStage)

Edit basic data

Work with documents

Select policy measure

Edit FC/JC data

Edit progress note

Upload new document

Document (Selected document name)

Category

Language

Publishable

Copyright Publicly available online - The URL must be provided.
 Publicly available offline - Further details (e.g. ISBN) must be provided.
 Not publicly available - Please state from what source you received this document and when.

Existing documents

Document

Category

Language

Publishable

Copyright Publicly available online - The URL must be provided.
 Publicly available offline - Further details (e.g. ISBN) must be provided.
 Not publicly available - Please state from what source you received this document and when.

Existing document list

#	Document name	Category	Language	Publishable	Availability	Action
1	E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01	Main report	English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Online	
2	E_GB_0001_ES_EN_01	Excutive summary	English	<input type="checkbox"/>	Offline	
3	E_GB_0001_MP_ZH_01	Multipurpose	Chinese	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Non-public	
.....						

Delete icon won't be visible for last document

Existing documents

#	Document name	Category	Language	Publishable	Availability	Action
1	E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01	Main report	English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Online	
2	E_GB_0001_ES_EN_01	Excutive summary	English	<input type="checkbox"/>	Offline	
3	E_GB_0001_MP_ZH_01	Multipurpose	Chinese	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Non-public	
.....						

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

DataStage is "New" or "FC in progress"

DataStage is "FC complete" or beyond

Mock page – Evaluation detail, document tab, for PA who’s not the owner:

9.2.3.4. Policy measure (PL) tab – SU/PA

Each evaluation must have at least one PL selected. PL data is maintained in a separate part of the application (3.3), and is available here to be selected.

PL can be identified by its code, which is in the following format:

P_[2-letter country code]_[4-digit number]

Sample: P_GB_0001, P_CN_0005

a) Data in the tab:

- List of selected PL(s)

This list shows selected PL(s)’s code and English title. The data is from [PLUsage] and [PLSummary].

For new evaluation the list will be empty initially.

- List of available PLs

This list shows all the available PLs in the same format. Note only completed PLs (i.e. the PLs with “PLCompleted” flag being true in [PLSummary] table in the database) are considered available.

More details about PL data are in PL section (3.3).

b) Action availability:

Action		Own Ea	En	Other Ea	DataStage
[+] buttons in available PL list	SU	√	√	√	New
	PA	√			New
[-] buttons in selected PL list	SU	√	√	√	New
	PA	√			New

[Create new PL] button	SU	√	√	√	Any except Abandoned
	PA	√			Any except Abandoned

c) Action description:

- [+] buttons in the available PL list:

The PL will appear in the selected PL list and disappear from the available one, and the table [PLUsage] will be updated to record this.

- [-] buttons in the selected PL list:

The PL will disappear from the selected PL list and re-appear in the available one, and the table [PLUsage] will be updated accordingly.

- Create new PL:

If no suitable PL is found in the available PL list, new PL needs to be created first. Researcher can use [Create new PL] button on this page to go to creating new PL page (3.3.4), or use the PL menu item to go to PL list page and use the creating new PL button there.

- Check PL details:

TBA at later stage if time/resource permits

Select a PL in either of the two PL lists, and click the view icon, the PL's detail will be displayed in a read-only box on the page, showing the selected items in the PL questionnaire.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, policy measure tab, for PA who's not the owner:

Mock page – Evaluation detail, policy measure tab, for SU or PA as the owner:

SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001) Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

(Current PubType)

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Selected policy measure(s) Create new policy measure

#	Code	Title	Action
1	PL_GB_0001	(PL title for PL_GB_0001 aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa)	- [eye icon]
2	PL_GB_0003	(PL title for PL_GB_0003)	- [eye icon]
3	PL_FR_0001	(PL title for PL_FR_0001)	- [eye icon]

Available policy measures View PL details - TBA

#	Code	Title	Action
1	PL_GB_0002	(PL title for PL_GB_0002 aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa)	+ [eye icon]
2	PL_GB_0004	(PL title for PL_GB_0004)	+ [eye icon]
3	PL_FR_0002	(PL title for PL_FR_0002)	+ [eye icon]
4	PL_Z1_0001	(PL title for PL_Z1_0001)	+ [eye icon]
5	PL_Z2_0001	(PL title for PL_Z2_0001)	+ [eye icon]

Data table with searching/paging/sorting facilities

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

9.2.3.5. Factual/judgemental characterisation (FC/JC) tab – SU

The purpose of this tab is to provide an easy way for SU to check FC/JC related data and take relevant actions on them. It's not the FC/JC editing page which is in FC/JC data related pages section (3.4).

This tab will only make sense for an Ea. So if the evaluation details page is called for an En there will only be a message in this tab to remind SU to assign an owner first.

User can only work on FC/JC after PL is selected. If this tab is called for an Ea with PL, only the owner name will be displayed, and a reminder for SU to select PL(s) first.

The tab contains two boxes, for FC and JC respectively.

a) FC box:

- There will be some read-only data, including:
 - The owner name. It's in the [Basic data] tab but will be displayed here too as a quick reference.
 - DataStage related to FC, to show if the FC hasn't been set, is in progress, or complete.
 - When DataStage is "JC in progress" and beyond, two checkboxes to show whether or not PM has made some comments on FC, and whether the comments have been checked.
- [View/Edit] button, to take user to the FC pages (3.4), to view and/or edit FC data. FC data accessibility can be summarised below:

DataStage/Code	PubType code	SU	Owner PA	Non-owner PA
New / 1	NO	Edit	Edit	n/a
FC in progress / 2	NO	Edit	Edit	View
FC complete / 3, no PM	Any except NO/AB	Edit	Edit	View
FC complete / 3, has PM	Any except NO/AB	View	View	View
JC in progress / 4	Any except NO/AB	View	View	View
JC complete / 5	Any except NO/AB	View	View	View
SU consider FC / 6	NO	Edit	View	View
SU consider JC / 7	Any except NO/AB	View	View	View
JC approved / 8	Any except NO/AB	View	View	View

b) JC box:

b-1) Read-only data:

- PM details:
 - For evaluation in "FC complete" with PM already assigned, and "JC in progress", PM name and initial contact date will be displayed.
 - For evaluation in "JC complete" and beyond, the PM who has done the JC will be displayed as previous PM, because the assignment should have been released by then. JC completion date will be displayed too.
- DataStage related to JC, to show if the JC hasn't been set, is in progress, complete, or it's for SU to consider, or it's already been approved.
- Available PM list:

Since a PM can only be working on one evaluation at a time, only available PMs (i.e. those who don't have current assignment) can be used for assignment, based on [PAvailable] value in [PolicyMaker] table in the database. The list of available PMs will be displayed when assignment related actions are available.

b-2) PM assignment related data and actions:

Actions in this box are only available to certain DataStages, as summarised in the table below:

DataStage/Code	Assign PM	Re-assign PM	Release PM	Reset password
FC complete / 3, no PM	Y, initial PM	N	N	N
FC complete / 3, has PM	N	Y Inactive PM	Y Inactive PM	Y Forget password before entering any data
JC in progress / 4	N	Y Inactive PM	Y Inactive PM	Y Forget password
JC complete / 5	Y Unsatisfied JC	N PM dropped	N	N PM dropped
SU consider FC / 6	N	N	N	N
SU consider JC / 7	Y Unsatisfied JC	N PM dropped	N	N
JC approved / 8	N	N	N	N

PM's login account in PM authentication database:

A PM can be assigned many times. The login account will be created when a PM is assigned for the first time, and the same account will be used in the later assignments. The PM's email will be used as username, and an initial password will be generated by the application in this format: The first letters from PM's forename and surname plus the assigned evaluation code. So if a PM named Mary Smith is assigned to an evaluation E_GB_0001, the initial password will be set to "ms+E_GB_0001". More details on PM account are in PM account pages (3.6).

Detailed description about the buttons:

- [Assign] button for assigning initial PM to an evaluation:

This button will do it when DataStage is "FC complete" and no PM has been assigned to an evaluation, i.e. this will be the initial assignment for the evaluation.

When it's clicked, the following will happen:

- The assignment will be recorded in [PMAssignment] table in the database, details including PM, evaluation and its owner, initial contact date, and the [PMCurrent] flag will be set to true, indicating this assignment is a current one, and will be accessible for data entering in SiperPortalPM site for the assigned PM (Note if a PM already has a past assignment for the evaluation the same assignment record will be reused);
- The [PAvailable] flag in [PolicyMaker] table will be set to false, so this PM can't be assigned to work on other evaluations;
- The assigned PM should also be recorded in table [FJSummary].
- Login account:
 - If the PM hasn't been used in the past a login account will be created in the PM's authentication database, and an auto email will be sent to the PM with initial login details and other relevant information about the assignment. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM1, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
 - If the PM already has a login account no new one will be created. An auto email will be sent to the PM about the assignment. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM2, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
- If SU is doing this for an Ea owned by others (e.g. a PA), the owner PA of the Ea should be copied into the above auto email.

- [Assign] button for assigning PM to a post-JC evaluation:

This button will do it when DataStage is “JC complete” or “SU consider JC”. This means that JC has been done but not satisfied, and SU decided to re-do it with another JC. Evaluation in these DataStages has no PM because once JC is submitted PM’s assignment will be dropped.

When it’s clicked, the following will happen:

- In [PMAssignment] table, same as in initial assignment action, plus the following: The [AssignmentDoneDate] should be set to null;
- In [PolicyMaker] table, same as in initial assignment action;
- In [FJSummary] table, record the new PM, and re-set flags [JCCompleted], [PMCommented] and [PMCommentPassed] to false.
- Delete old JC data: Delete JC and FC comment entered by previous PM for current evaluation in [FJDetails] and [FJPMComment], and re-set JC section flags to false in [FJValidation]; More details on JC data are in JC editing pages (3.4.6).
- In [Evaluation] table, DataStage should be changed to “FC complete”;
- Login account, same as in initial assignment action;
- If SU is doing this for an Ea owned by others (e.g. a PA), the owner PA of the Ea should be copied into the above auto email.

- [Release] button:

This button will release the assigned PM, usually due to PM being inactive for a long time. It’s only available for “FC complete” with PM already being assigned, or “JC in progress”, because these are the only two DataStages that have assigned PMs. Information will be displayed to remind SU that the JC data entered by the PM will be deleted.

When the button is clicked the following will happen:

- In [PMAssignment] table, the [PMCurrent] flag for the PM assignment with this evaluation will be set to false, indicating this is a past assignment. The initial contact date will remain;
- In [PolicyMaker] table, the [PAvailable] flag for the PM will be re-set to true, so he/she can be assigned to other evaluations;
- Identify JC data’s [FJSummaryId] for the released PM for current Ea by [PolicyMakerId] in table [FJSummary], delete relevant JC data in tables [FJDetails] and [FJPMComment], and updated relevant values in [FJValidation] and [FJSummary]; More details on JC data are in JC editing pages (3.4.6).
- In [Evaluation] table, DataStage should be changed to “FC complete”;
- Login details: These will remain in the PM authentication database;
- If SU does this to an evaluation owned by someone else, the owner should get email notification too. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM4, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.** No auto email will be sent to the released PM.

- [Re-assign] button:

This button is only available for “FC complete” with PM already being assigned, or “JC in progress”, because these are the only two DataStages that have assigned PMs.

This button is actually the combination of assigning (for new PM) and releasing (for old PM).

When it’s clicked, the following will happen:

- In [PMAssignment] table, the new assignment will be recorded for new PM (same as assigning), so the new PM will now have a current assignment; the old assignment for old PM will remain but marked as past;
- In [PolicyMaker] table, new PM will be set as unavailable and old one available, in their [PAvailable] flags;

- The assigned PM should be updated in table [FJSummary], and re-set flags [JCCompleted], [PMCommented] and [PMCommentPassed] to false;
- Delete old JC data: Delete JC and FC comment entered by old PM for current evaluation in [FJDetails] and [FJPMComment], and re-set JC section flags to false in [FJValidation]; More details on JC data are in JC editing pages (3.4.6).
- In [Evaluation] table, DataStage should be changed to “FC complete”;
- Login account: For new PM same as in assigning action, for old PM same as in releasing action;
- If SU is doing this for an Ea owned by others (e.g. a PA), the owner PA of the Ea should be copied into the auto email sent to new PM, and get an alert for the assignment been dropped for old PM. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM3, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.** Note the previous PM won't get any auto notification.

- Re-assign same PM for password re-setting purpose ([Reset password] button):

This action is for re-setting password for an existing PM, and only available for DataStage “FC complete” when a PM has already assigned, or “JC in progress”, when there is definitely an assigned PM.

- The JC data (in [FJSummary], [FJDetail], [FJValidation] and [FJPMComment]) related to or entered by the PM will remain.
- The following data will remain unchanged too: [PAvailable] in [PolicyMaker], [PMCurrent] in [PMAssignment], DataStage in [Evaluation].
- The PM's current account in PM authentication data database will remain but the password will be reset to the original system-generated one, and auto email will be sent out to the PM. **Auto-email ID = EvAssingPM5, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.** If the evaluation is owned by someone else the owner will be copied in. Login details setting rule will be the same as in assigning initial PM, see more details in relevant part above in this section.

Note:

Once a PM has been assigned to an evaluation, researcher must take caution to avoid causing unnecessary confusion when doing re-assigning and releasing. Although a researcher can't tell if a PM is currently logged in to the SiperPM site to work on an evaluation, the last login date is displayed in JC box as part of the PM related details. It's researcher's responsibility to check this date before re-assigning or releasing a PM. This date is updated by Siper PM site every time a PM logs in and stored in table [PolicyMaker], the value will be cleared once an assignment is cancelled or completed.

b-3) JC related actions:

Actions in this box are only available to DataStage in “JC in progress” or beyond. Detailed availabilities are summarised in the table below:

DataStage/Code	(Edit FC)	View JC	Edit JC	Pass to PA for new PM	(Re-assign PM)	Approve JC
JC in progress / 4	N/A	Y	N	N	Y	N
JC complete / 5	N/A	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
SU consider FC / 6	Y	Y	N	N	N	N
SU consider JC / 7	N/A	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
JC approved / 8	N/A	Y	N	N	N	N

[View/Edit JC] button is only enabled after a PM is assigned to the evaluation and is entering JC data, i.e. when DataStage is “JC in progress” or beyond. Clicking the button will take SU to the JC editing pages (3.4.6).

[Edit FC] button isn’t in this box but in FC box. It’s included here because SU will need to go to FC editing pages if DataStage is “SU consider FC”, which means PM completed JC and made comment on FC, therefore SU needs to check FC and decide what to do.

Detailed descriptions on DataStage-specific actions:

- DataStage = “JC in progress”:
 - [View JC] button: This is available for SU to view JC data in JC editing pages in read-only mode. SU shouldn’t make changes in JC data if PM is working on it.
 - [Re-assign] button (in Assignment box): SU can decide to re-assign a new PM, if the current PM is inactive for a long time. See details for [Re-assign] button in this section.
- DataStage = “JC complete”:
 - [Edit JC] button: This is available for SU to view/edit JC data in JC editing pages. DataStage can be changed back to “JC in progress” as the result of SU’s data changing, or stay as “JC complete”, see more details in JC details page section 3.4.6.
 - [Approve JC] button: Only available for “JC complete”. If SU is satisfied with JC it can be approved. DataStage will be changed to “JC approved”, and ownership will be dropped, with the current owner being recorded as previous owner in table [Evaluation].
 - [Assign] button (in Assignment box): SU can also assign a new PM him/herself, if JC is checked and not satisfied. See details for [Assign] button in this section, for quick reference: DataStage will be changed to “FC complete” when assigning PM, existing JC data and FC comment will be deleted. If the evaluation is owned by someone else the owner will get an auto email as an alert. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM1 or EvAssignPM2, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

- DataStage = “SU consider FC”:

This DataStage indicates that PM has completed JC and made comments on FC, therefore SU must check the FC.

- [Edit FC] button (in FC box): This will take SU to FC editing pages. An extra [Submit] button will be available on all FC section pages, only visible in DataStage “SU consider FC”, for SU to confirm that the comments are checked and passed.

See more details in FC details page section 3.4.5. For quick reference: When [Submit] button on FC details pages is clicked, DataStage will be turned from “SU consider FC” to “JC complete”,

PubType will be changed from “Data not ready” to “Data ready”, and flag [PMCommentPassed] in [FJSummary] will be set to true. If the evaluation is owned by someone else the owner will get an auto email as an alert, so the owner can start checking JC. **Auto-email ID = PassToPAForCheckingJC, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

- [View JC] button: When in this DataStage, SU can't edit JC, but can view it. The DataStage will remain unchanged.

- DataStage = “SU consider JC”:

This DataStage indicates that PA has checked JC and isn't satisfied; therefore SU must check PA's remarks and decide what to do.

- [Edit JC] button: Same as in “JC complete” above.
- [Assign] button (in Assignment box): Same as in “JC complete” above.

Please refer to appendix 2/3/10 and the JC section below for more details.

9.2.3.6. Factual/judgemental characterisation (FC/JC) tab – PA

The purpose of this tab is to provide an easy way for PA to check FC/JC related data and take relevant actions on them. It's not the FC/JC editing page which is in FC/JC data related pages section (3.4).

This tab will only make sense for an Ea. So if the evaluation details page is called for an En there will only be a message in this tab to remind PA that the evaluation needs to have an owner assigned first.

User can only work on FC/JC after PL is selected. If this tab is called for a PL-less Ea, there will only be a message to remind PA that he/she should select PL(s) first.

PA can only work on own Ea. If the tab is called for an Ea owned by others, it will be displayed in the read-only mode.

The tab contains two boxes, for FC and JC respectively.

a) FC box:

- There will be some read-only data, including owner name, FC status and PM comment related information. This is similar to SU in 3.2.3.5.
- [View/Edit] button, to take user to the FC pages (3.4), to view and/or edit FC data. PA can only edit FC before it's completed. For DataStage “FC complete” and beyond PA can only view FC. See more details in FC box part for SU.

b) JC box:

b-1) Read-only data for quick reference:

This part is the same as SU, in 3.2.3.5.

b-2) PM assignment related data and actions:

Actions in this box are only available to certain DataStages. Detailed availabilities and action descriptions are the same as for SU in 3.2.3.5.

b-3) JC related actions:

Actions in this box are only available to DataStage in “JC in progress” or beyond. Detailed availabilities are summarised in the table below:

DataStage/Code	View FC	View JC	Pass to SU	(Assign PM to re-do JC)	Approve JC
JC in progress / 4	Y	Y	N	Y	N
JC complete / 5	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
SU consider FC / 6	Y	Y	N	N	N
SU consider JC / 7	Y	Y	N	Y	N
JC approved / 8	Y	Y	N	N	N

[View FC] button is always available, for PA to view PM’s comment on FC in JC editing pages.

[View JC] button is always available, for PA to view JC data in JC editing pages in read-only mode.

Other DataStage-specific actions:

- DataStage = “JC in progress”:
 - [Assign PM] button (in Assignment box): PA can decide to assign a new PM, if the current PM is inactive for a long time. See details for [Assign PM] button in 3.2.3.5.
- DataStage = “JC complete”:
 - [Approve JC] button: Only available for “JC complete”. If PA is checked JC and satisfied it can be approved. DataStage will be changed to “JC approved”, and ownership will be dropped, current owner will be recorded as previous owner in table [Evaluation].
 - [Pass to SU for JC] button: If PA checked JC and isn’t satisfied, this button will set DataStage to “SU consider JC”. PA must provide reasons for doing so (in [Remarks]). An auto email will be sent to the SU’s general email account. **Auto-email ID = PassToSUForJC, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
 - [Assign PM] button (in Assignment box): If SU checked JC and decided a new PM is needed to re-do it, the [NewPMNeeded] flag will be set to true and the information will be displayed here. PA can assign a new PM. See details for [Assign] button in 3.2.3.5, for quick reference: DataStage will be changed to “FC complete” when a new PM is assigned.
- DataStage = “SU consider FC”:

This DataStage indicates that PM has completed JC and made comments on FC, therefore SU must check the FC. PA can’t do anything except viewing FC/JC data.

- DataStage = “SU consider JC”:

This DataStage indicates that PA has checked JC and isn’t satisfied; therefore SU must check PA’s remarks and decide what to do.

- [Assign PM] button (in Assignment box): Same as in “JC complete” above.

Mock pages for this tab are done for different role and DataStage, including

- a) FC stages, for SU and owner-PA
- b) JC in progress, for SU and owner-PA
- c) JC complete, for SU
- d) JC complete, for owner-PA
- e) SU consider FC, for SU and owner-PA
- f) SU consider JC, for SU
- g) SU consider JC, for owner-PA

- h) JC approved, for SU and owner-PA
- i) All stages, for non-owner-PA

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, FC stages, for SU and owner-PA:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The current page is 'Evaluation details - E_GB_0001'. The title is '(Title for E_GB_0001)' and the current PubType is '(Current PubType)'. The Data stage is '(Current DataStage)'. The page has several tabs: 'Edit basic data', 'Work with documents', 'Select policy measure', 'Edit FC/JC data', and 'Edit progress note'. The 'Edit FC/JC data' tab is active. The page is divided into two main sections: 'Factual characterisation' and 'Judgemental characterisation'. The 'Factual characterisation' section has fields for 'Owner', 'FC data status', and 'PM comment', and an 'Action' button labeled 'Edit/View FC data'. The 'Judgemental characterisation' section has fields for 'Policy maker' and 'JC data status', and a sub-section for 'Assign policy maker' with a warning message. Annotations include: 'Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"' pointing to the title; 'A reminder will be displayed if no PL is selected.' pointing to a message in the 'Factual characterisation' section; 'Button text depends on FC status. PA can only view it when it's completed' pointing to the 'Edit/View FC data' button; and 'Actions only available if PL is selected' pointing to the 'Assign policy maker' section. A footer contains '(Standard footer here)' and a link 'Link back to evaluation list'.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, JC in progress, for SU and owner-PA:

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying the 'SiperPortalAdmin' interface. The page title is 'Evaluation details - E_GB_0001' with a subtitle '(Title for E_GB_0001) (Current PubType)'. The 'Data stage' is 'JC in progress'. The interface includes a navigation menu with 'Evaluation' selected, and a set of tabs: 'Edit basic data', 'Work with documents', 'Select policy measure', 'Edit FC/JC data', and 'Edit progress note'. The main content is divided into three sections: 'Factual characterisation', 'Judgemental characterisation', and 'Work on judgemental characterisation'. The 'Factual characterisation' section shows 'FC data status' as 'Complete' and 'PM comment' with checkboxes for 'Policy maker commented on FC' (checked) and 'Policy maker comments checked by SU' (unchecked). A 'View FC data' button is present. The 'Judgemental characterisation' section shows 'JC data status' as 'In progress' and includes an 'Assign policy maker' section with an 'Available PMs' dropdown, 'Re-assign policy maker', 'Release policy maker', and 'Reset password' buttons. The 'Work on judgemental characterisation' section has a 'View JC data' button. Three yellow callouts provide context: one points to the 'View FC data' button stating 'Even SU shouldn't edit FC if DataStage is "JC in progress", i.e., when PM is working on the data.'; another points to the 'Policy maker commented on FC' checkbox stating 'Information displayed for "JC in progress" or beyond. Read only'; and a third points to the 'Reset password' button stating 'Resetting password only available for "FC complete" and "JC in progress"'. A footer contains a 'Link back to evaluation list' and '(Standard footer here)'.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, JC complete, for SU:

A Web Page

http://

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (SU name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001) Data stage JC complete
(Current PubType)

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Factual characterisation

Owner (Owner name)
FC data status Complete
PM comment Policy maker commented on FC:
Policy maker comments checked by SU:
Action

Judgemental characterisation

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)
JC data status Complete

Assign policy maker

Available PMs Available policy maker list
Action

Work on judgemental characterisation

Action
Note: JC must be checked and satisfied before it's approved.

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, JC complete, for owner-PA:

A Web Page

http://

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (PA name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)

Data stage JC complete

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Factual characterisation

Owner (Owner name)

FC data status Complete

PM comment Policy maker commented on FC:
Policy maker comments checked by SU:

Action

Judgemental characterisation

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)

JC data status Complete

Assign policy maker

Available PMs Available policy maker list

Action **New policy maker required by SU!**

Work on judgemental characterisation

Action Judgemental characterisationcan data can be viewed

If you've checked JC and are not satisfied, you can pass it to SU to consider.
Please give your reasons here:

(PA's remarks for JC)

Note: JC must be checked and satisfied before it's approved.

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, SU consider FC, for SU and owner-PA:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)

Data stage SU consider FC

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Factual characterisation

Owner (Owner name)
FC data status (Empty / In progress / Complete)
PM comment Policy maker commented on FC:
Policy maker comments checked by SU:

Action Text on button will be "View FC data" for PA

Judgemental characterisation

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)
JC data status Complete, with comment on FC

Assign policy maker

Assigning / releasing PM action isn't available for current DataStage (SU consider FC)

Work on judgemental characterisation

Action

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, SU consider JC, for SU:

A Web Page

http://

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (SU name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001) Data stage SU consider JC
(Current PubType)

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Factual characterisation

Owner (Owner name)
FC data status Complete
PM comment Policy maker commented on FC:
Policy maker comments checked by SU:
Action

Judgemental characterisation

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)
JC data status Complete, checked by PA and not satisfied

Assign policy maker

Available PMs Available policy maker list
Action

Work on judgemental characterisation

Action Judgemental characterisation can data can be viewed or edited

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, SU consider JC, for owner-PA:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (PA name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)

Data stage SU consider JC

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

Factual characterisation

Owner (Owner name)
FC data status Complete
PM comment Policy maker commented on FC:
Policy maker comments checked by SU:
Action

Judgemental characterisation

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)
JC data status Complete, checked by PA and not satisfied

Assign policy maker

Available PMs Available policy maker list
Action New policy maker required by SU!

Reminder depending on SU's action

Work on judgemental characterisation

Action

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, JC approved, for SU and owner-PA:

Mock page – Evaluation detail, FJ/JC tab, All stages, for non- owner-PA:

9.2.3.7. Progress note tab – SU/PA

TBA at later stage if time/resource permits

Progress note is for internal communication purpose. The notes are stored in [ProgressNote] table in the database.

- New note:

SU can add new note to any En and Ea.

PA can add new note to own Ea.

A note should contain no more than 1000 characters.

- Previous notes:

The date and first few characters of the notes will be displayed in a dropdown list sorted by the date.

User can select one to view the full details.

Notes are viewable regardless of the ownership.

Mock page – Evaluation detail, progress note tab:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Evaluation details - E_GB_0001 Data stage (Current DataStage)

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)

Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

Edit basic data Work with documents Select policy measure Edit FC/JC data Edit progress note

New note
New note...
Add note

Previous notes
(Note date - The first xx characters of a note) View detail

Date (Date)
Creator (Creator name)
Content Full content of the note
Can be long
.....
.....

(Note date - The first xx characters of a note) View detail

Date (Date)
Creator (Creator name)
Content Full content of the note
Can be long
.....
.....

For SU on any Ea, PA on own Ea

For PA on other Ea

[Link back to evaluation list](#)

(Standard footer here)

9.3. Policy measure (PL) data related pages

9.3.1. Basic policy measure properties

- A PL must have a code, a title (in English), a country (or special country code, see details below), and a set of answers to the pre-defined PL questionnaire.
- PL's code is unique, generated when it's created, in a standard format:

P_[2-letter country code]_[4-digit number].

Sample code: P_GB_0001

- PL's English title contains 4 to 500 characters, will be used when user selects PL for an evaluation.
- A PL can also have a title in native language (optional), containing no more than 500 characters.
- An evaluation must have at least one PL, but there is no upper limit on a number of PL an evaluation can have.
- A PL can be selected by multiple evaluations.
- A PL has a creator, but not owned by the creator. Any researcher can modify a PL created by him/herself; or by others.
- When a PL is created, by default it's marked as uncompleted ([PLCompleted] flag in [PolicyMeasure] table is set to false), user can stop in the middle of the creating process and come back to finish it later. Only when the creating process is finished, i.e. all the questions are answered for a PL, it can be marked as completed. And only completed PLs will be listed as available for evaluation to choose.

9.3.2. PL data in the database

- PL summary data:

This is stored in table [PLSummary], including PL's code, titles (in English and in native language), creation and updating person and date, country (or special "country", more details in creating new PL page), whether the PL is completed (i.e. all the questions answered), and remarks.

- PL questionnaire data:

A set of pre-defined PL questionnaire data will be stored in a fixed 2-level structure in table [PLQuestion]. The PL items are grouped in 3 categories, each category contains a fixed number of items: Targets (10 items), Modalities (7 items), Policy objectives (15 items). The data in [PLQuestion] can't be changed.

- PL detail data:

This is a set of answers to the PL questionnaire. It's stored in table [PLDetail], and if the PL is for multiple countries, in table [PLAdditionalCountry] as well.

- PL usage data:

Stored in table [PLUsage], this link table will record the many-to-many relationship between PL and evaluation.

- Other related data:

PL will use the pre-defined geographic related data, including country list and supranational body list, which are stored in tables [Country] and [SupranationalBody]. They can be maintained by SU, more detail is in the support data section (3.7).

PL will also be linked to other tables such as [Evaluation] and [Researcher].

9.3.3. PL list page

PL list is the starting point for PL functionalities. It's available to both SU and PA.

a) Data in the view

PLs will be displayed in a list with searching / sorting / paging facilities. Details included are PL code, English title, country (or special “country”, more details in creating new PL page), creator and creation date, updater and updating date if applicable, completion flag, and usage (i.e. number of evaluations a PL is used by).

Extra column for SU:

For PLs that are not used by any evaluation, i.e. usage count is 0, a bin sign will be available, offering a deleting option to SU.

The data is from the [PLSummary] table and other few tables in the database, including [PLUsage] and [Country].

b) Actions available to both SU and PA:

- Create new PL:

The button is available to all.

- Go to a PL’s detail page:

The PL code in the list is a clickable link, pointing to the PL Summary page (3.3.5).

- Searching / sorting / paging facilities:

The text entered in the search box will be used to filter the list content.

Click the head of a column will get the list sorted by that column.

Number of PLs per page can be selected from a dropdown list, the options are 10/25/50/100.

c) Additional actions available to SU:

- Delete PL:

The column is only available to SU, and the bin sign is only visible if the usage count (i.e. number of evaluations the PL is used by) is 0.

When the bin sign is clicked a confirmation box will appear for SU to confirm the deleting action.

If the deleting is confirmed, the PL will be permanently deleted from the database, in [PLSummary], [PLDetail] and [PLAdditionalCountry] (if applicable) tables.

- Merge two PLs:

The button will launch the PL Merge page (3.3.7).

TBA at later stage if time/resource permits

Mock page – Policy measure list:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The 'Policy measure' menu item is highlighted. The main content area displays a table titled 'Policy measure list' with columns: Code, Title, Country, Creator, Updater, Completed, Usage, and Delete. The table contains four rows of data. Callout boxes highlight the 'Merge policy measures' button, the table's search/paging/sorting facilities, and the 'Delete' column which includes a bin icon.

Code	Title	Country	Creator	Updater	Completed	Usage	Delete
1	P_GB_0001	United Kingdom	Dumbledore	Dumbledore	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	
2	P_GB_0002	United Kingdom	Granger	Granger	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	5	
3	P_CN_0001	China	Potter	Granger	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2	
4	P_BE_0001	Belgium	Chang		<input type="checkbox"/>	0	

9.3.4. Create new PL page

This page is accessible to both SU and PA.

The following data must be selected / entered when creating a new PL:

- PL title in English. It must be between 4 to 500 characters.
- Geographical scope:
 - Single country

If this is selected, a country list will be displayed for user to select a country. The selected country's CountryCode will be used to generate the unique PLCode.

- Multiple countries

If this is selected, a special CountryCode "Z1" will be used to generate the unique PLCode, i.e. the PL code will be P_Z1_[4-digit number]. The countries will be selected on PL Summary page.

- Supranational body

If this is selected, a special CountryCode "Z2" will be used to generate the unique PLCode, i.e. the PL code will be P_Z2_[4-digit number]. The supranational body will be selected on PL Summary page.

PL's title in native language can also be entered but it's optional. If entered it must not exceed 500 characters.

Once the [Create and proceed] button is clicked, a new record will be added into the table [PLSummary] for the new PL with its unique PLCode, and user will be taken to the PL Summary page to complete the data entering process. The PL's completion flag is set to false at this point.

Mock page – Create new policy measure:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar containing 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure' (highlighted), 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The main content area is titled 'Create new policy measure' and contains the following form fields:

- Title (English):
- Title (Native):
- Creator: (Current researcher's name)
- Geographic scope: Single country, Multiple countries, Supranational body - e.g. EU, OECD
- Country: Please select a country from the list below: (Country list)

There are two buttons: 'Create and proceed' and 'Abort'. A note next to the country field states: 'This part only appears if single country is selected'. At the bottom, there is a link 'Link back to PL list' and a footer '(Standard footer here)'.

9.3.5. PL Summary page

PL Summary page can be called in two ways:

- To edit details of an existing PL:

Called from PL List page by clicking a PL's code, the selected PL's detail will be displayed. The PL status is completed.

- To finish the creating new PL process:

Called from the creating new PL page by clicking the [Create and proceed] button, the empty PL (with selected country) will be displayed. Different geographic scope related questions will show accordingly. The PL status is incomplete.

Data displayed:

- PL title in English – Editable to both SU and PA.
- PL title in native language – Editable to both SU and PA.
- Creator and updater name and date – View only.
- Geographical scope – View only.
- Further information, depending on the geographic scope:
 - Single country:

A group of radio buttons will be presented for user to choose if the PL is at national or regional level. No default selection is offered.

- Multiple countries:

Lists of available countries and selected countries will be displayed, with [Select] and [Remove] buttons in between. The result will be saved into table [PLAdditionalCountry] every time a country is selected or removed. The buttons will be enabled / disabled according to the number of countries already selected.

- Supranational body:

A list of supranational body (read from table [SupranationalBody]) will be displayed for user to choose from. An instruction will be presented too to let user contact SU if the suitable supranational body isn't available in the list, so SU can add it into the list.

- Remarks – Editable to both SU and PA.

Validation rules for PLSummary data:

- Title in English: Must have 4 to 500 characters, and should be unique.
- Title in native language: Optional. If entered it shouldn't exceed 500 characters.
- Additional question according to the geographic scope:
 - For single country:

National/regional level must be selected.

- For multiple countries:

2 to 10 countries must be selected.

- For supranational body:

A supranational body must be selected.

Actions available:

- [Save and proceed] button:

Validated data – title, remarks, national / regional level for single country, supranational body – will be saved in the table [PLSummary]. The completion flag won't be changed here.

- [Proceed without saving] button:

Move to PL Detail page without saving. The button will be disabled when data required hasn't been entered.

- [Select] / [Remove] button (for multiple countries only):

Multiple country selection will be updated in table [PLAdditionalCountry].

- [Cancel] button

Cancel the action and return to policy measure list page without saving.

Mock page – Policy measure summary:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Policy measure details - (PL code) Status: Incomplete

Title (English) (Title (in English) of the selected PL)
Created by (creator name) on (creation date)
Updated by (updater name) on (updating date)

Title (Native) (Title (in native language) of the selected PL)

Geographic scope Single country
Selected country (Country name)
Geographic level National level Regional level

Geographic scope Multiple countries
Which countries was the policy measure situated in?
Please select up to 10 countries from the list below.

Available country list Selected country list

Belgium Austria
United Kingdom
China Germany
.....

Select Remove

Geographic scope Supranational body
Supranational body Supranational body list

Please contact *** if the supranational body you needed isn't available.

Save and proceed Proceed without saving Cancel

[Link back to PL list](#)

(Standard footer here)

9.3.6. PL Detail page

PL Detail page will be called when [Save and proceed] or [Proceed without saving] button is clicked on PLSummary page. User can complete the PL questionnaire on this page.

Data displayed:

There are three boxes, each for a question, containing a set of checkboxes for user to select. Minimum and maximum items selectable will be displayed on top of each box.

Validation rules for PLDetail data:

At least one item must be selected in each group.

Actions available:

- [Save and complete] button:

Validated data will be saved into table [PLDetail]. The completion flag will now be set to true.

- [Go back without saving] button:

Go back to PL Summary page without saving.

- [Cancel] button

Cancel the action and return to policy measure list page without saving.

Mock page – Policy measure detail:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Policy measure details - (PL code) Status: Incomplete

(Title of the selected PL)

Targets (Recipient of the support)

Please select 1 to 10 items from the list:

- 1. Individuals (researcher, student, manager, entrepreneur, investor, etc.)
- Item 2
-
- Item 10

Modalities (How support is provided)

Please select 1 to 7 items from the list:

- 1. Direct financial support: grants, loans, guarantees, contracts, etc.
- Item 2
-
- Item 7

Policy objectives (Why the support is provided)

Please select 1 to 14 items from the list:

- 1. Enhancement of education and initial/further training
- Item 2
-
- Item 14

Save and complete Go back without saving Cancel

[Link back to PL list](#)

(Standard footer here)

9.3.7. PL Merge page – SU

TBA at later stage if time/resource permits

This page will enable SU to select two PLs and merge them to one.

9.4. Factual / Judgmental characterisation (FC/JC) related pages

9.4.1. Basic FC/JC properties

- One evaluation has one set of FC/JC attached to it.
- FC/JC is related to one researcher (owner) who enters FC data, and one PM who enters JC data. The SU can modify FC/JC data for any evaluation, however he/she won't be recorded as the person who enters FC/JC data.
- FC/JC's country will be the country selected when the evaluation is created, but will have additional data:
 - If the evaluation is for single country, the extra detail – for national or regional level – will be added in ([FJSummary]).
 - If the evaluation's selected CountryCode is Z1, i.e., "Multiple countries", the countries will be added in ([FJAdditionalCountry]).
 - If the evaluation's selected CountryCode is Z2, i.e., "Supranational body", the supranational body will be added in ([FJSummary]).
- Depending on the data entering status for FC and JC, the evaluation's DataStage changed from "New" to "JC approved". More details about the process are in Appendix 2 and 3.
- Not all the questions are answered, many are conditional. Full validation rules for FC/JC's completeness are in Appendix 5.
- PM can enter comment on FC, for questions marked as [PMCommentable] in table [FJQuestionnaire]. These are the top questions in each section, i.e. the questions with LevelA and LevelB flags, but not lower level flags. E.g., question 2.1 is PM commentable, but 2.1.1 isn't.
- FC data completed is the condition for SU to consider publishing evaluations. JC data status has no effect on evaluation's publishing consideration.

9.4.2. FC/JC data in database

a) FC/JC summary data:

This is stored in table [FJSummary], one record for each FC/JC set. Data includes

- The relations to other parts, such as EvaluationId, ResearcherId, PolicyMakerId, CountryId.
- Additional details on geographic scope, such as SupranationalBodyId, whether it's at national/regional level if it's for a single country.
- Various flags for operational needs, including
 - FC/JC data status: FCCompleted, JCCompleted, JCApproved.
 - PM's comment related information: PMCommented, PMCommentPassed.
 - Other information: NewPMNeeded.
- Owner's remarks, e.g. why the PA isn't satisfied with the JC.

Note:

The geographic scope data is stored in the [FJSummary] table, but this should be treated as an extension of the country data for an evaluation, not as part of the FC data. Hence the editing rules for this for some DataStage are different from FC data: For an evaluation which already has FJSummary data, it can be edited if DataStage hasn't reached "FC complete", but can't be deleted, regardless of the FC data duplication flag value.

b) FC/JC questionnaire data:

This part includes several tables, containing pre-defined data with fixed structure as a representation of the FC/JC questionnaire. This data is not related to individual evaluation, and cannot be changed.

- [FJSection]: This table contains section details of the FC/JC questionnaire, including section number and name, and whether it's for FC or JC.

- [FJQuestion]: A set of pre-defined FC/JC questionnaire data is stored in a fixed 5-level structure in this table. Apart from the data for questionnaire, the table also has many flags, showing whether a question is conditional, in free text type, visible, searchable, PM commentable, publishable, etc.
- [FJCondition]: A number of questions in the FC/JC questionnaire are conditional, whether they should be made visible or not will depend on the answers to other questions. The relations between the conditional questions and their trigger questions are stored here.
- [FJTree]: This is a subset of the table [FJQuestion], containing all parent-child pairs in the 5-level structure of the questionnaire.

c) FC/JC detail data:

This part is the actual answers to the FC/JC questionnaire, related to individual evaluations via [FJSummary] table. The data is stored in several tables:

- [FJDetail]: This table stores the answers to FC/JC questions.
- [FJAdditionalCountry]: When an evaluation is for multiple countries, the selected countries will be stored in this table.
- [FJPMComment]: PM's comments on PM commentable questions in FC sections are stored here, if PM makes them. An evaluation can have no PM comments.
- [FJValidation]: Record whether a FC/JC questionnaire is answered in full on section level. It provides an easy indicator to show which FC or JC sections are / aren't completed for an evaluation. The validation rules used to check the completeness of each section are in "Appendix 5 – FC & JC validation rules".

d) Other related data:

FC/JC will also use data from other parts of the database:

- The pre-defined geographic related data, including country list and supranational body list, which are stored in tables [Country] and [SupranationalBody].
- Evaluation and its DataStage data, in [Evaluation] and [DataStage] tables.
- Researcher details, in [Researcher] table.
- Policy maker details, in [PolicyMaker] table.

9.4.3. FC summary page – Editable

This page is the starting point for FC editing pages, will be displayed when user click [Edit FC] button on evaluation detail page's FC/JC tab. It's only accessible for SU and PA as owner of an Ea, and when an evaluation's DataStage is in "New" and "FC in progress".

Additional data on geographic scope for an evaluation will be taken here. Note the geographic scope data should be treated as an extension of the country data for an evaluation, not really a part of the FC.

a) Data displayed:

- The evaluation's title, code, DataStage and PubType, read only.
- Owner name – Only visible for SU (for PA the owner should be him/herself), view only.
- Geographic scope – View only.
- Further information, depending on the geographic scope:
 - Single country:

A group of radio buttons will be presented for user to choose if the evaluation is at national or regional level. No default selection is offered. The result is saved in [FJSummary].

- Multiple countries:

Lists of available countries and selected countries will be displayed, with [Select] and [Remove] buttons in between. The result will be saved into table [FJAdditionalCountry] every time a country is selected or removed. The buttons will be enabled / disabled according to the number of countries already selected.

- Supranational body:

A list of supranational body (read from table [SupranationalBody]) will be displayed for user to choose from. The result is saved in [FJSummary]. An instruction will be presented too to let user contact SU if the suitable supranational body isn't available in the list, so SU can add it into the list.

b) Validation rules for [FJSummary] data:

- For single country:

National/regional level must be selected.

- For multiple countries:

2 to 10 countries must be selected.

- For supranational body:

A supranational body must be selected.

c) Actions available:

- [Save and proceed] button:

Validated data – national / regional level for single country, supranational body – will be saved in the table [FJSummary].

- [Proceed without saving] button:

Move to FJ Detail page without saving. The button will be disabled when data required hasn't been entered.

- [Select] / [Remove] button (for multiple countries only):

Multiple country selection will be updated in table [FJAdditionalCountry].

- [Cancel] button

Cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page without saving.

Mock page – FC summary, editable:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. The user is logged in as '(Researcher name)'. The navigation menu includes 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The main content area is titled 'Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001' with a subtitle '(Title for E_GB_0001)' and '(Current PubType)'. The 'Data stage' is '(Current DataStage)'. The form has three main sections: 1. 'Owner' with a text input field '(Owner name)'. 2. 'Geographic scope' with three options: 'Single country', 'Multiple countries', and 'Supranational body'. The 'Single country' option includes a 'Selected country' dropdown and radio buttons for 'National level' and 'Regional level'. The 'Multiple countries' option includes a text input 'Which countries was the evaluation situated in?' and a selection interface with 'Available country list' (containing Belgium, United Kingdom, China, etc.) and 'Selected country list' (containing Australia, Germany). The 'Supranational body' option includes a dropdown 'Supranational body list'. At the bottom, there are three buttons: 'Save and proceed', 'Proceed without saving', and 'Cancel'. A link 'Link back to current evaluation detail page' is also present. Annotations include: 'Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"' pointing to the title; 'Only need to show owner for SU' pointing to the owner field; 'Possibility 1: If geographic scope = "Single country"' pointing to the single country section; 'Possibility 2: If geographic scope = "Multiple countries"' pointing to the multiple countries section; 'Possibility 3: If geographic scope = "Supranational body"' pointing to the supranational body section; and 'Button only enabled if required data is entered' pointing to the 'Proceed without saving' button.

9.4.4. FC summary page – Read only

This page will be displayed when user click [View FC] button on evaluation detail page's FC/JC tab, i.e., it's the page for PA who's not the owner of current Ea, or PA as an owner but the Ea's DataStage is "FC complete" or beyond.

a) Data displayed:

- The evaluation's title, code, DataStage and PubType.
- Owner name.
- Geographic scope – Single country, multiple countries or supranational body.
- Further information, depending on the geographic scope:
 - Single country:

The selected country name and national / regional level, read from [FJSummary].

- Multiple countries:

Lists of selected countries, read from table [FJAdditionalCountry].

- Supranational body:

The selected supranational body name read from [SupranationalBody].

b) Actions available:

- [Proceed] button:

This will take user to the first FC detail page (for FC section 1).

- [Cancel] button

Cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page.

Mock page – FC summary, read only:

9.4.5. FC detail pages

FC detail pages show the detailed FC questionnaire by section, and take / display the answers.

There will be 7 FC detail pages, each for a section in an evaluation’s questionnaire.

a) Data displayed:

- The evaluation’s title, code, DataStage and PubType, view only.
- Number and name of the current section in the FC questionnaire, view only.
- Owner name – Only visible for SU (for PA the owner should be him/herself), view only
- PM comment – Read only. PM’s comment is for all the top-level FC questions in each section, the [PMCommentable] flag for these questions are set to true in [FJQuestion] table.
- Detailed questions in the current section. Due to complexity the full page-by-page details will not be included here.

b) Data accessibility:

DataStage	SU	Owner PA	Non-owner PA
Pre-JC DataStages			
New, no PL and/or no owner	n/a	n/a	n/a
New, with PL and owner	Edit	Edit	n/a
FC in progress	Edit	Edit	View
FC complete, no PM	Edit	Edit	View
FC complete, with PM	View	View	View
In-JC DataStages			
JC in progress	View	View	View
Post-JC DataStages			
JC complete	View	View	View
SU consider FC	Edit, Re-submit	View	View
SU consider JC	View	View	View
JC approved	View	View	View

c) Actions available in viewing mode, to SU, owner PA and non-owner PA:

- Display data:

Due to the complexity full page-by-page details will not be listed.

- [Section x] buttons, x = 1 to 7:
 - “x” represents the section number, for FC sections 1 to 7. They will take user to relevant section page, no saving or validation is involved for viewing mode.
 - Colour code will be used to display the buttons, as an easy indication to a section’s completeness.
 - The button for current section will be highlighted and won’t be clickable.
- [Cancel] button:

Cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab).

d) Actions available in editing mode, to SU and owner PA, for pre-JC DataStages only

- Input data:

The questions in each section are grouped by top-level questions. Conditional questions are hidden unless the condition is met.

Due to complexity the full page-by-page details are not listed here.

- [Save and proceed] button:

This button is for saving FC data in all the pre-JC DataStages, for both SU and owner-PA, and available for all FC sections.

When it’s clicked, the following will happen:

- Validate (refer to Appendix 5 for validation rules) and save the data entered for all the questions in current section into [FJDetail].
- Update the [Validated] flag in table [FJValidation] for current section based on the section validation result.
- Check to see if evaluation’s DataStage and PubType need to be updated:
 - If an evaluation’s DataStage in table [Evaluation] is “New”, it should be changed to “FC in progress”; PubType should remain to be “Data not complete”.
 - If the DataStage is already “FC complete” and a section’s data is changed back to incomplete, DataStage needs to be changed back to “FC in progress”, and PubType should be changed back from “Data ready” to “Data not complete”.
- If the current section is completed, move to next section, otherwise stay in current section and show validation error message.

- [Save and complete] button:

This button is the alternative of [Save and proceed] but for last section that hasn't been answered. When it's clicked, the following will happen:

- (Same as in [Save and proceed]) Validate (refer to Appendix 5 for validation rules) and save the data entered for all the questions in current section into [FJDetail];
- (Same as in [Save and proceed]) Update the [Validated] flag in table [FJValidation] for current section based on the section validation result;
- Update flags in [FJSummary]: If the last section is completed, it means all the FC sections are completed. In this case turn the [FCCompleted] flag in [FJSummary] to true;
- Update in [Evaluation] for DataStage and PubType when all FC sections are complete (i.e. [FCCompleted] flag in [FJSummary] is set to true):
 - DataStage should be changed to "FC complete";
 - PubType should be changed to "Data ready";
- If the FC is complete, go to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab), otherwise stay in current section and show validation error message.

- [Section x] buttons, x = 1 to 7:

Same as in viewing mode.

- [Cancel] button:

Cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab) without saving.

Additional information:

- FC can be edited after it's completed, hence it's possible that an already completed FC can be changed to not-completed. So the validation rules must be applied to FC even if the evaluation is already in "FC complete" or beyond.
- For section 6 that contains scale items:
 - The scales have a default value of 50% (i.e. neutral in terms of agreeing or disagreeing), the validation rule is that user must move a slider. If 50% is the intended input, user must move a slider away and move back in order to pass the validation. The not-applicable checkboxes can overrule the scales if they are checked.
 - When a validated section 6 is re-visited and the scales contain 50% value, the section won't pass the validation unless the 50%-valued-slider(s) has been moved again (or the relevant not-applicable checkboxes are checked). This also means that if user re-visits an evaluation in "FC complete" which contains scale(s) with 50% value in section 6, and then click [Save and complete] button without moving the 50%-valued-slider(s) again, the section won't pass the validation, and the evaluation's DataStage will become "FC in progress".

e) Actions available in editing mode, to SU only, for DataStage "SU consider FC"

- Input data:

Same as in editing mode above.

SU can check PM's comment on each top level questions and modify FC if necessary.

- [Save] button:

This button is on all FC sections, and has similar functionality as the [Save and process/complete] buttons in pre-JC DataStages. When clicked for a section, the following will happen:

- Data will be validated and saved to [FJDetail], [Validated] flag in [FJValidation] will be updated accordingly (Note it's possible that the FC becomes incomplete in this process);

- The evaluation's DataStage will remain unchanged, i.e., it should stay as "SU consider FC". Note even when as the result of SU's data changing action a section becomes incomplete, the DataStage should still remain, in order to differentiate this type of evaluations with those that PA can work on;
- The evaluation's PubType should have been set to "Data not ready" in PM site when PM submitted the JC with FC comment. This should remain too.
- Similarly, the flag [FCCompleted] in [FJSummary] will be left as true;

- [Re-submit] button

This button will only be enabled when all the FC sections are completed. However FC data can be made incomplete as the result of SU's data-changing action, it's necessary to re-validate the current section and check if all sections are completed before re-submitting. If validation is failed SU will stay in current FC section view and [Re-submit] button will be disabled.

When FC is incomplete, in order to avoid PA accessing FC again the DataStage will not be changed back to "FC in progress". SU will need to re-submit FC as a fully answered set by clicking this button.

A reminding message will appear when the button is clicked, to remind SU that FC data should be saved and complete.

When the button is clicked the following will happen:

- In table [FJSummary]: The flag [PMCommentPassed] will be set to true, indicating the PM's comment on FC has been check and passed by SU, so the message can be displayed accordingly in FC box in evaluation details page's FC/JC tab.
- In table [Evaluation]: The DataStage will be turned to "JC complete", and PubType to "Data ready" again. This means the JC is ready to be approved, and the evaluation can be re-considered for publishing.
- If the evaluation is owned by someone else, an auto email will be sent to owner as an alert, so he/she can start checking JC. **Auto-email ID = PassToPAForCheckingJC, refer to Appendix 6 for email content**
- SU will be taken to the evaluation details view (FC/JC tab).

- [Cancel] button:

If the FC data is complete, this button will cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab) without saving. If SU has made the FC data incomplete, a warning message will show as a reminder, and return to evaluation detail page if user confirms the action.

Additional information for section 6 and scale items applies to the "SU consider FC" too.

Mock page – FC detail, pre-JC DataStages, editable:

A Web Page

⏪ ⏩ ✕ 🏠
http://
🔍

SiperPortalAdmin

[\(Researcher name\)](#) [Logout](#)

Home
Evaluation
Policy measure
Support data
Researcher acct
Policy maker acct
Report

Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001

(Title for E_GB_0001) Data stage (Current DataStage)

(Current PubType) Only visible when PubType isn't "NO"

(FC section number and name)

Owner (Owner name)

Policy maker (PM name)

Initially contacted on (initial contact date)

Questions.....

x.y1 (Question text) (Please tick all options that apply)

PM comment Policy maker's comment on this section.
Only visible for "JC in progress" and beyond

a. (Text for option a)

b. (Text for option b)

c. Other (Please specify)

d. Don't know

x.y2 (Question text) (Please tick only one option)

PM comment Policy maker's comment on this section.
Only visible for "JC in progress" and beyond

a. (Text for option a)

b. (Text for option b)

c. (Text for option c)

x.y3 (Question text)

PM comment No comment

x.y3.1 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	a. Text for x.y3.z.a	b. Text for x.y3.z.b	c. Text for x.y3.z.c
x.y3.2 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
x.y3.3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

x.y3.2.1 (Question text)

x.y3.2.1.1 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	a. Text for x.y3.2.1.z.a	b. Text for x.y3.2.1.z.b	c. Text for x.y3.2.1.z.c
x.y3.2.1.2 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

x.y3.2.1.1.1 (Question text)

a. (Text for option a)

b. (Text for option b)

c. (Text for option c)

x.y4 (Question text)

PM comment No comment

x.y4.1 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	a. Text for x.y4.z.a	b. Scale for x.y4.z.b
x.y4.2 (Question text adfakdjf ladf)	<input type="radio"/> Don't know	0 ———▶ 100
.....	<input type="radio"/> Don't know	0 ———▶ 100

x.y5 (Question text)

PM comment Policy maker's comment on this section.
Only visible for "JC in progress" and beyond

Save and proceed
Cancel

Button will be "Save and complete" for last incomplete section

Current section is highlighted and not clickable

Summary
Section 1
Section 2
Section 3
Section 4
Section 5
Section 6
Section 7

Move between different sections without saving. Colour code can be used to indicate if a section is completed or not

[Link back to current evaluation detail page](#)

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – FC detail, SU consider FC, editable:

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page header includes a 'University Logo' and the text 'SiperPortalAdmin'. A navigation menu contains links for 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct', 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The main content area is titled 'Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001' with a subtitle '(Title for E_GB_0001)'. To the right, it indicates 'Data stage SU consider FC'. Below this, there are fields for 'Owner (Owner name)', 'Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)', and 'JC completed on (JC completion date)'. A text area for 'Questions.....' contains the instruction '(Data entering page is the same as in pre-JC stages) FC should only be re-submitted when all the comments from PM are checked and necessary adjustments are done.' Below the text area are 'Save' and 'Cancel' buttons. A horizontal menu shows 'Summary', 'Section 1', 'Section 2', 'Section 3', 'Section 4', 'Section 5', 'Section 6', and 'Section 7'. A 'Re-submit' button is present, with a callout box pointing to it that says 'Re-submit button only enabled when all sections are complete'. A link 'Link back to current evaluation detail page' is also visible. The footer contains '(Standard footer here)'.

9.4.6. JC detail pages

JC detail pages show the detailed JC questionnaire by section, and take / display the answers.

Although JC data is entered by PM on a different site, these pages are necessary in the SiperPortalAdmin site because SU needs to be able to edit JC data, and owner PA needs to view JC data entered by PM in order to check and approve it.

There will be 4 JC detail pages, each for a section in the questionnaire.

a) Data displayed:

- The evaluation's English title, code, DataStage and PubType.
- Number and name of the current section in the JC questionnaire.
- Owner name.
- For "FC complete" with PM assigned or "JC in progress": PM name and initial contact date. For post-JC DataStages, previous PM name and assignment done date.
- Detailed questions in the current section.

Due to complexity the full page-by-page details are not included.

b) Data accessibility:

DataStage	SU	Owner PA	Non-owner PA
Pre-JC DataStages	n/a	n/a	n/a
JC in progress	View	View	View
JC complete	Edit, Re-submit	View	View
SU consider FC	View	View	View
SU consider JC	Edit, Re-submit	View	View
JC approved	View	View	View

c) Actions in viewing mode, available to both SU and PA:

- [Section x] buttons, x = 8 to 11:
 - “x” represents the section number, can be 8 to 11. They will take user to relevant section page, no saving or validation is involved for viewing mode. **Note this behaviour is different from the similar buttons in the SiperPortalPM site.**
 - Colour code will be used to display the buttons, as an easy indication to a section’s completeness.
 - The button for current section will be highlighted and won’t be clickable.
- [Cancel] button:

This will take user back to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab).

d) Additional actions in editing mode, available to SU only, in “JC complete” and SU consider JC” DataStages:

- [Save] button:

This button is in all JC sections so SU can update JC data directly in these two post-JC DataStages. When it’s clicked, the following will happen:

- Data will be validated and saved to [FJDetail]. [Validated] flag in [FJValidation] will be updated accordingly.
- The evaluation’s DataStage will remain unchanged, i.e., it should stay as “JC complete” or “SU consider JC”. Note even if as the result of SU’s data changing action a section becomes not validated, the DataStage should still remain, in order to differentiate this type of evaluations with those that PM can work on.
- Similarly, the flag [JCCompleted] in [FJSummary] will be left as true.

Additional information:

- It’s possible that the JC becomes incomplete in this process, if that happens the section will be marked as incomplete in [FJValidation].
- For JC Sections 9 and 10 where there are scale items:

The scales have a default value of 50% (i.e. neutral in terms of agreeing or disagreeing), the validation rule is that user must move a slider. If 50% is the intended input, user must move a slider away and move back in order to pass the validation. In section 9, the not-applicable checkboxes can overrule the scales if checked.

When section 9 or 10 is visited by SU it should have been completed. If the scales contain 50% value, the section won’t pass the validation unless the 50%-valued-slider(s) has been moved again (or in section 9’s case the not-applicable checkboxes are checked). This means the SU must move the 50%-valued-slider(s) to make the section complete.

- [Re-submit] button

This button will only be enabled if all the JC sections are completed. However JC data can be made incomplete as the result of SU’s data-changing action, it’s necessary to re-validate the current section and check if all sections are completed before re-submitting. And when JC is incomplete, in order to avoid PM accessing JC again the DataStage will not be changed back to “JC in progress”. SU will need to re-submit JC as a fully answered set by clicking this button, and should give relevant instructions if necessary.

A reminding message will appear when the button is clicked, to remind SU that JC data should be saved and complete.

If validation is failed SU will stay in current JC section view and [Re-submit] button will be disabled.

- For DataStage “JC complete”:

The evaluation isn’t passed from PA. Apart from saving the just entered the data and ensuring JC is complete, no other action is needed. This will mark the end of data entering from SU and the JC is ready to be approved. SU will be taken to the evaluation details view (FC/JC tab).

- For DataStage “SU consider JC”:

The evaluation is passed from PA. Same as in “JC complete” data just entered should be saved, CJ completeness should be checked, and reminding message will show when the button is clicked.

SU can choose to re-submit the JC in different ways, a radio button set will be visible in this case.

- If “JC satisfied” is ticked, the DataStage will be turned to “JC complete”. The owner-PA should get an auto email as an alert, so follow-up action (to approve JC by owner PA) can be taken. **Auto-email ID = PassToPAForJCPassed, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
- If need-new-PM is ticked, the DataStage will remain as “SU consider JC”, and flag [NewPMNeeded] in table [FJSummary] will be set to true. The owner-PA should get an auto email as an alert, so follow-up action (to assign a new PM by owner PA) can be taken. **Auto-email ID = PassToPAForNewPM, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
- If leave-it is ticked, DataStage will stay as “SU consider JC” and no other flags will be set. This means that SU will check the JC later.
- SU will be taken to the evaluation details view (FC/JC tab).

- [Cancel] button:

If the JC data is complete, this button will cancel the action and return to evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab) without saving. If SU has made the JC data incomplete, a warning message will show as a reminder, and return to evaluation detail page if user confirms the action.

Mock page – JC detail, viewing mode, for both SU and PA:

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001 Data stage (Current DataStage)

(Title for E_GB_0001)
 (Current PubType)
 (JC section name)

Owner (Owner name)
Policy maker (PM name)
 Initially contacted on (initial contact date)

For "JC in progress" DataStage

.....

Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
 JC completed on (JC completion date)

For post-JC DataStages

Questions.....
 (Question part is similar to FC)

Cancel

Section 8 Section 9 Section 10 Section 11

Current section is highlighted and not clickable

Move between different sections without saving. Colour code can be used to indicate if a section is completed or not

Link back to current evaluation detail page

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – JC detail, editing mode, for SU and DataStage "JC complete":

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (SU name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001 Data stage JC complete

(Title for E_GB_0001)
 (Current PubType)
 (JC section name)

Owner (Owner name)
Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
 JC completed on (JC completion date)

Questions.....
 (Data entering page is the same as in pre-JC stages)

Save Cancel

Section 8 Section 9 Section 10 Section 11

Re-submit

Re-submit button only enabled when all sections are complete

Current section is highlighted and not clickable

Move between different sections without saving. Colour code can be used to indicate if a section is completed or not

Link back to current evaluation detail page

(Standard footer here)

Mock page – JC detail, editing mode, for SU and DataStage “SU consider JC”:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (SU name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Factual characterisation for E_GB_0001

Data stage SU consider JC

(Title for E_GB_0001)
(Current PubType)
(JC section name)

Owner (Owner name)
Pre.Policy maker (Previous policy maker name who did the JC)
JC completed on (JC completion date)

Questions.....
(Data entering page is the same as in pre-JC stages)

Save Cancel

Section 8 Section 9 Section 10 Section 11

Re-submit JC when complete

- JC checked / amended and now satisfied
- JC not satisfied and new PM should be re-assigned to re-do JC
- Leave it as it is and check later

Re-submit

Link back to current evaluation detail page

(Standard footer here)

Annotations:

- Move between different sections without saving. Colour code can be used to indicate if a section is completed or not.
- Current section is highlighted and not clickable
- Re-submit button only enabled when all sections are complete

9.5. Researcher account maintenance functionalities

Properties of a researcher account:

- A researcher is someone with a university account and will be authenticated by the central CAS to use this application. Researcher data is stored within the application in table [Researcher] except the login details which won't be kept in the application.
- A researcher must be in one of two roles, SU or PA. Role definition is in table [Role]; the authorised activities for each role are in Appendix 1.
- A researcher can be assigned to multiple evaluations, but only one researcher can be assigned to an evaluation at a time.
- If a researcher has left his/her account will still be kept in the database but marked as unavailable. Only available researchers can be assigned to evaluations.

Note: New requirements added in this section are highlighted as purple. The development work is subject to resource availability.

9.5.1. Researcher list page

Researcher list is the starting point for maintenance functionalities for researcher data. It's available for both SU and PA.

a) Data on the page:

The researcher data will be displayed in a list with searching / sorting / paging facilities. Details included are name, username, title, position, role, number of evaluations currently assigned statistics for a researcher's assignments, and availability flag. The data is from [Researcher] and [Role] tables in the database.

Statistics for a researcher's assignments includes

- Open assignments – These are the evaluations with DataStage value being “New” and “FC in progress”.
- FC completed assignments – Evaluations' DataStage value is “FC complete”.
- JC completed assignments – Evaluations' DataStage value is “JC complete”. Note “SU to consider” ones, although might have JC completed, will not be counted in.

b) Actions available for different roles:

Action	SU	PA
Create new researcher	√	
Go to View researcher detail page		√
Go to Edit researcher detail page	√	

c) Action description:

- Create new researcher:

The [Create researcher] button is available to SU only, pointing to the Edit researcher detail page (3.5.2). The page is used for both creating and editing researcher details.

- Go to View researcher detail page:

For PA only – If clicking the username in the researcher list PA will be taken to the View researcher detail page (3.5.3).

- Go to Edit researcher detail page:

For SU only – If clicking the username in the researcher list SU will be taken to the Edit researcher detail page (3.5.2).

- Searching / sorting / paging facilities:
 - The text entered in the search box will be used to filter the content in the list.

- Click the head of a column will get the list sorted by that column.
- Number of researchers per page can be selected from a dropdown list.
- Note: The mock page doesn't show the full details of these but they are available.

Mock page – Researcher list (To be replaced):

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL 'http://'. The page title is 'SiperPortalAdmin'. There is a navigation menu with items: Home, Evaluation, Policy measure, Support data, Researcher acct (selected), Policy maker acct, and Report. A 'Logout' link is visible. A 'Create researcher' button is present. The main content is a table titled 'Researcher list' with the following data:

#	UserName	Role	Surname	Forename	Title	Position	Assignment	Active
1	mmm1111	SU	Dumbledore	Albus	Professor	Headmaster of Hotwarts	1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2	mmm2222	PA	McGonagall	Minerva	Professor	Head of Gryffindor House	5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3	mmm3333	PA	Snape	Severus	Professor	Head of Slytherin House	3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4	mmm4444	PA	Potter	Harry	Mr		0	<input type="checkbox"/>

Annotations in the image include: 'Only visible for SU' pointing to the 'Create researcher' button; 'University username' pointing to the 'UserName' column header; and 'Data table with searching/paging/sorting facilities' pointing to the table.

9.5.2. Edit researcher detail page – SU

This page is only available to SU, and can be used for two purposes and called in two ways:

- Clicking [Create new researcher] button on researcher list page, in order to create a new researcher account;
- Clicking a username in the researcher list, in order to edit/view existing researcher details.

a) Data on the page:

- Researcher data such as name, username, title, position, affiliation, contact details, etc. Note these are entered as free text; it's the SU's responsibility to ensure the accuracy of these details. The data is saved in [Researcher] table. More details about the table can be found in file "Appendix 7 - Data table details".
- Role – This should be either SU or PA. PA will be the default selection. The data is saved in [Researcher] table.
- Data only available to existing account:
 - Whether the researcher is active or not. Default is active, i.e., the flag [RAvailable] in [Researcher] table will be true. Only the active researchers will be included in the researcher list when assigning an owner to evaluations. SU can change the value of the [RAvailable] flag here to make a researcher being included or excluded in the available researcher list for evaluation assignment.
 - List of current assignment, i.e., the evaluation titles that the current researcher owns, and the total number of current assignments. Read only.
 - Assignment list for both current and completed ones, DataStage should cover "New", "FC in progress", "FC complete", "JC in progress" and "JC complete". Columns include evaluation's code, English title, country, published year, DataStage, PubType and creation date. Read only.

- Remarks.

b) Action description:

- [Create] button:

A new researcher account will be added into [Researcher] table, as an active one. Validation rules including surname/forename/username/email must be entered, and username must be unique. However, the application isn't able to check if a username is valid or not.

- [Save] button:

The selected researcher data will be updated. The validation rules are the same as in creating action.

- [Cancel] button:

Go back to researcher list page without saving or creating.

Mock page – Edit researcher detail, for SU (To be replaced):

The screenshot shows a web browser window titled 'A Web Page' with the URL 'http://'. The page header includes a 'University Logo' and the text 'SiperPortalAdmin'. A navigation menu contains 'Home', 'Evaluation', 'Policy measure', 'Support data', 'Researcher acct' (highlighted), 'Policy maker acct', and 'Report'. The main content area is titled 'Create / Edit researcher'. It contains the following form elements:

- Surname: text input field
- Forename: text input field
- Title: text input field
- UserName: text input field
- Role: radio buttons for 'Super User' and 'Project Associate' (selected)
- Position: text input field
- Affiliation: text input field
- Email: text input field
- Tel: text input field
- Active: checked checkbox
- Assignment: dropdown menu with 'List of evaluation title owned by the researcher' selected
- Remarks: large text area

 Annotations include a yellow box stating 'Data fields will be empty when creating new researcher' with arrows pointing to the Surname, Forename, Title, and UserName fields. A yellow bracket on the right side indicates 'Only visible when editing existing researcher' for the Assignment field. At the bottom are 'Create / Save' and 'Cancel' buttons, and a footer with '(Standard footer here)'.

9.5.3. View researcher detail page – PA

This page is only available to PA, and will be called when PA clicks a username in the researcher list.

All details of the selected researcher are displayed, including name, title, position, username, contact details, role, assignment details, etc. It's a read-only page, no action is available.

Mock page – View researcher detail, for PA (To be replaced):

http://

Researcher detail

Name Mr Harry Potter
UserName (UserName)
Role Super User Project Associate
Position Final year student
Affiliation Hogwarts
Email h.potter@hogwarts.wiz
Tel 123456789
Active
Assignment
Number of working assignments: 3

[Link back to researcher list page](#)

9.6. Policy maker (PM) account maintenance functionalities

PM account and PM authentication:

A PM is an external user without university account and is authenticated to use the PM site, which is a sub-site under the SiperPortalPublic site. SiperPortalPublic is a separate but related application. PM's authentication will be done by SiperPortalPublic's own authentication system, the database used for this purpose is [HumSiperPMAuth]. Full details for application SiperPortalPublic are in the specification P00418d - SiperPortalPublic.docx.

Although PM's authentication isn't done in this application, the login details are set here. PM's email will be used as username, and the password is initially generated by this application when a PM gets an assignment for the first time. The PM assigning process is covered in evaluation detail page's FC/JC tab (3.2.3.5, 3.2.3.6).

Apart from the login details, the other details of a PM are stored in table [PolicyMaker] in the main database, and the assignment details are in table [PMAssignment].

“Appendix 8 – Flowchart for PM working process on PM site” shows the PM's working process on SiperPortalPublic site, but it involves this site too.

Note: New requirements added in this section are highlighted as purple. The development work is subject to resource availabilities.

9.6.1. PM list page

PM list is the starting point for maintenance functionalities for PM data. It's available to both SU and PA.

a) Data on the page:

The PM data will be displayed in a list with searching / sorting / paging facilities. Details include name, **title**, position, affiliation, PM availability flag, and information on his/her assignments: One flag to show if a PM has a current assignment, **and a number to show how many past assignments he/she has (i.e., those with [CurrentAssignment] flag value being false in table [PMAssignment]).**

b) Action description:

- Create new PM:

The [Create PM] button will take user to the Edit PM detail page (3.6.2), the page is used for both creating and editing PM details.

- Go to Edit PM detail page:

PM's surname is a link, pointing to the Edit PM detail page (3.6.2).

- Searching / sorting / paging facilities:
 - The text entered in the search box will be used to filter the content in the list.
 - Click the head of a column will get the list sorted by that column.
 - Number of researchers per page can be selected from a dropdown list.
 - Note: The mock page doesn't show the full details of these but they are available.

Mock page – Policy maker list (To be replaced):

9.6.2. Edit PM detail page

This page is available to both SU and PA, and can be used for two purposes and called in two ways:

- Clicking [Create PM] button on PM list page, in order to create a new PM account;
- Clicking a surname in the PM list, in order to edit/view existing PM details.

a) Data on the page:

- PM's type, i.e. if it's created by SU/PA, or if it's self-created by delegated PM on SiperPortalPublic site.

For self-created type of PM, once the data is saved into [PolicyMaker] table an auto email will be sent to the owner to inform this. The email should cover the details of the new and old PMs, as well as the Ea. **Auto-email ID = PMSelfCreate, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

Upon receiving the notification, the owner needs to check the new PM's data, and re-assign the Ea to this new PM, therefore a new password will be generated for the new PM, which will be sent out as an auto email to him/her. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM1, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**

- PM's email. This is used as PM's username to login to the PM site. It's editable when creating a new PM, but only viewable once PM's account is created. If a PM needs to change email a new account should be created and the old one should be marked as unavailable.
- PM's details such as name, title, position, affiliation, etc. Note these are entered as free text, it's user's responsibility to ensure the accuracy of these details. The data is stored in [PolicyMaker] table. More details about the table can be found in file "Appendix 7 - Data table details".
- Data only available for existing PM:
 - Availability – This flag is stored as [PAvailable] in table [PolicyMaker], indicating whether the PM is available for being assigned to an evaluation. The default value is true. A PM can only be assigned to one evaluation at a time. Once an evaluation is assigned the PM will become unavailable, and will show as unavailable on this page. However a PM can be set as unavailable manually here even if no evaluation is assigned.

In summary, a PM's availability can be changed in the following ways:

Before the action	Action	After the action
Available	[Assign PM] button on Evaluation detail page: an evaluation is assigned to the PM.	Unavailable
Available	Tick available checkbox: No assignment, but the PM is manually marked as unavailable by SU or owner PA due to his/her inactiveness.	Unavailable
Unavailable	[Assign PM] button on Evaluation detail page (FC/JC tab): The evaluation is assigned to another PM. This case covers the PM delegation.	Available
Unavailable	[Release PM] button on Evaluation detail page, FC/JC tab: PM is released by SU/PA.	Available
Unavailable	[JC complete] button on SiperPortalPublic site: PM completed the JC and submitted it.	Available
N/A	[Create PM] button on SiperPortalPublic site: New PM (a delegated one by an existing assigned PM) enters own details and create a PM entry in [PolicyMaker] table.	Available

Note:

Once a PM is marked as unavailable, the availability checkbox will be disabled, i.e. SU/PA cannot manually make an unavailable PM available.

- Current assignment – Evaluation code and title, the initial contact date, and PM’s first login date. Read only.
- List of past assignments (if applicable). Read only.
- Remarks.

b) Actions available:

- [Create] button:

A new PM account will be added into [PolicyMaker] table, as an available one. Validation rules including surname/forename/email must be entered, and email must be unique as it will be used as the PM’s username in PM authentication.

- [Save] button:

The selected PM’s data will be updated in [PolicyMaker] table. The validation rules are the same as in creation action.

- [Cancel] button:

Go back to PM list page without saving or creating.

Mock page – Create / Edit policy maker detail:

A Web Page

University Logo SiperPortalAdmin (Researcher name) Logout

Home Evaluation Policy measure Support data Researcher acct Policy maker acct Report

Create / Edit policy maker

PM type Created by (Researcher name) / Self-created by the PM on PM site

Surname

Forename

Title

Position

Affiliation

Email

Re-type Email

Tel

Available

Assignment (Evaluation code and title)

Initially contacted on (initial contact date)

First logged in on (first login date)

Past assignment

Remarks

(Standard footer here)

Data fields will be empty when creating new PM

The checkbox will be disabled if the PM is unavailable, i.e., researcher can make a PM unavailable with this checkbox, but can't make a PM available here

Only visible when editing existing PM

9.7. Support data maintenance functionalities

Support data includes the following:

- Country
- Supranational body
- Document category
- Document language

They are pre-defined, and can only be maintained by SU.

9.7.1. Maintain Country data page

TBA when time/resource permits. More information is needed.

9.7.2. Maintain Supranational body data page

Following functions are available:

a) Edit existing supranational body's detail

Only the code and name can be edited, and the validation rules are simple, so the inline editing is used in this case. User can double click a supranational body's code or name in the list, update the value, and click [Enter] key to save the data. Validation error message is provided in a pop-up box. Validation rules: For code and name, the length must be within the valid limit, and unique.

b) Add new supranational body

An [Add] button is available, once clicked an add-new-supranational-body-panel becomes visible for user to enter data. The same validation rules apply. Once added in the new item will appear in the list.

c) Delete unused supranational body

An [Delete] column is included in the supranational body list, showing a [Delete] link for unused ones, and "In use" text for used ones. A selected item will be deleted if clicking the [Delete] link.

9.7.3. Maintain Document category data page

The document category data is used in the SPPublic site as the search criteria, hence can't be deleted, and new items can't be added in without changing the SPPublic site. The only updatable detail is the category name. User can double click a category's name in the list to edit it, and click [Enter] button to save it. Validation rules are that a name's length must be within the valid limit, and unique. Error message is provided in a pop-up box.

Note: The text appearing on the SPPublic site won't be changed here. This needs more work.

9.7.4. Maintain Document language data page

Same as document category.

9.8. Report functionalities

TBA at later stage if time/resource permits

The following data can be exported to spreadsheet:
(Detailed requirement TBA)

10. Technical overview

10.1. General information

- The application is written with MVC4 / .Net 4.5, JavaScript / JQuery are also used.
- The application's databases are hosted on the server SQLDef.dbs.ds.man.ac.uk,6503 (SQL Server 2012).
 - Testing databases: [HumSiperPortalDev] and [HumSiperPMAuthDev]
 - Production databases: [HumSiperPortal] and [HumSiperPMAuth]

Note these servers are outside of the University's firewall.

- The data in SiperPortalBasic's database [HumSiperBasicDev] will be migrated into [HumSiperPortal] once this application is launched.
- The web application are hosted on the University servers.
 - Testing site:

[\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalAdmin](http://hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalAdmin)

URL: <http://webnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalAdmin/>

- Production site:

[\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalAdmin](http://publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk/HUM/SiperPortalAdmin)

URL: <http://siper-admin.manchester.ac.uk/>

This is the site protected by the University's CAS.

- Depending on the publishable status, uploaded documents will be stored separately in two folders:
 - Publishable ones are stored outside of the admin site so to ensure those documents are accessible by the SiperPortalPublic site. URL for publishable documents:
 - Testing site:

[\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalUploads](http://hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalUploads)

- Production site:

[\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalUploads](http://publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk/HUM/SiperPortalUploads)

- Non-publishable ones are stored within the admin site under App_Data/_Docs_NonPublishable folder
- The permission setting for these folders must be made to allow full access, so authenticated users can upload / rename / delete the documents and subfolders.

10.2. Data schema

The applications will use two databases:

- [HumSiperPortal]: This is the main database for all the applications.
- [HumSiperPMAuth]: This is for PM authentication on SiperPortalPM site.

The schema is in file "Appendix 4 – Data schema".

10.3. Table details

Please refer to file "Appendix 7 – Data table details".

10.4. Related documents

- For application SiperPortalPM see "P00418c – SiperPortalPM" for details.
- For application SiperPortalPublic see "P00418d – SiperPortalPublic" for details.

11. Assumptions and other notes

This section summarises the assumptions of the project:

- The design and style of the static pages of the applications:

- SiperPortalPublic site:

This will be done by Marketing & Communication team. The University's style will be adopted.

- SiperPortalAdmin site:

As this is an internally used site, a very plain style will be used.

- SiperPortalPM site:

Styles similar to SiperPortalAdmin site will be adopted for this site.

- The domain registration:

This is dealt with centrally.

- Security certificate for SiperPortalPM site:

This is an authenticated site for external users hence a site security certificate needs to be applied and paid for. To be done via central IT.

- Many parts of this application will need to be integrated with other applications – SiperPortalPM / SiperPortalPublic. There may be alterations in this application due to the integration requirements at later stage.
- The FC/JC/PL questionnaires are fixed, in terms of structure, logic and accessibility by different roles. Due to the complexity of these questionnaires the full page-by-page design won't be covered in this document.
- The mock pages are only used as an illustrative tool to explain the design, and should only be viewed that way.

12. Glossary

12.1. User related

Term	Meaning
SU	Super user, the project team leader, with University account
PA	Project associate, with University account
PM	Policy maker, external, no University account
Researcher	SU, PA
Evaluation owner	Researcher who has been assigned to the Evaluation

12.2. Evaluation related

Term	Meaning
En	Evaluation without an owner
Ea	Evaluation with an assigned owner
PL	Policy measure
FC	Factual characterisation
JC	Judgemental characterisation

13. Contacts

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7.7 Annex 7: SIPER Portal PM Technical Specifications

(see next page)

P00418c

SiperPortalPM

Version 4.2Page Break

Revision History

Version	Date	Change description
1.0	17/06/2015	Initialversion.
1.1	01/07/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• UpdatedDataStagedetails to match the changes inSPAdmin.• Added details for introductory PDF file link, etc.
2.0	22/07/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• UpdatedDataStage/PubTypedetails to match the changes inSPAdmin.• Added more details related to PM account, auto emails, etc.
2.1	07/08/2015	Added more details related to PM account maintenance section.
2.2	27/10/2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Added details for auto-logout.• Added more details related to evaluation's documents.
3.0	08/01/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Updateddetails onsite hosting/security.• Updated details related to the core data schema change.
3.1	22/01/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Added details for recording login date/time.
3.2	04/02/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Updated the saving / moving logic on FC section pages.• Updated the detail related to theSiper'sgeneral email.
4.0	07/03/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Updated login page/ home page /

		<p>JC/FC section pages to meet the changed requirement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Added in evaluation dashboard page to meet the new requirement. • Removed functionalities related to past evaluations.
4.1	18/03/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amended details related to the SU's general email. • Added details related to the secured site for production site.
4.2	17/05/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updated details related to the button behaviours in JC data entering pages in order to meet the changed requirement. • Updated details related to the scale items.

Page Break

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1. Overview

SIPER stands for Science and Innovation Policy Evaluations Repository, which is a part of a larger scale multi-partner effort titled The Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS) project. SIPER's objective is "to identify, collect, characterise evaluation reports and present them to wider stakeholders, and to conduct academic research by analysing these evaluations."

The SIPER Portal project is required by the MBS's SIPER team. There will be four web applications for the project:

- Part A, SiperPortalBasic – The basic data gathering tool, for very few users in the Siper project team. It will offer the basic data gathering facilities for user to enter certain project data, full details can be seen in the specification for the tool – “P00418a – SiperPortalBasic”. This application will only be used as a temporary tool during phase 1, and will not be authenticated. The functionalities will be covered in the full version of the admin tool (Part B) at later stage.
- Part B, SiperPortalAdmin – The full version of the Siper Portal admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the Siper project team. It will be protected by the University’s CAS. The application offers facilities for researcher to administrate project data. Full details will be covered in the specification “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.
- Part C, SiperPM – An authenticated site with the access restricted to the external stakeholders (Policy Makers, or PMs), for them to work on authorized part of the project data. This will be protected by the application’s own authentication system. Full details will be covered in the specification – “P00418c – SiperPortalPM” (this document).
- Part D, SiperPortalPublic – A public site with searching facilities, for public user to search the project data. Full details will be covered in the specification – “P00418d – SiperPortalPublic”.

The development work will be carried out in phases (subject to review):

Phase	Description
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database forSiperPortalBasic • SiperPortalBasic
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Databases forSiperPortalAdminandSiperPortalPublic • Key functionalities ofSiperPortalAdminfor evaluation data • SiperPortalPublicsitestyles (static) • Authenticationrelated functionalitiesofSiperPortalPM
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities ofSiperPortalPM • Integration betweenSiperPortalAdminandSiperPortalPM
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key functionalities ofSiperPortalPublic • The rest of the functionalities for all applications

Page Break

2. Authentication and authorisation

1. Authentication

This application is protected by the application’s built-in authentication system. Users – Policy makers, or PMs – are external, their user account and initial login details are set in SiperPortalAdmin, and emailed to individual PM when an evaluation is assigned to him/her.

Evaluation owners (users of SiperPortalAdmin) know the initial passwords generated by SiperPortalAdmin (auto notification email with PM’s initial login details is copied to owner), but won’t know the password if PM changes it. In case of PM forgetting his/her password owner can reset it with the password-resetting functionality in the SiperPortalAdmin site, the existing data the PM already entered (if the PM has a current assignment) will remain.

Once a PM is assigned an evaluation and gets login details set, he/she can always access the site, even after the assignment is completed, i.e. a PM’s login details will not be expired. However the functionalities available depend on whether a PM has a current assignment or not. More details in relevant sections below.

More account related details are in section 3.6 “Account related pages”.

More technical details are in section 4 “Technical overview”.

2. **Authorisation for PM**

PM is the only type of user for this application and is authorised to access all the pages. However certain functionalities are only authorised for PM with a current assignment. See more details in relevant sections below.

Page Break

3. **Functional overview**

1. **Outline**

The purpose of the SiperPortalPM is to provide various facilities for PM to enter certain part of the required data for Siper project.

a. **Status of evaluations:**

Two types of status are used for an evaluation:

- **DataStage:**
A unique indicator for an evaluation’s data entering status, showing which stage an evaluation is currently in in terms of setting up evaluation data during the whole working process. Certain actions can be taken for evaluations in certain stages.
- **PubType**
A unique indicator for an evaluation’s publishing status.

Full DataStage details are stored in table [DataStage] and summarised below. DataStages not relevant to PM are greyed out:

Code	Name	PrecedingDataStage	SucceedingDataStage	Change triggered by	Possible matching PubTypecode
1	New	None	2	SU/PA	NO
2	FC in progress	1	3	SU/PA	NO
3	FC complete	2	4	SU/PA	Any except NO /AB
4	JC in progress	3	5, 6	PM	Any except NO /AB
5	JC complete	4, 6, 7	3, 8	PM	Any except NO /AB

6	SU consider FC	4	5	PM	Any except AB
7	SU consider JC	4	3, 5	PA	Any except NO /AB
8	JC approved	5	-	SU/PA	Any except NO /AB
9	Abandoned	1 ~ 8	1 ~ 8	SU	NO

Full PubType details are summarised below, for information only. Its value won't be changed in this application.

Code	Name	Relevant to this application
NO	Data not ready	No
RD	Data ready	Yes
FP	Published	No
PP	Partially published	No
ST	Stored	No
AB	Abandoned	No

b. **Menu items**

The top level menu items include the following:

- Home – Starting and ending page for the application, containing various information.
- Dashboard – Containing data of the currently assigned evaluation and all data entering functionalities.
- Manage account – For PM to change password, and for delegated user to setup own PM account.

Page Break

2. **Login and home pages**

1. **Login page**

This is the first page of the site. There is brief introduction information about the project and the site. PM can input username and password to login.

PM should have received an email when an evaluation is assigned to him/her, with the information about the assignment and login details. Username is the PM's email; initial password is generated by SiperPortalAdmin (more details are in "P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin", section 3.2.3.5, FC/JC tab – SU).

Login details are stored in database [HumSiperPMAuth], password is encrypted.

PM must use initial password to do the first login.

Once logged in, PM can change the password. More details are in section 3.6 “Account related pages”.

This page uses a checkbox to take information from user on delegation:

a. Default option:

User isn't a delegate or doesn't want to create a new PM account.

In this case login button will take user to the home page and PM can start entering data.

b. Delegation option:

User is a delegate and wants to create a new PM account for him/herself.

In this case user can check the checkbox before clicking the login button and will be taken to the “Create new PM account” page for him/her to provide own details, so a new PM account will be set up in the database. More details are in section 3.6 “Account related pages”.

Note: Creating a new PM account for delegate is only available to PM who has a current assignment. However the application can't decide if a PM has a current assignment or not since user hasn't logged in yet at the stage, hence must leave the option available to all.

Siper research team's general contact email – siper@manchester.ac.uk – is offered on the page, for PM to contact the team and request a new password to be generated, should him/her forget it. The email is only accessible to the SUs of the SiperPortalAdmin site. The recipient list is as follows:

Abdullah Gok abdullah.gok@mbs.ac.uk

Yanchao Li yanchao.li@mbs.ac.uk

Note there is another general email – superuser.siper@manchester.ac.uk – which has the same recipient list but is used for different purpose: The application generated email alert will use this as the SU email. More details are in “Appendix 6 - Auto email list”.

User will be automatically logged out if there is no action for a certain period of time. The default number is 30 minute, set in the application's configuration file (web.config).Page Break

Mock page – Login:

2. Home page

Authenticated PM will be directed to the home page, which contains the following details:

- More detailed introduction about the project and the site. The content depends on whether the PM has a current assignment or not. Note a PM can still login and see this page even without any current assignment if he/she has past assignments.
- For PM that has a current assignment, a [Proceed to data entry] button is available, pointing to the dashboard page.
- There are other links, pointing to a user manual in PDF format with detailed instruction on how to use the site; and a video clip as a demonstration. Please provide the URLs for these links

The page is also used as a finishing page for PM, to show a thank you message after PM submitted the input, or a confirmation message after a delegate created own PM account.

Other functions this page has:

- Use PM's username to retrieve assignment details from [PMAssignment] table in main database and see if there is a current assignment for user to work on; Use session variable to keep/pass this information between pages.
- [FirstLoginDate] in [PolicyMaker] table should be updated accordingly if it's the PM's first login.
- [LastLoginDate] in [PolicyMaker] table should be updated too. The information isn't used for this site, but will be displayed in SiperAdmin site for researcher to check, in order to avoid PM reassigning / releasing at an inappropriate time.

Page Break

Mock page – Home page as starting and finishing page:

Page Break

3. **Dashboard page**

This page contains basic evaluation information, document list, contact details of the researcher, and action buttons for data entering.

There are two ways to access the page: Via the [Dashboard for data entry] item on menu bar, and via the [Proceed to data entry] button on home page. The page is only available to PM with a current assignment. When a PM without current assignment accesses the page a message is displayed to explain.

1. **Data displayed**

- **Basic evaluation data:**

Code, titles, geographical scope related information, author, year published. The title in English will be displayed as the headline of the page. Read-only.

- **Document:**

The evaluation's documents are displayed in a plain list with no searching / sorting / paging facilities. Columns include document name, category, language, copyright related information, and view content action.

In the view content column, for each publishable document a view icon is available for PM to view its content in a separate tab/window; for non-publishable documents the column is left empty.

- **Contact details:**

Details of the evaluation's owner are displayed in this box, including name, email and telephone.

- Links to user manual and demo video are also available, same as the Home page.

2. **Actions:**

The data entering actions are grouped in two tasks, for JC and comment on FC, and a [Submit] button is also on the page.

a. **Task 1:**

Task 1 is to enter JC and is compulsory. There is a brief explanation in the box about the task.

Data input buttons for JC sections 8~11 take user to each JC section page to input data.

Texts used on the buttons are the section names as stored in the [FJSection] table in the database, i.e.:

- For Section 8: Part A Dissemination
- For Section 9: Part B Quality issues
- For Section 10: Part C Use of Evaluation
- For Section 11: Part D Further Comments

Data completion status for each section is indicated on buttons:

- Button for complete section is in green, additional text “Completed” is shown below the button.
- Button for incomplete section is in red, the additional text is “In progress”.

Note: For section 11, the status can be turned to complete by clicking the saving button on the section page, even if no content is entered.

b. **Task 2:**

Task 2 is to enter comment for FC and is optional. There is a brief explanation in the box about the task.

Data input buttons for FC sections 1~5 and 7 take user to each FC section page to view FC and make comments. Texts used on the buttons are the section names as stored in the [FJSection] table in the database, i.e.:

- For Section 1: Basic Information
- For Section 2: Topics Covered
- For Section 3: Evaluation Design
- For Section 4: Data collection Methods
- For Section 5: Data analysis Methods
- For Section 7: Researcher’s Comments

Commenting status for each section is indicated on buttons:

- If comments are made in a FC section, the button is in green, additional text “Commented” is shown below the button.
- If comments are not made in a FC section, the button is in yellow, the additional text is “Add comment”.

c. **Submit:**

[Submit your input] button is for user to submit the data. By default the button is disabled, will only be enabled when task 1 is complete. The button is larger and in orange. A message will be displayed above the button as a reminder for user to submit the data.

Clicking the submit button marks the end of the PM’s data entering process. When clicked, the following should happen:

- In [Evaluation] table: The evaluation’s DataStage is turned to “JC complete” if no comments are made to FC; or “SU consider FC” otherwise. If DataStage is changed to “SU consider FC” the PubType should be changed to “Data not ready” at the same time.
- In [PMAssignment] table: The assignment is marked as past (set [CurrentAssignment] to false), that means PM cannot edit data any more. The completion date is stored in [AssignmentDoneDate]. The session variables are updated too.
- In [FJSummary] table: The JC completed flag ([JCCompleted]) should be set to true, and the date is also recorded ([PMUpdatedDate]).
- In [PolicyMaker] table: Mark the PM as available (set [PAvailable] to true), so the PM can take new assignment again.

- User will be taken back to the home page with a thank you message.

Note once [Submit] button is clicked the assignment will become a past one, PM won't be able to edit it anymore. There is a pop up box showing the reminding message about this when user clicks the [Submit] button.

Page Break

Mock page – Dashboard for PM with current assignment:

Page Break

4. **JC details pages**

PM can edit JC data which is grouped in 4 pages, each for a JC section. The JC details pages have similar structure, and can be accessed by the data entering buttons in dashboard page's task 1 box.

These pages are only available to PM with a current assignment. When a PM without current assignment accesses the pages a message is displayed to explain.

a. **Data displayed:**

- **General information:**

This includes evaluation's code and title, from [Evaluation] table. Note only the current assignment is available.

The section number is replaced by Part A~D.

- **Section specific data:**

This is the detailed questions in current JC section. The section number in question numbers is removed to avoid confusion, e.g., Q8.2 is displayed as Q2 in section 8's page.

Note: The JC questionnaire is pre-defined data with fixed 5-level structure, not related to individual evaluation. The data is stored in 4 tables: [FJSection], [FJQuestion], [FJCondition], [FJTree]. This data cannot be changed.

b. **Action:**

- **[Save and proceed] button:**

This is available when there is at least one other incomplete JC section.

- Save data into [FJDetail] table in the database, and update [FJValidation] accordingly.
- If DataStage is still "FC complete", this should be changed to "JC in progress" now.
- If the validation and/or data saving action for current JC section are failed, the same section page remains, and a detailed validation failure message and/or an action error message will be displayed.
- If the validation is passed and the data is successfully saved, user will be taken to the first incomplete JC section page. Note an incomplete section can be before or after the current one, since user can start data entering from any section.

- **[Save and return to Dashboard] button:**

This is the button same as [Save and proceed], available when the current JC section is the last incomplete one.

- If the validation and/or data saving action for current JC section are failed, the same section page remains, and a detailed validation failure message and/or an action error message will be displayed.

- If the validation is passed and the data is successfully saved, user will be taken to the dashboard page. Note DataStage value won't be changed when this button is clicked (It will only be changed if PM clicks [Submit] button on the dashboard page).
 - Section buttons:

Section names are used as button names, retrieved from the [FJSection] table in the database, section numbers are replaced by "Part A~D". Colour code indicates if a section is complete (green) or not (red). Current section is highlighted in yellow and not clickable.

 - As long as the data is successfully saved, user will be taken to the selected JC section page, regardless of the data validation result for current section. Note user won't be able to see the validation failure message (if there is any) since he/she will be taken to another section, but will be able to notice the change of the section button colour.
 - If the data saving action is failed, the same section page remains, and an action error message will be displayed. Validation failure message will be shown as well if it exists.
 - Note this behaviour is different from the similar buttons in the SiperPortalAdmin site.
 - [Cancel] button:

New data entered is discarded. User is taken back to the dashboard page.
- c. **Additional information:**
- For question 8.1: A dropdown list of years is used for user to enter data. The list contains 25 years, starting from the current year.
 - For JC Sections 9 and 10 where there are scale items:
 - The scales have a default value of 50% and the validation rule is that user must move a slider. If 50% is the intended input, user must move a slider away and move back in order to pass the validation. In section 9, the not-applicable checkboxes can overrule the scales if checked.
 - When a validated section 9 or 10 is re-visited and the scales contain 50% value, the section won't pass the validation unless the 50%-valued-slider(s) has been moved again (or in section 9's case the not-applicable checkboxes are checked). This also means that if user re-visits a completed section 9 or 10 that contains scale(s) with 50% value, and then click another section's button without moving the 50%-valued-slider(s) again, the section will become incomplete.

Mock page – JC sections:

Page Break

5. **FC comment pages**

These pages provide facilities for PM to view evaluation's FC data by section, and make comments. There are 6 pages, each for a visible-to-PM FC section (i.e. section 1 to 5 and 7), with similar structure, and can be accessed by the data entering buttons in dashboard page's task 2 box.

These pages are only available to PM with a current assignment. When a PM without current assignment accesses the pages a message is displayed to explain.

- a. **Data displayed:**
- FC data in a section, read-only.

- Comments for PM-commentable questions.
- Section number won't be displayed in section's title.
- Section number won't be displayed in question numbers either, e.g. Q3.1 will be displayed as Q1 in section 3 page.

b. **Actions:**

- [Save] button:

Comments will be saved into [FJPMComment] table in the database. User will stay in the same JC section page.

A result message will be shown, which can be a successful message (when data is saved), or an action error message (when something is wrong and the saving failed).

If DataStage is still "FC complete", this should be changed to "JC in progress" now.

If [PMCommented] flag in [FJSummary] table hasn't been changed to true it should be changed now.

- Section buttons:

Section names are used as button names, as stored in the [FJSection] table in the database, section number won't be included. The function of these buttons is similar to [Save] button, but will take user to the selected FC section page after data is saved. Note there is no section button for current section.

- [Cancel] button:

New comment entered is discarded. User is taken back to the dashboard page.

Note:

- The FC questionnaire is pre-defined data with fixed 5-level structure, not related to individual evaluation. The data is stored in 4 tables: [FJSection], [FJQuestion], [FJCondition], [FJTree]. This data cannot be changed.
- [Section 6] is hidden to PM so won't be included here.
- Section 7 only contains one FC question. If this question has no value the comment will not be taken.
- For a particular evaluation, DataStage can be changed backwards, i.e., from "JC complete" or "SU consider JC" to "FC complete", by user of SiperPortalAdmin site.

Page Break

Mock page – FC sections for commenting:

Page Break

6. **Account related pages**

PM account details are stored in two databases:

a. [HumSiperPortal] – SiperPortal's main database

- Table [PolicyMaker]: PM account details

PM data is mainly entered by researchers (SU/PA) in SiperPortalAdmin.

In SiperPortalPM, a person delegated by a PM can also enter own data to setup a new PM account for him/herself, and wait for the evaluation's owner to change the assignment to him/her. In this case the flag [SelfCreated] flag will be set to true.

- Table [PMAssignment]: Assignment details

Assignment details are set in SiperPortalAdmin when an evaluation is assigned to a PM by a researcher. The [CurrentAssignment] flag will be initialised to true. In SiperPortalPM, the [CurrentAssignment] flag will be reset to false when PM completes the JC data entering and clicks the [Submit] button on evaluation details page, and the [AssignmentDoneDate] will be set up too in this table.

b. [HumSiperPMAuth] – Login details for PM authentication.

- Table [UserProfile]:

It contains PM's username, created when an evaluation is assigned to a PM by a researcher in SiperPortalAdmin.

- Table [webpages_Membership]:

This stores PM's encrypted password and related information, created when an evaluation is assigned to a PM by a researcher in SiperPortalAdmin, and can be changed by PM when changing password.

There are three pages in this section:

- Change password – the 1st item under [Manage your account] in menu bar.
- Maintain account details – the 2nd under [Manage your account] in menu bar.
- Create new PM – This doesn't appear in the dropdown menu.

1. **Change password page**

This page allows PM to change own password. Data is stored in table [webpages_Membership], database [HumSiperPMAuth].

PM can access this page to get password changed as long as he/she can login, this means that a PM can still change password even if there is no current assignment.

Users of SPAdmin site – SUs and PAs – won't get new password.

Page Break

Mock page – Change password:

2. **Maintain PM details page**

This page allows PM to update his/her details except the login details. It is available to PM as long as he/she has a valid login account, this means that a PM can still change his/her details even if there is no current assignment.

a. **Data editable:**

PM's details such as name, title, position, affiliation, etc. Note email can't be changed because it's used as the login username. PM's details are entered as free text, it's user's responsibility to ensure the accuracy of the details.

b. **Action:**

- [Save] button:
 - The updated details will be saved into [PolicyMaker] table.
 - An auto email will be sent out about the change and copied to the PM him/herself. The email should cover details of the PM, and if it's for a current assignment, evaluation's details will be included too.

- If a PM has a current assignment, the email will be sent to the owner. **Auto-email ID = PMDetailChange1. Refer to Appendix 6 for email content.** A copy will be sent to the general SU email too.
- If a PM has no current assignment, the email will be sent to the general SU email superuser.siper@manchester.ac.uk. **Auto-email ID = PMDetailChange2. Refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
- [Cancel] button:
Discard data and go back to Home page.

Page Break

Mock page – Maintain PM details:

3. Create new PM account page

A PM with a current assignment can delegate his/her assignment to someone else. In this case the delegate can use the application in two ways:

- He/she can use the original PM's login details to enter data without informing the evaluation owner. The owner won't know if it's originally assigned PM or delegate who provided the JC data.
- He/she can choose to setup own account as a new PM, and inform the evaluation owner who can then re-assign the evaluation to him/her, so he/she will act as a proper PM. This page is to enable a delegate to do this.

This page doesn't appear as a secondary menu item in the [Manage your account]'s dropdown menu. It can only be accessed from the login page, when user logs in with original PM's credentials, and selects the delegation option to create own account.

The function for creating new PM account is only available to PM with a current assignment. If the logged-in user select the delegation option but has no current assignment this page only shows an explaining message.

a. Data required:

PM's details such as name, title, position, affiliation, email, etc. Email will be used as the new PM's username and will be validated by the application to ensure it's in a valid format and is unique. Other details are entered as free text, it's user's responsibility to ensure the accuracy of these details. The data is stored in [PolicyMaker] table.

b. Action:

- [Create] button:
 - A new PM account is added into [PolicyMaker] table, as an available one ([PAvailable] flag set to true), and self-created ([SelfCreated] flag set to true).
 - An auto email is sent to the owner to inform this and copied to the new PM him/herself. The email content should cover details of both original and new PMs, and evaluation's details as well. A copy will be sent to Siper's general SU email too (refer to Login page section for details of the Siper general email). **Auto-email ID = PMSelfCreate. Refer to Appendix 6 for email content.**
 - In SPAdmin:
Upon receiving the notification, the owner can check the new PM's data, and take the following action:

The owner should re-assign the Ea to the new PM, therefore a new password will be generated for him/her and added into the authentication database, which will be sent out as an auto email to him/her. **Auto-email ID = EvAssignPM1, refer to Appendix 6 for email content.** By doing so the original PM will be released from the assignment and become available again, and the new PM will get the assignment and become unavailable in [PolicyMaker] table; and the assignment details will be updated too. Full details on re-assigning PM are covered in SPAdmin's specification.

- [Cancel] button:
Discard data and go back to Home page.

Mock page – Create new PM account:

Page Break

4. Technical overview

1. General information

- The application is written with MVC4 / .Net 4.5, JavaScript / JQuery is also used. Data is stored in SQL databases.
- The application's databases is hosted on the server SQLDef.dbs.ds.man.ac.uk,6503 (SQL Server 2012).

- Testing databases: [HumSiperPortalDev] and [HumSiperPMAuthDev]
- Production databases: [HumSiperPortal] and [HumSiperPMAuth]

Note these servers are outside of the University's firewall.

- The web application is hosted on the University's servers:

- Testing site:

[\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalPM](http://hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalPM)

URL: <http://webnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalPM/>

- Production site:

[\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalPM](http://publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk/HUM\SiperPortalPM)

URL: <https://siper.manchester.ac.uk/>

- Publishable documents are stored outside of the admin site and are accessible to PM users URL for publishable documents:

- Testing site:

[\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalUploads](http://hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalUploads)

- Production site:

[\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalUploads](http://publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk/HUM\SiperPortalUploads)

- The production site is protected by the application's own authentication system and has a dedicated IP address (instead of a shared one), in order for it to have its own security certificate (SSL certificate). The calls for the site will be automatically redirected to the secured server.

2. Data schema

The applications will use two databases:

- [HumSiperPortal]: This is the main database for all the SiperPortal applications.
- [HumSiperPMAuth]: This is for PM authentication on SiperPortalPM site.

The schema is in file "Appendix 4 – Data schema".

3. **Table details**

Please refer to file “Appendix 7 – Data table details”.

4. **Related documents**

For application SiperPortalAdmin see “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin” for details.

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5. **Assumptions and other notes**

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

6. **Glossary**

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

7. **Contacts**

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

7.8 Annex 8: SIPER Portal Public Technical Specifications

(see next page)

P00418d

SiperPortalPublic

Version 2.3

Revision History

Version	Date	Change description
1.0	16/11/2015	Initial version.
2.0	05/02/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content amended/added in based on the latest core data change. • Detail updated in CS panel. • Detail added/updated for FC data displaying in evaluation detail page. • Detail added related to site integration.
2.1	26/02/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detail added/updated for PL and FC data displaying in evaluation detail page.
2.2	04/05/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Search rules for FC related data (SC sections 3~6, in 3.2.4.3) rephrased to avoid ambiguity. • Search rules for Doc related data (SC sections 7, in 3.2.4.4) rephrased to avoid ambiguity. • Prime URL is added in.
2.3	24/05/2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some details in CB panel are updated, including mouse-over message; country list (for both PL and evaluation); published year list; document related criteria. • Google Analytics account related detail is added in.

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14. Overview

SIPER stands for Science and Innovation Policy Evaluations Repository, which is a part of a larger scale multi-partner effort titled The Research Infrastructure for Science and Innovation Policy Studies (RISIS) project. SIPER's objective is "to identify, collect, characterise evaluation reports and present them to wider stakeholders, and to conduct academic research by analysing these evaluations."

The SIPER Portal project is required by the MBS's SIPER team. There will be four web applications for the project:

- Part A, SiperPortalBasic – The basic data gathering tool, for very few users in the Siper project team. It will offer the basic data gathering facilities for user to enter certain project data, full details can be seen in the specification for the tool – "P00418a – SiperPortalBasic". This application will only be used as a temporary tool during phase 1, and will not be authenticated. The functionalities will be covered in the full version of the admin tool (Part B) at later stage.
- Part B, SiperPortalAdmin – The full version of the Siper Portal admin tool, an authenticated site for members of the Siper project team. It will be protected by the University's CAS. The application offers facilities for researcher to administrate project data. Full details will be covered in the specification "P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin".
- Part C, SiperPM – An authenticated site with the access restricted to the external stakeholders (Policy Makers, or PMs), for them to work on authorized part of the project data. This will be protected by the application's own authentication system.

Full details will be covered in the specification – "P00418c – SiperPortalPM".

- Part D, SiperPortalPublic – A public site with searching facilities, for public user to search the project data. Full details will be covered in the specification – "P00418d – SiperPortalPublic" (this document).

The development work will be carried out in phases.

The relationship of the four applications is illustrated in Appendix 14.

15. General information about SiperPortalPublic site

15.1. Data:

SiperPortalPublic will use the same database as SiperPortalAdmin, i.e. [HumSiperPortal].

15.2. Authentication and authorisation

The site will be publically available with no authentication. All the functionalities are accessible to all users.

15.3. Site structure

The site contains the following menu items:

Menu item	Type	Content
Home	Static	Introduction
Repository	Dynamic	Searchable Siper data retrieved from [HumSiperPortal]
About	Static	
Publications	Static	
News & events	Static	
Contact	Static	

The University website's styles will be adopted and provided by the Marketing and Communication team. A Siper-specific copyright statement will replace the University's general one.

This document only covers details of the Repository section.

16. Functional overview

16.1. Outline of the repository

16.1.1. Evaluation's availability on public site

Evaluation's availability on this site is dictated by its [PubType] value in table [Evaluation], set in application [SiperPortalAdmin] by SU. Only the published evaluations, i.e. evaluations with [PubTypeCode] value set to "FP" (Fully Published) will be available on the site.

The possible DataStages (in table [DataStage], refer to specification "P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin" for more details) for published evaluations can be

- FC complete
- JC in progress
- JC complete
- SU consider JC
- JC approved

Available properties for published evaluations include

- Basic data – Titles, geographical area information, author, published year
- Selected PL(s) – Title, details
- Documents – Name, category, language of both publishable and non-publishable documents, and content of the publishable ones
- Publishable FC questions and answers

An available evaluation can become unavailable again and disappear from the searchable evaluations in three cases:

- SU abandons an evaluation on SiperPortalAdmin site, its PubType will be changed to "Abandoned".
- SU changes an evaluation's PubType from "Published" to "Stored" on SiperPortalAdmin site.
- An evaluation's PubType is changed from "Published" to "Data not ready" when a PM submits JC data on SiperPortalPM site with his/her comment on FC. The evaluation's DataStage will be turned to "SU consider FC" by this action so SU can review/edit FC data again, and re-publish the evaluation.

16.1.2. Search criteria structure and combination logic

Search criteria is organised in a hierarchy and grouped in 7 sections. This is a pre-defined data and won't be changed. Each section contains a fixed number of sub-sections which can be a searchable item itself or an unsearchable title only; each sub-section contains a fixed number of searchable child-items.

Search criteria data is stored in tables [SCSection] and [SCDetail]. See table structure details in [Appendix 7 – Data table details].

Search section summary:

#	Section name	Sub-section type	Sub-section count
1	Related policy measure characteristics	Unsearchable	4
2	Evaluation characteristics: Basic	Unsearchable	6
3	Evaluation characteristics: Topics covered	Searchable	15
4	Evaluation characteristics: Design	Searchable	5
5	Evaluation characteristics: Data collection methods	Searchable	12
6	Evaluation characteristics: Data analysis methods	Searchable	9
7	Document properties	Unsearchable	2

Combination logic:

- Between sections: AND
- Between sub-sections within the same section:
 - Between unsearchable sub-sections: AND. This applies to section 1, 2, 7.
 - Between searchable sub-section: OR. This applies to section 3, 4, 5, 6.
- Between child-items within the same sub-section: OR
- Between searchable sub-section item and its child-item(s): Only use child-item(s) in the search criteria, searchable sub-section item's condition will be ignored. This applies to 11 searchable sub-sections which have children.

16.1.3. Search process:

A search process consists of the following steps:

- a) Build search criteria by selecting the searchable items in the **Search Criteria Builder panel (CB panel)** in the main search page. The panel displays full available search criteria.
- b) Check the selected search criteria in **Search Criteria Summary panel (CS panel)** in the main search page, and click [Search] button to start search.
- c) See a list of matching evaluations in the **Search Result panel (SR panel)** in the main search page as the search result.
- d) Click an evaluation title to see the details in the evaluation detail page.

More details are covered in relevant sections of this document.

16.2. Main search page

Main search page consists of the following parts:

- CB panel – Search criteria builder
- CS panel – Search criteria summary, and two buttons for user to start search or clear the selected search criteria
- SR panel – Search result

16.2.1. CB panel – Search criteria builder

CB panel uses an accordion to show available search conditions. The accordion has following features:

- By default no section is expanded. One section can be expanded at a time, for user to see the full detail of sub-sections and child-items under them, and do the selection. Clicking a section name will toggle its status between expanded and collapsed.
- All the searchable items, i.e., child-items in sub-sections and the searchable sub-section items, will have a checkbox attached for user to select/deselect.
- Searchable and unsearchable sub-section titles are highlighted in different colour to get them differentiated.
- Although most of the items will be matched into the relevant items in [PLQuestion] and [FJQuestion], the wording for these items is from [SCDetail] and is different from those in [PLQuestion] and [FJQuestion].
- An additional explanation message, if exists, will appear when user hovers mouse over an item's text, **and the text will be highlighted in bold**. This applies to sub-section title items and child-items, except the country names and publication year. The data for mouse-over-message is stored in table [SCDetail] (MouseOverMsg). **An information image will show at the end of the text for such items.**

An explanation text will be displayed on top of the CB panel to let user understand how to use the accordion.

A button is available for user to show or hide this panel.

16.2.1.1. Section 1: Related policy measure characteristics

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: PL's geographical area data and items in three PL groups.
 - Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable, hence no checkbox are attached to them.
 - Combination logic between sub-sections: AND.
- a) PL's geographical area information
- Country list from [Country] table will be displayed for user to select. **No limit on number of countries selected as search criteria.**
 - **The country rank used in the SiperPortalAdmin site is ignored here, the country list will be sorted alphabetically.**
 - Multiple countries / supranational body will be included in the list as a single item and showed on top of the list. User can select these items together with other single country items.
 - Combination logic between countries is OR.

b) PL detail

- PL-related search criteria data will be retrieved from [SCDetail] table and displayed in 3 groups as 3 sub-sections.
- Combination logic between child-items within a sub-section is OR.

16.2.1.2. Section 2: Evaluation characteristics: Basic

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Evaluation's geographical area data, published period, and some items from FC related data.
- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable.
- Combination logic between sub-sections: AND.

a) Evaluation's geographical area data

- Country list from [Country] table will be displayed for user to select. **No limit on number of countries selected as search criteria.**
- **The country rank used in the SiperPortalAdmin site is ignored here, the country list will be sorted alphabetically.**
- Multiple countries / supranational body will be included in the list as a single selectable item and showed on top of the list. User can select these items together with other single country items.
- Combination logic between countries is OR.

b) Published period

- Starting year and ending year can be selected from two dropdown lists.
- Both lists are initialised in a pre-defined way: Ending in the current year and the count of years in the list is stored in the application's configuration file (web.config), default to 25. **By default the current year is at the top of a list.**
- Once one value is selected from a list, another list will be adjusted accordingly to ensure a valid selection, i.e., the ending year is no earlier than the starting year.
- **Select the text at the beginning of these lists (i.e., "Starting year..." or "Ending year") will get the full list restored.**

c) Evaluation performer

- 3 Child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q1.1.a~c in table [FJQuestion].
- Combination logic between child-items is OR.

d) Timing of the evaluation

Similar to c) but for questions Q1.2.a~d in table [FJQuestion].

e) Purpose of the evaluation

Similar to c) but for questions Q1.3.a~c in table [FJQuestion].

f) Reference to programme logic

Similar to c) but for questions Q1.4.a~c in table [FJQuestion].

16.2.1.3. Section 3: Evaluation characteristics: Topics covered

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Items from FC related data.

- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are searchable, except the first one (Appropriateness).
 - Combination logic:
 - Between sub-sections: OR.
 - Between child-items in same sub-section: OR
 - Between a searchable sub-section item and its child-items: If any of the children are selected, the sub-section item's status should be ignored even if it's selected.
- a) Appropriateness
- Sub-section is unsearchable.
 - 3 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.1.a / Q2.1.2.a / Q2.1.3.a in table [FJQuestion].
- b) Coherence/complementarity to other measures/programmes
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.4.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- c) Goal attainment/effectiveness
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.5.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- d) Outputs
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.6.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 1 child-item in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.6.1.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if its child-item is selected.
- e) Outcomes and impacts
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.7.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 9 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.7.2.a~c / Q2.1.7.3.a~e / Q2.1.7.4.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- f) Value for money/return on investment
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.8.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- g) Programme implementation efficiency
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.9.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- h) Additionality
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.10.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 3 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.10.1.a~c in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- i) Policy/strategy development
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.11.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.

- j) Gender issues
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.12.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- k) Minority/inclusivity issues
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.13.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- l) Uptake of programme
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.14.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- m) Degree of stakeholder satisfaction
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.15.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- n) Collaborations/partnerships
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.16.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 8 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.16.1.a~c / Q2.1.16.2.a~c / Q2.1.16.3.a~b in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- o) Scope of mobility
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q2.1.17.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 2 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q2.1.17.1.a~b in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.

16.2.1.4. Section 4: Evaluation characteristics: Design

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Items from FC related data.
- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are searchable.
- Combination logic:
 - Between sub-sections: OR.
 - Between child-items in same sub-section: OR
 - Between a searchable sub-section item and its child-items: If any of the children are selected, the sub-section item's status should be ignored even if it's selected.
- a) Experimental
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q3.1.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- b) Quasi-experimental
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q3.1.b in table [FJQuestion].
 - 3 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q3.1.1.a~c in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.

- c) Non-Experimental
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q3.1.c in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- d) Included explicit comparison/benchmarking with similar measures
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q3.2.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- e) Benchmarked against previous phases/evaluations of programme/measure
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q3.3.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.

16.2.1.5. Section 5: Evaluation characteristics: Data collection methods

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Items from FC related data.
- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are searchable.
- Combination logic:
 - Between sub-sections: OR.
 - Between child-items in same sub-section: OR
 - Between a searchable sub-section item and its child-items: If any of the children are selected, the sub-section item's status should be ignored even if it's selected.
- a) Existing databases & monitoring data
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.1.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 2 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q4.1.1.1.a~b in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- b) Surveys
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.2.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 6 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q4.1.2.1.a~f in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- c) Interviews
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.3.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 6 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q4.1.3.1.a~f in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- d) Focus groups/workshops/meetings
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.4.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- e) Peer reviews (inc. stakeholder reviews)
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.5.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- f) Formalised data on IP (patents, etc.)
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.6.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.

- g) Publications data
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.7.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- h) Altmetrics data
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.8.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- i) CV data
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.9.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- j) Longitudinal tracking data
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.10.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- k) Site visits
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.11.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- l) Other
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q4.1.12.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.

16.2.1.6. Section 6: Evaluation characteristics: Data analysis methods

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Items from FC data.
- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are searchable.
- Combination logic:
 - Between sub-sections: OR.
 - Between child-items in same sub-section: OR
 - Between a searchable sub-section item and its child-items: If any of the children are selected, the sub-section's status should be ignored even if it's selected.
- a) Case study analysis
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.1.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- b) Network analysis
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.2.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- c) Econometric analysis
 - Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.3.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- d) Descriptive statistics

- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.4.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- e) Input/output, cost/benefit, return-on-investment analysis
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.5.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- f) Intellectual property (IP) data analysis
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.6.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 2 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q5.1.6.1.a~b in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- g) Publications data analysis
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.7.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - 2 child-items in this sub-section, matching into questions Q5.1.7.1.a~b in table [FJQuestion].
 - Note the status of the sub-section should be ignored if any of its child-items is selected.
- h) Altmetrics data analysis
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.8.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.
- i) Qualitative/quantitative text analysis
- Sub-section is searchable, and matches into question Q5.1.9.a in table [FJQuestion].
 - No child under this sub-section.

16.2.1.7. Section 7: Evaluation characteristics: Document properties

Outline of the section:

- Content in the section: Document languages and categories.
- Sub-section item type: The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable.
- Combination logic:
 - Between sub-sections: AND.
 - Between child-items in same sub-section: OR.

a) Language

Document language list from [SCDetail] table will be displayed for user to select. Only 4 languages are listed as individual items, the 5th item (other languages) will cover all the rest of the languages in [DocLanguage] table.

b) Category

Document category list from [SCDetail] table will be displayed for user to select.

16.2.2. CS panel – Search criteria summary and actions

Summary of the selected search criteria will be displayed to reflect the selection in the CB panel. Two buttons are in the panel for user to take action.

16.2.2.1. Search criteria summary

Once a searchable item is selected in the CB panel, it will show in the CS panel; and it will be removed from the summary if it's deselected.

Items will be displayed in different colours to indicate their type/status:

- A searchable item, including a searchable sub-section item or a child-item, will be displayed as white text on blue background.
- Searchable but not-selected sub-section items and unsearchable sub-section items will need to be displayed if some of their child-items are selected. These sub-section items will be displayed as white text on grey background.

A button is available for user to show or hide the criteria selection summary in this panel.

16.2.2.2. Search button

[Search] button is available in this panel for user to start search with the criteria in the summary.

If the button is clicked with no search criteria selected, a full evaluation list will be returned.

The search criteria will be applied in order, starting with the simple ones and the ones in unsearchable sub-sections. More details in relevant sections below.

16.2.2.3. Clear criteria button

[Clear criteria] button is available in this panel for user to clear the already selected search criteria and start again.

16.2.3. SR panel – Search result

Search result will be presented as a list of matching evaluations, with sorting / paging functions. Columns include EvaluationTitle, Country and PublicationYear. By default the list will be sorted by country then title.

Evaluation title will be clickable, pointing to the evaluation detail page.

16.2.4. Search process and rules

16.2.4.1. Section 1: Related policy measure characteristics

The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable, searches are done for child-items only. Since the combination logic between sub-sections in this section is AND, the evaluations will be filtered through the selected search criteria by sub-section.

- a) PL's geographical area data
 - When a country is selected, search should be done in two ways: for PL's country in [PLSummary], and in PL's multiple country list if that's applicable (in [PLAdditionalCountry]). For example, if a PL is for multiple countries, and the selected country is contained in the multiple country list, this PL should be considered as a match, therefore searched for in evaluations.
 - When multiple countries or supranational body is selected it should be treated as a single country item.
 - Country items are combined by OR.
 - Matching evaluations will be identified via table [PLUsage].
- b) PL data
 - Selected PL items will be searched against in table [PLDetail], combined by OR between items in same sub-section.
 - Matching evaluations will be identified via tables [PLSummary] and [PLUsage].

16.2.4.2. Section 2: Evaluation characteristics: Basic

The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable, searches are done for child-items only in the evaluations that match the search criteria selected in Section 1.

Since the combination logic for sub-sections in this section is AND, the evaluations left will be filtered through the selected search criteria by sub-section.

- a) Evaluation's geographical area data
 - When a country item is selected, search should be done for evaluation's country (in [Evaluation]), and in its multiple country list if that's applicable (in [FJAdditionalCountry]). Evaluations will be identified via [FJSummary].
 - When multiple countries or supranational body is selected it should be treated as a single country item.
- b) Published period
 - Matching evaluations will be identified by PublishedYear in [Evaluation].
 - Search can be done for starting or ending year only.

c) Evaluation performer

For selected child-items, find the related FC questions by [MatchingQId] in [SCDetail] (in this case it will be questions Q1.1.a~c in table [FJQuestion]), search for these questions in table [FJDetail], and identify the matching evaluations via [FJSummary].

d) Timing of the evaluation

Similar to c), but the questions to be searched for in table [FJDetail] are Q1.2.a~d.

e) Purpose of the evaluation

Similar to c), but the questions to be searched for in table [FJDetail] are Q1.3.a~c.

f) Reference to programme logic

Similar to c), but the questions to be searched for in table [FJDetail] are Q1.4.a~c.

16.2.4.3. Section 3~6: Evaluation characteristics: Topics covered / Design / Data collection methods / Data analysis methods

The sub-section items in these sections are searchable (except the first one in Section 3 – Appropriateness).

Combination logic:

- Between sub-sections: OR.
- Between child-items in same sub-section: OR
- Between a searchable sub-section item and its child-items: If any of the children are selected, the sub-section item's status should be ignored even if it's selected.

Searching process:

For selected searchable sub-section item and/or child-item, find its related FC question by [MatchingQId] in table [SCDetail], search for the FC questions in table [FJDetail], and identify the matching evaluations via [FJSummary].

The same process should be applied to all 4 sections one by one.

16.2.4.4. Section 7: Evaluation characteristics: Document properties

The sub-section items in this section are unsearchable, searches are done for child-items only.

a) Language only

- Search will be done in [Document] table and matching evaluations will be identified accordingly.
- When individual languages are selected, search for it/them; When “Other languages” is selected, search will be done for any language except the not-selected individual languages.

b) Category only

- Search will be done in [Document] table for selected category, and matching evaluations will be identified accordingly.

c) Both Language and category

Search should be done for language-category pair, not individually, as indicated in the example below:

Search criteria: Language1 (L1), Language2(L2), Category1(C1), Category2(C2)

Matching documents should be L1+C1 or L1+C2 or L2+C1 or L2+C2

Note document's category and language names can be updated in the SiperPortalAdmin site by SU, the change won't affect the texts used here which need to be updated in the database.

“Appendix 11 – Searching rules” contains more technical details on searching rules.

Mock page – Main search page

A Web Page
http://
Q

University Logo

Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository (Siper)

RISIS Logo

Home
Repository
About
Publications
News & events
Contact

Search in Siper Repository

Select your search criteria Hide / show the CB panel Hide

Please click on the search options panels below to show/hide details of search criteria.

1: Related policy measure characteristics

1 Geographical area

2 Target group

Individuals

Additional explanation message will appear when user hovers mouse over an item's text

Search criteria builder (CB) panel:
 Only one section in the accordion is expanded at a time
 Non-selectable sub-sections highlighted in red, selectable ones green
 Checkboxes are attached to all selectable items

.....

3 Modality

4 Objective

2: Evaluation characteristics: Basic

3: Evaluation characteristics: Topics covered

4: Evaluation characteristics: Design

5: Evaluation characteristics: Data collection methods

6: Evaluation characteristics: Data analysis methods

7: Document properties

Summary of your selected search criteria

Hide / show the search criteria summary

Hide

1: Related policy measure characteristics

12: Target group Individuals Universities

13: Modality Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.

2: Evaluation characteristics: Basic

3: Evaluation characteristics: Topics covered

4: Evaluation characteristics: Design

5: Evaluation characteristics: Data collection methods

6: Evaluation characteristics: Data analysis methods

7: Document properties

7.1: Language English French

7.2: Category Appendices Executive summary Main report Multipurpose Other Terms of reference

Search

Clear criteria

Search result

#	Title	Country	Year
1	Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone	United Kingdom	2011
2	Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets	USA	2010
3	Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban	Multiple countries	2014
4	Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire	Supranational body	2015
.....			

Search result (SR) panel:
 Matching evaluations are displayed in a list with paging/sorting facilities

(Site footer)

16.3. Evaluation detail page

The details of a selected evaluation from the search result list will be displayed in this page.

The selected evaluation's title is on top of the page, its details are displayed in 3 panels:

- Basic data and document
- PL
- FC

[Return to search] button is available on top of the page to take user back to the main search page. User can also go to main search page by clicking the menu item for "Repository".

A search criteria summary panel is always visible at the bottom of the page, for information purpose.

16.3.1. Basic data and document panel

Details available in this panel include the following:

a) Basic evaluation data

- Titles:
 - The English title
 - The one in native language if applicable
- Evaluation's geographical area related information, it can be one of the following:
 - A single country, with additional information on national or regional level
 - Multiple countries, with all the country names
 - A supranational body
- Author
- Published year

b) Documents

- List of uploaded documents (including both publishable and non-publishable ones), covering documents' name, category, language, and publishable flag.
- For publishable ones there will also be a button pointing to the full content of the PDF file (will be opened in a separate browser tab).

Data is retrieved from various tables in the database, including [Evaluation], [Document], [FJSummary], [FJAdditionalCountry], etc.

A button is available for user to show or hide this panel.

Mock page – Evaluation detail page, basic data and document panel:

A Web Page

http://
Q

Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository (Siper)

Home Repository About Publications News & events Contact

Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone

Return to search

Basic information
Hide

Title (English) Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone

Title (Native) 哈利·波特与魔法石

Country United Kingdom, national level
OR Multiple countries: France, Spain, United Kingdom
OR EUREKA

Author J K Rowling

Published year 1997

Document(s)

#	Document name	Category	Language	Publishable	View/Download
1	E_GB_0001_MR_EN_01	Main report	English	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2	E_GB_0001_ES_EN_01	Excutive summary	English	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	E_GB_0001_MP_ZH_01	Multipurpose	Chinese	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Publishable document's content can be viewed / downloaded in a separate tab

Policy measure related information
Show

Factual characterisation related information
Show

Summary of your selected search criteria

1: Related policy measure characteristics

12: Target group Individuals Universities

13: Modality Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.

7: Document properties

7.1: Language English French

7.2: Category Appendices Executive summary Main report Multipurpose Other Terms of reference

Search condition summary (CS) panel: Only the sections containing selected items will be displayed.

(Site footer)

16.3.2. PL panel

Details showing in this panel are PL related data.

a) PL lists used by the evaluation, including PL's title and country (or multiple countries, or supranational body).

b) Full PL details

Full details for PLs used in current evaluation will be displayed in the box, including

- PL's title
- Geographical area information:
 - For a single country: Country name, with additional information on national / regional level.
 - For multiple countries: All the country names.
 - For supranational body: The body name.
- PL items in 3 groups: Only the selected ones will be displayed in each group.

A button is available for user to show or hide the PL detail box.

Data is retrieved from tables [PLSummary], [PLQuestion], [PLDetail], [PLAdditionalCountry] etc.

A button is available for user to show or hide the PL panel. A show/hide button for PL detail part is also available within the PL panel. The default status for selected PL detail box is hidden.

Mock page – Evaluation detail page, PL panel, PL detail panel is hidden:

A Web Page

http://
Q

Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository (Siper)

Home Repository About Publications News & events Contact

Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone

Return to search

Basic information
Show

Policy measure related information
Hide

Policy measures used by the evaluation

#	Title	Country
1	PL_GB_0001 aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa	United Kingdom
2	PL_Z1_0003 bbbbbbb bbbbb bbbb b	Multiple countries
3	PL_Z2_0001 cc cccc cccccccc ccc	Supranational body
.....		

Policy measure details

Hide / show the PL details → Show

Factual characterisation related information
Show

Summary of your selected search criteria

1: Related policy measure characteristics

12: Target group Individuals Universities

13: Modality Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.

Search condition summary (CS) panel:
Only the sections containing selected items will be displayed.

7: Document properties

7.1: Language English French

7.2: Category Appendices Executive summary Main report Multipurpose Other Terms of reference

(Site footer)

Mock page – Evaluation detail page, PL panel, PL detail panel is shown:

A Web Page
http://
Q

Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository (Siper)

Home
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Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone

Return to search

Basic information Show

Policy measure related information Hide

Policy measures used by the evaluation

#	Title	Country
1	PL_GB_0001 aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa	United Kingdom
2	PL_Z1_0003 bbbbbbb bbbbb bbbb b	Multiple countries
3	PL_Z2_0001 cc cccc cccccccc ccc	Supranational body

Policy measure details Hide / show the PL details Hide

PL_GB_0001 aaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaaa

Geographic area:
United Kingdom, national level

Title in native language:
神奇动物在哪里

Targets (Recipient of the support):

- * Universities
- * Research Organisations
- * Public organisations - non-R&D performing
- * Firms (no size-specific focus)

Modalities (How support is provided):

- * Indirect financial support: tax & fiscal incentives (e.g. R&D credits)
- * Infrastructure support (e.g. access to & construction/upgrading of research infrastructure)
- * Non-financial support (e.g. training ,coordination & advisory/information support/provision)

Policy objectives (Why the support is provided):

- * Supporting broader (multiple) interactions (e.g. through clusters or networks)
- * Supporting the protection of IP

PL_Z1_0003 bbbbbbb bbbbb bbbb b

Geographic area:
Multiple countries: France, Spain, United Kingdom

Targets (Recipient of the support):

- * Universities

Modalities (How support is provided):

- * Infrastructure support (e.g. access to & construction/upgrading of research infrastructure)

Policy objectives (Why the support is provided):

- * Supporting broader (multiple) interactions (e.g. through clusters or networks)

PL_Z2_0001 cc cccc cccccccc ccc

Factual characterisation related information Show

Summary of your selected search criteria

1: Related policy measure characteristics

12: Target group Individuals Universities

13: Modality Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.

7: Document properties

7.1: Language English French

7.2: Category Appendices Executive summary Main report Multipurpose Other Terms of reference

Search condition summary (CS) panel:
Only the sections containing selected items will be displayed.

(Site footer)

16.3.3. FC panel

Details showing in this panel are the publishable FC questions (questions in FC section 1 to 5) and answers.

The data will be grouped by FC section. Only the selected items are displayed in each section.

The question texts used to display FC details are different from those used in SiperPortalAdmin site when FC data is entered. These texts are stored in field [QTextPubSite] in table [FJQuestion] and are only used for the public site. The answer data is from tables [FJSummary], [FJDetail], [FJAdditionalCountry], etc.

A button is available for user to show or hide the FC panel. Within the panel, a button is available for each FC section too, user can use the button to show or hide a section.

Mock page – Evaluation detail page, FC panel (no detailed mock pages for FC sections):

A Web Page

← → ✕ 🏠

Science and Innovation Policy Evaluation Repository (Siper)

[Home](#) [Repository](#) [About](#) [Publications](#) [News & events](#) [Contact](#)

Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone

Basic information

Policy measure related information

Factual characterisation related information

Section 1: Basic Characteristics

1.1: Evaluation performer
 External to programme (within government, including court of auditors)
 External to programme and government ('independent')

1.2: Timing of the evaluation
 Ex ante (before the implementation of the measure/programme)

1.3: Purpose of the evaluation
 Summative (descriptive, judgemental)
 Formative (developmental, supporting)
 Other:

1.4: Reference to programme logic
 Partially included

FC panel in evaluation detail page:
 5 panels for 5 FC sections.
 In a FC section panel, only the details of
 selected items will be displayed.

FC question texts are different from those
 in admin and PM sites

Section 2: Topics Covered

Section 3: Evaluation Design

Section 4: Data Collection Methods

Section 5: Data Analysis Methods

Summary of your selected search criteria

1: Related policy measure characteristics

12: Target group	Individuals Universities
13: Modality	Direct financial support: scholarships, fellowships, etc.

7: Document properties

7.1: Language	English French
7.2: Category	Appendices Executive summary Main report Multipurpose Other Terms of reference

Search condition summary (CS) panel:
 Only the sections containing selected
 items will be displayed.

(Site footer)

17. Technical overview

17.1. General information

- The application will be written with MVC4 / .Net 4.5 / AngularJS, JQuery / Bootstrap will also be used. Data will be stored in MS SQL database.
- The application's databases will be hosted on server SQLDef.dbs.ds.man.ac.uk, 6503 (SQL Server 2012).
 - Testing database: [HumSiperPortalDev]
 - Production database: [HumSiperPortal]
- The website will have its own external domains:

si-per.eu / si-per.com / si-per.uk / si-per.net

- The web application will be hosted on the University's servers:
 - Testing site:

\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalPublic

URL: <http://webnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk/SiperPortalPublic/>

- Production site:

\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalPublic

URLs: si-per.eu / si-per.com / si-per.uk / si-per.net

The URL si-per.eu will be the prime one.

- The publishable documents are uploaded by authenticated SiperPortalAdmin site, but stored outside of the admin site to ensure those documents are accessible by the SiperPortalPublic site. Folders for publishable documents:

- Testing site:

\\hum-devnet.humanities.manchester.ac.uk\SiperPortalUploads

- Production site:

\\publishwwf.ds.man.ac.uk\HUM\SiperPortalUploads

17.2. Data schema

The application uses the same database [HumSiperPortal]. The schema is in file "Appendix 4 – Data schema".

17.3. Table details

Please refer to file "Appendix 7 – Data table details".

17.4. Tracking the site's usage with Google Analytics

An Google account is set up in order to use the Google Analytics to track the site's usage. The account details are as follows:

Email: siper.team@gmail.com

Password: s!perteam

To check the usage of your site, go to www.google.com/analytics/ and sign in to the Google Analytics (top-right corner) with this account. Note the setting is done by the University's IT, the tracking URL used is the prime one, i.e. si-per.eu, and attached to the above Google account. Any change request should be raised to the IT Support Centre.

17.5. Related documents

For application SiperPortalAdmin see "P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin" for details.

18. Assumptions and other notes

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

19. Glossary

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

20. Contacts

Same as in “P00418b – SiperPortalAdmin”.

Report on the content and technical structure of the **VICO** Infrastructure

Politecnico di Milano

RISIS "Research infrastructure for research and
innovation policy studies"

FP7, Grant agreement no: 313082

Task 6, Workpackage 6, coordinated by **AIT**
Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH

Content and technical structure of the VICO Updated database

1 Basic characteristics

Name and short description of the database

Name of the database: VICO Updated.

Short description of the database: The VICO Updated database contains geographical, industry and accounting information on companies founded starting from 1/1/1988, which have received at least one venture capital or angel investment starting from 1/1/1998, operating in seven European countries (Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom) and Israel. Its uniqueness lies in the overall number of companies (17,863), the country coverage, and the extent of information gathered (thanks to the combination of data provided by different proprietary datasets, i.e. Thompson One Private Equity, Zephyr, Crunchbase and Orbis). Moreover, it provides basic information on 7,834 distinct investors, of which 6,182 Venture Capitalists and 1,511 Business Angels.

Aim of the database (context of data acquisition)

The database has been developed in the context of the WP20 of the project “RISIS - Research Infrastructure for Research and Innovation Policy Studies”, funded by the European Commission under the Seventh Framework Programme. The aim of the RISIS project was to update and enlarge the already existing VICO database, developed within the project “VICO – Financing Entrepreneurial Ventures in Europe”.

Legal name of operating organization

POLITECNICO DI MILANO, Department of Management, Economics and Industrial Engineering, located in VIA LAMBRUSCHINI 4/B, MILANO, 20156, Italy represented by Cristina Masella, Head of Department or her authorised representative.

Database location and type of access

The database is located at Politecnico di Milano, Milan. The access is ‘on site’ only. Detailed information on the rules for visits are available at <http://risis.eu/risis-registration/>.

2 Information on substantive content of VICO Updated

2.1 Definition and description of observations

Units and definition of observations

The database includes companies that have received at least a venture capital or angel investment starting from 1/1/1998 and located in seven European countries (Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom) and Israel. Data can be broadly classified as *company-level* data, *investor-level* data and *investment-level* data. Detailed information was collected for each company, investor, and investment, including company's accounting information, investor type, and deal-specific information for each investment round (e.g. round date, amount invested).

Number of observations

The database consists of 17,863 companies and 7,834 investors (Venture Capitalists, Business Angels, Crowdfunding, Others). Companies and investors have been involved in a total of 28,044 investment rounds. As several investors might be involved in the same investment round (i.e. syndicated investment rounds), the total number of observations concerning investment-level data (i.e. all the company-investor-round dyads) is 52,657.

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

Where are the data retrieved from

The geographical coverage of the database includes seven European countries, as in the previous version of VICO, with the addition of Israel. More specifically, the criteria for inclusion of a company in VICO Updated were:

1. Companies founded starting from 1/1/1988.¹
2. First investment received starting from 1/1/1998.
3. Companies established in Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, United Kingdom and Israel.

In order to identify companies, investors and investments we used three source databases: two commercial databases (Thomson One Private Equity and Zephyr) and the free on-line database Crunchbase (www.crunchbase.com). Thus, we defined a unique list of companies to be included in VICO Updated by merging information on companies that were recorded in the three source databases. Companies' names were disambiguated using Excel add-on fuzzy matching and manual checks. Figure 1 reports the 17,863 companies included in VICO Updated and highlights the overlaps among the three source databases. Thomson One Private Equity is the main source of information of the VICO Updated database, accounting for 13,058 companies. However, it is worth pointing out that the inclusion of companies coming from Zephyr and Crunchbase allowed to significantly increase the coverage of the database, with additional 4,805 companies.

¹ The database also contains information on companies for which the foundation year is not available (5,475 companies).

Figure 1: Source databases for the population of companies

Company-level data

The main sources for company general information (e.g., name of the company, address, industry, status) were again Thomson One Private Equity, Zephyr, and Crunchbase. In case of overlap among the three source databases (see again Figure 1), we considered Thomson One Private Equity as the primary source of company-level information (the same approach has been used also for investor- and investment-level information). For instance, we used information from Thomson One Private Equity for the 1,454 companies that are present in all the three source databases, the 3,742 companies that are present in Thomson One Private Equity and Zephyr, and the 517 companies that are present in Thomson One Private Equity and Crunchbase. If the company was not present in Thomson One Private Equity, we used information from Zephyr and, finally, from Crunchbase if the company was present only in this last database. This approach allows to obtain a better harmonization of the information, as Thomson One Private Equity is the most relevant data source in VICO Updated. Furthermore, it is worth pointing out that Thomson One Private Equity is a widely used source of data in the empirical studies on entrepreneurial finance².

Additional accounting information was collected from Orbis. Accounting data are available for 14,425 companies (80.75% of the sample) from 2005 to 2014 where available.

Further sources of information were used to improve data availability and reliability. More specifically, using the concordance tables provided by Eurostat, company industries were reclassified according to the NACE Rev. 2 classification, when the information was not available in this format. For instance, companies in Thomson One Private Equity were classified according to the NAICS classification instead of NACE. Furthermore, in case of mismatch between the foundation date reported in the different original source datasets and Orbis, we obtained the correct foundation year through other additional sources, i.e. company websites, press releases, and online company directories such as, e.g., www.bloomberg.com. Finally, we used these additional sources in order to assign NACE codes to companies obtained from Crunchbase, as this source database does not provide a standardized industry classification (neither NACE nor NAICS).

² Kaplan, S. N., & Lerner, J. (2015). *Venture Capital Data: Opportunities and Challenges*. In *Measuring Entrepreneurial Businesses: Current Knowledge and Challenges*. University of Chicago Press.

Investment- and investor-level data

The main source of investment- and investor-level data were again the three source databases Thompson One Private Equity, Zephyr and Crunchbase. As in the case of companies, we harmonized investors' names and created a unique list of investors by merging information coming from these three sources.

Missing data on the type of investor were integrated using additional sources, such as company websites and press releases. Table 1 reports the different types of investor that are recorded in VICO Updated.

Table 1: Types of investor for the population of companies

Type of investor	Total Number	Percent
Independent VC	3,906	49.91
Corporate VC	1,327	16.96
Bank-affiliated VC	723	9.24
Governmental VC	191	2.44
University VC	35	0.45
Business Angel	1,511	19.31
Crowdfunding	3	0.04
Other	130	1.66
Total	7,826	100

How are the data processed in terms of data cleaning

All variables were checked for reliability and internal consistency. As aforementioned, companies' and investors' names were disambiguated using Excel add-on fuzzy matching and manual checks.

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

General description of variables for the main units of observation

In what follows, we report the main variables for each unit of observation, i.e. the company, the investor and the investment. The full description of the VICO Updated variables is reported in Section 4.2.

Company-level data

For each firm the following information have been collected:

- a) General company information:
 - Company ID (Company ID code, Company Name)
 - Address (Nation, City, Street, Zip Code, ISO codes);
 - Industry classification (including NACE Rev. 2 codes, description, main section);
 - Foundation year;
 - Listed status (including year of IPO);
 - Status (active, acquired, bankrupt).

- b) Accounting data: accounting data up to a 10-year time horizon (2005-2014):
 - Income statement figures;
 - Balance sheet figures;
 - Number of employees.

Investor-level data

Data include the following investor-level information:

- Investor ID (Investor ID code, Investor Name);
- Address (Nation, City, Zip Code, ISO codes);
- Type of investor (Type of VC: Independent VC, Corporate VC, Bank-affiliated VC, Governmental VC, University VC; BA; Crowdfunding; Other);
- Year of foundation of the VC management company;
- Number of funds managed by VC management company;
- Status (active or inactive).
- Industry classification (including NACE Rev. 2 codes, description, main section) where available

Investment-level data

Deal-specific information for each investment round:

- Date of the investment;
- Total amount invested.

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

Information on the sectorial classifications used and listing of all categories for each classification scheme

Companies' sectorial classification follows the NACE Rev. 2 classification. The distribution of companies according to the NACE Rev. 2 Main Sections is reported in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of companies by industry

NACE Rev. 2 Main Section	N. Companies	Percent
C - Manufacturing	4,193	25.09
D - Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	175	1.05
E - Water supply; sewerage, waste management	91	0.54
F - Construction	185	1.11
G - Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	1,061	6.35
H - Transportation and storage	162	0.97
I - Accommodation and food service activities	146	0.87
J - Information and communication	6,399	38.29
K - Financial and insurance activities	646	3.87
L - Real estate activities	134	0.80
M - Professional, scientific and technical activities	1,981	11.85
N - Administrative and support services activities	641	3.84
P - Education	113	0.68
Q - Human health and social work activities	299	1.79
R - Arts, entertainment and recreation	133	0.80
S - Other service activities	213	1.27
Other	139	0.83
Total	16,711	100.00

Information on the temporal coverage used

As the VICO Updated database focuses on early-stage investments, the population of companies was restricted to those founded starting from 1/1/1988, which received the first investment starting from 1/1/1998, up to 24/03/2015 (the time of the data collection). Table 3 and 4 report the distribution of the companies by foundation year and year of the first investment received.

Table 3: Distribution of companies by foundation year

Foundation year	N. Companies	Percent
before 1990	225	1.82
1990≤y<1995	846	6.83
1995≤y<2000	2,594	20.94
2000≤y<2005	3,324	26.83
2005≤y<2010	3,191	25.76
2010≤y≤2015	2,208	17.82
Total	12,388	100.00

Table 4: Distribution of companies by the year of the first investment received

First Investment Year	N. Companies	Percent
before 2000	1,238	6.93
2000≤y<2005	5,800	32.47
2005≤y<2010	4,724	26.45
2010≤y≤2015	6,101	34.15
Total	17,863	100.00

Information on the geographical coverage and classifications used

For each company, the database includes information on the country, the city, and the ZIP code (where available). We plan to collect additional information on the geographical coordinates (i.e. latitude and longitude) of both companies and investors by the end of 2016. The geographical distribution (according to the country in which the company is located) of the companies is reported in Table 5.

Table 5: Distribution of companies by country

Country	N. Companies	Percent
Belgium	556	3.11
Finland	1,044	5.84
France	3,865	21.64
Germany	3,096	17.33
Israel	1,239	6.94
Italy	738	4.13
Spain	1,454	8.14
United Kingdom	5,871	32.87
Total	17,863	100.00

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data**Information on the number of missing value**

Table 6 reports the number of missing values and the percentage of missing values with respect to the number of observations (i.e. the number of companies, investors and investment) for the variables concerning general company information, investors and investments. For a description of all variables included in the VICO Updated database please see Table 7 in Section 4.2.

Table 6. Missing values

Company general information	N. of missing values	% of missing	Total
CompanyID	0	0.00%	17863
CompanyName	0	0.00%	17863
CompanyAddress	953	5.34%	17863
CompanyCity	708	3.96%	17863
CompanyNation	0	0.00%	17863
CompanyZipCode	3221	18.03%	17863
Company_ISO_A2	0	0.00%	17863
Company_ISO_A3	0	0.00%	17863
Company_ISO_n	0	0.00%	17863
CompanyNAICCode	7359	41.20%	17863
CompanyNACERev2codes	14039	78.59%	17863
CompanyNACERev2descriptions	14039	78.59%	17863
CompanyMarket	17063	95.52%	17863
CompanyNACERev2codes_rev	2656	14.87%	17863
CompanyNACERev2descriptions_rev	2656	14.87%	17863
CompanyNACERev2mainsection_rev	2665	14.92%	17863
CompanyNACERev2mainsection_Orbis	4714	26.39%	17863
CompanyNACERev2Corecode_Orbis	4714	26.39%	17863
CompanyNACERev2Corecodes_Orbis	4714	26.39%	17863
CompanyFoundedYear	5475	30.65%	17863
CompanyListed	2299	12.87%	17863
CompanyIPODate	106	18.50%	573
CompanyAcquired	4751	26.60%	17863
CompanyFailed	2240	12.54%	17863
FirstInvestmentReceivedYear	0	0.00%	17863
FirstInvestmentReceivedDate	0	0.00%	17863
AgeAtFirstInvestmentReceived	5475	30.65%	17863
d_Orbis (accounting info not available)	3438	19.25%	17863
Investor information	N. of missing values	% of missing	Total
InvestorID	0	0%	7834
InvestorName	0	0%	7834
InvestorNation	1125	14%	7834
InvestorCity	5183	66%	7834
InvestorZipCode	3522	45%	7834
Investor_ISO_A2	1126	14%	7834
Investor_ISO_A3	1128	14%	7834
Investor_ISO_n	1129	14%	7834
InvestorNACERev2codes	5566	71%	7834
InvestorNACERev2descriptions	5566	71%	7834
InvestorFoundedYear	3530	45%	7834
InvestorStatus	5019	64%	7834
InvestorType	8	0%	7834
InvestorNoofFundsManaged	5017	64%	7834

Investment information	N. of missing values	% of missing	Total
CompanyID	0	0%	52657
RoundNumber	0	0%	52657
InvestorID	0	0%	52657
InvestmentDate	0	0%	52657
InvestmentYear	0	0%	52657
TotalEquityInvested_round	3589	6.82%	52657
RoundNumber_min	0	0%	52657
RoundNumber_max	0	0%	52657
ThompsonOnePrivateEquity	0	0%	52657
Zephyr	0	0%	52657
Crunchbase	0	0%	52657

Estimation of data quality issues with respect to data acquisition, reliability of retrieving system

Data were collected using different source databases as described before, thus data quality depends primarily on data quality of these sources. It is worth pointing out that these sources has been already used (separately) in empirical studies on entrepreneurial finance. Moreover, data were also checked for reliability and consistency.

3 Legal issues encountered and access conditions

The owner of the database is Politecnico di Milano. Access rights to the VICO Updated database must be therefore in compliance with a Non disclosure agreement that has to be signed by visitors. The access to the VICO Updated database is only available ‘on site’.

4 Technical structure of VICO Updated

4.1 Information on the database system

The database is currently available in the .dta format (Stata). In the future, we plan to make available the database also in the .accdb format (MS Access).

4.2 Technical variable definition

The database is organized in four tables, namely “Company general information”, “Company accounting information”, “Investor information” and “Investment information”. Tables 8, 9, 10 and 11 report the name, the type (float, string, boolean, date) and a description of all variables included in the VICO Updated database. Unique identifiers are reported in bold.

Table 8. Company general information

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	4 letters string ("VICO") + numeric progressive code.
CompanyName	string	Name of the company
CompanyAddress	string	Company's address
CompanyCity	string	Company's city
CompanyNation	string	Company's country
CompanyZipCode	string	Company's ZIP code
Company_ISO_A2	string	Company's ISO Alpha-2 letters code
Company_ISO_A3	string	Company's ISO Alpha-3 letters code
Company_ISO_n	string	Company's ISO numeric-3 digits code
CompanyNAICCode	string	Company's NAIC code(s)(only if Thompson One Private Equity=1)
CompanyNACERev2codes	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 code(s)(only if Zephyr=1)
CompanyNACERev2descriptions	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 description(s) for NACE Rev. 2 codes (only if Zephyr=1)
CompanyMarket	string	Text field with a description of company's industry (only if Crunchbase=1)
CompanyNACERev2codes_rev	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 code(s)reclassified
CompanyNACERev2codes_rev1-10	string	Split of multiple company's NACE Rev. 2 codes reclassified in different variables
CompanyNACERev2descriptions_rev	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 description(s) for NACE Rev. 2 codes reclassified
CompanyNACERev2descriptions_rev1-9	string	Split of multiple company's NACE Rev. 2 descriptions reclassified in different variables
CompanyNACERev2mainsection_rev	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 main section(s)reclassified
CompanyNACERev2mainsection_rev1-5	string	Split of multiple company's NACE Rev. 2 main sections reclassified in different variables
CompanyNACERev2mainsection_Orbis	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 main section (only if d_Orbis=1)
CompanyNACERev2Corecode_Orbis	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 core code (only if d_Orbis=1)
CompanyNACERev2Corecodedes_Orbis	string	Company's NACE Rev. 2 description for NACE Rev. 2 core code (only if d_Orbis=1)
CompanyFoundedYear	float	Year of foundation of the company
CompanyListed	boolean	1 if the company ever went through an IPO
CompanyIPODate	float	Date on which the IPO occurred
CompanyAcquired	boolean	1 if the company was ever acquired
CompanyFailed	boolean	1 if the company was liquidated
FirstInvestmentReceivedDate	float	Date on which the company received its first round of investment.
FirstInvestmentReceivedYear	float	Year in which the company received its first round of investment.
AgeAtFirstInvesmentReceived	float	Age of the company when first invested.
d_Orbis	boolean	1 if the company was found in Orbis (therefore accounting info are available)

Table 9. Company accounting information

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	4 letters string ("VICO") + numeric progressive code.
Year	float	Year to which the accounting data refers to
ID_Num	long	Encoded variable of CompanyID
CompanyName	string	Name of the company
Companyname_Orbis	string	Name of the company in Orbis database
FixedassetsthEUR	float	Total amount (after depreciation) of non current assets. (Intangible assets+Tangible assets+Other fixed assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
IntangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All intangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TangiblefixedassetsthEUR	float	All tangibles assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtherfixedassetsthEUR	float	All other Fixed Assets (after depreciation). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CurrentassetsthEUR	float	Total amount of current assets. (Stocks+Debtors+Other current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
StockthEUR	float	Total inventories. Thousand Euro. Nominal
DebtorsthEUR	float	Trade receivables. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentassetsthEUR	float	All other current assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashcashequivalentthEUR	float	Detail of other current assets=amount of cash at bank and in hand of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalassetsthEUR	float	Total Assets. (Fixed assets+Current assets). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ShareholdersfundsthEUR	float	Total Equity (Capital+Other shareholders funds). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CapitalthEUR	float	Issued Share capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthershareholdersfundsthEUR	float	All shareholders funds not linked with the Issued capital. Thousand Euro. Nominal
NoncurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities of the company. (Long term debts+Other non current liabilities+Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LongtermdebtthEUR	float	Long-term financial debts to credit institutions (>1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthernoncurrentliabthEUR	float	All long-term liabilities not related to financial institutions (including Provisions). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ProvisionsthEUR	float	Detail of other non current liabilities=Provisions. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities of the company (Loans+Creditors+Other current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
LoansthEUR	float	Short-term financial debts to credit institutions (<1Year). Thousand Euro. Nominal
CreditorsthEUR	float	All debts to suppliers and contractors. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OthercurrentliabilitiesthEUR	float	All current liabilities not payable to financial institutions nor trade debts. Thousand Euro. Nominal
TotalsharehfundsliabthEUR	float	Total Shareholders Equity and liabilities. (Shareholders funds+Non current liabilities+Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal to drop
WorkingcapitalthEUR	float	Net working capital (Stocks+Debtors-Creditors). Thousand Euro. Nominal
NetcurrentassetsthEUR	float	Net current assets (Current Assets-Current liabilities). Thousand Euro. Nominal
EnterprisevaluethEUR	float	Sum of the Market capitalisation, the Long term debts and the Loans (to financial institutions) minus the Cash and cash equivalent (for listed companies only). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TurnoverthEUR	float	Total operating revenues (Net sales+Other operating revenues+Stocks variations). Thousand Euro. Nominal
SalesthEUR	float	Net sales. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofgoodssoldthEUR	float	Costs of sold goods, production and services. Thousand Euro. Nominal
GrossprofitthEUR	float	Turnover – Costs of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OtheroperatingexpensessthEUR	float	All costs not directly related to the production of goods sold. Thousand Euro. Nominal
OperatingPLEBITthEUR	float	Earnings before interests and taxes (Gross profit – Other operating expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialrevenuethEUR	float	All financial revenues (interests, incomes from shares,..). Thousand Euro. Nominal

FinancialexpensesthEUR	float	All financial expenses (interest charges, write-off financial assets,...). Thousand Euro. Nominal
FinancialPLthEUR	float	Resut from financial activities. (Financial revenues – Financial expenses). Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLbeforetaxthEUR	float	Earnings before taxes. (Operating profit+Financial profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
TaxationthEUR	float	All taxes paid by the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLaftertaxthEUR	float	Earnings after taxes. (Profit before taxation – Taxation) Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherrevenuethEUR	float	All extraordinary revenues and other revenues not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherexpensesthEUR	float	All extraordinary expenses and other expenses not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExtrandotherPLthEUR	float	All extraordinary and other result not belonging to the ordinary activities of the company. Thousand Euro. Nominal
PLforperiodNetincomethEUR	float	Net income for the Year. (Profit after taxation+Extraordinary and other profit). Thousand Euro. Nominal
ExportrevenuethEUR	float	Revenues from exports. Thousand Euro. Nominal
MaterialcoststhEUR	float	Detail of the cost of materials used only for goods produced. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CostsofemployeeesthEUR	float	Detail of all the employees costs of the company (including pension costs). Thousand Euro. Nominal
DepreciationAmonththEUR	float	Total amount of depreciations and amortizations of the assets. Thousand Euro. Nominal
InterestpaidthEUR	float	Total amount of interest charges paid for shares or loans. Thousand Euro. Nominal
RDexpensesstthEUR	float	Total amount of R&D expenses. Thousand Euro. Nominal
CashflowthEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
AddedvaluethEUR	float	Profit for period+Depreciation+Taxation+Interests paid+Cost of employees. Thousand Euro. Nominal
EBITDAthEUR	float	Operating profit+Depreciation. Thousand Euro. Nominal
Numberofemployees	float	Total number of full time employees of the company

Table 10. Investor information

Variable	Type	Description
InvestorID	long	Encoded variable of InvestorName
InvestorName	string	Name of the investor
InvestorNation	string	Investor's country
InvestorCity	string	Investor's city
InvestorZipCode	string	Investor's ZIP code
Investor_ISO_A2	string	Investor's ISO Alpha-2 letters code
Investor_ISO_A3	string	Investor's ISO Alpha-3 letters code
Investor_ISO_n	int	Investor's ISO numeric-3 digits code
InvestorNACERev2codes	string	Investor's NACE Rev. 2 code(s) (only from Zephyr) (if a company)
InvestorNACERev2descriptions	string	Investor's NACE Rev. 2 description(s) for NACE Rev. 2 codes (only from Zephyr) (if a company)
InvestorFoundedYear	float	Year of foundation of the investor (if a company)
InvestorStatus	string	Investor status: active or inactive (if a company)
InvestorType		Type of investor: Independent VC; Corporate VC; Bank affiliated VC; Governmental VC; University VC; Business Angel; Crowdfunding; Other
InvestorNoofFundsManaged	int	Number of investor's funds managed (if a VC)

Table 11. Investment information

Variable	Type	Description
CompanyID	string	4 letters string ("VICO") + numeric progressive code.
RoundNumber	float	Progressive number of the round of investment in the database
InvestorID	long	Encoded variable of InvestorName
InvestmentDate	float	Date of the round of investment.
InvestmentYear	float	Year of the round of investment.
TotalEquityInvested_round	float	Total amount invested in the round of investment. Thousand Euro. Nominal
RoundNumber_min	float	Company's minimum number of investment rounds
RoundNumber_max	float	Company's maximum number of investment rounds
ThompsonOnePrivateEquity	boolean	1 if the company was found in Thompson One Private Equity
Zephyr	boolean	1 if the company was found in Zephyr
Crunchbase	boolean	1 if the company was found in Crunchbase

5 Further planning of the opening of *VICO*

Opening of the current version of the VICO Updated database will take place in May, 2016. We expect to open a new release of the database with additional information on geographical coordinates of companies and investors, and patenting activity of companies during 2017.